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POLYTECHNIQUE
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Implementation of Particle Image Velocimetry in Turbomachinery Flows

Thesis submitted by Mizuki OKADA

in fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor in Engineering Sciences and Technology (ULB - “Docteur en Sciences de l’Ingénieur et Technologie”)

Academic year 2023-2024

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

2D2C	Two-Dimensional Two-Component
2D3C	Two-Dimensional Three-Component
4HP	Four Hole Probe
5HP	Five Hole Probe
AIM	Anisotropy Invariant Map
AOI	Angle of Incidence
B2B	Blade-to-Blade
BBO	Basset-Boussinesq-Ossen
BFS	Backward Facing Step
Bis-MSB	1,4-Bis-(2-MethylStyryl)-Benzene
BM	Barycentric Map
BPP	Blade passing frequency
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
COP	Cascade Outlet Plane
CTA	Constant Temperature Anemometry
DA	Degree of Anisotropy
DEHS	Di-Ethyl-Hexyl-Sebacat
FOV	Field of View
FWHM	Full-Width at Half-Maximum
GTF	Geared Turbo Fan
HPT	High Pressure Turbine
HW	Hot-Wire

ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IW	Interrogation Window
KR620	Kiton Red 620
LPT	Low Pressure Turbine
Nd:YAG	Neodymium-doped Yttrium Aluminum Garnet
Nd:YLF	Neodymium-doped Yttrium Lithium Fluoride
NGV	Nozzle Guide Vane
OD	Optical Density
P567	Pyrrromethene 567
PIV	Particle Image Velocimetry
PLA	Phase Lock Average
PMMA	Polymethyl Methacrylate
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged-Navier-Stokes
Rh-6G	Rhodamine 6G
Rh-B	Rhodamine B, Rhodamine 610
RMS	Root-Mean-Square
ROI	Region of Interest
SPLEEN	Secondary and Leakage Flow Effects in High-Speed Low Pressure Turbines
TG	Turbulence Grid
TI	Turbulence Intensity
VKI	von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics

Greek symbols

α	Camera angle	[degree]
β	Yaw angle (Primary flow angle)	[degree]
Λ	Eigenvalue matrix	[-]
Φ	Eigenvector matrix	[-]
Δ_q	Uncertainty of generic quantity q	[-]
γ	Pitch angle, Specific heat ratio	[degree], [-]
λ	Wavelength, eigenvalue	[m], [-]
μ	Dynamic viscosity	[Pa · s]

ω	Vorticity	[1/s]
ϕ	Rotor phase, eigenvector	[degree], [-]
ρ	Density of fluid	[kg/m ³]
ρ_p	Density of particle	[kg/m ³]
σ	Standard deviation	[-]
σ_p	Surface tension of particle	[Pa · s]
τ_{rlx}	Relaxation time	[s]
θ	Angular misalignment between the calibration and laser sheet plane	[degree]
$K_{\omega,s}$	Streamwise vorticity coefficient	[-]

Roman symbols

\mathbf{a}	Anisotropy stress tensor	[-]
\mathbf{F}	Force	[N]
\mathbf{I}	Identity matrix	[-]
\mathbf{n}	Unit vector	[-]
\mathbf{S}	Time coefficient matrix	[-]
\mathbf{U}	Snapshot matrix	[]
\mathbf{x}	Eigen vector	[-]
a	Speed of sound	[m/s]
C	Blade true chord	[m]
C_D	Drag coefficient	[-]
C_s	Scattering cross section	[m ²]
C_{ax}	Blade axial chord	[m]
C_{exp}	Exponent coefficient	[-]
C_{freq}	Characteristic frequency	[1/s]
C_{off}	Offset coefficient	[-]
D	Diameter	[m]
d_p	Particle diameter	[m]
DA	Degree of anisotropy	[-]
E_o	Eötvös number	[-]
F_S	Scaling factor	[m/pixel]

g	Gravitational acceleration, cascade pitch	$[\text{m/s}^2], [\text{m}]$
H	Blade height	$[\text{m}]$
h	Rotor span position	$[\text{m}]$
h_r	Rotor span	$[\text{m}]$
I	Anisotropy invariant	$[-]$
I_0	Laser intensity	$[\text{J/m}^2]$
L_{img}	Length in the imaging plane	$[\text{m}]$
L_{real}	Length in the real world	$[\text{m}]$
M	Mach number	$[-]$
m_p	Mass of particle	$[\text{kg}]$
n	Refractive index	$[-]$
P_s	Static pressure	$[\text{Pa}]$
R	Gas constant, Reynolds stress	$[\text{J}/(\text{K} \cdot \text{kg})], [\text{m}^2/\text{s}^2]$
R_ρ	Density ratio	$[-]$
R_f	Light Reflectance	$[-]$
Re	Reynolds number	$[-]$
Re_p	Particle Reynolds number	$[-]$
St	Strouhal number	$[-]$
T	Temperature	$[\text{K}]$
t	Time	$[\text{s}]$
T_r	Light Transmittance	$[-]$
t_s	Pulse separation time	$[\text{s}]$
t_{te}	Trailing edge thickness	$[\text{m}]$
TI	Turbulence intensity	$[-]$
TKE	Turbulence kinetic energy	$[\text{m}^2/\text{s}^2]$
u, v, w	Velocity component	$[\text{m/s}]$
V	Velocity	$[\text{m/s}]$
x	Axial or longitudinal position	$[\text{m}]$
X_d	Particle displacement	$[\text{m}]$
y	Pitchwise or transverse-wise position	$[\text{m}]$

z	Spanwise position	[m]
z_{obj}	Front focal length	[m]

Subscripts and superscript

'	Fluctuating component
0	Total quantity
2 <i>C</i>	Two-component
3 <i>C</i>	Three-component
—	Mean component
<i>axi</i>	Axial component
<i>crs</i>	Crosswise component
<i>CS</i>	Correlation statistics based quantity
<i>rad</i>	Radial component
<i>str</i>	Streamwise component
<i>tan</i>	Tangential component
<i>typeA</i>	Type A uncertainty
<i>typeB</i>	Type B uncertainty
<i>x</i>	x component
<i>y</i>	y component
<i>z</i>	z component

Abstract

This thesis addresses the experimental investigation of turbomachinery flows by means of particle image velocimetry (PIV). The geometrical complexity and unique operating conditions of turbomachinery devices involve particularly intricate phenomena such as blade wakes, secondary flows, stator-rotor interaction, transitional boundary layer, and more. Understanding the mechanism behind these complex fluid behaviors is crucial for improving the modeling accuracy widely employed in machine designs.

The use of PIV is an attractive investigation approach due to its non-intrusiveness and capability to offer whole-field velocity information. On the other hand, the specific features of turbomachinery devices pose various challenges to implementing this technique. The main objective of this thesis, therefore, is to explore the feasibility and capability of PIV in turbomachinery-related applications and provide guidelines for successful implementation of this measurement technique.

The experimental test campaigns took place in three test facilities at the von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics: the L-12 low-speed wind tunnel equipped with an active turbulence grid, the S-1 high-speed wind tunnel hosting a linear low-pressure turbine cascade, and the CT-3 short-duration high-speed rotating test rig fitted with a single high-pressure turbine stage.

To support the PIV measurements, two experimental techniques were developed. The first involved using fluorescent tracer particles to eliminate undesired light reflections and distinguish specific flows. The second is a laser endoscope that allows the insertion of a laser sheet in a confined test section where optical access is restricted.

The measurement on the active turbulence grid presented the core capability of PIV combined with the fluorescent particle. The active turbulence grid consisting of six cylindrical bars with a diameter of 10 mm was tested in a rectangular test section of the L-12 wind tunnel operated at 5 m/s inlet flow condition. The bar cylinders have small holes from which a synthetic jet was injected into the flow to control turbulence characteristics downstream of the bar. The main flow and the synthetic jet injection were distinguished by seeding a typical non-fluorescent oil particle to either of the flows and the fluorescent particle to the rest. A set of image pre-processing steps effectively extracted the jet-only flow field. The flow unsteadiness behind the grid was investigated by applying the proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) to the PIV velocity fields. The synthetic jet filled the bar wake and diminished the large-scale Karman vortex formation. The PIV also identified the turbulence field behind the grid in terms of the turbulence intensity (TI) and integral length scale, suggesting the synthetic jet facilitates the uniformity of turbulence characteristics.

The PIV measurements on the transonic linear cascade in the S-1/C wind tunnel were carried out in three configurations: on the midspan blade-to-blade (B2B) plane upstream of the cascade, on the midspan B2B in the cascade passage and downstream, and on the cascade outlet plane (COP) 50% downstream of the blade trailing edge. The cascade was tested at $Re_{out, is} = 70k - 120k$, $M_{out, is} = 0.70 - 0.95$, matching the typical operating condition of

low-pressure turbine stages employed in modern geared turbo-fan engines. Testing with and without the upstream turbulence grid (TG) simulated two inlet TI levels.

The measurement on the upstream B2B plane verified the functionality of PIV as an investigation tool for the inlet flow condition in the cascade testing. The laser endoscope delivered the laser sheet in the cascade inlet where there was no access through an optical window. A parametric study on the data acquisition and processing settings showed a high sensitivity of measured TI to the particle displacement, suggesting recording images with multiple pulse separation times. The mean flow fields for the on- and off-design flow conditions showed a reasonably good agreement with results obtained from 5HP measurements and RANS predictions. PIV measured TI of 1.7-2.0% with the TG, and 0.6-1.0% without TG, globally matching the values measured with a hot-wire probe.

The measurement on the blade passage B2B plane demonstrated the performance of PIV in a transonic flow with high-velocity gradients and cross-validated RANS prediction and 5HP measurement results. The high-speed flow condition and strong curvature of the blade made particles drift from the fluid streamline, resulting in the lack of particles near the blade suction surface. A Lagrangian particle tracking simulation predicted particles sizing below $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ are necessary for seeding near the blade surface. The global flow topology for the on- and off-design conditions showed a good agreement between PIV and RANS. The comparison of pitchwise distributions of Mach number and yaw angle at 50% downstream of the trailing edge presented a significant intrusiveness effect on the probe measurement, highlighting an advantage of PIV as a non-intrusive technique.

The measurement on the COP utilized a stereoscopic setup to investigate secondary flows near the cascade endwall. The Mach number, flow angles, and streamwise vorticity distributions obtained with PIV displayed the typical secondary flow topology, aligning with the results obtained with 5HP measurements. The three-component velocity fluctuations characterized the turbulence field at COP in terms of TI, degree of anisotropy, and anisotropy invariants. The results were consistent with the literature, confirming the potential use of PIV for studying anisotropic turbulence fields in high-speed cascade flows.

Lastly, the measurement on the high-pressure turbine stage in CT-3 was conducted as a feasibility study of PIV in a short-duration rotating test facility, the most challenging testing environment among the three test cases. The adoption of the rainbow rotor, in which multiple blade geometries were involved in a single rotor disk, made this test case even more ambitious. The region of interest was on a tangential plane at 38%, 50%, and 58% of the channel span, covering a full rotor pitch and 5 - 15% rotor axial chord downstream of the rotor trailing edge. An evaluation of convergence history concluded a minimum of 200 pairs of snapshots were required to achieve a converged phase-lock-average flow field. The presented setup, utilizing a high-speed PIV system with an acquisition frequency of 1 kHz, provided a sufficient number of samples for rainbow-averaged PLA from a single blow-down test whose testing time lasted 250 ms. Sector-resolved PLA, in which the flow fields of different blade geometries were individually averaged, required 7-10 repetitive tests because of the reduced number of sector-bounded snapshots available. The measurement results reasonably agreed with the RANS prediction, suggesting the prospect of PIV in challenging turbomachinery applications.

1

Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Understanding and modeling of fluid dynamics are the keys to developing new fluid devices and improving the performance of machines. It is a challenging task due to the inherent complexity evolved with the unique characteristics of fluids such as non-linearity, turbulence, and transition from laminar to turbulent state.

One of the fluid machines that involve particularly intricate behaviors of fluids is turbomachinery. Turbomachinery devices have flow passages confined with complex geometries such as curved blades, endwalls, and various technological features, e.g. blade tip clearances, cooling holes, and rim seal gaps. This complexity makes the fluid motion inherently three-dimensional and diversifies their scales. As depicted in Fig. 1.1, the fluid moves not just along the streamlined passage, but also involves blade wakes, tip leakage flows, endwall flows, and interaction between them [1, 2]. The interaction between rotating and stationary parts in turbines or compressors leads to additional unsteady flow phenomena which require specialized analysis techniques. In general, turbomachinery components are operated at varying speeds and conditions. Some operate at transonic or even supersonic speed, where compressibility effects like the formation of shock waves and changes in fluid properties become significant (Fig. 1.2). Turbomachinery often deals with turbulent flows, which can affect flow separations, growth and dissipation of secondary flows. For example, the transition process in the blade surface boundary layer is triggered by freestream fluctuation [3]. Prediction of absolute losses downstream of cascades also requires the turbulence to be accurately modeled [4]. The accurate modeling of turbulence is challenging, requiring extensive experimental database and advanced computational techniques.

Researchers and engineers have been continuously working on developing new techniques, computational tools, and experimental methods to tackle these challenges and gain deeper insights into the intricate behavior of fluids.

Figure 1.1: A secondary flow model in a turbine cascade [5].

Figure 1.2: VKI LS-94 turbine blade, $M_{out,is} = 0.79$, $Re_{out,is} = 2.8 \times 10^6$ case. Density gradient based contours: (a) RANS $k - \omega$, (b) U-RANS $k - \omega$, (c) LES, (d) Experiments, schlieren photograph [6].

In terms of experimental approaches, aerothermal probes have been playing a main role in the investigation of turbomachinery flows [7–14]. On the other hand, several studies highlighted the limitation in the accuracy of physical probe measurements due to the finite size of probes [11, 15–18]. For example, Fig. 1.3 illustrates the intrusiveness of a probe alternating the static pressure distribution of a transonic turbine vane row. Moreover, for some specific flow conditions present in turbomachinery, calibration of probes is not always easy to carry out in common calibration benches [19]. Therefore there is an urgent demand for advanced measurement techniques that enable the acquisition of extensive datasets with high spatial and temporal resolution while eliminating intrusive effects by measurements.

Figure 1.3: Static pressure contours across the vane row at midspan for transonic flow condition. Obtained from a steady-RANS simulation [18].

As an alternative measurement technique, Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) has gained popularity thanks to its non-intrusiveness and capability to provide whole-field velocity information. It offers several advantages for studying fluid motion and understanding complex flow phenomena:

1. Quantitative whole-field velocity measurements: Unlike traditional point-wise velocity measurements, PIV measures velocity fields over an entire plane or region simultaneously. This ability allows researchers to obtain detailed quantitative flow field information covering large and small-scale spatial structures including flow patterns, vortices, and other fluid dynamic phenomena. The information about the instantaneous velocity field is valuable to investigate the turbulence in the flow. The spatial resolution can be also controlled by selecting adequate optical equipment, enabling the detection of small-scale flow features.
2. Non-Intrusive Technique: PIV is essentially a non-intrusive technique, meaning that it doesn't require physical probes or sensors to be placed within the flow to sample the information, minimizing disturbance to the flow field. Furthermore, the contact-less approach enables measurements in the area where physical probes can not be placed such as in or vicinity of blade passages.

3. Fast Data Acquisition: PIV system can acquire multi-point data simultaneously. With high-speed PIV systems, it is possible to capture transient events and time-dependent phenomena with high temporal resolution. The ability to quickly acquire a large amount of data will reduce testing time compared to the time-consuming single-point traversing measurement technique.
4. Unnecessity of flow-related calibration: PIV estimates flow velocities by analyzing images of particles moving within the flow. While performing image calibration is essential for converting distance units from image sensor pixels to the physical domain, the flow-related calibration typically required for physical probes is unnecessary. This capability is particularly valuable when calibration under the specific conditions found in turbomachinery flows is challenging to achieve.
5. Database for validation: The high-density flow field information obtained with PIV is suitable for validating computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations and physical probe measurements. Cross-checking PIV data with other experimental and numerical results is helpful to assess the accuracy of each technique and to gain insights into model shortcomings.

Despite its advantages, PIV also has limitations such as the sensitivity to particle size and seeding density, the effect of image background noise, and potential errors due to out-of-plane motion. Implementation of the technique in complex testing environments is also one of the main challenges. To achieve the goal of experimental campaigns, carefully designed experiments have to be performed. While there is available literature that covers measurement principles and some recommendations for the experimental setup, the applied cases are mostly limited to idealized simulation or simplified experimental environments.

The Turbomachinery and Propulsion Department of the von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics (VKI) has accumulated expertise in experimental measurement techniques such as multi-hole pressure probes and hot-wire probes over many years. Despite the variety of techniques available, PIV has been scarcely employed in its turbine test rigs. With an increasing demand for non-intrusive whole-field measurement techniques to expand research capabilities, a study is needed to demonstrate the feasibility of PIV techniques.

Some of the test facilities involved in this thesis are capable of simulating engine-relevant conditions, albeit with increased complexity in both hardware and operation. Developing countermeasures for the challenges posed and identifying limitations of PIV measurements are essential to assess the potential uses of the technique for future research projects. Moreover, the dissemination of such information benefits the turbomachinery research community by improving proficiency and inspiring employment of the technique in similar test facilities. Therefore, the present thesis aims to provide detailed guidelines and extended outcomes of PIV measurement techniques applied to turbomachinery flows. The following paragraphs introduce the three PIV applications, each conducted in different experimental campaigns at the VKI. The major outcomes of each application are outlined in subsection 1.2.

Applications

The first application is an active turbulence grid tested in the L-12 low-speed wind tunnel. A synthetic jet is injected from holes made in the bars comprising the turbulence grid. This test case is the most accessible for PIV systems among the three cases thanks to the fully transparent rectangular test section and low-speed operating conditions (Fig. 1.4). PIV measurements are conducted to study the effect of the synthetic jet on the development of flow structures and turbulence fields downstream of the grid. A novel fluorescent tracer particle is introduced to validate a simultaneous measurement technique of multi-constituent flows.

Figure 1.4: Left: The test section of active turbulence grid in the L-12 low-speed wind tunnel. Right: The synthetic jet from the grid visualized by fluorescent imaging.

The second application is a transonic turbine cascade tested in the S-1/C high-speed wind tunnel. PIV measurements on the blade-to-blade plane and the cascade outlet plane are conducted on the SPLEEN C1 [20] high-speed low-pressure turbine (LPT) blades linearly installed in the elbow of the wind tunnel. A new optical endwall is designed to provide optical access for this first PIV measurement campaign performed in the wind tunnel (Fig. 1.5). The unique flow conditions, involving low Reynolds numbers $70k \leq Re_{out, is} \leq 120k$ and transonic Mach numbers $0.7 \leq M_{out, is} \leq 0.95$, as well as unsteady, high-velocity gradient flow behaviors, pose challenges for achieving ideal seeding density and distribution. This test case evaluates the capability of the technique as an investigation tool for the complex flow structures and anisotropic turbulence fields in such an environment.

The third application is a high-pressure turbine (HPT) stage tested in the CT-3 isentropic compression tube annular cascade facility. This test case is the most challenging among the three for implementing PIV systems. The test rig is a blow-down type, allowing the testing time of only about 200-300 ms. The rotor is accelerated during the blow-down, making phase-locked data acquisition, typically employed for continuously operating test rigs, non-trivial. The test section is heavily instrumented and covered with metallic casings as seen in Fig. 1.6, strictly limiting the optical and seeding accesses. The flow path is confined by rotating blades and curved casings and endwalls, yielding excessive light reflections. This case serves as a proof-of-concept demonstration, dealing with the optical arrangement, systems synchronization, and processing of deteriorated particle images due to optical distortion and

Figure 1.5: The linear cascade test section in the S-1/C high-speed wind tunnel.

light reflections.

Figure 1.6: Left: The test section of the CT-3 compression tube test rig. Right: The nozzle guide vane row installed in the test section.

1.2 Outline

Chapter 2 reviews the methodology, starting with an introduction to the fundamentals of PIV and particular techniques developed for turbomachinery applications in the present thesis. A sub-micron scale fluorescent particle was developed for separating particle image signals from undesired reflections and measuring multi-constituent flows. Laser endoscopes were designed and manufactured to deliver a laser beam inside the confined test section of turbine

test rigs. In the latter part of Chapter 2, the data reduction and uncertainty analysis methods employed for the deriving quantities presented in the experimental result (Chapter 5) are addressed.

Chapter 3 introduces three test cases that PIV was applied:

1. Active turbulence grid in the low-speed wind tunnel (L-12)
2. Linear low-pressure turbine cascade in the high-speed wind tunnel (S-1/C)
3. Rotating high-pressure turbine stage in the high-speed compression tube rig (CT-3)

For each test case, a subsection is assigned to provide its literature review and to describe the test rig, test conditions, PIV setup, and data processing method. In case numerical simulations were performed in parallel, their setups are also addressed.

Chapter 4 presents the results of the three test cases aforementioned. The uncertainties in measured quantities are calculated using the method described in Chapter 2.

The active turbulence grid case demonstrates the use of the fluorescent particle for simultaneous measurement of the synthetic jet and global flows. The influence of the synthetic jet on the main flow is investigated in terms of the mean and turbulence flow characteristics. The flow structure behind the bars, characterized by periodic flow oscillation, is analyzed using the proper-orthogonal-decomposition (POD) technique.

The case involving the linear low-pressure turbine cascade presents the measurement results carried out on the cascade midspan inlet blade-to-blade plane, the cascade midspan passage/outlet blade-to-blade plane, and the cascade outlet plane near the endwall. A parametric study is conducted at the cascade inlet to evaluate the effect of the acquisition and post-processing settings on the derived flow quantities. The results in the passage and downstream of the cascade midspan are compared against steady RANS simulations and five-hole-probe measurements, emphasizing the vane-probe interference effect in transonic cascade flows. PIV results obtained at the cascade outlet plane near the endwall are cross-validated with five-hole-probe measurements. The discussion also covers turbulence anisotropy, highlighting the utility of PIV in high-speed turbomachinery applications.

The rotating high-pressure turbine stage case demonstrates the proof-of-concept of PIV measurement in the most challenging testing environment undertaken in this thesis. The flow fields obtained by PIV are phase-lock-averaged and compared against a steady RANS simulation result, establishing the feasibility and capability of PIV.

Finally, Chapter 5 addresses the conclusions of this study including a guideline for the implementation of PIV in turbomachinery-related applications and future perspectives of the technique.

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2

Methodology

2.1 Particle image velocimetry

2.1.1 Basic principle

In PIV, the fluid velocity is estimated from the displacement of tracer particles recorded in images. There are various variants of PIV techniques [1, 2], however, the description in this section focuses on solely the ones employed in the presented thesis.

For the sake of simplicity, we consider a basic, most commonly employed, two-dimensional two-component (2D2C) planar PIV technique. A schematic of a typical setup of a 2D2C planar PIV is presented in Fig. 2.1 [2].

Before image recording, tracer particles are seeded in the flow of interest. The plane of interest within the flow is illuminated twice by a short-pulse-length light sheet with a known pulse separation time. The light scattering from illuminated particles is registered on the image sensor of a camera. Thanks to the use of a short-pulse-length light, the particles are recorded frozen in the image at the instant location. Modern digital PIV systems employ the so-called *multi-frame/single-exposure* technique, with which the particles illuminated by the first and second pulsed light sheet are recorded in two frames separately. The advantage of this recording technique is that it can preserve the temporal order of the particle images and hence the directional ambiguity can be omitted.

Eq.2.1 is the principal formula used to derive the velocity of a flow with PIV. X_d represents the particle displacement estimated by analyzing two consecutive particle images. The fluid velocity V , assumed to be represented by the particle velocity, is computed by dividing the particle displacement with the separation time t_s between two consecutive illuminations. Finally, a scaling factor F_s , which accounts for the image magnification and the pixel size of the image sensor, is multiplied to convert from pixel units to real-world units.

Figure 2.1: A typical experimental arrangement for planar 2D2C PIV in a wind tunnel. [2]

$$V = f(F_s, X_d, t_s) = F_s \frac{X_d}{t_s} \quad (2.1)$$

The most commonly employed method for evaluating particle images to estimate particle displacement is image cross-correlation. Fig. 2.2 illustrates the concept of the image cross-correlation method for PIV. The whole image is first divided into small areas called interrogation windows. The cross-correlation over the interrogation windows of two single-exposed frames provides the correlation map whose peak corresponds to the particle displacement.

The principle of PIV can be extended to a simultaneous three-component measurement system by adding cameras viewing from other directions. Stereoscopic PIV systems employ two cameras focusing on the same measurement plane but with different viewing angles. Two pairs of in-plane velocity components are used to reconstruct the three components of the velocity field on the measurement plane. The principle of the stereoscopic PIV systems is illustrated in Fig. 2.3, and detailed explanations can be found in [1–3]. Stereoscopic PIV has an additional advantage to the two-component planar PIV: the quantification of the normal-to-plane component eliminates bias errors introduced by perspective.

2.1.2 Challenges for turbomachinery applications

The use of PIV in turbomachinery facilities poses different and more severe challenges compared to its use for simplified experimental test cases, which usually allow a modification or rebuild of the test section to meet the requirements of the ideal PIV installation. This is often not the case for turbomachinery applications, where the test facility is designed to satisfy various constraints due to operational and safety reasons. Furthermore, a radical change in the design of such a facility is highly costly.

Several challenges are anticipated for PIV in turbomachinery applications: installation of the seeding equipment, attaining a homogeneous seeding distribution in the region of interest, minimizing the wind tunnel contamination, dealing with limited optical access, minimizing

Figure 2.2: Conceptual arrangement of frame-to-frame image sampling associated with double frame/single exposure Particle Image Velocimetry. [2]

Figure 2.3: Left: Stereoscopic imaging configurations with tilted camera viewing angles [3]. Right: Velocity reconstruction in stereoscopic PIV system [2].

light reflections on the turbine blades and endwall, managing restricted time for the in-situ setup and measurement, achieving synchronization of PIV system with the test rig operation and rotating components.

2.1.2.1 Seeding

Seeding is one of the most critical parts of the successful execution of PIV measurements. The particle image density, in other words, the number of particle images per interrogation window, needs to be high and uniform so that the cross-correlation can be performed in space with high accuracy. To achieve a high spatial resolution for resolving large-scale as well as small-scale structures, the field of view (FOV) must be sufficiently large while the interrogation window size becomes small, hence a higher seeding density is required. A powerful seeding generator that can produce a large amount of tracer particles per second is needed for this purpose.

At the same time, the particle must be small enough to follow the fluid motion accurately without alternating the flow. Turbomachinery flows are typically characterized by strong velocity gradients such as wakes, boundary layers, secondary flows, and shockwaves. The flow traceability of particles is discussed in detail in subsection 2.2.

However, there is a contradiction in the requirement of the particle size. The seeded particles must be also large enough to scatter a sufficient amount of light to allow the camera to capture images with a high signal-to-noise ratio. In general, the intensity and distribution of light scattered by a small particle is described as a function of the particle's size, shape, polarization, observation angle, orientation, and the ratio of the refractive indices of the particles and the surrounding medium [2].

A convenient measure of the (spatially integrated) light scattering capability, the scattering cross section C_s , was introduced by Melling [4], defined as the ratio of the total scattered power P_s to the laser intensity I_0 incident on the particle. Fig. 2.4 shows the variation of the scattering cross section C_s as a function of the ratio of the particle diameter d_p to the laser wavelength λ for spherical particles with a refractive index $n = 1.6$. The smaller the particle size, the more a powerful light source is required to obtain sufficient light scattering. The sudden drop in C_s for the $d_p/\lambda < 1$ region indicates a transition from the Mie-scattering to the significantly weaker Rayleigh-scattering regime. Common illumination sources for PIV include Nd:YAG and Nd:YLF lasers with wavelengths of 532 nm and 527 nm, respectively. To observe Mie-scattering using these lasers, the minimum particle size is limited to be larger than the wavelength of lasers ($d_p > 0.5\mu\text{m}$).

2.1.2.2 Limited optical access

PIV measurements require optical accesses for cameras to capture particle images and for a light sheet to illuminate the particles in the interrogated areas. For planar PIV, an ideal orientation of the optical system is to maintain the light sheet perpendicular to the optical axis of a camera [2], and thus a conventional measurement setup requires two optical accesses (one for a camera view and one for a laser sheet insertion). This requirement is particularly challenging for turbomachinery applications since the packed hardware geometries limit the size of viewing ports as well as the space for optical and recording instruments (See Fig. 1.6 as an example). The use of stereoscopic or tomographic systems with highly skewed view

Figure 2.4: Light scattering cross section as a function of the particle size d_p . [4]

angles [5] would only need a single optical window, however, the skewed view angles induce a bias error in the out-of-plane component [6].

Nevertheless of the hardware constraints of turbomachinery applications, it is still a common approach to provide camera view access by installing transparent optical windows made of glass or acrylic into test facilities (e.g. [7–10]). The advantages of optical windows are their high light transmission and relatively easier inspection of the flow path inside the casing. On the other hand, optical windows require a large space, and the curvature of the window's inner surface, matching the annular flow path, can introduce optical distortions. Some studies have reported more advanced approaches, such as a combination of optical window and mirrors [11] and the use of an imaging borescope [12].

In most PIV measurements, a laser sheet is inserted into the measurement area directly or through transparent windows or walls. However, when it comes to turbomachinery applications, realizing such optical access with optimal orientation may not be possible due to the accessibility to the test section. The situation is more challenging in annular rigs as a laser sheet must be delivered through round casings. Several studies have shown the successful employment of laser endoscopes to introduce illumination light sheets inside the test section [7–10]. The different probe designs presented in the literature indicate the need for specific designs for every application.

2.1.2.3 In-situ setup and system synchronization

Turbomachinery test facilities that can reproduce the engine-representative flow conditions are often controlled remotely and are not flexible to stop-start operations. The running cost of such facilities can be significant since they typically require a large energy consumption and trained personnel for the operation. Such circumstances limit the number of tests and in-situ setup of measurement parameters, thus making successful employment of PIV measurements more challenging.

In the case of a short-duration test facility, the acquisition sequence of the measurement system has to be aligned with the rig operation. PIV measurements in transonic/supersonic transient wind tunnels were reported [13–15], for a testing time ranging from 10 to 40 seconds. If moving components such as turbine rotors or wake generator bars exist, the trigger-

ing of PIV image acquisition needs to be synchronized with them. To the best of the author's knowledge, the experiments reported by Bryanston-Cross et al. [7, 16] are the unique test cases performed in a blow-down and rotating testing environment.

2.1.2.4 Image quality

Another challenge in practical PIV measurement operation is undesired strong light reflections on surfaces of channel walls or obstacles. In certain instances, the presence of reflections can pose significant challenges for experimentalists since vector calculations become impossible when particle images are obscured by excessive reflections. Furthermore, the incidence of excessively strong light in image sensors can cause damage to pixels and worst case scenario permanent loss of the image signals. Such a situation is frequently encountered when small particles are used to ensure traceability thus a powerful light source is employed. The light reflection becomes further pronounced in applications with complex geometries with highly reflective surfaces such as turbomachinery applications.

The accuracy of the measured quantity from PIV is directly related to the quality of the image calibration. For facilities with limited access, the development of a sophisticated calibration system is necessary. Especially for the stereoscopic PIV, a very small misalignment on the order of millimeters will lead to severe errors of the out-of-plane component [2]. A self-calibration technique [17] is often necessary to correct the unavoidable misalignment.

2.2 Dynamics of tracer particles

2.2.1 Generation of tracer particles

Given the availability of devices at the institute and required particle production capacity, Laskin-nozzle seeding generators, *PIVpart45* and *PIVpart14* from *PIVTEC* (Fig. 2.5), are employed for seeding. The Laskin-nozzle, as sketched in Fig. 2.6, is a simple device consisting of a cylinder with 1 mm exit holes arranged circumferentially. Above these nozzle exit holes, a disc plate with 1 mm liquid feed holes is attached. Supplying high-pressure air to the nozzle immersed in a liquid bath (typically, mineral or vegetable oil), a jet is created from the nozzle exits. The interaction between the jet and liquid produces small particles [18].

For measurements presented in this thesis, the tracer particles are made of either *Palas Di-Ethyl-Hexyl-Sebacat (DEHS)* or *Shell Ondina X 420*. Table 2.1 addresses the specifications of the materials. The nominal diameter of tracer particles is around 0.9 - 1.0 μm as shown in Fig. 2.7. Typical seed output per jet is approximately 10^8 particles/second and the liquid atomization rate is about $1 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}$ [19, 20]. The total mass production rate of the seeding particle is therefore approximated to be $\dot{m}_p = 9.12 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg/s}$ and $8.16 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg/s}$ for DEHS and *Ondina X420*, respectively.

In gaseous flow, the mass fraction (\dot{m}_p/\dot{m}_f), defined as the mass of particles per unit mass of fluid, must be maintained below 0.25% to avoid two-phase flow effects [1]. Hereafter we consider PIV measurements in air. Injecting tracer particles with a density of ρ_p at the typical atomization rate of $1 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}$, the minimum mass flow rate $\dot{m}_{f,min}$ required to exclude two-phase flow effects is estimated by:

Figure 2.5: Seeding generators. Left: PIVpart14, Right: PIVpart45. [19, 20]

Figure 2.6: Sketch of the Laskin nozzles. [20]

Table 2.1: Specification of DEHS [21, 22] and Ondina X420 [23, 24].

	DEHS	Ondina X 420	
Density, ρ_p	912	816	kg/m
Dynamic viscosity, μ_p	$1.9 - 2.3 \times 10^{-3}$	NA	Pa · s
Kinematic viscosity, ν	NA	40 (at 293 K)	mm ² /s
Surface tension, σ_p	3.2×10^{-2}	NA	N/m
Flash point	> 473	498	K
Refractive index	1.45	1.45	-

Figure 2.7: (a) Particle size distribution for vegetable oil atomized at 1 bar using PIVpart14/45. (b) Particle size distribution for DEHS atomized at 1 bar using PIVpart14/45. [19, 20]

Table 2.2: Estimated mass flow rate for three test campaigns and mass fraction of DEHS particles seeded using PIVpart45.

	L-12	S-1/C	CT-3
Estimated mass flow rate	0.26 kg/s	1.94 kg/s	> 5 kg/s
Mass fraction (DEHS, PIVpart45)	0.0004%	0.00005%	< 0.00002%

$$\dot{m}_{f,min} = \frac{1 \cdot 10^{-9} \times \rho_p \times N_{jet}}{0.25 \cdot 10^{-2}} \quad (2.2)$$

Where N_{jet} is the number of jets created by Laskin nozzles. Fig. 2.8 presents the relation of the minimum mass flow rate of a wind tunnel with the number of Laskin nozzle jets used to seed oil droplets made of either DEHS or *Ondina X420*. The maximum number of jets are 14 and 45 for *PIVpart14* and *PIVpart45*, respectively. Table 2.2 summarizes the estimated mass flow rate and mass fraction for the experimental campaigns conducted in L-12, S-1/C, and CT-3 wind tunnels. The mass fraction is estimated assuming the use of 45 jets with DEHS oil, which provides the highest particle mass production rate from a single seeding generator. The mass fraction is far less than 0.25%, ensuring the absence of the two-phase flow effects due to the particle injection.

Figure 2.8: Minimum mass flow rate of a wind tunnel when tracer particles are injected by Laskin nozzles at $1 \text{ mm}^3/\text{s}$. Solid line: DEHS. Dashed line: Ondina X 420.

2.2.2 Governing equation of particle motion in a fluid

The differential equation governing the three-dimensional motion of a particle in a flow is expressed by the Basset-Boussinesq-Ossen (BBO) equation [4] and added terms for the gravity force and the buoyancy force.

$$m_p \frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_p}{\partial t} = \mathbf{F}_D + \mathbf{F}_{\nabla P} + \mathbf{F}_{A.M} + \mathbf{F}_{Basset} + \mathbf{F}_B \quad (2.3)$$

Where \mathbf{V}_p is the absolute velocity of particle and m_p is the particle mass. Assuming the particle is spherical with the diameter of d_p and density of ρ_p , the particle mass m_p is written

as:

$$m_p = \frac{\pi}{6} \rho_p d_p^3 \quad (2.4)$$

\mathbf{F}_D is the drag force that dominates the particle motion in most of fluid-particle systems:

$$\mathbf{F}_D = -\frac{\pi}{8} \rho d_p^2 (\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V}) |\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V}| C_D \quad (2.5)$$

where ρ is the fluid density and \mathbf{V} is the absolute velocity of fluid. C_D is the drag coefficient which is a function of the particle shape and particle Reynolds number Re_p .

$$Re_p = \frac{\rho |\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V}| d_p}{\mu} \quad (2.6)$$

Where μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid.

$\mathbf{F}_{\nabla P}$ is the force introduced by the pressure gradient surrounding the particle caused by the acceleration of the surrounding fluid:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\nabla P} = \frac{\pi}{6} \rho d_p^3 \frac{d\mathbf{V}}{dt} \quad (2.7)$$

$\mathbf{F}_{A.M}$ is the added mass force:

$$\mathbf{F}_{A.M} = -\frac{\pi}{12} \rho d_p^3 \frac{d(\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V})}{dt} \quad (2.8)$$

\mathbf{F}_{Basset} is the Basset history integral which takes into account the resistance caused by the unsteadiness of the flow field:

$$\mathbf{F}_{Basset} = -\frac{3}{2} d_p \sqrt{\pi \mu \rho} \int_{t_0}^t \frac{d(\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V})}{d\xi} \frac{d\xi}{\sqrt{t - \xi}} \quad (2.9)$$

\mathbf{F}_B is the body force acting on the particle. Here we consider the gravity \mathbf{F}_c , buoyancy \mathbf{F}_b , and centrifugal \mathbf{F}_c forces:

$$\mathbf{F}_B = \mathbf{F}_b + \mathbf{F}_c + \mathbf{F}_g \quad (2.10)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_g = \frac{\pi}{6} \rho_p d_p^3 \mathbf{g} \quad (2.11)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_b = -\frac{\pi}{6} \rho d_p^3 \mathbf{g} \quad (2.12)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_c = \frac{m V_{p,\theta}}{r^2} \mathbf{n}_r = \frac{\pi}{6} \rho_p d_p^3 \frac{V_{p,\theta}^2}{r} \mathbf{n}_r \quad (2.13)$$

where \mathbf{g} is the gravitational acceleration vector, $V_{p,\theta}$ is the tangential component of particle velocity with respect to the curvature of the streamline r , and \mathbf{n}_r is the unit vector in the radial direction.

Dividing by the particle mass, Eq. 2.3 is rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_p}{\partial t} = & -\frac{1}{24} \frac{Re_p}{\tau_{rlx}} |\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V}| C_D + \frac{1}{R_\rho} \frac{d\mathbf{V}}{dt} - \frac{1}{2R_\rho} \frac{d(\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V})}{dt} \\ & - \frac{1}{72\tau_{rlx}} \sqrt{\frac{Re_p d_p^3}{|\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V}|}} \int_{t_0}^t \frac{d(\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V})}{d\xi} \frac{d\xi}{\sqrt{t-\xi}} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{R_\rho}\right) \mathbf{g} + \frac{V_{p,\theta}}{r^2} \mathbf{n}_r \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

where R_ρ is the density ratio of the particle substance and the fluid, and τ_{rlx} is the relaxation time defined as:

$$R_\rho = \frac{\rho_p}{\rho} \quad (2.15)$$

$$\tau_{rlx} = \frac{\rho_p d_p^2}{18\mu} \quad (2.16)$$

For PIV experiments in gaseous flows, the density ratio of a particle to a fluid is often $R_\rho \gg 1$. For example, the density ratio of a DEHS oil droplet to air is $R_\rho = 707$. When the velocity gradient of the flow $d\mathbf{V}/dt$ (observed by the moving particle) and the gradient of the velocity gap between the particle and the fluid $d(\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V})/dt$ are small with respect to the density ratio R_ρ or the relaxation time τ_{rlx} , the second, third, and the fourth term on the right-hand side of Eq. 2.14 are often neglected [25]. The simplified form of Eq. 2.14 is:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_p}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{24} \frac{Re_p}{\tau_{rlx}} |\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V}| C_D + \mathbf{g} + \frac{V_{p,\theta}}{r^2} \mathbf{n}_r \quad (2.17)$$

Given the properties of fluid and particle and the velocity gap between them, the remaining unknown value is the drag coefficient C_D .

2.2.2.1 For low particle Reynolds number ($Re_p < 1$)

When the particle Reynolds number is less than unity, the drag coefficient is estimated analytically [26]:

$$C_D = \frac{8}{Re_p} \left(\frac{2 + 3\kappa}{1 + \kappa} \right) \quad (2.18)$$

where κ is the viscosity ratio of the particle substance to fluid ($= \mu_p/\mu$). For steady creeping flow (also known as the Stokes flow), the drag coefficient from Stokes's law is obtained as [26]:

$$C_D = \frac{24}{Re_p} \quad (2.19)$$

Substituting eq. 2.19 into eq. 2.20, the drag force is simplified to the Stokes' drag force:

$$\mathbf{F}_{D,Stokes} = -3\pi\mu d_p (\mathbf{V}_p - \mathbf{V}) \quad (2.20)$$

2.2.2.2 For high particle Reynolds number ($Re_p \geq 1$)

For the flow condition with the Reynolds number larger than unity, the drag coefficient can not be estimated anymore analytically due to the shape deformation of the particle and turbulence effect. Therefore, Numerical solutions and experimental databases are used to investigate the motion of particles. While drops made of fluid can deform when they are traveling in an external fluid media, it is known that liquid particles for a small Eötvös number $Eo < 0.15$ in air are closely spherical and the correlation for rigid sphere particles can be used [26]. The Eötvös number is defined as:

$$Eo = \frac{g\rho d_p^2}{\sigma_p} \quad (2.21)$$

where σ_p is the surface tension of the particle. Considering a DEHS particle with a diameter of $1 \mu\text{m}$, the Eötvös number is estimated to be about $Eo = 2.8 \times 10^{-7}$. Since Eo is much smaller than 0.15, we consider the seeding particles to be spherical in the investigated flows.

The drag coefficient of a spherical particle varies depending on the Re_p since the flow field surrounding the particle develops as the Reynolds number increases as shown in Fig. 2.9. The distribution of surface pressure on a sphere is associated with the flow field, resulting in the variation of drag coefficient.

Figure 2.9: Streamlines for flow passing a sphere from right to left. Values of stream function ψ are indicated [26]

Fig. 2.10 shows the conventional correlation for the drag on a sphere in a steady motion and presents a deviation of the standard drag coefficient from Stokes law. This figure indicates real drag coefficient is greater than the Stokes' drag, the neglected drag coefficient in the Stokes solution rises about 10% of the total drag coefficient at $Re_p = 1$. This deviation is mainly due to the existence of vortexes around the particles. As a summary, Table 2.3 presented in [27] gives correlation formulas suitable for each range of Reynolds numbers. For simplification, the correction of Schiller-Naumann [28] written as follows is employed for calculations in this study (including Lagrangian particle tracking simulation presented in section 4.2.2.2).

For $0 < Re_p < 800$,

$$C_D = \frac{24}{Re_p} (1 + 0.15Re_p^{0.687}) \quad (2.22)$$

For $800 \leq Re_p$,

$$C_D = \frac{24}{Re_p} \cdot 0.44Re_p^{2/4} \quad (2.23)$$

Figure 2.10: Drag coefficient of a sphere as a function of particle Reynolds number (standard drag curve). [26]

2.2.3 Estimation of particle frequency response in turbulent flows

In this subsection, we evaluate the response of particle motion against turbulent flows. For PIV measurements in gases, only the first term on the right-hand side (drag force) is important (see subsection 2.2.2). Note that here we assume the absence of shear effects and centrifugal forces for simplicity. Furthermore, neglecting the gravity force and considering only the terms aligned to the direction of the drag force and removing the absolute value sign, the governing equation Eq. 2.17 is reduced to:

$$\frac{\partial V_p}{\partial t} = -\frac{C_D Re_p}{24\tau_{rlx}} (V_p - V) = -C_{freq} (V_p - V) \quad (2.24)$$

where C_{freq} is the characteristic frequency of the particle motion [4] written as:

Table 2.3: Empirical correlations for the drag coefficient of spherical particles valid for $Re_p (= Re_t) < 200000$ [27].

Year	Investigator	C_d v Empirical correlation
1929	Goldstein [3] $Re_t < 2$	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t}$ (1 + polynomial of Re_t)
1933	Schiller-Naumann [4] $2 < Re_t < 800$	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.15 Re_t^{0.687})$
1940	Lapple-Shefferd [1]	Historical SDC data plot Fig. 1
1959	Torobin-Gauvin [5] $1 < Re_t < 100$	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.197 Re_t^{0.63} + 0.0026 Re_t^{1.38})$
1970	Kaskas [6]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} + \frac{4}{Re_t^{0.5}} + 0.4$
1970	Clift-Gauvin [7]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.15 Re_t^{0.687}) + \frac{0.42}{1 + \frac{47500}{Re_t^{1.16}}}$
1973	Brauer [8]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} + \frac{3.73}{Re_t^{0.5}} - 4830 Re_t^{0.5} / (1 - 300000 Re_t^{1.5}) + 0.49$
1982	Concha-Barrientos [9]	Power series up to power 7
1986	Flemmer-Banks [10] $Re_t < 8600$	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} 10^a a = 0.261 Re_t^{0.369} - 0.105 Re_t^{0.431} - 0.124 / (1 + (\log 2 Re_t))$
1986	Turton-Levenspiel [11]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.173 Re_t^{0.657}) + \frac{0.413}{1 + \frac{16300}{Re_t^{1.45}}}$
1987	Khan-Richardson [12]	$C_d = (2.25 Re_t^{-0.31} + 0.36 Re_t^{0.06})^{3.45}$
1989	Haider-Levenspiel [13]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.1806 Re_t^{0.6459}) + \frac{0.4251}{1 + \frac{58801.95}{Re_t}}$
1991	Hesket et al. [14]	Very complex
1993	Ganser [15]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.1118 Re_t^{0.6567}) + \frac{0.4305}{1 + \frac{3305}{Re_t}}$
1994	Hartman et al. [16]	See Turton Levenspiel
2003	Brown-Lawler [17]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.15 Re_t^{0.681}) + \frac{0.407}{1 + \frac{8710}{Re_t}}$
2008	Almedeij [18]	Very complex using 4 segments
2009	Cheng [19]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} (1 + 0.27 Re_t^{0.43} + 0.47 [1 - \exp(-0.04 Re_t^{0.38})])$
2013	Mikhailov-Freire [20]	Six polynomial terms in Goldstein's formula
2013	Terfous et al. [21] $50 < Re_t < 7400$	$C_d = 2.6589 + 21.683/Re_t + 0.131/Re_t^2 - 10.616/Re_t^{0.1} + 12.216/Re_t^{0.2}$
2015	Hongli et al. [22]	$C_d = \frac{24}{Re_t} + \frac{4.5}{T} + 0.087363 Re_t (1 + \frac{Re_t}{122}) + \text{complex error function}$

$$C_{freq} = \frac{C_D Re_p}{24 \tau_{rlx}} \quad \left(= \frac{1}{\tau_{rlx}} \text{ for the Stokes flow regime} \right) \quad (2.25)$$

Applying the Laplace transform to the Eq. 2.24 leads:

$$\frac{1}{C_{freq}} \mathcal{L} \left[\frac{\partial V_p}{\partial t} \right] + \mathcal{L} [V_p] = \mathcal{L} [V] \quad (2.26)$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{L} [V_p]}{\mathcal{L} [V]} = \frac{\mathcal{L} [V] C_{freq} + V_p(0)}{\mathcal{L} [V] (s + C_{freq})} \quad (2.27)$$

where $V_p(0)$ is the initial condition (at $t = 0$) of the particle velocity, here we consider $V_p(0) = 0$ focusing on the frequency response amplitude. Substituting $\omega = 2\pi f$ into s , the particle response in the frequency domain dependent on the C_{freq} is obtained.

$$\left| \frac{V_p}{V} \right| = \frac{C_{freq}}{2\pi f + C_{freq}} \quad (2.28)$$

This transfer function requires an estimation of the velocity gap $|V_p - V|$ which is used for the computation of Re_p (therefore C_{freq}).

Fig. 2.11 shows the relative fluctuation amplitude of particle to the fluid $|V_p/V|$ with assumption of (A) $|V_p - V| = 0$ and (B) $|V_p - V| = 10$ m/s. The fluid temperature is set to a constant value of 293 K. For the case of 1 μm DEHS particle moving in the fluid with ambient pressure, $|V_p/V| > 0.95$ is achieved below the frequency of 3 kHz. The low-pressure case

in which the absolute pressure of the flow is set to 1 kPa shows a very small effect on the particle response. While the plots of $1\ \mu\text{m}$ DEHS at atmospheric pressure and low pressure from case (A) do not show a difference, the plots from case (B) imply that the lower pressure of the fluid adversely affects the frequency response of the particle. This is due to the value of C_{freq} which is normally a function of Re_p becomes independent from Re_p when no velocity gap is assumed. Nevertheless, the deviation of the frequency response is small for a modest particle velocity gap. On the other hand, an increment of the diameter of the particle shows a significant impact, the particle with $5\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter can follow 95% of the fluid fluctuation only below 200 Hz.

Figure 2.11: The response of particles with different diameters in turbulent flows with different pressures. With initial condition of (A) $|V_p - V| = 0$ and (B) $|V_p - V| = 10\ \text{m/s}$.

The estimated frequency response of tracer particles is compared with the analysis made by Mei [29]. He defined the cut-off frequency $f_{\text{cut-off}}$ of the particle based on either 50% or 200% energy response:

$$f_{\text{cut-off}} = \frac{\nu_p}{\pi} \left(\frac{\epsilon_{\text{cut-off}}}{d_p/2} \right)^2 \quad (2.29)$$

where ν_p is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and $\epsilon_{\text{cut-off}}$ is the 50% cut-off Stokes number. For $R_\rho > 1.621$, $\epsilon_{\text{cut-off}}$ is defined as:

$$\epsilon_{\text{cut-off}} = \left[\left(\frac{3}{2R_\rho^{1/2}} \right)^n + \left(\frac{0.932}{R_\rho - 1.621} \right)^n \right]^{1/n}, \quad n = 1.05 \quad (2.30)$$

Fig. 2.12 shows the dependence of cut-off frequency on the particle diameter made of either DEHS or *Ondina X420*. For a particle sizing $d_p = 1.0\ \mu\text{m}$, the cut-off frequency is estimated to be about 65 kHz. This value is consistent with the frequency at which the fluctuation amplitude becomes 50% in Fig. 2.11.

2.2.4 Estimation of particle response through a shock

For high-speed (transonic and supersonic) flow, the motion of a particle of high density ratio R_ρ can be represented by Eq. 2.24, if a suitable expression for the drag coefficient C_D is

Figure 2.12: Cut-off frequencies as a function of particle diameters. Solid line: DEHS droplets. Dashed line: Ondina X420 droplets.

inserted [4]. The largest velocity gap between the particle and the fluid can be caused by a shock wave potentially occurring in the blade passage for the high-Mach number test cases.

Considering a shock wave as a negative step response with a magnitude of A , V is now written as:

$$\begin{aligned} V &= 0 \quad (t < 0) \\ V &= -A \quad (t \geq 0) \end{aligned} \quad (2.31)$$

$$\mathcal{L}[V] = \int_0^{+\infty} -A \cdot e^{-st} dt = -\frac{A}{s}$$

Note that the fluid velocity is set to zero for $t < 0$ for convergence of the Laplace transform. Substituting $\mathcal{L}(V)$ into the Eq. 2.27, the particle motion in s domain is described as:

$$\mathcal{L}[V] = \frac{A(C_{freq} + V_p(0))}{s(s + C_{freq})} \quad (2.32)$$

Assuming the particle is perfectly tracing the fluid before entering the shock wave, the initial condition of the particle velocity becomes $V_p(0) = 0$.

$$\mathcal{L}[V] = -A \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{s + C_{freq}} \right) \quad (2.33)$$

Applying the inverse Laplace transform for the above equation, the response of the particle relative to the fluid motion through the shock wave is obtained as:

$$V_p = -A (1 - e^{-C_{freq}t}) \quad (2.34)$$

Now, padding the initial velocity (the velocity upstream the shock wave) V_{ini} , the above equation becomes:

$$V_p = V_{ini} - A (1 - e^{-C_{freq}t}) \quad (2.35)$$

Fig 2.13 illustrates the response of a particle over a shock wave in (A) time-domain and (B) space-domain. The magnitude of the step is set to $A = 100$ m/s. Similarly to Fig. 2.11, different particle diameters and different pressures of the surrounding fluid are considered

($P_{low} = 1$ kPa). It is observed that lower pressure of fluid and larger size of particle negatively affect the particle response. For the case of $1 \mu\text{m}$ DEHS droplet in the ambient pressure flow, the particle motion lag can be up to 2 mm. This value is often larger than the vector resolution of PIV (~ 0.5 mm), resulting in a non-negligible filtering effect.

Figure 2.13: The response of particles with different diameters through a shock-wave. Two (A) Time-domain. (B) Space-domain.

2.2.5 Estimation of particle drift due to centrifugal force

For particles following curved streamlines such as those in flows over a cylinder or turbine blade, the inertia of the particles causes a deviation in their trajectories from the streamline. Fig. 2.14 illustrates a conceptual sketch of particle motion in a turning flow. The particle's velocity at any point on its trajectory is expressed by the radial and tangential components, $V_{p,r}$ and $V_{p,\theta}$. Since our interest lies in the particle drift in the radial direction due to centrifugal force, we assume the radial component of the flow is zero ($V_{f,r} = 0$) and the tangential component of the particle's velocity is equal to that of the fluid, $V_\theta = V_{f,\theta} = V_{p,\theta}$. The radial velocity gap between the particle and the fluid is $V_r = V_{p,r} - V_{f,r} = V_{p,r}$. The centrifugal force acting on the particle in the radial direction is:

$$F_c = \frac{mV_\theta^2}{r^2} = \frac{\pi}{6} \rho_p d_p^3 \frac{V_\theta^2}{r} \quad (2.36)$$

Figure 2.14: A particle traveling in a turning flow.

One may assume that the radial velocity component is the terminal velocity of the particle, where the centrifugal force is balanced with the drag resistance, $F_c = F_D$ [30]. Combining Eqs. 2.20 and 2.13 leads to:

$$\frac{\pi}{6} \rho_p d_p^3 \frac{V_\theta^2}{r} = \frac{\pi}{8} \rho_f d_p^2 V_r^2 C_D \quad (2.37)$$

Thus the ratio of radial to tangential velocity components becomes:

$$\frac{V_r^2}{V_\theta^2} = \frac{4}{3} \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_f} \frac{d_p}{r C_D} \quad (2.38)$$

For the case where the Stokes' law is applied, the above equation is simplified to:

$$\frac{V_r}{V_\theta} = \frac{d_p^2}{18\nu} \frac{\rho_p}{\rho_f} \frac{V_\theta}{r} \quad (2.39)$$

Fig. 2.15 shows V_r/V_θ for DEHS droplets of varying sizes moving in air. Each line represents a different ratio of local tangential velocity to the curvature of the streamline, $V_\theta/r = 1, 100, \text{ and } 10000$. It is evident that a higher radial (drifting) velocity occurs when the flow turns curves faster and the particles are larger.

Figure 2.15: Ratio of radial velocity to tangential velocity for DEHS droplet particle moving in air.

As an example, we consider a flow turning over the suction surface of the SPLEEN C1 blade, where the curvature is approximately $r \approx 15\text{mm}$ as shown in Fig. 2.16. The local freestream speed is about 150 m/s, resulting in the ratio of local tangential velocity to the curvature of the streamline of approximately 10000. If a DEHS droplet sizing $1 \mu\text{m}$ is seeded in this flow, the plot in Fig. 2.15 gives that the radial velocity of the particles would be about 3% of the tangential velocity, thus $V_r = 0.03 \times V_\theta = 4.5 \text{ m/s}$.

Now we estimate the trajectory of a particle in the turning flow. For sake of simplicity we consider the flow is a two-dimensional irrotational vortex with circulation of Γ . In the cylindrical coordinate, the radial flow velocity is zero ($V_{f,r} = 0$) and the tangential flow velocity is $V_{f,\theta} = \Gamma/2\pi r$ [31]. Recalling the assumption $V_\theta = V_{f,\theta} = V_{p,\theta}$, the circumferential distance traveled in a short time interval dt is $V_\theta dt = r d\theta$. The radial distance the particle moves during the time interval dt is $dr = V_r dt$. These give the following relation:

$$d\theta = \frac{r V_r}{V_\theta} dr \quad (2.40)$$

Figure 2.16: A sketch of the SPLEEN C1 blade.

Substituting the expressions for V_θ and V_r , then integrating from r_1 to r_2 , we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\theta &= \int_{r_1}^{r_2} \frac{rV_r}{V_\theta} dr \\ &= \frac{18\pi\nu}{d_p^2 R_\rho \Gamma} (r_2^2 - r_1^2)\end{aligned}\quad (2.41)$$

Where $\Delta\theta$ is the variation of particle location in the circumferential (θ) direction. Finally, the radial position of the particle at a given circumferential location is written as:

$$r_2 = \sqrt{\frac{d_p^2 R_\rho \Gamma}{18\pi\nu} |\Delta\theta| + r_1^2} \quad (2.42)$$

Fig. 2.17-left illustrates the trajectories of DEHS droplets of varying sizes following an irrotational vortex flow. The particle is released at a radius of 15 mm. To match $V_{f,\theta} = 150$ m/s at $r = 15$ mm, the circulation is set to $\Gamma = 14$ m²/s. The right figure shows the deviation of particle location in radial direction from the constant radius $r = 15$ mm. The impact of centrifugal force is already evident for a 1 μ m particle, the radial deviation amounts to about 1 mm after traveling 150 degrees of the turn. While a more accurate estimation is available from numerical approaches such as Lagrangian particle tracking, this simple calculation is helpful for first understanding the challenges of seeding in the vicinity of a high-speed turbine blade.

Figure 2.17: Left: Trajectory of particles with different sizes in an irrotational vortex.

2.3 Fluorescent particles

2.3.1 State-of-art

In order to overcome the problem of undesired light reflection appearing in particle images, various approaches can be undertaken. The most common approach is coating surfaces with black paint, which absorbs incident light to some extent [7, 32]. However, a high-intensity laser pulse can induce the ablation of coating material in a short period. Fig. 2.18 shows ablated matte-black paint applied to the endwall of a linear turbine cascade tested in the S-1/C wind tunnel. The picture was taken after approximately 10000 PIV image recordings. This situation is often encountered in measurements in high-speed flows since tracer particles are typically submicron scale, necessitating the use of high-intensity laser systems. In addition, in some test cases, additional coating may not be desirable, for instance, due to the requirement of a high-level surface quality for studying boundary layer development.

Figure 2.18: An ablated matte-black paint applied to the endwall of a linear turbine cascade in S-1/C.

Other approaches are to have well-polished surfaces to avoid diffusive light reflection and to make the propagation direction of the light parallel to the model surface as reported by Kähler et al. [33] (Fig. 2.19). However, it is not affordable to have such surfaces and illumination orientations for some applications with complex geometries.

Alternatively, tracer particles doped with dye and a wavelength-specific optical filter are utilized to extract the fluorescent light emitted by particles from reflection noises. This approach offers the advantage of not requiring surface treatment on the obstacles. Additionally, fluorescent particles can serve as labels in multi-phase or multi-constituent flows. For instance, one can distinguish a jet or spray from the surrounding flow by seeding one with fluorescent particles and the other with regular non-fluorescent ones. Such an approach can be potentially extended to investigations of rim-seal purge flows or blade film cooling flows. Employing two cameras equipped with appropriate optical filters, it becomes possible to simultaneously capture both global and specific flow fields. Such an approach has been applied for simultaneous measurements of two-phase flow mixing and interactions [34–36] and multi-constituent flows [37, 38]. In this study, the labeling capability of the fluorescent particle is assessed in the test case of the active turbulence grid (see sections 3.1 and 4.1).

Fluorescence is a type of luminescence, which is a light emitted from susceptible molecules (fluorophores) electronically excited by either physical, mechanical, or chemical mechanisms. When the excitation is done by light photons, the luminescence phenomenon is termed photoluminescence which can be further divided into two categories, fluorescence and phosphorescence. The lifetime of fluorescence is about 10^{-8} seconds whereas phosphorescence

Figure 2.19: Top: Sketch of the transparent test section with the flat plate located in the center. *a* Seeding supply; *b* laser-beam; *c* light-sheet optic; *d* mirrors. The graph above the plate indicates the calculated disturbance of the boundary layer edge velocity U_e/U due to the finite size of the model. Bottom: Acquired particle image. Perfect suppression of undesired wall-reflections due to tangential model illumination. (image size: $1,000 \cdot 150$ pixel) [33]

has much longer lifetime of $10^{-3} - 10^0$ seconds [39]. The fluorescence process consists of three main events, 1. Excitation (absorption), 2. Internal conversion and vibrational relaxation, 3. Emission of photons as illustrated in Jablonski energy diagram Fig. 2.20. The efficiency of excitation and absorption is dependent on the light spectrum. In general, the efficiency is < 1 , hence fluorescence emissions have less energy and they are shifted to longer wavelength than excitation light, as known as the Stokes shift. A commonly used parameter in describing fluorescence efficiency is quantum yield [39], which is the efficiency of fluorescence emission relative to all of the possible pathways for relaxation. It is generally expressed as the ratio of the number of photons emitted to that of absorbed. The quantum yield varies depending on the fluorophore and environmental factors such as pH, concentration, and solvent polarity.

Figure 2.20: One form of a Jablonski diagram.. [39].

The use of fluorescent tracer particles is a common technique in liquid flows as the constraints for the selection of the tracer particles are less strict compared to those for gas flows.

For example, particles for liquid flow can be large (from micron- to milli- scale), and matching their density to the flow medium is often possible. Furthermore, the majority of liquid flow applications are closed-loop, therefore tracer particles seeded in the flow can be reused repeatedly. This point is practically important as commercially available fluorescent particles are expensive to use as one-time seeding material (several hundreds of euros per 0.1 - 10 g).

In gaseous flows, particles in micron or sub-micron size are generally required to fulfill acceptable flow traceability. Moreover, a large quantity of tracer particles is required for seeding in wind tunnels, especially those with large-scale, high-speed, and open-looped systems.

Lee and Nishida [36] used fluorescent particles for a two-phase flow aiming at velocity field measurements of large liquid phase droplets and surrounding gas simultaneously and independently. Tracers (6.3 - 8.5 μm diameter) for the air motion were made of Rhodamine B (Rh-B) - water solution and illuminated by a 532 nm wavelength Nd:YAG laser. The light emitted from the fluorescent tracers was discriminated from the light scattered from the large droplets by an optical low-pass filter.

Similarly, Kosiwczuk et al. [40] investigated the use of fluorescent particles for two-phase flow, but both tracers for air motion and large droplets were dye-doped. Stilbene 420 was dissolved in methanol and formed into 1-5 μm droplets using a nebulizer to track the gas-phase flow. The particles were illuminated by a frequency-tripled Nd:YAG laser (355 nm wavelength) and fluorescence emissions were separated by a set of optical filters. It is assumed that these methanol-base fluorescent particles can be only used in a room or low-temperature environment due to the low boiling point of methanol (64.7 C°).

Chennaoui et al. [41] developed micron-sized Bis-MSB dye-doped o-xylene droplet which has a high excitation efficiency in the UV light range. The dye performance in the droplets was evaluated quantitatively in stable emulsion state and PIV was performed in a laboratory flow around a metal blade.

Petrosky et al. [42] demonstrated PIV using Kiton Red 620 (KR620) doped submicron scale Polystyrene Latex microspheres in a free jet and a two-phase flow apparatus. A conventional 532 nm double pulsed Nd:YAG at 200 mJ/pulse intensity illuminated the flow and a 560 nm long pass optical filter blocked Mie scattered light and reflections.

Bhattacharya et al. [5] performed PIV in a multistage research compressor using Rhodamine B 610 (Rh-B) doped tracer particles based on propylene glycol includes 1.3% by volume of ethanol to reduce surface tension of the seeding fluid. A 532 nm Nd:YAG laser illuminated flow and a 540 nm long pass filter blocked undesired reflections. Table 2.4 shows the summary of the fluorescent tracer particles used for PIV measurements in gas-phase flows.

In this study, an alternative fluorescent-doped tracer particle was explored for application in turbomachinery flows. The specified requirements are outlined as follows:

- Easy preparation
- Sub-micron size
- High fluorescent emission efficiency at 527 - 532 nm wavelength excitation (for Nd:YLF and Nd:YAG laser system)
- Large enough Stokes shift

Table 2.4: List of fluorescent particles used for gas-phase flows.

Dye	Medium	Diameter	Boiling point of medium	Excitation wavelength	Laser pulse intensity	Filter	Ref.
Rh-B	Water	6.3 - 8.5 μm	373 K	532 nm	25 mJ	560 nm low-pass filter	[36]
Stilnebe 420	Methanol	1 - 5 μm	338 K	355 nm	110 mJ	475AGSP BG12	[40]
Bis-MSB	O-xylene	1 μm	417 K	355 nm	30 mJ	-	[41]
KR620	Polystyrene latex microspheres	1 μm	703 K	532 nm/ 527 nm	200 mJ/ 4 mJ	560 nm low-pass filter	[42]
Rh-B	Propylene glycol + ethanol (1.3%)	NA	461 K	532 nm	NA	540 nm low-pass filter	[5]
P567	DEHS	1 μm	523 K	527 nm	22 mJ	532 \pm 10 nm band-stop filter	

- Feasibility to be seeded in large quantities economically
- Temperature resistance (500 K < Flash point)
- Low hazardous impact on the environment and human body

2.3.2 Materials for fluorescent tracer particles

For the base medium of particles, Di-Ethyl-Hexyl-Sebacat (DEHS) is selected as it has been widely used for PIV in gaseous flows and it is compatible with Laskin nozzle particle generators which can produce a large number of submicron droplets (approximately 10^8 particles / second). It also has a higher boiling point of 523 K compared to other candidates such as methanol or olive oil. Pyrromethene 567 (P567) is selected as a fluorescent dye considering its high fluorescent emission efficiency at 527 nm wavelength excitation and solubility in DEHS [43]. The dependency of the fluorescence intensity of P567 on temperature has a positive slope (Fig. 2.21), which is favorable for conducted measurements in high enthalpy flows.

In addition, it must be noted that toxicities of materials are also important aspects as seeded gas is inherently more difficult to contain in designated space than liquid. Table 2.5 summarizes the hazardousness classification of fluorescent dyes according to regulation (EC) No 1272/2008. While KR620 is an attractive product that has no classification as a hazardous substance, it is not used in this study due to its uncertainty in the fabrication process of dyed particles. While KR620 is known to dissolve in water and alcohols [44], the solubility characteristic in DEHS is not verified. The application reported by Petrosky et al. [42] dopes polystyrene particles with KR-620, involving several fabrication processes requiring special know-how and equipment. The hazardous level of P567 is in general lower compared to the most commonly used Rhodamine 6G or Rhodamine B. Nevertheless, the product must be dealt with care, with the installation of proper protective measures such as ventilators and masks in order to avoid contamination of respiratory organs as well as skin and eye protection.

2.3.3 Spectroscopy measurements on bulk P567-DEHS solution

Spectroscopic measurements were conducted to investigate the transition of the emission spectrum due to the Stokes shift and its dependency on dye concentrations. Fig. 2.22 shows the preparation of the specimens. The quantity of dye was measured based on its weight

Figure 2.21: Fluorescence versus temperature for Pyrromethene 567 and Rhodamine 640 [45].

Table 2.5: Hazardousness classification of fluorescent dyes based on regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.

Dye	Signal	Skin	Eye	Oral	Aquatic hazard	Specific target organ toxicity
Rh-6G	Danger	Sensitization H317	Serious damage H318	Toxic if swallowed H301	Very toxic H400, H410	-
Rh-B	Danger	-	Serious damage H318	Harmful if swallowed H302	Harmful H412	-
Stilnebe 420	Danger	Irritation H315	Serious damage H318	-	Harmful H412	May cause Respiratory irritation H335
Bis-MSB	Warning	-	Irritation H319	Harmful if swallowed H302	May harmful H413	-
P567	Warning	Irritation H315	Irritation H319	-	-	May cause Respiratory irritation H335
KR620	-	-	-	-	-	-

while DEHS was measured based on its volume. The dye was dissolved into DEHS with the help of agitation and heating ($< 100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

The dye solutions were contained in disposable cuvettes (*BRAND 759030*) made of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) with external dimensions of $12.5\text{ mm} \times 12.5\text{ mm}$. The cuvettes were held vertically using a 3D-printed cuvette holder whose inner surfaces were painted black in order to minimize internal reflection. The solutions were excited by a high-speed dual cavity Nd:YLF laser system (Quantronix Darwin-Duo, 527 nm wavelength) as shown in Fig. 2.23 and 2.24. The fluorescent spectra of these bulk solutions were measured using a spectrometer (Ocean Optics HR4000) in a similar setup described in Kosiwczuk et al. [40].

Figure 2.22: Preparation of DEHS-P567 solutions for spectroscopy test.

Cuvette + holder

Test setup

Figure 2.23: Spectroscopy setup.

Figure 2.24: Schematic of spectroscopy setup.

The data acquisition setting and laser operating setting are presented in Table 2.6. The spectroscopy measurement was carried out at room temperature (293 K). Table 2.7 shows the variation of tested specimens. The maximum concentration tested was 5 g/L since adding more amount of P567 resulted in agglomerations of the dye particles in the solution.

Table 2.6: The setup parameters for spectroscopy.

Laser: Quantronix Darwin Duo		
Laser current	11	A
Laser pulse intensity	< 8	mJ
Laser repetition	1000	Hz
Spectrometer: Ocean Insight: HR4000CG-UV-NIR		
Spectrometer exposure	1	s
Number of samples for averaging	10	acquisition
Wavelength resolution	0.270	nm

The light emission spectra of the empty cuvette and pure DEHS solution contained in the cuvette when excited by Nd:YLF laser are shown in Fig. 2.25. The sharp intensity signal is observed at 527 nm, and there is no significant fluorescent light emission. The fluctuation in the values is due to the sampling noise.

Fig. 2.26 shows the light emission spectra of P567 + DEHS solution for different concentrations. For better visibility, each plot is moving-window averaged over three adjacent

Table 2.7: List of specimens.

Sample ID	Solvent	Solute	Concentration g/L
1	-	-	-
2	DEHS	-	0
3	DEHS	P567	0.001
4	DEHS	P567	0.005
5	DEHS	P567	0.01
6	DEHS	P567	0.05
7	DEHS	P567	0.1
8	DEHS	P567	0.5
9	DEHS	P567	1
10	DEHS	P567	5

Figure 2.25: Light emission spectrum of cuvette and DEHS excited by Nd:YLF laser. The plotted data were the moving average of the nearest three points (center and adjacent values in both wavelength-wise).

wavelength samplings. The average processing is reasonable in this plot because the spectrum curves are continuous and seamless. The maximum fluorescent light emission is observed at 0.005 g/L, and as the dye concentration decreases, the peak wavelength is shifted to the shorter wavelength. Over different concentrations, the emission peaks appeared in a range between 540 and 585 nm. The non-linearity of fluorescence intensity to the dye concentration is due to the fluorescence quenching [39]. Presumably, the effect of so-called “inner-filter” or “self-absorption” has a dominant impact in the present case. The light emission measured by the instrument is attenuated due to the absorption of the excitation light and the absorption of the emitted fluorescence through the optically dense fluorescent solution itself. The apparent fluorescence intensity and spectral distribution can be strongly dependent on the optical density of the sample, the orientation and depth of the optical path, and the geometry of the container (cuvette) and illumination.

Figure 2.26: Fluorescent light emission of P567 + DEHS excited by Nd:YLF laser. The specimen was contained in the cuvette. The plotted data were the moving-window average of the nearest three points (center and adjacent values in both wavelength-wise).

For example, Fig. 2.27 [39, 46] illustrates the fluorescence spectra of anthracene contained in a 1 cm × 1 cm cuvette at different dye concentrations. The fluorescence intensity decreases as the concentration increases. The pronounced attenuation of the blue edge of the emission is due to the overlap of the absorption and emission spectra. This re-absorption effect can significantly impact the fluorescence wavelength spectra. Fig. 2.28 [39] shows Rhodamine 6G solutions at different concentrations (left) and their emission spectra. The shorter wavelength part of the emission is absorbed in higher-concentration solutions, resulting in the emission spectra shifting dramatically to longer wavelengths.

Due to this fluorescence quenching effect, the spectroscopic measurement on bulky dye solutions does not represent the fluorescence emission on sub-micron scale droplets with corresponding dye concentrations. The same statement is found in the literature [41]. Still, the acquired data is helpful to forecast the possible spectra and to determine proper optical filters. An optical density (OD)-6 optical band-stop filter that has a central wavelength of 532 nm with 10 nm Full-Width-at-Half-Maximum (FWHM) was selected for the following measurements in order to effectively separate excitation light and fluorescence emission.

Figure 2.27: Fluorescent emission spectra of Anthracene solutions at different concentrations. A $1\text{ cm} \times 1\text{ cm}$ cuvette was used with right-angle observation. [39, 46]

Figure 2.28: Effect of concentrations on the color and emission spectra of Rhodamine 6G. The concentrations of R6G are 5×10^{-6} , 1.6×10^{-4} , and $5.7 \times 10^{-3} M$ [39].

2.3.4 Characteristics evaluation on fluorescent particles in low-speed wind tunnel L-12

An evaluation of the characteristics of the fluorescent particles was conducted in the L-12 low-speed wind tunnel of VKI. The detailed description of the wind tunnel is found in 3.1.3. First, the dye concentration suitable for PIV measurements in the form of sub-micron droplets is assessed by comparing pixel intensities of raw fluorescent particle images. Solutions with seven dye concentrations, 0, 0.75, 1.00, 1.25, 1.50, 1.75, and 2.00 g/L, are prepared and formed into sub-micron particles by the *PIVTEC PIVPart14* Laskin nozzle seeding generator. Fig. 2.29 shows the test setup. The particles are seeded in the blower installed upstream of the settling chamber. The channel of the test section is made of acrylic plates and has an approximately 200 mm \times 150 mm sectional area. An 18 mm-high backward-facing step (BFS) is installed in the middle of the test section. The mean flow speed at the wind tunnel exit is set to 5 m/s. A high-speed Phantom M310 camera and a high-speed Nd:YLF (527 nm wavelength) *Quantronix Darwin-Duo* laser are synchronized at 1 kHz by digital delay/pulse generators (*MODEL DG535*). The camera is equipped with a *Nikon AF Micro-Nikkor 60mm f/2.8D* lens. An optical band-stop filter (532 nm central cut-off wavelength, 10 nm FWHM) is attached to the lens when fluorescent images are taken.

Figure 2.29: Fluorescent particle measurement setup in L-12 low-speed wind tunnel.

Fig. 2.30 presents (A) a field of view with a calibration plate, (B) raw particle image capturing Mie scattering, and (C, D) raw particle images capturing fluorescent light emissions at dye concentrations of 0.75 g/L and 2.0 g/L, respectively. The close-up view near the bottom corner of the BFS is shown in Fig. 2.31. The RMS of calibration fitting by pin-hole model is 0.27 pixels for Mie scattering and 0.32 pixels for fluorescent (with the optical filter) setups.

The pulse intensity is regulated to 8 mJ for the recording of Mie scattering images to avoid damaging the camera sensor. On the other hand, 22 mJ pulse energy is used for fluorescent particle imaging. The lens aperture is set to $f/4.0$ for all cases. In the Mie scattering test case, a significant light reflection is captured on the wall surfaces and neighboring pixels. On the other hand, the fluorescent imaging technique substantially suppresses reflection while maintaining signals of the particle images. For cases C and D, the light sheet reflection on the bottom plate are not visible, but the location of the bottom plate surface can be recognized from the mirrored particle image appearing near $y = 0$. Among fluorescent cases, a slightly better contrast of particle image against the background is observed at the higher dye concentration as shown in (C) and (D).

Figure 2.30: (A) Calibration image, (B) particle image with Mie scattering, (C) fluorescent particle image with 0.75 g/L and (D) 2.0 g/L dye concentrations. The red rectangle indicates the ROI used for histogram presented in Fig. 2.32.

Fig. 2.32 (A) illustrates pixel intensity histograms within ROI of 3000 fluorescent particle images for different dye concentrations. The intensity is normalized by the bit depth of the camera sensor. The ROI is indicated with a red rectangle in Fig. 2.30 (D) and is defined in the area where the illumination is homogeneous, background noise is low, and a high seeding concentration is achieved. The higher the dye concentration, the population peak of pixel intensity shifts towards a higher level. Fig. 2.32 (B) presents a plot of area-averaged pixel intensity of each histogram for corresponding dye concentrations. Within the measured range, the relation is almost linearly proportional, implying the absence of the self-absorption effect at the demonstrated particle size and seeding density. The optimum dye concentration is therefore to be chosen considering the cost and solubility of the dye, sensitivity of cameras, and performance of optical filters. The demonstrations in this study show practically achievable setups that can be also applicable to typical PIV applications.

To validate the efficacy of the reflection removal, the fluorescent particle was also tested

Figure 2.31: Close-up view of (B) pararticle image with Mie scattering, (C) fluorescent particle image with 0.75 g/L and (D) 2.0 g/L dye concentrations.

Figure 2.32: (A) Histogram of pixel intensity averaged over ROI of 3000 images for different dye concentrations. (B) Plot of mean pixel intensities for different dye concentrations.

with an actual research turbine blade. Fig. 2.33 (A) shows the tested turbine blade manufactured in titanium alloy (Ti6Al4V) which was previously tested under an engine representative test condition in a high-speed rotating turbine test facility (CT-3) at the VKI [47]. The blade was placed in the rectangular test section in the L-12 wind tunnel. The same instruments used for the aforementioned tests with BFS were employed. The laser sheet was arranged so that the laser sheet impinges on the blade suction side. The camera captures images on the blade-to-blade plane as shown in Fig. 2.33 (B) (C). Pure DEHS particles and the fluorescent particles with 2.0 g/L dye concentration were tested. The aperture of the lens and laser pulse intensity were set to $f/11$ and 9 mJ for the recording of pure DEHS particle images (Mie-scattering images), whereas fluorescent particle images were recorded with $f/4$ and 22 mJ.

Figure 2.33: Test setup with a research turbine blade placed in the L-12 low-speed wind tunnel.

Fig. 2.34 presents exemplary instantaneous particle images of (left) Mie scattering and (right) fluorescent emission signals. The Mie scattering image exhibits a strong light reflection appearing as a line on the blade suction surface. Additionally, the blade hub endwall is evident in the background as it is illuminated by diffusion reflection. On the contrary, the fluorescent image shows none of them. Within such images, the minimum wall-normal distance that PIV can measure is not limited by pixel saturation caused by reflections on the surface. Instead, the vector resolution near the wall is constrained by either the finite interrogation window size required for cross-correlation algorithms or the particle image size.

Fig. 2.35 shows instantaneous vector fields computed from (left) Mie scattering and (right) fluorescent images presented in Fig. 2.34. A zoomed view and correlation map of the interrogation window indicated with the red rectangle are presented in the bottom left corner. A multi-pass cross-correlation method starting from 128-pixel initial square windows to 24-pixel final square windows was used for vector computation. The window overlap was set to 50% for the last pass, resulting in a vector computation every approximately 0.5 mm. Computed vectors were validated through peak-to-peak ratio and median filter while no smoothing nor vector interpolation tools were activated. Close to the blade surface (the area indicated with a red rectangle), the correlation map in the Mie scattering image is strongly affected by the reflection, thus the vector estimation in this region is questionable. In the fluorescent PIV case, thanks to the suppression of the reflection, a distinctive peak can be found in the correlation map and also the vector field shows a small vortex resolved near the wall with a reasonable continuity along the surroundings.

Furthermore, a statistical assessment of image quality is demonstrated by comparing the

Figure 2.34: Exemplary particle images. Left: Mie scattering particle image. Right: Fluorescent particle image.

Figure 2.35: Instantaneous vector fields computed from Fig. 2.34. Left: From Mie scattering particle image. Right: From fluorescent particle image. The 3D maps show correlation maps of the interrogation windows indicated by red rectangles.

number of valid vectors at each interrogation window over 1500 instantaneous datasets as shown in Fig. 2.36. Before vector computation, mean background subtraction, moving window background subtraction, and particle intensity normalization were performed. Note that, the area at top left corner of the field of view was poorly illuminated therefore vector estimation was often not successful. Overall, the fluorescent PIV improved the number of valid vectors by approximately 5% compared to conventional Mie scattering PIV, conceivably thanks to a high signal-to-noise ratio resulting from the reduction of background noise.

Remarkably, a large fraction of vectors near the perimeter of the blade hub platform (indicated by a red dotted line) were labeled invalid for the Mie scattering case. Arguably, some vectors in this region were computed from high-contrast image patterns consisting of the illuminated hub surface (high intensity) and empty background (low intensity). Such vectors should be discarded as they do not represent the flow. Minimizing background reflections in raw images is therefore important to obtain reliable measurement results and is even more crucial in applications containing moving parts such as turbomachinery because background image subtraction is usually not applicable due to image-to-image variations. Under such circumstances, the advantage of the fluorescent PIV technique as a countermeasure against undesired reflections is further emphasized.

Figure 2.36: Fraction of retained valid vector over 1500 instantaneous vector fields. Left: From Mie scattering particle image. Right: From fluorescent particle image.

2.4 Laser endoscopes

Applications of PIV measurements often require a case-specific approach to realize suitable optical access. Having adequate optical access is challenging for turbomachinery test facilities due to the confined flow path and the complex geometry of test rigs. A solution for this challenge is to use a laser endoscope that delivers the light source into the interrogated region of the test facility. Fig. 2.37, 2.38, 2.39, 2.40 show the designs of laser endoscope employed in precedent studies. Each test rig has specific integration features such as the size and location of the slot for measurement probes, therefore developing a tailored laser endoscope suited for each environment is necessary. This section discusses the design of laser endoscopes employed in the presented studies.

Figure 2.37: The light sheet endoscope used at MIT. [16].

Figure 2.38: Two different light sheet endoscopes used for PIV. (A) The endoscope used at Graz University of Technology [48]. (B) The endoscope used at DLR [49]

Figure 2.39: The light sheet endoscope used at the Technical University of Darmstadt [12]

Figure 2.40: The laser endoscope for volumetric illumination used at the University of Bath [50]

Table 2.8: Required specifications for laser sheet endoscope.

Required specification	
Outer diameter	8 mm
Length of insertion part	200 mm
Sheet angle	90 degree
Beam waist location	Adjustable
Sealing	Airtight (Up to 1 bar)

2.4.1 Required specifications

The first consideration is to define the design space for the structure of the endoscope. For the PIV application to the CT-3 test rig, the outer diameter of the endoscope was imposed to be 8 mm due to the limited access existing in the casing components. For S-1/C, there was no strict restriction in terms of mechanical assembly features. The required length of the insertion part (cylinder part) of the endoscope is about 200 mm for setting the laser sheet at the blade midspan. The output of the endoscope needs to be a laser sheet that illuminates the plane perpendicular to the scope axis for an ideal right-angle orientation between the camera and the laser sheet. The thickness of the laser sheet and the location of the beam waist should be adjustable in order to offer the versatility of the scope. The part of the endoscope inserted into the test section must be sealed since both S-1/C and CT-3 operate under a vacuumed condition. The maximum pressure difference the endoscope needs to hold is 1 bar. Finally, the optics used in the endoscope must be available off-the-shelf to avoid excessive cost. The requirements are summarized in Table. 2.8.

2.4.2 Selection of optics for the endoscope head

To form the laser sheet from a laser beam and bend it 90 degrees, the use of a cylindrical lens and a mirror or a right-angle prism is considered. The cylindrical lens must be embedded in the tip of the endoscope otherwise a diverging laser sheet is intercepted by the internal

wall of the scope cylinder. Considering the imposed outer diameter of 8 mm as well as the minimum wall thickness of the cylinder to ensure structural strength and assemblability, the size of the optics has to be smaller than 6 mm. The optics found available off-the-shelf are listed in Table 2.9.

Table 2.9: Off-the-shelf optics for laser endoscope.

Optics type	Serial number	Supplier	Size	Description
Plano-concave cylindrical lens	LK1395L1	Thorlabs	4 mm x 6 mm	$f = -3.91$ mm N-BK7 $T_r > 90\%$ @ 532 nm
Plano-concave cylindrical lens	LK1523L1	Thorlabs	4 mm x 6 mm	$f = -5.79$ mm N-BK7 $T_r > 90\%$ @ 532 nm
Right-angle prism	PS905	Thorlabs	Length of legs: 3 mm	N-BK7 $T_r > 90\%$ @ 532 nm
Right-angle prism	PS909	Thorlabs	Length of legs: 5 mm	N-BK7 $T_r > 90\%$ @ 532 nm
Right-angle prism mirror	49-405	Edmund optics	Length of legs: 3 mm	N-BK7 with Al coating $R_f > 95\%$ @ 450 - 650 nm LIDT: 0.2 J/cm
Right-angle prism mirror	MRA05-K13	Thorlabs	Length of legs: 5 mm	N-BK7 with K13 coating $R_f > 98\%$ @ 532 nm AOI: 0 to 45 degree LIDT: 8 J/cm
Right-angle prism mirror	45-591	Edmund optics	Length of legs: 5 mm	N-BK7 with Al coating $R_f > 95\%$ @ 450 - 650 nm LIDT: 0.2 J/cm

LIDT: Laser-induced damage threshold. Values presented are for a pulsed laser with 532 nm wavelength and 10 ns pulse length.

AOI: Angle of incidence

T_r : Transmittance.

R_f : Reflectance.

For the cylindrical lens, LK1523L1 is chosen considering the modest refractive power of the lens compared to LK1395L1. Too wide diverging angle can result in a protrusion of the laser sheet from the downstream mirror/prism surface and the outlet opening of the endoscope head. For the optics to bend the laser sheet 90 degrees, MRA05-K13 is selected based on the high reflectance, the wide range of acceptable angle of incidence (AOI), and the relatively high laser-induced damage threshold (LIDT).

2.4.3 Design of endoscopes

Two endoscopes, TUR1715-301 and TUR2022-A02, were designed and manufactured at VKI. TUR1715-301 is the first prototype originally designed for use in the CT-3 test rig during a test campaign titled *NEXT: Numerical and Experimental Research for High-Pressure Turbines* [51, 52]. TUR2022-A02 is the second prototype designed for use in the C-1 low-

speed linear cascade test facility during the *Power-to-Olefins* project [53] (not presented in this thesis) and in the S-1/C high-speed linear cascade test facility the *SPLEEN* project.

Fig. 2.41 illustrates the overview of the insertion part of laser endoscope TUR1715-301. The insertion part of the endoscope is composed of three cylindrical parts, a head part, a joint part, and an extension part. All pieces were made of brass tubes with an outer diameter of 8 mm to fit the existing slot for probes in the CT-3 test section. The head part has two pockets machined laterally to accommodate the optics. The upper pocket hosts LK1523L1 cylindrical lens and the opening was closed with a thin brass sheet cover. The lower pocket accommodates the MRA05-K13 right-angle prism mirror, and the opening was closed with a window made of a small Plexiglas plate. Due to the limited space and necessity of minimum thickness of the plate and surface to be bonded, a small excess of enclosure from the outer surface of the cylinder had to be tolerated. The inner diameter of the beam inlet of the head part was enlarged to 6.5 mm to provide maximized access for optics assembly. For bonding the optics to the head part, *Norland Optical Adhesive 61 (NOA 61)* was used. Once the optics were embedded in the head part, the head part and the joint part were sealed with the bond. An internal M7×1 thread was machined in one side of the joint part and external M7×1 threads were made in both sides of the extension cylinder. This modular assembly feature allows the user to individually exchange the extension part and the head part. A sealing tape must be used for the connection between the joint part and the extension part to secure the airtightness. Furthermore, a removable head provides a noticeable convenience for the precision alignment of the laser beam.

Fig. 2.42 presents the whole view of the laser endoscope TUR1715-301 and Table 2.10 lists the consisting parts. Upstream the insertion part, several adaptors were attached to have a standard optical component thread (SM1) that allows flexible interchange of upstream parts. For TUR1715-301, a non-rotating zoom housing (*Thorlabs SMINRI*) that can adjust the tube length within a range of 50.8 mm was attached. At the inlet end of the endoscope, typically a spherical lens was attached to converge the laser beam. The thickness and the location of the beam waist were controlled by the selection of the spherical lens and the length of the zoom housing. For the test cases performed in this thesis, a plano-convex spherical lens with a focal length of 515 mm was used.

The path and irradiance distribution of the laser beam through the endoscope were predicted using a free demo version of a commercial ray tracing software, *Photon Engineering FRED*. Fig. 2.43 displays the 3D model of the ray tracing simulation. The input laser beam was simulated by a Gaussian envelope function with a $1/e^2$ radius of 1.25 mm. For simplicity and scalability, the total power of the light source was set to 1.0 W. The demo version restricted the number of traceable rays, resulting in the discretization of the beam profile with only 21 rays. A plano-convex spherical lens with a focal length of 515 mm, which controls the laser sheet thickness, was positioned between the light source and the endoscope cylinder. In the scope head, a plano-concave cylindrical lens with a focal length of -5.79 mm, a mirror prism, and a sealing window were modeled to account for ray refraction through each optical component.

Fig. 2.44 presents the beam profiles (irradiance) examined at analysis planes 1-3 indicated in Fig. 2.43. Analysis plane 1 shows the input Gaussian beam profile. The analysis planes 2 and 3, located 100 mm and 200 mm away from the endoscope, respectively, show a thin laser sheet profile as expected. The multiple peaks observed in the outlet beam profiles are

Figure 2.41: The insertion part of TUR1715-301 laser endoscope.

Figure 2.42: The overview of TUR1715-301 laser endoscope.

Table 2.10: List of parts used in TUR1715-301 laser endoscope. The indicator is shown in Fig. 2.42.

Indicator	Part number	Description
1	TUR1715_301.01	Scope head
2	TUR1715_301.02	Scope head joint
3	TUR1715_301.03	Scope cylinder
4	TUR1715_301.04	M7 - M27 adapter
5	SM1A55	M27 - SM1 adapter
6	SM1L05	SM1 lens tube 0.5 inch
7	SM1L10	SM1 lens tube 1.0 inch
8	SM1NR1	Telescopic lens tube
9	SM2A6	SM1 - SM2 adapter
10	SM2T1	SM2 female-female tube
11	SM2NFM2	SM2-Fmount adaptor
12	TUR1715_301.07	Tip cylindrical lens cover
13	TUR1715_301.06	Tip window
14	MRA05-K13	Right angle mirror prism
15	LK1523L1	Plano-concave cylindrical lens ($f = -5.79$ mm)
16	NA	Plano-convex spherical lens ($f = 515$ mm)

Figure 2.43: 3D model of ray tracing simulation.

principally due to the limited number of traceable rays, preventing the accurate estimation of the actual irradiance distribution. Nevertheless, the ray tracing simulation verified the absence of major interference between the endoscope body and the laser beam and outlined the irradiance at the outlet, demonstrating the proof-of-concept of the endoscope design.

Figure 2.44: Distribution of irradiance examined at analysis planes 1-3.

The design of TUR2022-A02 took place after several uses of the TUR1715-301. Based on the experience with the first prototype, a few updates were implemented in the design of TUR2022-A02. Fig. 2.45 and 2.46 show the design of the head part and overview of the TUR2022-A02 endoscope. A major modification was applied to the design of the head part, while parts 5-11 are maintained the same as the TUR1715-301 endoscope. The items that differ from the TUR1715-301 endoscope are listed in Table. 2.11 It was found that the window made of *Plexiglas* attached to the endoscope head is prone to damage due to the high-intensity laser pulses at the location. The use of *Plexiglas* for the window was a compromised choice since manufacturing such a small piece out of more durable materials such as quartz glass was not readily available. TUR2022-A02 was not planned to be used in CT-3 test rig, thus the outer diameter of the endoscope was increased to 9 mm. The increased diameter opened up the design space, allowing the use of an off-the-shelf quartz glass cylinder as a window while the light sheet optics remained the same. The light sheet optics were mounted on the internal body and it was fastened between the scope cylinder and top cap, and covered with the window.

The implementation of these scopes in the test facilities is described in section 3.2.5 and 3.3.3.

Table 2.11: List of parts used in TUR2022-A02 laser endoscope. The indicator is shown in Fig. 2.46.

Indicator	Part number	Description
1	TUR2022_A03_011	Scope head cap
2	TUR2022_A03_010	Scope head internal body
3	TUR2022_A03_013	Scope cylinder
4	TUR2022_A03_014	$\phi 8$ - M27 adapter
13	TUR1715_301_06	Tip quartz cylinder window
14	MRA05-K13	Right angle mirror prism
15	LK1523L1	Plano-concave cylindrical lens ($f = -5.79$ mm)

Figure 2.45: The insertion part of TUR2022-A02 laser endoscope.

Figure 2.46: The overview of TUR2022-A02 laser endoscope.

2.5 Data reduction procedures

2.5.1 Velocity components and flow angle

In PIV measurements, the components of flow velocity are computed from the estimated particle displacement X_{di} in corresponding directions i , separation time between two successive laser pulses t_s , and scaling factor F_s that converts the displacement information from pixel-domain to physical-domain.

$$V_i = F_s \frac{X_{di}}{t_s} \quad (2.43)$$

$(i = x, y, z, \text{ or axi, tan, rad})$

Fig. 2.47 illustrates a coordinate system of an exemplary turbine cascade.

Figure 2.47: Coordinate system of an exemplary turbine cascade.

The flow angle is decomposed into two components, the yaw angle (primary flow direction) β and pitch angle γ . The yaw angle is the angle between the axial direction and the flow velocity projected on the xy - (axial-tangential) plane. The pitch angle is the angle between the axial direction and the flow velocity projected on the xz - (axial-span) plane. The two components are calculated by:

$$\beta = \tan^{-1} \frac{V_y}{V_x} \quad \text{or} \quad = \tan^{-1} \frac{V_{\text{tan}}}{V_{\text{axi}}} \quad (2.44)$$

$$\gamma = \tan^{-1} \frac{V_z}{V_x} \quad \text{or} \quad = \tan^{-1} \frac{V_{\text{rad}}}{V_{\text{axi}}} \quad (2.45)$$

For the analysis of secondary flows for turbine cascades, the velocity is decomposed into streamwise, crosswise, and spanwise components (denoted as V_{str} , V_{crs} , and V_{rad} , respectively) using the following equations:

$$V_{\text{str}} = V_{\text{axi}} \cos \overline{\beta_{MS}} + V_{\text{tan}} \sin \overline{\beta_{MS}} \quad (2.46)$$

$$V_{\text{crs}} = V_{\text{tan}} \cos \overline{\beta_{MS}} - V_{\text{axi}} \sin \overline{\beta_{MS}} \quad (2.47)$$

where $\overline{\beta_{MS}}$ is the mean yaw angle at the blade midspan ($\overline{\beta_{MS}} = \tan^{-1} \overline{V_{\text{tan}}/V_{\text{axi}}}$).

2.5.2 Vorticity

Vorticity is defined as the curl of the velocity field. The out-of-plane vorticity component ω_z from the two-dimensional evaluation plane (xy-plane) is computed as [54]:

$$\omega_z = \frac{\partial V_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial V_x}{\partial y} \quad (2.48)$$

From a PIV measurement on a single plane (e.g. cascade outlet plane), other vorticity components ω_x and ω_y cannot be computed due to lack of the velocity gradient information in plane-normal direction. According to simplifying assumptions described by Perdichizzi [55] and Taremi's application [56], Crocco's theorem [57] derives the in-plane vorticity components from the out-of-plane vorticity ω_z , in-plane spatial gradient of total pressure $P_0(x, y)$ (e.g. obtained by aerodynamic probe traversing measurements), and three velocity components on the plane, $V_x(x, y)$, $V_y(x, y)$, and $V_z(x, y)$ (e.g. obtained by stereo 2D3C-PIV).

$$\omega_x = \frac{1}{V_z} \left(V_x \omega_z + \frac{a^2}{\gamma} \frac{\partial (\ln P_0)}{\partial y} \right) \quad (2.49)$$

$$\omega_y = \frac{1}{V_z} \left(V_y \omega_z - \frac{a^2}{\gamma} \frac{\partial (\ln P_0)}{\partial x} \right) \quad (2.50)$$

Where a is the speed of sound. Note that γ in Eq. 2.49 and 2.50 is the specific heat ratio, not the pitch angle.

The streamwise vorticity coefficient $K_{\omega,s}$ is computed for the cascade outlet plane measurement in S-1/C. The method of Gregory-Smith et al. [58] and the normalization reported by Taremi [56] leads:

$$K_{\omega,s} = \frac{C}{V_{\text{out,is}}} (\omega_{\text{axi}} \cos \beta_{\text{MS}} + \omega_{\text{tan}} \sin \beta_{\text{MS}}) \quad (2.51)$$

where C is the blade chord length, $V_{\text{out,is}}$ is the isentropic cascade outlet flow speed, and β_{MS} is the primary flow direction (yaw angle) at the blade midspan.

2.5.3 Isentropic Mach number

The Mach number is the ratio of the flow speed $|V|$ to the speed of sound a .

$$M = |V|/a \quad (2.52)$$

The flow speed is available from PIV measurements. The speed of sound is defined as:

$$a = \sqrt{\gamma RT} \quad (2.53)$$

where γ is the specific heat ratio, R is the gas constant, and T is the static temperature. From the isentropic flow equations, the local static temperature is computed as [59]:

$$\frac{T}{T_0} = \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M^2\right)^{-1} \quad (2.54)$$

Combining Eq.2.52 - 2.54, the local Mach number can be calculated from the velocity field and the cascade inlet total temperature:

$$M = \sqrt{\frac{V^2}{\gamma R T_0 - \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} V^2}} \quad (2.55)$$

The estimation of Mach number combining the local velocity field obtained from PIV and the upstream total temperature is also used in [60, 61].

2.5.4 Turbulence quantities

The instantaneous velocity components V_i ($i = x, y, z$ or axi, tan, rad) is decomposed into the mean quantity \bar{V}_i and the unsteady (fluctuating) part V'_i .

$$V_i = \bar{V}_i + V'_i \quad (2.56)$$

The mean velocity component \bar{V}_i from the finite number of samples N is computed as:

$$\bar{V}_i = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^N V_{i,m}}{N} \quad (2.57)$$

$V_{i,m}$ is the instantaneous velocity component. The root-mean-square (RMS) of fluctuating part of each velocity component $V'_{i,\text{RMS}}$ is synonymous with its standard deviation σ_{V_i} calculated as:

$$V'_{i,\text{RMS}} = \sigma_{V_i} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{m=1}^N (V_{i,m} - \bar{V}_i)^2}{N - 1}} \approx \sqrt{\overline{V_i'^2}} \quad (2.58)$$

Turbulence intensity

The single-component turbulence intensity TI_i is given by dividing the RMS of velocity fluctuation by the mean flow speed $|\bar{V}|$. For the computation of local turbulence intensity, the local values of $V'_{i,\text{RMS}}$ and $|\bar{V}|$ are used as proposed by MacIsaac et al. [62]. This nondimensionalization method tends to magnify the apparent turbulence intensity in areas with low mean velocity magnitude, such as those near the endwall and blade surfaces. Nevertheless, when representing turbulence in this way, it highlights the implicit impact of turbulent fluctuations on the local mean flow. Therefore, this parameter form is appropriate for studying losses and the mixing process.

$$TI_i = \frac{V'_{i,\text{RMS}}}{|\bar{V}|} \quad (2.59)$$

The two-component turbulence intensity TI_{2C} for i and j components is calculated as:

$$TI_{2C} = \sqrt{\frac{V_{i,\text{RMS}}'^2 + V_{j,\text{RMS}}'^2}{2}} / |\bar{V}| \quad (2.60)$$

The three-component turbulence intensity TI_{3C} for i, j and k components is calculated as:

$$TI_{3C} = \sqrt{\frac{V_{i,RMS}'^2 + V_{j,RMS}'^2 + V_{k,RMS}'^2}{3}} / |\bar{V}| \quad (2.61)$$

Turbulence kinetic energy

The two-component turbulence kinetic energy TKE_{2C} is defined as:

$$TKE_{2C} = \frac{V_{i,RMS}'^2 + V_{j,RMS}'^2}{2} \quad (2.62)$$

The three-component turbulence kinetic energy TKE_{3C} is defined as:

$$TKE_{3C} = \frac{V_{i,RMS}'^2 + V_{j,RMS}'^2 + V_{k,RMS}'^2}{3} \quad (2.63)$$

Degree of anisotropy

The degree of anisotropy (DA) was introduced by Porreca et al. [63] to compare the fluctuating velocity components in the three directions.

$$DA_{3C} = \frac{\overline{2V_i'^2}}{\overline{V_j'^2 + V_k'^2}} \quad (2.64)$$

For the evaluation of turbomachinery flows, the streamwise, crosswise, and spanwise (radial) components are taken for the velocity decomposition ($i, j, k = \text{str, crs, rad}$). In case the degree of anisotropy is computed from in-plane two-component, it is defined as:

$$DA_{2C} = \frac{\overline{V_i'^2}}{\overline{V_j'^2}} \quad (2.65)$$

For such decomposition, the value of DA higher than 1 means that the streamwise fluctuation is more dominant than the secondary flow (crosswise and spanwise) components and vice versa.

As an alternative, the symmetric degree of anisotropy (DA_{sym}) is defined as:

$$DA_{\text{sym},3C} = \frac{\sqrt{2\overline{V_i'^2}} - \sqrt{\overline{V_j'^2 + V_k'^2}}}{\sqrt{\overline{V_i'^2}}} \quad (2.66)$$

For in-plane two-component, $DA_{\text{sym},2C}$ is:

$$DA_{\text{sym},2C} = \frac{\sqrt{\overline{V_i'^2}} - \sqrt{\overline{V_j'^2}}}{\sqrt{\overline{V_i'^2}}} \quad (2.67)$$

Unlike the original DA , DA_{sym} is zero-centered; thus, the sign of the quantity directly indicates whether the turbulence field is streamwise component dominant or crosswise and radial components dominant. This feature is convenient for the visualization of DA with zero-centered colormap.

Reynolds stress

For the sake of simplicity and complying with the convention, the velocity fluctuation components V_i' ($i = x, y, z$ or axi, tan, rad) are written with u_i' or u' , v' and w' in the present and the following parts of the sections.

The Reynolds normal stresses R_{uu} , R_{vv} and R_{ww} (excluding the density ρ) are:

$$R_{uu} = \overline{u'^2}, \quad R_{vv} = \overline{v'^2}, \quad R_{ww} = \overline{w'^2} \quad (2.68)$$

The Reynolds shear stresses R_{uv} , R_{vw} and R_{wu} are:

$$R_{uv} = \overline{u'v'}, \quad R_{vw} = \overline{v'w'}, \quad R_{wu} = \overline{w'u'} \quad (2.69)$$

Anisotropy invariant map

Another approach for describing the turbulence characteristics of fluids is the use of scalar invariants of the Reynolds stress tensor. A thorough description of the mathematical formulation is provided in Appendix B. The normalized anisotropy Reynolds stress tensor, \mathbf{a} or a_{ij} , is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} = a_{ij} &= \frac{\overline{u_i' u_j'}}{2k} - \frac{\delta_{ij}}{3} \\ &= \frac{1}{6k} \begin{bmatrix} 2\overline{u'u'} - \overline{v'v'} - \overline{w'w'} & 3\overline{u'v'} & 3\overline{u'w'} \\ 3\overline{u'v'} & 2\overline{v'v'} - \overline{u'u'} - \overline{w'w'} & 3\overline{v'w'} \\ 3\overline{u'w'} & 3\overline{v'w'} & 2\overline{w'w'} - \overline{u'u'} - \overline{v'v'} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.70)$$

where k is the turbulent kinetic energy $k = (\overline{u'u'} + \overline{v'v'} + \overline{w'w'})/2$ and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker's delta. The first, second, and third invariants of the anisotropy tensor, I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 , are written as:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 \\ &= a_{ii} \\ &= 0 \\ I_2 &= \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3 + \lambda_1 \lambda_3 \\ &= -(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2^2) \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} a_{ij} a_{ji} \\ I_3 &= \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 \\ &= -\lambda_1 \lambda_2 (\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \\ &= \frac{1}{3} a_{ij} a_{jk} a_{ki} \end{aligned} \quad (2.71)$$

The realizability of the turbulence state imposes limiting conditions written as:

$$\begin{aligned} -1/3 &\leq a_{ii} \leq 2/3 \\ -1/2 &\leq a_{ij} \leq 1/2, \quad (i \neq j) \end{aligned} \quad (2.72)$$

These limits lead to the realizable range of invariants of the anisotropy tensor as:

$$\begin{aligned} -1/36 &\leq 3I_3 \leq 2/9 \\ -2I_2 &= \frac{2}{9} + 2 \cdot 3I_3 \\ -2I_2 &= \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{4}{3} |3I_3|^{2/3} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.73)$$

The resultant is a triangle plotted in $I_2 I_3$ -plane, called the anisotropy invariant map (AIM) of Lumley and Newman [64] [65] or simply, the Lumley triangle. As it is yielded based on the limit values of the anisotropy tensor, all the possible states of turbulence must be contained in this triangle. Furthermore, the AIM provides the characteristic states of turbulence based on the location of the plotted turbulence state in the triangle, as depicted in Fig. 2.48.

Figure 2.48: Anisotropy invariant map (Lumley triangle) with designations of the state of turbulence. Figure adopted from Andersson et al. [66]

Barycentric map

Banerjee et al. [67] introduced another method to visualize the state of turbulence anisotropy using a barycentric map (BM). The BM is presented by a triangle whose vertices are defined by three points x_{1c} , x_{2c} and x_{3c} in the Euclidean space as shown in Fig. 2.49. x_{1c} corresponds to the one-component (1c) state of turbulence where there is only one component of turbulent kinetic energy. x_{2c} corresponds to the two-component (2c) isotropic state of turbulence where there are two equal turbulent components while the rest vanishes. x_{3c} corresponds to the three-component (3c) isotropic state of turbulence where three equal turbulent components exist.

The coordinate of a point (x_n, y_n) that represents the anisotropy state in the BM is calculated by the combination of the vertex. If BM is plotted such that the triangle is equilateral

Figure 2.49: Barycentric map of the anisotropic tensor. [67]

with its vertices at $x_{1c} = (1, 0)$, $x_{2c} = (0, 0)$ and $x_{3c} = (1/2, \sqrt{3}/2)$, the point representing the anisotropy state in Cartesian coordinate is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} x_n &= C_{1c}x_{1c} + C_{2c}x_{2c} + C_{3c}x_{3c} = C_{1c} + \frac{1}{2}C_{3c} \\ y_n &= C_{1c}y_{1c} + C_{2c}y_{2c} + C_{3c}y_{3c} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}C_{3c} \end{aligned} \quad (2.74)$$

where C_{1c} , C_{2c} and C_{3c} are normalized coefficients whose values range from 0 to 1 and are satisfying:

$$C_{1c} + C_{2c} + C_{3c} = 1 \quad (2.75)$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_{1c} &= \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 \\ C_{2c} &= 2(\lambda_2 - \lambda_3) \\ C_{3c} &= 3\lambda_3 + 1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.76)$$

Componentality contours

The AIM and BM are useful to grasp the state of turbulence anisotropy with respect to the limiting state. On the other hand, these techniques cut out the information on the spatial distribution of the Reynolds stress in the physical domain during the mapping process, thus the physical context is not evident. Besides, when the data size is large, such as data over a plane or a volume, the map becomes overcrowded and too complicated to comprehend. One of the visualization techniques that shows the state of turbulence anisotropy is the componentality contours introduced by Emory and Iaccarino [68]. The basis of this technique is to assign a color map constructed from the barycentric map coordinates to each physical coordinate. They proposed the modified color map for the RGB channel as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} R \\ G \\ B \end{bmatrix} = C_{1c}^* \mathbf{n}_1 + C_{2c}^* \mathbf{n}_2 + C_{3c}^* \mathbf{n}_3 \quad (2.77)$$

$$C_{ic}^* = (C_{ic} + C_{off})^{C_{exp}} \quad (2.78)$$

where C_{off} and C_{exp} are the offset and exponent coefficients which the user can select based on which region of BM is being focused. \mathbf{n}_i is a 3×1 vector that defines the color scheme. For example, $\mathbf{n}_1 = [1, 0, 0]^T$, $\mathbf{n}_2 = [0, 1, 0]^T$ and $\mathbf{n}_3 = [0, 0, 1]^T$ assign red, green and blue to each vertex of BM triangle. Examples of colormap for the componentality contours are illustrated in Fig. 2.50.

Figure 2.50: Application example of componentality color contours. Contours for the Détery C flow using the SST model. (a) Mach contours ($M = 0$: black, $M = 1.4$: white, 15 uniformly speed contours). (b) The RGB colormap, described by $[1, 0, 0]^T$, $[0, 1, 0]^T$, and $[0, 0, 1]^T$, $C_{off} = C_{exp} = 0$, and (c) associated componentality contours. (d) The black-white colormap, described by $[1, 1, 1]^T$, $[1, 1, 1]^T$, and $[0, 0, 0]^T$, and (e) associated contours. [68]

2.5.5 Proper orthogonal decomposition

Proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) is a data analysis technique that decomposes a dataset into a linear combination of orthogonal modes. The technique is also known as principal component analysis (PCA) and Karhunen-Loève decomposition [69]. The POD method has been utilized as a powerful processing tool for a large amounts of high-dimensional data, typically for determining dominant coherent flow structures underlying in turbulent

flows [70]. The capability of POD allowing users to simultaneously analyze and combine space–time data makes the method compatible especially with PIV datasets [71–73].

In this thesis, the technique is applied to the PIV datasets acquired at the downstream of the active turbulence grid to analyze the impact of the synthetic jet on the unsteady flow structure behind the grid bars (see section 4.1.6).

In this subsection, a brief explanation of the technique is given to introduce the concept of the technique. For more detailed descriptions, see [74, 75]. Assuming applying the technique to results obtained from PIV measurements, consider a set of m instantaneous two-dimensional two-component velocity fields consisting of $n = N_x \times N_y$ vectors in space. Focusing on the unsteady dynamics of the fluid motion, only the fluctuating parts of the velocity, $u'(x_i, y_j, t_k)$ and $v'(x_i, y_j, t_k)$, are considered. Where x_i and y_j are the spatial coordinate of the vector ($1 \leq i \leq N_x$, $1 \leq j \leq N_y$) and t_k is the time instant of each instantaneous velocity field ($1 \leq k \leq m$).

All fluctuating velocity data is summarized into one ($m \times n^*$) snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} , with $n^* = 2n$.

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} u'(x_1, y_1, t_1) & \dots & u'(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, t_1) & v'(x_1, y_1, t_1) & \dots & v'(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, t_1) \\ u'(x_1, y_1, t_2) & \dots & u'(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, t_2) & v'(x_1, y_1, t_2) & \dots & v'(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, t_2) \\ \vdots & & \vdots & \vdots & & \vdots \\ u'(x_1, y_1, t_m) & \dots & u'(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, t_m) & v'(x_1, y_1, t_m) & \dots & v'(x_{N_x}, y_{N_y}, t_m) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.79)$$

The $n^* \times n^*$ covariance matrix \mathbf{C} of this snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} is computed by:

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{m-1} \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{U} \quad (2.80)$$

Since the covariance matrix \mathbf{C} is symmetric, it can be diagonalized as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C} &= \mathbf{\Phi} \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{\Phi}^T \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11} & \phi_{12} & \dots & \phi_{1n^*} \\ \phi_{21} & \phi_{22} & \dots & \phi_{2n^*} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \phi_{n^*1} & \phi_{n^*2} & \dots & \phi_{n^*n^*} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & \lambda_{n^*} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11} & \phi_{21} & \dots & \phi_{n^*1} \\ \phi_{12} & \phi_{22} & \dots & \phi_{n^*2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \phi_{1n^*} & \phi_{2n^*} & \dots & \phi_{n^*n^*} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.81)$$

where $\mathbf{\Phi}$ is an orthogonal matrix whose columns are the eigenvectors of the covariance matrix \mathbf{C} . Each eigenvector (each column of $\mathbf{\Phi}$) is the proper orthogonal mode, (also called spatial mode) of the dataset. $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is a diagonal matrix whose elements are eigenvalues ordered from the largest (λ_1) to the smallest (λ_{n^*}), each representing the energy content of the corresponding mode.

The fluctuation snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} can be now projected onto each spatial mode (eigenvector) by:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{U}\Phi$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & \dots & s_{1n^*} \\ s_{21} & \dots & s_{2n^*} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ s_{m1} & \dots & s_{mn^*} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{U} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11} & \dots & \phi_{1n^*} \\ \phi_{21} & \dots & \phi_{2n^*} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \phi_{n^*1} & \dots & \phi_{n^*n^*} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.82)$$

The columns of \mathbf{S} is the time coefficients of the corresponding modes. For example, s_{k1} ($1 \leq k \leq m$) is the time coefficient (amplitude) of the first spatial mode $[\phi_{11}, \phi_{21}, \dots, \phi_{m1}]^T$ at the time instant t_k . Inversely, the original fluctuation snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} can be obtained as:

$$\mathbf{U} = \mathbf{S}\Phi^{-1} = \mathbf{S}\Phi^T$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & \dots & s_{1n^*} \\ s_{21} & \dots & s_{2n^*} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ s_{m1} & \dots & s_{mn^*} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11} & \dots & \phi_{n^*1} \\ \phi_{12} & \dots & \phi_{n^*2} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \phi_{1n^*} & \dots & \phi_{n^*n^*} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} \\ s_{21} \\ \vdots \\ s_{m1} \end{bmatrix} [\phi_{11} \quad \dots \quad \phi_{n^*1}] + \dots + \begin{bmatrix} s_{1n^*} \\ s_{2n^*} \\ \vdots \\ s_{mn^*} \end{bmatrix} [\phi_{1n^*} \quad \dots \quad \phi_{n^*n^*}] \quad (2.83)$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^{n^*} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^k$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^k = \begin{bmatrix} s_{1k} \\ s_{2k} \\ \vdots \\ s_{mk} \end{bmatrix} [\phi_{1k} \quad \dots \quad \phi_{n^*k}] \quad (2.84)$$

As a result, the original fluctuation snapshot matrix \mathbf{U} is decomposed into a sum of n^* contributions of $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^k$ based on n^* proper orthogonal modes. Since the spatial modes (eigenvectors) are organized in a descending order based on the corresponding eigenvalues, one may consider that the original fluctuation snapshot matrix can be mostly represented by the first several modes $1 \leq k \leq l (\leq n^*)$ when they account to a large portion of the total energy.

$$\mathbf{U} \approx \sum_{k=1}^{k=l} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}^k \quad (2.85)$$

Eq. 2.85 indicates that it is also possible to reconstruct the flow using a selected number of modes for a specific time period. This process allows dimensionality reduction of the problem, and extraction of the dominant flow structure representing the most of the unsteady flow phenomena that are sometimes difficult to detect in the noisy raw data.

2.6 Uncertainty analysis

The quantification of uncertainty in Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV) measurements presents a formidable challenge, given the multitude of influential parameters. These parameters include the configuration and calibration of the optical system, the quality of seeding particles, variations in flow velocity gradients, the intricacies of vector computation algorithms, the choice of data reduction procedures, and numerous other factors. In the following section, a comprehensive enumeration of these parameters is provided. It is imperative to note that, despite these extensive discussions, not every PIV test case can encompass the entirety of these factors, primarily due to constraints on the availability of requisite information for accurate estimation.

In this study, the methodology for uncertainty calculation bases on ISO/IEC GUIDE 98-3:2008 [76]. The ISO method evaluates the measurement uncertainty with two methods, type A and type B.

2.6.1 Fundamentals of uncertainty evaluation

2.6.1.1 Type A uncertainty

The type A method evaluates the uncertainty by the statistical analysis of a series of observations. The statistical approach used in this study for the type A method is to calculate the standard deviation of the mean of a series of independent observations. As an example, consider a generic quantity q_i which is a value estimated from i th independent observation. If the observation is repeated N times, the estimated mean quantity \bar{q} is calculated as:

$$\bar{q} = \sum_{i=1}^N q_i / N \quad (2.86)$$

The standard uncertainty of the mean, $\Delta_{\bar{q}}$, is estimated using the standard deviation σ of the mean:

$$\Delta_{\bar{q}} = \frac{\sigma_{\bar{q}}}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (2.87)$$

$$\sigma_{\bar{q}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (q_i - \bar{q})^2}{N - 1}} \quad (2.88)$$

2.6.1.2 Type B uncertainty

The type B method evaluates the uncertainty by means of other than the type A method, the type B uncertainty can be retrieved from various sources such as manufacturer's specifications, data provided in other reports, and experience with, or general knowledge of, the behavior and property of relevant materials and instruments.

2.6.1.3 Probability distribution of measured or estimated values

The uncertainty of a quantity is obtained based on the probability distribution of the measured or estimated value. The standard uncertainty calculated with type A method requires a large

number of repeated observations which is assumed to have Gaussian distribution as shown in Fig. 2.51-top. For such a case, the standard uncertainty is expressed by the Eq. 2.87. On the other hand, when only little information is available about the value, for example when evaluating using Type B method, one can not determine the exact value distribution. For such a case, one may suppose that the probability distribution has a symmetric, rectangular shape with lower and upper bounds of a centered to the estimated value of q_e (Fig. 2.51-bottom). The standard uncertainty of this rectangular probability distribution is [76]:

$$\Delta_q = \frac{q_e}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (2.89)$$

Figure 2.51: Probability density function in Gaussian distribution (top) and rectangular distribution (bottom). [76]

2.6.1.4 Propagation of uncertainty

When the uncertainty of the subject quantity q is not directly available but the relation to the other quantities whose uncertainty is known, the propagation of uncertainty is used to calculate the uncertainty of q . Assume the quantity q is related to the other quantities a, b, \dots by a function f :

$$q = f(a, b, \dots) \quad (2.90)$$

If their uncertainty is known to be $\Delta_a, \Delta_b, \dots$, the propagated standard uncertainty of q is estimated by [77]:

$$\Delta_q = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial a}\right)^2 \Delta_a^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial b}\right)^2 \Delta_b^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial a}\right) \left(\frac{\partial q}{\partial b}\right) \Delta_a \Delta_b + \dots} \quad (2.91)$$

If the uncertainties of variables of f ($\Delta_a, \Delta_b, \dots$) are independent to each other, the cross terms will become zero.

2.6.1.5 Combined uncertainty

The individually estimated standard uncertainties, $\Delta_{q,1}, \Delta_{q,2}, \dots$, can be combined by root sum of the squares:

$$\Delta_{q_{\text{combined}}} = \sqrt{\Delta_{q,1}^2 + \Delta_{q,2}^2 + \dots} \quad (2.92)$$

2.6.2 Basic concept of PIV uncertainty

An instantaneous velocity V [m/s] measured by PIV is described as a function of the scale factor F_s [m/pixel], the particle displacement X_d [pixel], and the separation time of the successive image frames t_s [s].

$$V = f(F_s, X_d, t_s) = F_s \frac{X_d}{t_s} \quad (2.93)$$

According to the propagation of uncertainty, the uncertainty of the velocity contributed by these variables, denoted by Δ_V , is expressed as:

$$\Delta_V = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial F_s}\right)^2 \Delta_{F_s}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial X_d}\right)^2 \Delta_{X_d}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial t_s}\right)^2 \Delta_{t_s}^2} \quad (2.94)$$

where Δ_{F_s} , Δ_{X_d} , and Δ_{t_s} are the uncertainty of corresponding parameters F_s , X_d , and t_s . The sensitivity coefficients for each variable are obtained as:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial F_s} = \frac{X_d}{t_s} \quad (2.95)$$

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial X_d} = \frac{F_s}{t_s} \quad (2.96)$$

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t_s} = -\frac{F_s \cdot X_d}{t_s^2} \quad (2.97)$$

Alternatively, Eq. 2.94 is rewritten in non-dimensional form:

$$\frac{\Delta_V}{V} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta_{F_s}}{F_s}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{X_d}}{X_d}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{t_s}}{t_s}\right)^2} \quad (2.98)$$

The error sources of PIV measurements are grouped into two categories. The error sources in the first category are those that can not be quantified by analyzing the recorded

images. For example, the errors originated from the timing of the involved hardware components (synchronizer, cameras, laser, etc), precision of calibration target, misalignment of light sheet and calibration target, and particle response lag are hidden factors that are not readily visible in the recorded particle images.

The error sources in the second category are those that can ideally be estimated from the recorded images using uncertainty quantification methods. For example, the uncertainties of particle displacement associated with particle image size, seeding density, camera noise, and particle intensity variations have been quantified by a posteriori image analysis methods such as the uncertainty surface method [78], image matching and particle disparity method [79], and correlation statistics method [80].

In the following sub-sections, the treatment of each uncertainty component is discussed.

2.6.2.1 Scaling factor

The scaling factor is given by the ratio of the reference length on the calibration target plane in the real world L_{real} [m] to the corresponding length projected on the imaging plane L_{img} [pixel] [81].

$$F_s = \frac{L_{\text{real}}}{L_{\text{img}}} \quad (2.99)$$

Physical reference scale length in the real world

The physical reference scale length is a known geometry of the calibration target, such as the distance between two reference dot markers printed on a calibration target. The uncertainty of the physical reference length $\Delta_{L_{\text{real}}}$ is determined by the precision of fabrication. For the presented study, calibration dot patterns were printed by a laser printer with a resolution of 600 dpi (≈ 0.04 mm/dot). The precision of printing is estimated to be the same magnitude of the printing resolution and the uncertainty distribution is expected to be rectangular, thus $\Delta_{L_{\text{real}}}$ is:

$$\Delta_{L_{\text{real}}} = 0.04\text{mm}/\sqrt{3} = 0.023\text{mm} \quad (2.100)$$

The sensitivity coefficient of F_s for L_{real} is:

$$\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial L_{\text{real}}} = \frac{1}{L_{\text{img}}} \quad (2.101)$$

Computed reference scale length on the image

The computed reference scale length on the image L_{img} is the number of pixels corresponding to the physical reference scale length that appears on the image sensor. The distance is retrieved by either a software algorithm detection or manual selection on a computer screen by the user. If a software algorithm is used to get the scaling factor, the RMS fit can be considered as the standard uncertainty.

$$\Delta_{L_{\text{img}}} = \text{RMS}_{\text{fit}} \quad (2.102)$$

If the scaling factor is obtained by the user's manual selection, it is reasonable to estimate that the uncertainty of reading of the reference marker center is up to 0.5 pixels with the rectangular distribution. Assuming that two readings are required to obtain the reference distance, the total standard uncertainty is:

$$\Delta_{L_{\text{img}}} = \sqrt{\left(0.5\text{px}/\sqrt{3}\right)^2 + \left(0.5\text{px}/\sqrt{3}\right)^2} \quad (2.103)$$

The sensitivity coefficient of F_s for L_{img} is:

$$\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial L_{\text{img}}} = -\frac{L_{\text{real}}}{L_{\text{img}}^2} \quad (2.104)$$

Translational misalignment of calibration target to the laser sheet

The alignment of the calibration plate to the laser sheet is performed by visual observation, thus a certain amount of misalignment dz is expected. For experiments presented in this thesis, a translational misalignment is estimated to be up to 0.5 mm, approximated as half of the laser sheet thickness. Assuming the uncertainty distribution is a rectangular shape, the standard uncertainty of translational misalignment Δ_{dz} is:

$$\Delta_{dz} = 0.5\text{mm}/\sqrt{3} = 0.29\text{mm} \quad (2.105)$$

The uncertainty of translational misalignment yields an uncertainty in the physical scale length L_{real} . The scale factor as a function of the translation misalignment is written as:

$$F_s = \frac{L_{\text{real}}(1 + dz/z_{\text{obj}})}{L_{\text{img}}} \quad (2.106)$$

where z_{obj} is the front focal length which is determined from the positioning of cameras. The sensitivity coefficient of F_s for dz is:

$$\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial (dz)} = \frac{L_{\text{real}}}{L_{\text{img}} z_{\text{obj}}} \quad (2.107)$$

Angular misalignment of calibration target to the laser sheet

The angular misalignment of the calibration target plane to the laser sheet $d\theta$ is estimated to be up to 1 degree (= 0.017 rad) with the rectangular uncertainty distribution. The standard uncertainty of angular misalignment $\Delta_{d\theta}$ is:

$$\Delta_{d\theta} = 0.017\text{rad}/\sqrt{3} = 0.01 \quad (2.108)$$

A generic form of scale factor considering the angular misalignment is written as:

$$F_s = \frac{L_{\text{real}}^2}{(z_{\text{obj}} \sin d\theta + L_{\text{real}} \cos d\theta) L_{\text{img}}} \quad (2.109)$$

The sensitivity coefficient of F_s for $d\theta$ is:

$$\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial \theta} = \frac{L_{\text{real}}^2}{(z_{\text{obj}} \cos d\theta - L_{\text{real}} \sin d\theta) L_{\text{img}}} \quad (2.110)$$

Assuming the angular misalignment of the calibration plate is not biased, $d\theta$ is regarded as 0 in the sensitivity coefficient, thus eq. 2.110 is rewritten as:

$$\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial \theta} = \frac{L_{\text{real}}^2}{z_{\text{obj}} L_{\text{img}}} \quad (2.111)$$

Total uncertainty of scaling factor

The total uncertainty of scaling factor Δ_{F_s} is calculated using the following equation.

$$\Delta_{F_s} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial L_{\text{real}}}\right)^2 \Delta_{L_{\text{real}}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial L_{\text{img}}}\right)^2 \Delta_{L_{\text{img}}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial dz}\right)^2 \Delta_{dz}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial F_s}{\partial d\theta}\right)^2 \Delta_{d\theta}^2} \quad (2.112)$$

The non-dimensional form is written as:

$$\frac{\Delta_{F_s}}{F_s} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta_{L_{\text{real}}}}{L_{\text{real}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{L_{\text{img}}}}{L_{\text{img}}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{dz}}{dz}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{d\theta}}{d\theta}\right)^2} \quad (2.113)$$

2.6.2.2 Particle displacement

Random image noise, particle image size, density, intensity variation, and spatial filtering

In this paragraph, the effects of random image noise, particle image size, particle image density, intensity variation of particle image, and spatial filtering on the uncertainty of estimated particle displacement are discussed. Multiple error sources are bundled in a single paragraph since all sources are evaluated by a single uncertainty quantification method.

- Random image noise

The presence of random noise in recorded images reduces the correlation signal thus causing erroneous estimation of particle displacement. Scharnowski and Kähler [82] investigated the effect of random noise on the uncertainty of particle displacement varying the seeding density and the noise level. Fig. 2.52 shows the shift vector uncertainty as a function of noise level σ_n relative to the maximum particle image intensity I_0 , based on synthetic image analysis.

- Particle image density

The particle image density plays an important role in the estimation of particle displacement. Keane and Adrian [83] reported that the validity of PIV measurements is related to the effective number of particles appearing in the images. The three key parameters to be concerned are the number of particles within the interrogation window, the in-plane loss of particle pairs, and the out-of-plane loss of particle pairs. Generally speaking, the correlation peak amplitude increases when the number of particle images in the interrogation window increases. Fig. 2.53 from [2] illustrates the measurement uncertainty of particle displacement as a function of the number of particle image density (number of particles per pixel N_{ppp}) and interrogation window size for a fixed particle image diameter.

-Particle image size

In most of modern PIV cross-correlation algorithms, the particle displacement X_d is estimated with the sub-pixel interpolation scheme which finds a sub-pixel position of the corre-

Figure 2.52: Particle displacement uncertainty $\Delta X_{d,RMS}$ computed from synthetic PIV images as a function of the image noise level σ_n/I_0 for different particle image densities N_{ppp} . Particle image diameter and interrogation window size were set to 3.0 pixels and 32×32 pixels, respectively. [82]

Figure 2.53: Measurement uncertainty as a function of the particle image density for various interrogation window sizes. [2]

lation peak (particle displacement) by a curve fitting based on discrete peak and neighboring values. For a large particle image size, the variation of particle image intensity over the particle diameter decreases and this leads to an inaccurate estimation of the particle center location with the multi-point peak fitting. For a small particle size, the particle image is not properly resolved by the discrete pixel of the sensor thus there are not enough samples for the accurate multi-point peak fitting. The particle image size as small as or smaller than a single pixel results in the peak-locking effect which biases the displacement estimation towards an integer pixel.

Fig. 2.54 displays the measurement uncertainty as a function of the particle image diameter for a fixed number of particles per pixel based on synthetic image analysis [2]. The evaluation was performed for different interrogation window sizes using single-pass evaluation and multiple-pass evaluation with Gaussian window weighting and iterative image deformation based on bi-cubic intensity interpolation, respectively. For single-pass PIV evaluation, the optimal particle image diameter for single-pass PIV evaluation to be around 1.5-2.0 pixels as reported by Willert [84] based on Monte-Carlo simulations and by Westerweel [85] based on theoretical model. For the multi-pass PIV evaluation, the optimal particle image diameter is increased and its range becomes wide, around 3 to 6 pixels. Moreover, the minimum uncertainty is reduced by about an order compared to the single-pass evaluation scheme.

Figure 2.54: Measurement uncertainty in digital cross-correlation PIV evaluation with respect to varying particle image diameters [2]

- Intensity variation of particle image

The variation of particle image intensity resulting from a motion of particles through an intensity profile of the light sheet, a misalignment of the consecutive light pulses, or overlapping particles affect the accuracy of particle displacement estimation. Fig. 2.55 shows the RMS error of particle displacement estimated based on synthetic image analysis with PIV processing by Nobach et al. [86]. The particle image diameter, the particle number density, and interrogation window size were set to 3 pixels, $0.0195 \text{ pixel}^{-2}$, and 32×32 pixels, respectively. The result was verified experimentally under a controlled environment by the same authors. It was found that the RMS deviation of the estimated displacement amounts to about 0.1 pixels for commonly used best practice setups (particle image diameter of 2 to 5 pixels

and an out-of-plane component being 2/9 to 2/5 of the light sheet thickness).

Figure 2.55: RMS deviation of the displacement estimate as a function of the out-of-plane displacement component [86]

- Spatial filtering

The particle displacement computed using the PIV algorithm represents an average of the displacements of multiple particles contained within each interrogation window. Consequently, the resulting particle displacement is somewhat smoothed, and this smoothing effect can be approximated by a linear filter function as reported by Scarano and Riethmuller [87]. Wieneke [88] retrieved the linear spatial filter function $F(x)$ representing the spatial filtering effect in PIV processing using commercial software *Davis* from *LaVision*. The spatial filter function was obtained by the inverse Fourier transform of the wavelength response function $R(\lambda)$ which is a ratio of the measured to true amplitude of spatial velocity fluctuation. Synthetic images containing sine-wave periodic shear flow $V_x = \sin 2\pi y/\lambda$ for different wavelengths were generated and processed for evaluation. Fig. 2.56 presents the wavelength response function and spatial filter function for iterative multi-pass processing with Gaussian weighted 32×32 pixel interrogation window and 75% overlap. The spatial filter function of such a PIV processing is represented by a mixture of Gaussian and Mexican-hat functions, and the filter length L_{sr} is smaller than the input interrogation window size.

While the information on filter function gives an idea of the limitation of spatial resolution of PIV for a specific PIV processing scheme, the velocity gradients smaller than the resolvable scale remain unknown and thus truncated. Meanwhile, these small-scale velocity gradients are still encoded in the image and the resultant small-scale particle displacement contributes to the measurement uncertainty similar to the random motion of the particles within the interrogation window [88].

- Uncertainty quantification approach

One can assume that the uncertainty sources discussed in this subsection 2.6.2.2 are essentially encoded in the recorded images. While various theoretical analysis and *a-priori* quantification approaches have been reported [89] [90], it is not often applicable to real experimental cases since they are mostly based on synthetic image analysis or ideal situations.

Figure 2.56: Wavelength response functions for 1-6 passes (top) and corresponding filter functions (bottom) using Gaussian IW. [88]

For most of the experiments carried out in the real world, many parameters that influence the measurement uncertainty can not be identified. Given these drawbacks of *a-priori* approaches, the presented study adopted *a-posteriori* uncertainty quantification approaches to evaluate the effect of the error sources discussed in this paragraph.

The correlation statistics method [80] was chosen on the ground of high sensitivity to image noise, out-of-plane motion (particle pairs loss and intensity variation), particle image density, and random particle motion as well as its practicality, i.e. the uncertainty is available as an output quantity in *Davis* PIV processing software. The reliability of the method is also reported by Sciacchitano [91]. For a detailed description of the uncertainty estimation by correlation statistics, the reader is referred to the work of Wieneke [80].

Perspective projection

When two-dimensional two-component PIV is employed and there is a flow component perpendicular to the light sheet exists, perspective errors will be present in the measured velocities. This error is corrected by employing a stereoscopic camera configuration. The standard uncertainty of particle displacement due to the perspective projection $\Delta_{d,pers}$ is described as:

$$\Delta_{d,pers} = V_z \tan \phi_i \quad (2.114)$$

where V_z is the out-of-plane velocity component and ϕ_i is the angle between the optical axis and a line of sight from the lens center of the measurement location. The subscript i indicates that ϕ varies depending on the local point of measurement. The sensitivity coefficient of X_d for $X_{d,pers}$ is:

$$\frac{\partial X_d}{\partial X_{d,pers}} = 1 \quad (2.115)$$

Particle traceability

The velocity PIV measures is the one of tracer particles instead of the fluid's. For most of the PIV, especially for air flows, there is a difference between these two velocities which is defined as particle slip velocity. Therefore, the velocity measured by PIV inherently leads to an erroneous measurement result. The motion of the particle relative to the fluid is governed by eq. 2.3 as discussed in 2.2. The error related to the particle traceability is not straightforward to estimate, thus the effect is not included in the uncertainty analysis of this thesis.

Total uncertainty of particle displacement

The total uncertainty of particle displacement is calculated using the following equation.

$$\Delta_{X_d} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial X_d}{\partial X_{d,subpx}}\right)^2 \Delta_{X_{d,subpx}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial X_d}{\partial X_{d,CS}}\right)^2 \Delta_{X_{d,CS}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial X_d}{\partial X_{d,pers}}\right)^2 \Delta_{X_{d,pers}}^2} \quad (2.116)$$

The non-dimensional form is written as:

$$\frac{\Delta_{X_d}}{X_d} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta_{X_{d,subpx}}}{X_{d,subpx}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{X_{d,CS}}}{X_{d,CS}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{X_{d,pers}}}{X_{d,pers}}\right)^2} \quad (2.117)$$

2.6.2.3 Separation time

Accuracy of triggering time of synchronizer

The separation time is controlled by synchronizer, and its timing accuracy of triggering pulse generation is obtained from the specification sheet of the synchronizer. For *Programmable Time Unit (PTU9)* from *LaVision*, the typical jitter between all outputs is stated as < 1 ns in the manual. Considering the jitter has a rectangular distribution, the standard uncertainty of separation time due to the accuracy of PTU9 triggering pulse timing $\Delta_{t_s,PTU9}$ is described as:

$$\Delta_{t_s,PTU9} = 1\text{ns}/\sqrt{3} = 0.57\text{ns} \quad (2.118)$$

For *Stanford-DG535 Digital Delay/Pulse Generator*, the typical uncertainty in the time delay between outputs is found in Fig. 2.57 [92]. The separation times (Time between two outputs) in the current study are set below $10 \mu\text{s}$, thus, one can read the timing error to be below 1 ns. Assuming the error has a rectangular distribution, the standard uncertainty of separation time due to the accuracy of *Stanford-DG535* triggering timing $\Delta_{t_s,DG535}$ is described as:

$$\Delta_{t_s,DG535} = 1\text{ns}/\sqrt{3} = 0.57\text{ns} \quad (2.119)$$

Figure 2.57: Maximum error vs. time delay for *Stanford-DG535 Digital Delay/Pulse Generator* [92]

The sensitivity coefficient of t_s for $t_{s,PTU9/DG535}$ is:

$$\frac{\partial t_s}{\partial t_{s,PTU9/DG535}} = 1 \quad (2.120)$$

Accuracy of laser pulse timing

In Q-switched lasers, there are timing delays and fluctuations (jitter) between the Q-switch trigger and pulse emission. The exact values of the timing jitter of the lasers used in this study were not found in the manuals. A typical value of 1 ns is considered as the timing jitter of employed lasers. Assuming a rectangular distribution for the timing jitter, the standard uncertainty of separation time due to the laser pulse jitter is described as:

$$\Delta_{t_s,laser} = 1\text{ns}/\sqrt{3} = 0.57\text{ns} \quad (2.121)$$

The sensitivity coefficient of t_s for $t_{s,laser}$ is:

$$\frac{\partial t_s}{\partial t_{s,PTU9/DG535}} = 1 \quad (2.122)$$

Total uncertainty of separation time

The total uncertainty of separation time is calculated using the following equation.

$$\Delta_{t_s} = \sqrt{\Delta_{t_s,PTU9/DG535}^2 + \Delta_{t_s,laser}^2} \quad (2.123)$$

The non-dimensional form is written as:

$$\frac{\Delta_{t_s}}{t_s} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta_{t_s,PTU9/DG535}}{t_{s,PTU9/DG535}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{t_s,laser}}{t_{s,laser}}\right)^2} \quad (2.124)$$

2.6.3 Uncertainty of instantaneous quantities

2.6.3.1 Instantaneous velocities from planar PIV

The standard uncertainties of instantaneous velocity components measured by PIV (Δ_{V_x} , Δ_{V_y}) are expressed by eq.2.94 replacing X_d with X_{dx} or X_{dy} .

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{V_x} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial F_s}\right)^2 \Delta_{F_s}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial X_{dx}}\right)^2 \Delta_{X_{dx}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial t_s}\right)^2 \Delta_{t_s}^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{X_{dx}^2}{t_s^2} \Delta_{F_s}^2 + \frac{F_s^2}{t_s^2} \Delta_{X_{dx}}^2 + \frac{F_s^2 X_{dx}^2}{t_s^4} \Delta_{t_s}^2} \end{aligned} \quad (2.125)$$

Assuming the uncertainty of the scaling factor is isotropic in both directions, y component is computed in the same way as x component. Hereafter, the description of y component is omitted unless necessary.

The standard uncertainty of instantaneous two-component velocity magnitude $\Delta_{|V_{2C}|}$ is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{|V_{2C}|} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial |V_{2C}|}{\partial V_x}\right)^2 \Delta_{V_x}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial |V_{2C}|}{\partial V_y}\right)^2 \Delta_{V_y}^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{V_x^2 \Delta_{V_x}^2 + V_y^2 \Delta_{V_y}^2}{V_x^2 + V_y^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.126)$$

$$\frac{\partial |V_{2C}|}{\partial V_x} = \frac{V_x}{\sqrt{V_x^2 + V_y^2}} \quad (2.127)$$

The standard uncertainty of instantaneous three-component velocity magnitude $\Delta_{|V_{3C}|}$ is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_{|V_{3C}|} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial|V_{3C}|}{\partial V_x}\right)^2 \Delta_{V_x}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial|V_{3C}|}{\partial V_y}\right)^2 \Delta_{V_y}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial|V_{3C}|}{\partial V_z}\right)^2 \Delta_{V_z}^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{V_x^2 \Delta_{V_x}^2 + V_y^2 \Delta_{V_y}^2 + V_z^2 \Delta_{V_z}^2}{V_x^2 + V_y^2 + V_z^2}}\end{aligned}\quad (2.128)$$

$$\frac{\partial|V_{3C}|}{\partial V_x} = \frac{V_x}{\sqrt{V_x^2 + V_y^2 + V_z^2}}\quad (2.129)$$

2.6.3.2 Instantaneous velocities from stereoscopic PIV

In stereo-PIV, the three velocity components V_x , V_y , and V_z are reconstructed from the two sets of two in-plane velocity components, V_{x1} , V_{y1} , V_{x2} , V_{y2} , computed from the dewarped image pairs of each camera 1, 2. When the stereo cameras are oriented with an angle $\alpha_1 - \alpha_2$ in the $x - z$ plane and an angle $\beta_1 - \beta_2$ in the $y - z$ plane (see Fig. 2.58), the formulae of velocity reconstruction are given as [3]:

$$V_x = \frac{V_{x2} \tan \alpha_1 - V_{x1} \tan \alpha_2}{\tan \alpha_1 - \tan \alpha_2}\quad (2.130)$$

$$V_y = \frac{V_{y2} \tan \beta_1 - V_{y1} \tan \beta_2}{\tan \beta_1 - \tan \beta_2}\quad (2.131)$$

$$\begin{aligned}V_z &= \frac{V_{x2} - V_{x1}}{\tan \alpha_1 - \tan \alpha_2} \\ &= \frac{V_{y2} - V_{y1}}{\tan \beta_1 - \tan \beta_2}\end{aligned}\quad (2.132)$$

Note that the camera angles, α_1 , α_2 , β_1 , and β_2 , have positive and negative signs depending on the position.

In the presented study, the camera angles were estimated by pinhole models implemented into *Davis* PIV software. If the viewing axes of cameras become colinear in either of their two-dimensional projections, i.e. $\beta_1, \beta_2 = 0$, the formula of V_y component (eq. 2.131) is re-written using eq. 2.132 to avoid the numerator approaches zero.

$$\begin{aligned}V_y &= \frac{V_{y1} + V_{y2}}{2} + \frac{V_{x2} - V_{x1}}{2} \left(\frac{\tan \beta_2 - \tan \beta_1}{\tan \alpha_1 - \tan \alpha_2} \right) \\ &= \frac{V_{y1} + V_{y2}}{2} + \frac{V_z}{2} (\tan \beta_2 - \tan \beta_1)\end{aligned}\quad (2.133)$$

Hereafter, we employ eq. 2.133 as the experiments were carried out with colinear camera orientation in the present study.

The Taylor-series uncertainty propagation provides the uncertainty of each stereo 2D3C velocity component as:

Figure 2.58: Stereoscopic viewing geometry in xz -plane.

$$\Delta_{V_x} = \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial V_{x1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial V_{x2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x2}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial \alpha_1} \right)^2 \Delta_{\alpha_1}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial \alpha_2} \right)^2 \Delta_{\alpha_2}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.134)$$

$$\Delta_{V_y} = \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_y}{\partial V_{y1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{y1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_y}{\partial V_{y2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{y2}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_y}{\partial V_z} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_z}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial \beta_1} \right)^2 \Delta_{\beta_1}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial \beta_2} \right)^2 \Delta_{\beta_2}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.135)$$

$$\Delta_{V_z} = \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_z}{\partial V_{x1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_z}{\partial V_{x2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x2}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_z}{\partial \alpha_1} \right)^2 \Delta_{\alpha_1}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_z}{\partial \alpha_2} \right)^2 \Delta_{\alpha_2}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.136)$$

where $\Delta_{V_{x1}}$, $\Delta_{V_{x2}}$, $\Delta_{V_{y1}}$, and $\Delta_{V_{y2}}$ are the uncertainties of planar 2D velocity for each camera and Δ_{α_1} , Δ_{α_2} , Δ_{β_1} , and Δ_{β_2} are the uncertainties of camera angle in $x - z$ plane and $y - z$ plane, respectively.

While a rigorous approach is to take into account the all elemental uncertainty sources, the contributions of the uncertainties of camera angle are known to become negligible for zero disparity after converged self-calibration (Bhattacharya et al. [93]). Thus, the eq. 2.134-2.136 are reduced to:

$$\Delta_{V_x} = \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial V_{x1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial V_{x2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x2}}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.137)$$

$$\Delta V_y = \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_y}{\partial V_{y1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{y1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_y}{\partial V_{y2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{y2}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_y}{\partial V_z} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_z}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.138)$$

$$\Delta V_z = \left[\left(\frac{\partial V_z}{\partial V_{x1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_z}{\partial V_{x2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V_{x2}}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.139)$$

Now, the question is how to calculate the uncertainties of planar 2D velocities for each camera, ΔV_{x1} , ΔV_{x2} , ΔV_{y1} , and ΔV_{y2} . In the present study, the computation of velocity fields from raw images is performed using commercial PIV software *Davis* PIV which does not output the uncertainties of planar 2D velocities for each camera. Instead, the software estimates the uncertainties of stereo 2D3C velocities based on the correlation statistics method ($\Delta V_{x,CS}$, $\Delta V_{y,CS}$, and $\Delta V_{z,CS}$). These uncertainties are already propagated using above-mentioned formulae. Considering the uncertainty due to the remaining elements $\Delta V_{x,other}$ those are not taken into account by the correlation statistics method in *Davis*, the propagated uncertainty of each stereo 2D3C velocity component is expressed as:

$$\Delta V_x = \left[\Delta_{V_{x,CS}}^2 + \Delta_{V_{x,other}}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.140)$$

Eq. 2.140 repeats for the other velocity component V_y and V_z . The uncertainties of stereo 2D3C velocities based on correlation statistics $\Delta V_{x,CS}$, $\Delta V_{y,CS}$, and $\Delta V_{z,CS}$ are directly available in the output data from *Davis*.

The remaining, $\Delta V_{x,other}$, $\Delta V_{y,other}$, and $\Delta V_{z,other}$ are estimated using eq. 2.137 - 2.139. Since the uncertainty based on correlation statistics (which takes into account the effect of X_d) is isolated, ΔV_{x1} , ΔV_{x2} , ΔV_{y1} , and ΔV_{y2} are now due to only the uncertainty of scaling factor ΔF_s and the uncertainty of separation time Δt_s . Recalling eq. 2.94 but excluding contribution of X_d leads:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V_{x1} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial V_{x1}}{\partial F_{s1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{F_{s1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_{x1}}{\partial t_s} \right)^2 \Delta_{t_s}^2} \\ \Delta V_{x2} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial V_{x2}}{\partial F_{s2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{F_{s1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_{x2}}{\partial t_s} \right)^2 \Delta_{t_s}^2} \\ \Delta V_{y1} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial V_{y1}}{\partial F_{s1}} \right)^2 \Delta_{F_{s1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_{y1}}{\partial t_s} \right)^2 \Delta_{t_s}^2} \\ \Delta V_{y2} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial V_{y2}}{\partial F_{s2}} \right)^2 \Delta_{F_{s1}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial V_{y2}}{\partial t_s} \right)^2 \Delta_{t_s}^2} \end{aligned} \quad (2.141)$$

2.6.3.3 Instantaneous flow angles

The uncertainty of instantaneous in-plane flow angle $\Delta \beta$ is calculated with an analogous approach of instantaneous velocity magnitude using the uncertainties of instantaneous velocities.

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_\beta &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial\beta}{\partial V_x}\right)^2 \Delta_{V_x}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial\beta}{\partial V_y}\right)^2 \Delta_{V_y}^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{V_y^2 \Delta_{V_x}^2 + V_x^2 \Delta_{V_y}^2}{V_x^2 V_y^2}}\end{aligned}\quad (2.142)$$

$$\frac{\partial\beta}{\partial V_x} = \frac{-V_y}{V_x^2 + V_y^2} \quad (2.143)$$

$$\frac{\partial\beta}{\partial V_y} = \frac{V_x}{V_x^2 + V_y^2} \quad (2.144)$$

2.6.3.4 Instantaneous isentropic Mach numbers

The isentropic Mach number M is a function of velocity magnitude $|V|$ and upstream total temperature T_0 as introduced by Eq. 2.55. The uncertainty of isentropic Mach number Δ_M is calculated by:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_M &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial |V|}\right)^2 \Delta_{|V|}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial T_0}\right)^2 \Delta_{T_0}^2} \\ &= \gamma R \sqrt{\left(T_0^2 \Delta_{|V|}^2 - \frac{1}{4} |V|^2 \Delta_{T_0}^2\right) \left[\gamma R T_0 - \frac{\gamma-1}{2} |V|^2\right]^{-3/2}}\end{aligned}\quad (2.145)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial M}{\partial |V|} &= \gamma R T_0 \left(\gamma R T_0 - \frac{\gamma-1}{2} |V|^2\right)^{-3/2} \\ \frac{\partial M}{\partial T_0} &= -\frac{\gamma R |V|}{2} \left(\gamma R T_0 - \frac{\gamma-1}{2} |V|^2\right)^{-3/2}\end{aligned}\quad (2.146)$$

2.6.4 Uncertainty of time-averaged quantities

2.6.4.1 Time-averaged velocities

When mean velocity field is computed by averaging N instantaneous velocity fields, the standard uncertainty of mean velocity $\Delta_{\bar{V}_{x,\text{typeA}}}$ is calculated by type A evaluation, which leads:

$$\Delta_{\bar{V}_{x,\text{typeA}}} = \frac{\sigma_{V_x}}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (2.147)$$

$$\sigma_{V_x} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (V_{x,i} - \bar{V}_x)^2}{N-1}} \quad (2.148)$$

The combined standard uncertainty of the mean velocity measured by PIV is expressed by:

$$\Delta_{\overline{V_x}} = \sqrt{\overline{\Delta_{V_x}}^2 + \Delta_{\overline{V_x}, \text{typeA}}^2} \quad (2.149)$$

where $\overline{\Delta_{V_x}}$ is the mean of Δ_{V_x} , which is the uncertainty of instantaneous velocity component. Here, the uncertainty of the instantaneous velocity component is treated as a separated uncertainty source from the type A uncertainty by considering it as a systematic uncertainty for the mean value.

The expanded combined uncertainty scaled by a coverage factor k is:

$$\Delta_{(k)\overline{V_x}} = k\Delta_{\overline{V_x}} \quad (2.150)$$

The coverage factor k is determined based on the error distribution and the effective number of samples. In this study, the distribution is assumed to be Gaussian as is the case in [91] and the number of samples for each test case is more than 500. Therefore it is reasonable to use $k = 1.96$ for the estimation of a confidence interval of 95%.

2.6.4.2 Time-averaged flow angles

The uncertainty of time-averaged in-plane flow angle $\Delta_{\overline{\beta}}$ is calculated with the analogous approach of time-averaged velocity. The standard uncertainty of mean flow angle estimated by type A evaluation is:

$$\Delta_{\overline{\beta}, \text{typeA}} = \frac{\sigma_{\beta}}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (2.151)$$

The combined standard uncertainty of the mean flow angle measured by PIV is expressed by:

$$\Delta_{\overline{\beta}} = \sqrt{\overline{\Delta_{\beta}}^2 + \Delta_{\overline{\beta}, \text{typeA}}^2} \quad (2.152)$$

where $\overline{\Delta_{\beta}}$ is the mean of Δ_{β} , which is the uncertainty of instantaneous flow angle.

2.6.4.3 Time-averaged Mach numbers

The uncertainty of time-averaged Mach number $\Delta_{\overline{M}}$ is calculated with the analogous approach of time-averaged velocity. The standard uncertainty of the mean Mach number estimated by type A evaluation is:

$$\Delta_{\overline{M}, \text{typeA}} = \frac{\sigma_M}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (2.153)$$

The combined standard uncertainty of the mean Mach number measured by PIV is expressed by:

$$\Delta_{\overline{M}} = \sqrt{\overline{\Delta_M}^2 + \Delta_{\overline{M}, \text{typeA}}^2} \quad (2.154)$$

where $\overline{\Delta_M}$ is the mean of Δ_M , which is the uncertainty of instantaneous Mach number.

2.6.5 Uncertainty of turbulence quantities

2.6.5.1 Turbulence intensities

A single component turbulence intensity TI_x is computed by:

$$TI_x = \frac{\sigma_{V_x}}{|\bar{V}|} \quad (2.155)$$

The uncertainty of standard deviation is (Benedict and Gould [94]):

$$\Delta\sigma_{V_x} = \frac{\sigma_{V_x}}{\sqrt{2(N-1)}} \quad (2.156)$$

Applying uncertainty propagation method, the uncertainty of TI_x is computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{TI_x} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial TI_x}{\partial \sigma_{V_x}}\right)^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TI_x}{\partial |\bar{V}|}\right)^2 \Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2}{|\bar{V}|^2} \left[\frac{1}{2(N-1)} + \frac{\Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2}{|\bar{V}|^2} \right]} \\ &= TI_x \sqrt{\frac{1}{2(N-1)} + \frac{\Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2}{|\bar{V}|^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.157)$$

where the sensitivity coefficients are calculated as:

$$\frac{\partial TI_x}{\partial \sigma_{V_x}} = \frac{1}{|\bar{V}|} \quad (2.158)$$

$$\frac{\partial TI_x}{\partial |\bar{V}|} = -\frac{\sigma_{V_x}}{|\bar{V}|^2} \quad (2.159)$$

The two-component turbulence intensity TI_{2C} is computed by:

$$TI_{2C} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2}{2}} / |\bar{V}| \quad (2.160)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{TI_{2C}} &= \left[\left(\frac{\partial TI_{2C}}{\partial \sigma_{V_x}}\right)^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TI_{2C}}{\partial \sigma_{V_y}}\right)^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_y}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TI_{2C}}{\partial |\bar{V}|}\right)^2 \Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \left[\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_y}}^2}{2|\bar{V}|^2 (\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2)} + \frac{(\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2) \Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2}{2|\bar{V}|^4} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= TI_{2C} \left[\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^4 + \sigma_{V_y}^4}{2(N-1) (\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2)} + \frac{\Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2}{|\bar{V}|^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.161)$$

where the sensitivity coefficients are calculated as:

$$\frac{\partial TI_{2C}}{\partial \sigma_{V_x}} = \frac{\sigma_{V_x}}{2|\bar{V}|} \left(\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2}{2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.162)$$

$$\frac{\partial TI_{2C}}{\partial |\bar{V}|} = -\frac{1}{|\bar{V}|^2} \left(\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.163)$$

The three-component turbulence intensity TI_{3C} is computed by:

$$TI_{3C} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 + \sigma_{V_z}^2}{3}} / |\bar{V}| \quad (2.164)$$

The uncertainty of TI_{3C} is computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{TI_{3C}} &= \left[\left(\frac{\partial TI_{3C}}{\partial \sigma_{V_x}} \right)^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TI_{3C}}{\partial \sigma_{V_y}} \right)^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_y}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TI_{3C}}{\partial \sigma_{V_z}} \right)^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_z}}^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{\partial TI_{3C}}{\partial |\bar{V}|} \right)^2 \Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \left[\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_y}}^2 + \sigma_{V_z}^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_z}}^2}{3|\bar{V}|^2 (\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 + \sigma_{V_z}^2)} + \frac{(\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 + \sigma_{V_z}^2) \Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2}{2|\bar{V}|^4} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.165) \\ &= TI_{3C} \left[\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^4 + \sigma_{V_y}^4 + \sigma_{V_z}^4}{2(N-1)(\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 + \sigma_{V_z}^2)} + \frac{\Delta_{|\bar{V}|}^2}{|\bar{V}|^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

where the sensitivity coefficients are calculated as:

$$\frac{\partial TI_{3C}}{\partial \sigma_{V_x}} = \frac{\sigma_{V_x}}{3|\bar{V}|} \left(\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 + \sigma_{V_z}^2}{3} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.166)$$

$$\frac{\partial TI_{3C}}{\partial |\bar{V}|} = -\frac{1}{|\bar{V}|^2} \left(\frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2 + \sigma_{V_y}^2 + \sigma_{V_z}^2}{3} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2.167)$$

2.6.5.2 Turbulence kinetic energies

The uncertainty of two-component turbulent kinetic energy $\Delta_{TKE_{2C}}$ is computed by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{TKE_{2C}} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial TKE_{2C}}{\partial V'_{x,RMS}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V'_{x,RMS}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TKE_{2C}}{\partial V'_{y,RMS}} \right)^2 \Delta_{V'_{y,RMS}}^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2 + \Delta_{\sigma_{V_y}}^2} \end{aligned} \quad (2.168)$$

Note that $V_{i,\text{RMS}'} = \sigma_{V_i}$. The uncertainty of three-component turbulent kinetic energy $\Delta_{TKE_{3C}}$ is computed by:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_{TKE_{3C}} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial TKE_{3C}}{\partial V'_{x,\text{RMS}}}\right)^2 \Delta_{V'_{x,\text{RMS}}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TKE_{3C}}{\partial V'_{y,\text{RMS}}}\right)^2 \Delta_{V'_{y,\text{RMS}}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial TKE_{3C}}{\partial V'_{z,\text{RMS}}}\right)^2 \Delta_{V'_{z,\text{RMS}}}^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sqrt{\Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2 + \Delta_{\sigma_{V_y}}^2 + \Delta_{\sigma_{V_z}}^2}\end{aligned}\quad (2.169)$$

2.6.5.3 Reynolds normal stresses

The Reynolds normal stress $R_{V_x V_x}$ for the x -component of velocity is defined as the variance of V_x [95]:

$$R_{V_x V_x} = \sigma_{V_x}^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (V_{x,i} - \bar{V}_x)^2 \quad (2.170)$$

The uncertainty of Reynolds normal stress is computed as:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta_{R_{V_x V_x}} &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial R_{V_x V_x}}{\partial \sigma_{V_x}}\right)^2 \Delta_{\sigma_{V_x}}^2} \\ &= \sqrt{4\sigma_{V_x}^2 \frac{\sigma_{V_x}^2}{2(N-1)}} \\ &= R_{V_x V_x} \sqrt{\frac{2}{N-1}}\end{aligned}\quad (2.171)$$

2.6.5.4 Reynolds shear stresses

The Reynolds normal stress $R_{V_x V_y}$ for the x and y components of velocity is defined as the covariance of V_x and V_y :

$$R_{V_x V_y} = \sigma_{V_x V_y}^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N (V_{x,i} - \bar{V}_x) (V_{y,i} - \bar{V}_y) \quad (2.172)$$

The uncertainty of Reynolds shear stress $\Delta_{R_{V_x V_y}}$ is the uncertainty of covariance $\Delta_{\sigma_{V_x V_y}^2}$. This is estimated by (Bendat and Piersol [96]):

$$\Delta_{R_{V_x V_y}} = \Delta_{\sigma_{V_x V_y}^2} = \sigma_{V_x} \sigma_{V_y} \sqrt{\frac{1 + \sigma_{V_x V_y}^2 / (\sigma_{V_x}^2 \sigma_{V_y}^2)}{N-1}} \quad (2.173)$$

2.7 Summary of chapter 2

Chapter 2 introduced the fundamental principles of particle image velocimetry and highlighted particular challenges in implementing the technique for turbomachinery applications.

The dynamics of particle motion were evaluated analytically, revealing the particle response in turbulent flows and high-velocity gradient flows. For a 1 μm DEHS oil droplet used as a tracer particle, the frequency of velocity fluctuation, at which the particle can recover 95% of its amplitude, is estimated to be up to 3 kHz. When subjected to a modest shockwave with a step velocity deceleration of 100 m/s, which is expected to appear in high-speed cascade tests, the particle is predicted to require 2 mm, or 100 ms, to reach the post-shock fluid velocity.

A fluorescent particle was developed for PIV measurements in gas flows to remove undesired reflections and enable simultaneous multi-constituent flows. The particle is created using a laskin-nozzle seeding generator and a solution composed of DEHS and Pyromethane 567. Spectroscopy measurements revealed the fluorescence emission spectra with a peak at around 540 - 585 nm, proving a sufficient Stokes shift for distinguishing the particle image from the laser beam and its reflection. The fluorescence intensity is dependent on the dye concentration due to the fluorescence quenching. In the form of sub-micron droplets, the fluorescence quenching is not evident, resulting in the intensity linearly proportional to the dye concentration. The fluorescent particles were tested in a low-speed wind tunnel equipped with a backward-facing step and a metallic turbine blade. Using a band-stop optical filter, reflections on the surfaces were effectively removed from the recorded images.

PIV measurements in turbomachinery often require a laser endoscope to deliver a laser beam inside confined test sections. Two prototype laser endoscopes are designed to satisfy several requirements for the test cases. Both scopes include a plano-concave cylindrical lens and a mirror prism to create a laser sheet illuminating the plane normal to the probe axis.

In the section on data reduction procedures, coordinate systems and equations utilized for calculating quantities of interest are introduced.

The last section described the uncertainty analysis method based on ISO/IEC GUIDE 98-3:2008. The uncertainty of instantaneous velocity is evaluated by expanding the uncertainty of the scaling factor, particle displacement, and separation time. The uncertainties of quantities derived from the measured velocity fields are also addressed. Since numerous input parameters, including temporal and spatial information, are required to calculate the uncertainties, this chapter describes only the evaluation method. The estimated uncertainties for each test case are presented in Chapter 4.

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3

Test cases

In Chapter 3, three test cases involved in this thesis are introduced. The first test case is the active turbulence grid installed in the rectangular test section of the L-12 continuously running low-speed wind tunnel. The second test case examines the SPLEEN C1 linear turbine cascade under transonic flow conditions in the S-1/C continuously running closed-loop wind tunnel. The third test case works on the rotating high-pressure turbine stage hosted by the CT-3 short-duration compression tube test rig. The chapter is divided into three main sections, each assigned to a test case. Each section includes a literature review, descriptions of the test rig and flow condition, PIV setup, and numerical setup if necessary. The results are presented in Chapter 4.

3.1 Active turbulence grid tests in a low-speed wind tunnel (L-12)

This section is dedicated to the PIV test case conducted in the L-12 low-speed wind tunnel. The test article is the active turbulence grid designed by Bertelli [1]. The section introduces the research background, literature review, objectives, and experimental setup. The results of the test case are provided in subsection 4.1.

3.1.1 Background and literature review

The characteristics of turbulence are known to have a significant impact on airfoil aerodynamics. One of the most important aspects is the influence on the laminar to turbulent boundary layer transition [2]. For example, Mayle [3] addressed three important modes of boundary layer transition in gas turbine flows: natural, bypass, and separated-flow transitions. As depicted in Fig. 3.1, these transition modes are affected by the inlet flow turbulence.

Figure 3.1: Topology of the different modes of transition in a Reynolds number, acceleration parameter plane [3].

The accurate prediction of boundary layer development by numerical approaches remains challenging due to the lack of correct modeling of the transition mechanisms coupled with a wide range of turbulence characteristics and diversified pressure gradients. To establish a robust and accurate transition model, it is necessary to obtain experimental databases that cover a broad spectrum of turbulence parameters such as turbulence intensity and length scale.

However, generating an appropriate turbulence field is practically not straightforward, especially when various turbulence characteristics have to be matched while complying with other flow parameters and test rig constraints.

The most common method to generate turbulence is the use of passive grids such as meshes and bars as found in several precedent studies [4–7]. Roach [4] carried out a parametric study of the aerodynamic characteristics of grids and provided a useful correlation to estimate the turbulence intensity and length scale as well as their decay with downstream distance for different grid types. While using a passive grid is a simple and well-established approach, the use of a fixed bar geometry lacks flexibility in the production and independent control of diversified turbulence characteristics.

Several methods capable of generating turbulence with some flexibility have been introduced in the past, for example: wall-jet type [8], cross-flow injection type [9], combustor simulator type [5, 10], moving-grid type [11] and jet-grid type [12–17].

At the VKI, Bertelli [1] designed a jet-grid type turbulence generator. Hereafter we call it "active turbulence grid". The jet-grid concept is based on momentum supply in the main-stream flow by using continuous, adjustable, and distributed compressed jet injections. The variation of turbulence levels downstream of the grid results from the interactions and mixing of the turbulent bar wakes with the synthetic jet injections and the blockage effect of the passive grid. Fig. 3.2 shows the conceptual sketch of the jet-grid type turbulence generator. The air injections are blown from an auxiliary pressure system into a hollowed passive grid and discharged through small injection holes in the upstream or/and downstream direction. Up-stream jets can be used to control the boundary layer separation on the grid bars by reducing the wake width and consequently reducing the effective solidity and the static pressure drop of the grid. On the other side, downstream jets can smooth the downstream flow field by fill-

ing in the bar wakes for better flow homogeneity or, if the jets are strong enough, make the bar wakes unstable (due to the additional shear in the jets themselves) to elevate the turbulence level.

Figure 3.2: Conceptual sketch of jet-grid turbulence generator.

For the efficient and reliable design of this type of device, a better understanding of the interaction between the jet and main flow, and turbulence production mechanism and its characteristics is of great importance. The investigation on the intermediate or far wake, i.e. at downstream distances greater than ten cylinder diameters [18, 19], is typically conducted by means of physical probe measurement such as a single or multi hot-wire probe [20]. In the near wake region where the flow is highly turbulent and directionally unsteady, quantitative measurements are possible only with non-intrusive techniques. For such a case, a time-resolved PIV measurement is an attractive approach as it can provide instantaneous flow field data with high spatial resolution with temporal context.

Since the late 90s, when the PIV was established as a standard measurement technique, various researchers have applied the technique to the investigation of cylinder wakes [21–25]. The PIV measurements on the interaction between the cylinder wake and jet have been performed by [26–34].

3.1.2 Objectives

In this study, high-speed PIV measurements are conducted to obtain time-resolved data of the unsteady flow field downstream of the active turbulence jet grid designed by Bertelli [1]. The ultimate goal of this test is understanding the mechanism of the turbulent flow generated near the bar wake and its turbulence characteristics, including the impact of the synthetic jet injection. In addition to a conventional Mie-scattering particle image recording technique, the fluorescent particles presented in section 2.3 are utilized to enable the simultaneous multi-

constituent flow measurement. With this method, the mainstream flow and auxiliary jet injection are distinguished by simultaneously recording the Mie scattering and fluorescence particle images. Either the mainstream or jet injection is tagged with the novel fluorescent particle made of dye-doped DEHS solution, and the rest is seeded with non-fluorescent oil droplets made of *Shell Ondina X420*. The individual and combined flow fields of the main flow and synthetic jet serve as a database for analyzing the dynamics of flow structure downstream of the active turbulence grid, revealing the interaction between the main flow and jet, and the characteristics of the turbulence field.

3.1.3 Test rig

A sketch of the continuously running open return wind tunnel L-12 of the von Karman Institute is shown in Fig. 3.3. The wind tunnel is driven by a centrifugal fan powered by a 700 W variable-speed AC motor. The facility consists of a diffuser fitted with wire meshes, a settling chamber fitted with a honeycomb panel and a 5.76:1 contraction. The typical test section has a cross-section of $0.2 \text{ m} \times 0.2 \text{ m}$ and longitudinal lengths up to 1 m. The maximum flow speed is 15 m/s. At the outlet of the exit nozzle, a ventilation duct is installed to avoid contamination of the laboratory by seeding particles.

Figure 3.3: The overview of VKI L-12 low speed wind tunnel.

3.1.4 Active turbulence grid

A schematic of the test section is illustrated in Fig. 3.4. The flow channel has a $200 \text{ mm} \times 200 \text{ mm}$ square cross-section bounded by transparent walls made of *Plexiglas* (acrylic) glass. The active turbulence grid consisting of six round bars is installed in the test section through slots made in the side walls maintaining its axis perpendicular to the longitudinal direction. The bars are distributed vertically with an equal space of 30 mm. The design of the bar is shown in Fig. 3.5, the outer diameter, D , is 10 mm and the inner diameter is 8 mm. Eight through-holes, each with a diameter of 2.1 mm, are machined at uniform 25 mm intervals along the span of the bar, maintaining consistent opening direction. The openings

are closed with tape in case the no- or mono-synthetic air injection is required. During the PIV measurement campaign, the fourth hole is aligned to the center of the wind tunnel.

The bottom plate of the test section has a slot for probe measurement, allowing longitudinal and spanwise traversing. Downstream of the test section, an exit nozzle which has the same cross-section and about 1 m length was attached to avoid sudden change in the flow channel.

Figure 3.4: The test section of L-12 for active turbulence grid measurements.

Figure 3.5: Design of the bar for the active turbulence grid.

Fig. 3.6 illustrates the secondary air system for the active turbulence grid. The air is distributed to each bar from a plenum chamber fed by a 7 bar compressed air pipeline in the laboratory. A part of the air from the 7 bar air pipeline is sent to a Laskin nozzle seeding generator (*PIVpart14* or *PIVpart45*) and the rest is bypassed directly to the plenum chamber. Multiple manual valves are used to regulate the mass flow rate of the secondary air. The mass flow rate is measured in one of the distribution pipes connecting the plenum chamber and the bar by *AALBORG GFMS-010015 Model GFM47* mass flow meter.

Figure 3.6: Secondary air system for the active turbulence grid.

3.1.5 PIV setup

3.1.5.1 Optical access

The test section is made of transparent *Plexiglas* plates except for the turbulence grid bars and fabricative parts such as screws and metal thread inserts. Fig. 3.7 illustrates the optical arrangement for the PIV measurements carried out in the presented test cases.

Two high-speed cameras (*Dantec SpeedSense 310*) both equipped with *Nikon AF Micro-Nikkor 60mm f/2.8D* are placed in front of each sidewall with their optical axis perpendicular to the measurement plane. Each camera is used in 2D2C-PIV configuration to acquire the same FOV images, aiming at distinguishing the synthetic jet and the main flow. For this purpose, one of the cameras (camera 2) is equipped with an OD6 band-stop optical filter whose blocking FWHM wavelength is 532 ± 10 nm.

A high-speed laser system *Quantronix Darwin Duo* with a wavelength of 527 nm is employed for particle illumination. The laser beam is steered above the test section through an articulated laser guide arm and transformed into a laser sheet with an approximate thickness of 1-1.5 mm using light sheet optics. The light sheet optics are composed of a spherical convex lens and a cylindrical plano-concave lens. The first lens controls the light sheet thickness while the second one diverges the beam to create a laser sheet. The light sheet is inserted through the top plate of the test section and aligned to the center of the test section. With the current setup, the PIV ROI covers about the area of $60 \text{ mm} \times 36 \text{ mm}$ located downstream of the third bar counted from the top.

The image acquisition including the synchronization of the laser system and cameras is done using *Dantec Dynamic Studio* with a *Dantec High Performance Synchronizer*.

To minimize the reflection, the turbulence grid bars are painted matt-black. The slot of the bottom plate is closed with a black sheet during the PIV measurements in order to minimize the flow leakage through the slot.

Figure 3.7: Optical arrangement of PIV measurement in L-12 wind tunnel.

3.1.5.2 Seeding

Two types of oil droplets are employed as tracer particles, one is made of *Shell Ondina X 420* oil and the other is made of the fluorescent oil composed of DEHS oil and Pyromethene 567 (P567) fluorescent dye. The dye concentration of P567 in DEHS was 1.5 g/L. The development of the fluorescent oil is described in subsection 2.3. Laskin-nozzle seeding generators (Fig. 2.5) are used for atomization, a *PIVpart45* for *Ondina X 420* and a *PIVpart14* for DEHS-P567 fluorescent oil. The nominal diameter of both tracer particles is expected to be 0.9 - 1.0 μm as shown in Fig. 2.7. Seeding in the main flow is achieved by injecting particles into the blower of the wind tunnel. Seeding in the synthetic jet from the active turbulence grid is achieved by injecting particles in the plenum chamber of the secondary air system Fig. 3.6.

3.1.5.3 Test conditions

In order to set the main flow condition, the settling chamber is equipped with a total pressure probe and static pressure tap, providing the upstream total pressure P_{01} and static pressure P_{s1} . At the inlet of the test section, a static pressure P_{s2} is measured by a pressure tap instrumented in the bottom plate. From the Bernoulli's equation for incompressible flows, the flow speed at the inlet of the test section is calculated as:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\rho} (P_{01} - P_{s2})} \quad (3.1)$$

where ρ is the density of air, calculated from the equation of state for perfect gas:

$$\rho = \frac{P_{s1}}{RT} \quad (3.2)$$

The main mass flow rate \dot{m} is computed as:

$$\dot{m} = \rho AV \quad (3.3)$$

where A is the cross-sectional area of the test section. The mass flow rate of secondary flow \dot{m}_s is directly measured by the mass flow meter as described in subsection 3.1.4.

Table 3.1 presents three PIV test cases (case ID: A-C) performed in L-12 wind tunnel. The main flow speed at the inlet was maintained $V_\infty = 5$ m/s throughout all test cases. The Reynolds number with respect to the bar diameter is calculated to be $Re = \rho|V_\infty|D/\mu = 3225$. PIV measurements are carried out for two scenarios, no synthetic jet injection (passive) and 1% downstream injection (active). For all cases, the measurement plane is aligned with the central injection hole of the bar. The type of seeding particles for the main flow and synthetic jet are switched to evaluate the effectiveness of the setup for differentiating the jet from the main flow. Fig. 3.8 displays exemplary images for each test case.

Table 3.1: Test conditions of PIV measurements in L-12 with the active turbulence grid.

Test case	Main flow speed	Injection mass flow ratio \dot{m}_s/\dot{m}	Injection direction	Main flow seeding	Injection flow seeding
A	5 m/s	0.0 %	-	Fluo	
B		5.0 %	Downstream	Ondina	Fluo
C				Fluo	Ondina

3.1.5.4 Image calibration

A single-level calibration target consisting of a regular dot pattern with 1 mm diameter and 2 mm space interval is used for image calibration. The target pattern is laser printed on a paper sheet, then it is attached to both sides of a 3D-printed base block. The calibration target plate is held by optical posts and placed in position using a traverse system constructed beneath the test section as shown in Fig. 3.9. The traverse system consisted of two motorized single-axis translation stages for adjustment in spanwise and vertical directions. The axial location and the plate angle are set using manual adjustment tools.

Calibration images are taken before starting the wind tunnel. First, one side of the calibration target is aligned to the measurement plane and a calibration image is taken with the camera in focus. Afterward, the calibration target is traversed in the plane-normal (spanwise) direction until the target on the other side is aligned with the measurement plane. Once the alignment is done, a calibration image is taken with the second camera which is now in focus.

The image calibration is performed using *Davis* PIV processing software. The 3rd-order polynomial function is selected for the fitting function in order to take into account arbitrary

Figure 3.8: Exemplary images of camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right) for test case A (Top), B (Middle) and C (bottom).

Figure 3.9: Traverse system in L-12 wind tunnel.

Table 3.2: Image calibration parameter obtained with 3rd-order polynomial fitting.

PIV setup	Test case	Parameter	Camera 1	Camera 2
Passive mode	A	RMS of fit [pixel]	0.23	0.21
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	20.46	
Active mode	B	RMS of fit [pixel]	0.23	0.25
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	20.50	
	C	RMS of fit [pixel]	0.23	0.19
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	20.48	

distortions caused by the optical windows. Table 3.2 lists the image calibration parameters for each PIV setup.

After image calibration in *Davis*, a conversion of the calibration target coordinate system to the measurement coordinate system was performed using *MATLAB*. Fig. 3.10 illustrates the schematics of the coordinate systems. The origin of measurement coordinate system is aligned to the center of the turbulence grid bar (the third bar counting from the top) and xy -axes correspond to the longitudinal and vertical directions.

Figure 3.10: Measurement and calibration coordinate systems.

3.1.5.5 Image recording

Table 3.3 presents the image recording parameters for the PIV measurements. The recording is made at acquisition frequency of 1000 Hz and 2000 double-frame snapshots are recorded for each test case. The separation time between the successive frames is set to 50 μ s. The laser pulse intensity is set to its maximum value: about 22 mJ/pulse. In order to make the FOV cover at least ± 0.5 bar pitch and 5 bar diameter downstream of the bar, the magnification factor is limited to about 0.39. The relatively large pixel size (20 μ m) and low pixel resolution (1200 \times 800) of the camera sensors results in the scaling factor of $F_s = 0.05$ mm/px and nominal particle displacement of 5 px.

Table 3.3: Image recording parameters of PIV measurements. f_{rec} : PIV recording frequency, N_{rec} : the number of pairs of images, I_0 : Laser pulse intensity, t_s : pulse separation time, X_d : estimated nominal particle displacement, F_s : Scaling factor.

V_∞	f_{rec}	N_{rec}	I_0	t_s	X_d	F_s
5 m/s	1000 Hz	2000	22 mJ	50 μ s	5 px/ t_s	0.05 mm/px

3.1.5.6 Image pre-processing

A subtraction of the time-averaged image is applied to the raw images in order to minimize image background noise and strong reflections appearing on the surface hit by the laser sheet.

For the images obtained from camera 2 in test case B, the particle signals are distributed only locally where the synthetic jet reaches. Directly proceeding to the cross-correlation step without further processing would result in numerous spurious vectors in regions devoid of particle signals. Hence, a masking filter that extracts jet-only image signal is created using additional image pre-processing steps to ensure that vectors are computed only within the jet. The result of the processing schemes for jet extraction is described in the result section 4.1.1.

3.1.5.7 Vector computation

Vector fields are computed using *Davis II* multi-pass cross-correlation algorithm. The interrogation window sizes for the starting and final paths are set to 128 \times 128 pixels and 32 \times 32 pixels with 50% overlaps. This setting resulted in vector spatial resolutions of about 0.75 mm. Table 3.4 summarizes the setting for image pre-processing and vector computations employed for the current test case.

Table 3.4: Setting for PIV processing.

	Camera 1 Mie scattering Image	Camera 2 Fluorescence image
Image preprocessing	Time-mean image subtraction Min/Max filter, L=4	Time-mean image subtraction Computation of particle seeding density (ppp) Creation of mask ($0.005 < ppp$) Masking with ppp mask Min/Max filter, L=4
Vector computation	Planar-PIV (2D2C) multi-pass cross-correlation Initial pass: 1 Initial IW size: 128×128 px with 50% overlapping and square weighting Final pass: 3 Final IW size: 32×32 px with 50% overlapping and round weighting Intermediate and final validation: Universal outlier detection : Remove if residual > 2.0 : Reinsert if residual < 3.0 : Filter region = 5×5 : Minimum number of vectors: 3 Final vector field treatment : Remove groups with 5 vectors : Interpolation	

3.2 Linear cascade tests in a high-speed wind tunnel (S-1/C)

This section is dedicated to the PIV test case conducted in the S-1/C continuously running high-speed wind tunnel. The test article is the SPLEEN C1 [35] transonic low-pressure turbine cascade. The section introduces the research background, literature review, objectives, and experimental setup. The results of the test case are provided in subsection 4.2.

3.2.1 Background and literature review

3.2.1.1 High-speed low-pressure turbines for aircraft engines

The ultra-high by-pass geared turbofan (GTF) is a key-enabler engine architecture to comply with the target reduction of noise and emissions by 2050. By decoupling the rotational velocity of the fan and LPT through a gearbox, the LPT stage count as well as engine weight and dimension can be reduced comparatively to a modern direct drive LPT [36].

In this engine architecture, the LPT operates at transonic exit Mach numbers ($M_{out} > 0.70$) and low-Reynolds numbers typically encountered during cruising regime as shown in Fig. 3.11 and 3.12 [37, 38]. The combination of these flow conditions results in a challenging environment where compressibility interacts with the transitional boundary layer encountered in LPTs [39, 40]. Experimental databases for this range of flow conditions that can be used to validate CFD tools and improve low-order models are still scarce. As an example, Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) computations using turbulence models still struggle to capture wake mixing and, therefore, lack accuracy in loss prediction [41].

Figure 3.11: Reynolds number variation through a medium-sized gas turbine engine [37].

Figure 3.12: Variation of Reynolds number in an low-pressure turbine for a civil aircraft flight envelope [37].

3.2.1.2 Current status of measurement techniques for high-speed LPTs

Investigations of LPT blading tested at engine-relevant conditions have been mostly conducted by means of aerothermal probes such as multi-hole pressure probes [6, 42–46]. The immersion of probes in transonic flow fields encountered in turbomachinery applications introduces non-negligible effects in the flow being measured [47–49] as well as the testing article [50, 51]. These effects become increasingly more impactful as the Mach number of the flow field in which the probe is immersed increases [52].

Turbulence characteristics, which is a critical flow parameter as identified by Mayle [3], are typically quantified by hot-wire (HW) probe measurements. HW testing in low-density transonic flows, however, suffers from inaccuracies resulting from the measured voltage being sensitive to velocity, density, temperature, and angle fluctuations [53]. This requires specific probes and calibrations to accurately predict the turbulence intensity, length scale, and turbulence anisotropy.

Alternatively, PIV, as it is a non-intrusive measurement technique, is an interesting solution for characterizing the high-speed flow field in turbomachinery passages without altering its topology. Also, unlike HW testing, PIV measurement can quantify turbulent quantities independently from the density level of the flow.

3.2.1.3 PIV measurements in linear cascade test rigs

The capabilities of PIV in high-speed flows are reported by Sartor et al. [54] and Scharnowski et al. [55]. The following part of the section reviews past studies that implemented PIV in linear cascades to survey the state-of-the-art of PIV measurements in such kinds of applications.

Woisetschläger et al. [56, 57] used PIV in a linear arrangement of the turbine profile to investigate the vortex shedding from the blade trailing edge. The measurement was performed in a wind tunnel of Graz University of Technology for the flow condition of $Re = 10.9 \times 10^5$ and $M = 0.77$. The air was continuously supplied to the wind tunnel by a centrifugal compressor. The turbulence level in velocity was 2% at the flow inlet. Two flat glass optical windows of 100×180 mm and 15 mm thick were granted for camera view and a laser sheet was inserted from the exit flow direction through a laser sheet probe (Fig. 3.13).

Laser pulse separation time was set to 1 μ s and PIV acquisition frequency was 15 Hz. *AGF 2.0D* particle generator provided DEHS oil droplets at 1 μ m in front of the turbine blade cascade through an 8 mm pipe, operated at 0.5-1 bar overpressure. Using the theory provided by Mei [58], They have estimated that 1 μ m droplets could follow the amplitude of about 20kHz velocity fluctuations with 95% of their amplitude. Fig. 3.14 shows the processing technique for vortex shedding-phase resolved evaluation. The vortex center was detected by applying the convolution window function to the velocity field acquired by PIV. Based on this information, the velocity fields were sorted by the vortex-shedding phase. Combined with the results of laser vibrometer measurements, they revealed the change of boundary layer from laminar to turbulent flow between $Re = 7 \times 10^5$ and $Re = 9 \times 10^5$. As a result, they concluded PIV is a helpful tool even in the investigation of high-frequency phenomena at small geometric scales.

Stieger et al. [59] utilized a combination of HW probe, fast response pressure transducers (*Kulite XCS-062*), and PIV to investigate unsteady transition mechanism of a boundary layer

Figure 3.13: Experimental PIV setup at Graz University of Technology [56, 57]. Notation in the left figure: 1. VKI-1 turbine blade cascade, 2. Tailboard, 3. Laser vibrometer, 4. Mirror, 5. Light-sheet optics, 6. Camera for PIV.

Figure 3.14: Evaluation of PIV recordings from (a) the two images recorded to (b) the instantaneous fields of vorticity. By detecting the vortex centres in these instantaneous data the recordings were sorted by phase. So, in addition to (c) the mean velocity field, (d) the phase-resolved velocity (periodic fluctuation) and vorticity were also obtained. PS denotes pressure side [56, 57].

on the suction surface of a low-pressure turbine blade. The measurement was carried out in the wind tunnel of Cambridge University, operated at a low Reynolds number in the range of $1.6 - 2.0 \times 10^5$. The static turbine cascade was subjected to periodical wakes generated by traversing bars as shown in Fig. 3.15.

Figure 3.15: Experimental PIV setup at Cambridge University [59].

The PIV measurements were performed in order to identify the responsible flow structure for the pressure fluctuation that was revealed by the fast response pressure transducers mounted on the blade surface. The PIV captured a small portion (19.0 mm square field of view) of the rear suction surface of the cascade through a 105 mm focal length lens. The pulse separation time was set to 3 ms providing particle displacements between 3 to 6 pixels. The data acquisition rate was 15 Hz which was not fast enough to capture a sequence of images within one bar passing cycle. *TSI Six-Jet Atomisers* generated seeding particles made of groundnut oil. The seeding was injected into the plenum chamber of the wind tunnel approximately 3 m upstream of the bar passing cascade. The final vector grid spacing after post-processing was $152 \mu\text{m}$. Vortices embedded in the boundary layer on the suction surface were observed by PIV as shown in Fig. 3.16 and were attributed to the source of large amplitude pressure fluctuations.

Rehder et al. [60] investigated three-dimensional flow and heat transfer with leakage ejection in the casing region of shrouded vanes. The measurement was performed in the cascade wind tunnel of DLR. Fig. 3.17 shows the schematics of the measurement setup. Three linear cascades were installed in the low-speed wind tunnel. The upper endwall of the flow duct was contoured with an opening angle of 15 degrees. The small leakage gap was placed in the corner of the backward-facing step 28 mm upstream of the vane leading edge. Two different leakage gap geometries for tangential and perpendicular ejection were tested. The lower endwall was equipped with a large observation window for optical measurement technique. The facility was a blow-down type and the measuring time lasted up to 20 minutes. The most

Figure 3.16: Left: Turbine cascade profile and location of PIV measurement. Right: Instantaneous vector map and computed streamlines from PIV measurement over the rear suction surface. [59].

upstream of the flow pass was atmospheric air and the most downstream was a large vacuum vessel. The Mach number of the cascade was set by an adjustable diffuser and the Reynolds number was dependent on the Mach number.

Figure 3.17: Experimental PIV setup at DLR [60].

The test was conducted for inlet Mach number of 0.25, exit Mach number of 0.523, inlet Reynolds number of 1.10×10^6 , and outlet Reynolds number of 2.10×10^6 . The inlet turbulence level was adjusted to 10% by an active turbulence generator mounted in the flow inlet. The leakage air whose mass flow rate varied 0% - 2% was provided by high pressure supply system and it was heated to a preset temperature. 2D2C-PIV measurement was performed at the near endwall region (5 – 35 mm above the endwall) and center vane leading edge. The light sheet was introduced to the test section by a laser sheet probe of 14 mm diameter. The laser sheet probe was inserted upstream of the cascade from the optical endwall. The optical axis was perpendicular to the light sheet and therefore not parallel in the spanwise direction.

The results are shown in Fig. 3.18. The figure on the top shows the measured velocity vectors and Mach number contours in the light sheet plane at 5 mm distance from the sidewall acquired with three camera positions. The out-of-plane component of velocity vectors was calculated from multi-plane velocity fields by considering the continuity equation for incompressible flow. It revealed the effect of leakage flow and geometries of the leakage gap on the secondary flow behavior and end wall heat transfer.

Figure 3.18: Top row: Velocity vectors and Mach number contours at 5 mm distance from the sidewall (zero leakage flow). Bottom row: Near wall 3D streamlines calculated from PIV measurements [60].

Sangston et al. [61], Bear et al. [62], Gross et al. [63] used a stereoscopic PIV system to investigate total pressure loss development within and downstream of a low-pressure turbine cascade. The experiments were carried out on a linear cascade of seven LPT blades with and without endwall contouring installed in the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) low-speed wind tunnel facility. This review focuses on the setup and results presented in [62]. The freestream turbulence intensity was set to 3% using a turbulence grid upstream of the blade row. The inlet flow condition was set to realize $Re = 1.0 \times 10^5$ based on inlet velocity and axial chord. PIV measured within and downstream of the cascade on axial chord planes at 69, 70, 71, 94, 95, 96, 149, 150, and 151% axial chord as shown in Fig. 3.19.

Measurements were conducted on closely spaced planes to calculate out-of-plane derivatives. Two cameras were fitted with Scheimpflug adapters and 532 nm band-pass optical filters, and positioned downstream of the blade row. The three adjacent measurement planes remained in focus without adjustment, and the laser sheet was traversed between each closely spaced plane without stopping the wind tunnel. The incompressible RANS momentum equation was rearranged to form an equation for the total pressure gradients in the local streamwise direction expressed solely based on velocity data, allowing the computation of the total pressure loss coefficient from PIV data. The comparison of PIV results against the implicit large eddy simulation (ILES) prediction presented a good agreement as shown in Fig. 3.20. The outcome of the experiment included an analysis of how the passage vortex, suction surface

Figure 3.19: (A) Diagram of the low-speed wind tunnel facility of AFRL. (B) PIV measurement plane locations. [62].

Figure 3.20: Total pressure transport (\dot{P}_t) contours with total pressure loss coefficient isolines and secondary velocity vectors: (a) ILES at 70% C_{ax} , (b) ILES at 95% C_{ax} , (c) ILES at 150% C_{ax} , (d) PIV at 70% C_{ax} , (e) PIV at 95% C_{ax} , (f) PIV at 150% C_{ax} . [62]

corner separation vortex, and trailing edge shed vortex contribute to the generation of losses in both the passage and the wake. The results revealed that the propagation of losses through and downstream of the passage was linked to the transport of total pressure.

Boerner et al. [52] evaluated the influence of five-hole-probe (5HP) on the wake flow field by 2D2C-PIV in a transonic turbine cascade rig of the University of the Bundeswehr Munich. The test facility, shown in Fig. 3.21, is an open-loop continuously operating wind tunnel with an open test section optimized for linear cascade. The Reynolds and Mach numbers were varied independently to achieve realistic turbomachinery flow conditions.

Figure 3.21: High-speed cascade wind tunnel (HGK) test facility of the University of the Bundeswehr Munich [52].

The operating range of the test facility was $2 \times 10^5 \leq Re/L \leq 1.6 \times 10^7 m^{-1}$ and $0.2 \leq Ma \leq 1.05$. Experimental cases for three different turbine exit flow Mach numbers (0.84, 0.95, 1) at probe Reynolds numbers of 6,500 and 13,000 were presented in the paper. The experimental setup is presented in Fig. 3.22-left. The 5HP was traversed in the pitchwise direction while maintaining its axial position 40% axial chord length downstream of the blade trailing edge. Acrylic glass windows were installed in each sidewall around the center blade of the cascade. DEHS particles of approximately $1 \mu m$ diameter were produced by a *LaVision Aerosol generator* and seeded into the settling chamber through a multi-hole nozzle. A laser system was placed outside the pressure tank and a laser sheet was introduced through a glass window into the pressure tank. The velocity vector was plotted per 0.5 mm after the PIV processing and 2000 frames were used to obtain averaged velocity fields. Fig. 3.22-right shows the normalized Mach number contours of clean field measured by PIV for low and high Mach number cases.

Fig. 3.23 presents the Normalized Mach number differences between clean and 5HP-inserted flow fields. The PIV measurements on the 5HP inserted into the flow field revealed a slight blockage effect of less than 1% for the investigated exit flow Mach number cases. A local flow perturbation close to the probe head was observable, but they were not influencing the wake flow field significantly. A good agreement of Mach number topology between 5HP and PIV measurements was shown in transonic flow regimes. However, it was revealed that blunt head-shaped 5HP overestimates flow velocity in a wake region due to both total and static pressure gradients appearing in such region. This means, that intrusive measurements

Figure 3.22: Left: Experimental setup of 5HP traverse and PIV field of view in the cascade wake at midspan. Left: Mach number of clean flow field calculated from PIV normalized with the reference Mach number of the 5HP (Dashed line shows 5HP wake traverse path; blade numbers in boxes) [52].

such as 5HPs and hot wire anemometers have considerable errors on their measurement data depending on their designs. Measurements by non-intrusive techniques such as PIV or LDV have great importance in order to acquire a reliable experimental database.

Figure 3.23: Normalized Mach number differences of the Mach numbers calculated from the PIV velocity fields with inserted 5HP subtracted by the “clean”-field (“highMa”-case) [52].

In the same facility of the University of the Bundeswehr Munich, Chemnitz et al. [64] conducted measurements using PIV, 5HP, and Constant Temperature Anemometry (CTA) to provide comprehensive three-dimensional turbulent flow quantities. The experiments were performed downstream of a high-speed low-pressure turbine cascade under engine-representative conditions. The schematics of the test section and measurement setup are shown in Fig. 3.24.

Placing an additional endwall near the former midspan, a new boundary layer was formed from the inserted endwall leading edge. Isentropic Mach number $M_{2,is} = 0.6$ and isentropic

Figure 3.24: Schematics of setup in side view (left) and from top (right), cascade not to scale [64].

Reynolds number $Re_{2, is}/C = 2.15 \times 10^6$ at the cascade outlet were chosen as the operating point. The laser beam was guided via a series of mirrors, and inserted to the test section from the bottom of the cascade. The light sheet thickness was chosen to be approximately 2 mm. The scale factor was about 12 px/mm. 1 μm diameter DEHS droplets were provided by a Laskin-type aerosol generator and droplets were injected inside the settling chamber by a multi-hole rake. A regular dot pattern 2D calibration target with five equidistant views was used as a 2D3C planar calibration. 10000 PIV frames were recorded with an acquisition frequency of 15 Hz. The vector resolution was 1.3 mm after all the PIV processing. A general agreement of time-averaged velocity fields between PIV, 5HP, and CTA was reported as shown in Fig. 3.25. The most noticeable deviations were found in the regions of strong angular gradients which led to higher measurement uncertainties especially for 5HP and CTA due to the finite dimension and geometry of the probes. The turbulence fields were also computed from PIV data as shown in Fig. 3.26. Deviations of measured turbulent fluctuation quantities between PIV and CTA amounted up to 3% near the passage vortex core region. The limitation of CTA measurements was revealed due to the finite probe size and individual wire geometry. The capability of PIV combined with other techniques such as 5HP and CTA was evaluated such that it can provide reliable time-resolved flow data in complex flow presents in modern low-pressure turbine stages featuring high-Mach and low-Reynolds numbers.

Figure 3.25: Left: Normalized velocities from PIV with secondary velocity vectors and corresponding vortex cores (PIV = black markers). Middle: Deviations between PIV and 5HP. Right: Deviations between PIV and CTA [64].

Recently, Canepa et al. [65] carried out PIV measurements in the low-speed wind tunnel at the University of Genova to investigate the wave-boundary layer interaction over a blade

Figure 3.26: Three-dimensional turbulence components in wake and secondary flow region from PIV [64].

suction surface. The test section consisted of a seven-blade planar cascade, representative of a highly accelerated low-pressure turbine row. The inlet freestream turbulence intensity was set to 6% by means of a turbulence grid. Additionally, upstream wakes were simulated by the moving bar system as illustrated in Fig. 3.27.

Figure 3.27: Schematics of PIV setup (on the top) and FOV of two cameras (on the bottom). [65].

The measurement was performed for four flow conditions, varying the reduced frequency of incoming wake and flow coefficient. The Reynolds number was maintained at $Re_{out} = 120k$. Two cameras were used simultaneously to observe two separated areas in the boundary layer on the blade suction side, one behind the velocity peak region and the other close to the blade trailing edge as shown in Fig. 3.27-bottom. $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ vaseline oil droplets were seeded at the wind tunnel entrance, the seeding flow rate was tuned to obtain a particle concentration of 4-5 particles per interrogation window. The separation time between consecutive frames was set to $40 \mu\text{s}$, which was optimized for the velocity gradients in the boundary layer. A total

amount of 2000 image pairs were recorded for each flow condition. Applying time-mean and phase-locked average, mean and periodic (wake-induced) boundary layer characteristics were successfully obtained as shown in Fig. 3.28. Furthermore, POD was applied to different phases in order to investigate the main flow structures involved in the wake-boundary layer interaction process. Fig. 3.29 presents the vectorial representation of the first POD mode computed at three different phases and two exemplary higher-order modes representative of finer scale fluctuations carried by wakes.

Figure 3.28: Time-mean velocity vectors measured by PIV. Contour of streamwise velocity component U . Grey line represents the boundary layer thickness [65].

Figure 3.29: Exemplary POD modes at different phases. Contour plots report the turbulent kinetic energy production per mode [65].

Table 3.5 shows the summary of precedent studies. While these studies have provided valuable information for better understanding of turbine flows, for most of cases the Reynolds numbers investigated are relatively high ($Re_{out} > 200k$) [57] or the outlet Mach number is subsonic ($M_{out} < 0.6$) [59, 64, 65] for realistic engine operating conditions. The experiments in subsonic flow are usually more accessible for detailed measurements in space and time, but the tests do not capture the impact of compressibility, and the combined effect of transonic and low-Reynolds flow regime is still not well investigated. To the best of the author's knowledge, there are only a few works in open literature reporting PIV measurements in low-Reynolds transonic turbine cascades [52, 66].

Table 3.5: Precedent PIV measurements in linear turbine cascade test rigs.

Facility type	Lab	Testing time	$Re_{out}/10^3$	M_{out}	Inlet TI	Type of PIV	ROI	Rec. freq.	Nb. rec.	Seeding
Transonic WT	TU Graz [56]	Continuous	1090	0.77	2%	2D2C	B2B - Near blade TE	15 Hz	300	DEHS oil droplet 1 μm
Open-circuit low-speed WT	Cambridge [59]	Continuous	160 - 200	NA	NA	2D2C	B2B - BL of blade SS	15 Hz (Phase locked)	NA	Groundnut oil mist Size: NA
Blow down WT	DLR [60]	200 mins	2100	0.523	10%	2D2C	B2B - Near hub gap	NA	50	NA
Open-circuit low-speed WT	AFRL [61][62][63]		100	NA	3%	2D3C	Axial Plane - Blade passage - Cascade outlet	NA	2000	NA
			120	0.6	2 - 8%	2D2C	B2B - Blade passage	8 - 10 Hz	1000 - 10000	DEHS oil droplet 0.1 - 2.0 μm
			200 - 160 / C	0.84 - 1.00	0.4 - 7.5%	2D2C	B2B - Cascade outlet with probe	NA	2000	DEHS oil droplet 1 μm
Open-circuit transonic WT	BW Munich [67] [52] [66] [64]	Continuous	60 - 120	0.7	4%	2D3C	B2B - Inflow - Cascade outlet	15 Hz (Phase locked)	5000	DEHS oil droplet
			215 / C	0.6	6.9%	2D3C	Axial plane - Cascade outlet	15 Hz	10000	DEHS oil droplet 1 μm
Low-speed WT	U Genova [65]		160	NA	6%	2D2C	B2B - BL of blade SS	6 Hz (Phase locked)	2000	Vaseline oil droplet 1 μm
Closed-loop transonic WT	VKI (Current study)		70 - 120	0.7 - 0.95	0.9 - 2.5%	2D2C/ 2D3C	B2B - Inflow - Cascade passage outlet Axial plane - Cascade outlet	15 Hz	2000	DEHS oil droplet 1 μm

3.2.1.4 Objectives

In view of the current state-of-the-art, this work is conducted with the aim of verifying the capability of PIV technique in low-Reynolds transonic turbine flows. In particular, it is of interest to establish a knowledge base from which one can derive the limitations of the technique, as well as determine the optimal data acquisition and processing setup for achieving the most accurate results. Additionally, the outcomes of the measurement fills the lack of experimental databases for transonic turbine flows, where physical probe measurements suffer from probe interference effects. Special attention is given to turbulence quantities, as they have prominent impacts on the boundary layer development of low-pressure turbine blades and are also key flow behaviors that numerical approaches seek to model accurately.

The measurements are performed in the VKI S-1/C transonic linear cascade equipped with the SPLEEN C1 blade exploited in the EU project SPLEEN [68, 69]. The outlet Mach and Reynolds numbers are varied between 0.70-0.95 and 70k-120k, respectively.

A standard two-dimensional two-components (2D2C) PIV system is employed for measurements on the midspan blade-to-blade (B2B) plane in and downstream of the blade passage. A two-dimensional three-component (2D3C) stereoscopic PIV system is utilized for measurements on the midspan B2B plane upstream of the cascade as well as on the cascade outlet plane (COP) located near the endwall. Each PIV measurement investigates the mean and turbulent flow characteristics of the transonic turbine flow. The results are compared against HW and 5HP measurements and RANS predictions, cross-validating the accuracy of each technique and quantifying the probe-interference effect.

3.2.2 Test rig

A schematic of the continuously running closed-loop wind tunnel S-1/C of the von Karman Institute is shown in Fig. 3.30. The wind tunnel is driven by a 615 kW 13-stage axial flow compressor. The cascade Mach and Reynolds numbers are independently adjusted by regulating the compressor rotational speed and the flow density inside the loop. The latter is achieved by regulating the net mass flow being removed from the loop through a vacuum pump. The flow temperature is always kept near ambient by means of a heat exchanger.

Fig. 3.31 shows a sketch of the cascade test section installed in one of the turning elbows of the wind tunnel. The flow path of the test section elbow comprises the wind tunnel walls and guide plates, a boundary layer lip, and the cascade module. A passive turbulence grid (TG) is used to reach the desired freestream TI. The freestream TI without the grid is reported to be around 0.90% [6]. Installing the TG 400 mm upstream of the central airfoil leading edge, the HW measurement registered a nominal TI of 2.4% [68]. Although the facility can perform tests using a rotating wake generator, PIV measurements are conducted without it due to significant structural vibrations caused by the rotating component.

3.2.3 SPLEEN C1 high-speed cascade

The test article is the SPLEEN C1 cascade whose experimental database has been collected at VKI within the H2020 Clean Sky 2 project SPLEEN (Secondary and Leakage Flow Effects in High-Speed Low-Pressure Turbines) in collaboration with Safran Aircraft Engines [35]. Fig. 3.32 illustrates the blade geometry. The two-dimensional blade profile represents the

Figure 3.30: The overview of VKI S-1/C test rig.

Figure 3.31: The cascade test section of S-1/C.

rotor hub geometry of a geared LPT. The airfoil is designed for transonic outlet flow conditions, high deflection, and low flow acceleration. The linear cascade consists of 23 blades with a span of 165 mm. Table 3.6 summarizes the geometry of the tested cascade. A thorough description of the test case are available in [68].

Figure 3.32: SPLEEN C1 blade geometry.

3.2.4 Test conditions

The current setup enables testing at a range of outlet isentropic Mach number $M_{out, is}$ and outlet isentropic Reynolds number $Re_{out, is}$ between 0.70 and 0.95, and 70k and 120k, respectively. The computation of $M_{out, is}$ and $Re_{out, is}$ are performed with the following equations:

$$M_{out, is} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma - 1} \left[\left(\frac{P_{out, is}}{P_{0, in}} \right)^{-\frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma}} - 1 \right]} \quad (3.4)$$

$$Re_{out, is} = \frac{\rho_{out, is} V_{out, is} C}{\mu_{out, in}} \quad (3.5)$$

The cascade outlet static pressure $P_{out, is}$ is measured by means of endwall pressure taps placed downstream of the blade trailing edge. The inlet total pressure $P_{0, in}$ is retrieved from a total pressure probe placed upstream of the TG. The pressure drop across the TG is taken into account by applying an empirical total pressure drop coefficient. The outlet isentropic density ρ is obtained from the ideal gas equation:

$$\rho_{out, is} = \frac{P_{out, s}}{R T_{out, s}} \quad (3.6)$$

The cascade outlet static temperature is computed using the following isentropic equation:

Table 3.6: SPLEEN C1 cascade geometry.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Scaling factor	-	1.60	[-]
Chord	C	52.28	[mm]
Axial chord	C_{ax}	47.61	[mm]
Pitch	g	32.95	[mm]
Blade span	H	165	[mm]
Max thickness / Chord	-	0.127	[-]
Trailing edge thickness	t_{te}	0.87	[mm]
Throat opening	o	19.40	[mm]
Stagger angle	ζ	24.40	[deg]
Trailing edge Wedge angle	δ_{SS}	6.48	[deg]
Inlet metal angle	$\beta_{\text{metal, in}}$	37.30	[deg]
Outlet metal angle	$\beta_{\text{metal, out}}$	53.80	[deg]
Compressible Zweifel lift coefficient	Zw_{comp}	0.94	[-]
Diffusion factor	DF	0.196	[-]
Circulation coefficient	C_0	0.61	[-]

$$T_{\text{out, s}} = T_{0, \text{in}} \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} M_{\text{out, s}}^2 \right)^{-1} \quad (3.7)$$

The cascade outlet isentropic velocity is calculated by:

$$V_{\text{out, is}} = M_{\text{out, is}} \sqrt{\gamma R T_{\text{out, s}}} \quad (3.8)$$

Finally, the outlet isentropic dynamic viscosity $\mu_{\text{out, is}}$ is computed using the Sutherland's law:

$$\mu_{\text{out, is}} = \frac{1.458 \times 10^{-6} T_{\text{out, is}}^{3/2}}{T_{\text{out, s}} + 110.4} \quad (3.9)$$

PIV measurements for three test configurations, on the B2B plane upstream of the cascade (B2B upstream), on the B2B plane in the cascade passage (B2B passage), and on the cascade outlet plane (COP), are performed separately. Details of the measurement planes are described in the following sections. The flow conditions investigated in the scope of this work are summarized in Table 3.7. Due to limited availability of the facility, the flow conditions for the B2B upstream and COP configurations are reduced. The stability of the flow condition is displayed in Fig. 3.33, 3.34, and 3.35 for each measurement configuration. The horizontal and vertical error bars indicate the maximum variation of the outlet isentropic Reynolds and Mach numbers during PIV image recording. The standard deviation of outlet isentropic Reynolds and Mach numbers (σ_{Re} , σ_M) are reported in the legend. Injecting tracer particles in the wind tunnel increases the air density, leading to an increase in the Reynolds number. To minimize Reynolds number variation during testing, a total of 2000 PIV image pairs are acquired by recording 500 image pairs four times. The variations in the outlet flow quantities are more pronounced for lower Reynolds number cases, as regulating air density at very low levels is challenging with the limited capacity of the vacuum pump.

Table 3.7: Test cases of PIV measurements in S-1/C.

TG	Re	M	B2B Upstream	B2B Passage	COP
With	70k	0.70	-	✓	✓
		0.90	✓	✓	✓
		0.95	-	✓	✓
	120k	0.70	✓	✓	-
		0.90	✓	✓	-
Without	70k	0.70	✓	✓	-
		0.90	✓	✓	-
		0.95	-	✓	-
	120k	0.70	✓	✓	-
		0.90	✓	✓	-

Figure 3.33: Test condition for measurements on the upstream B2B plane. Left: testing without the TG. Right: testing with the TG.

Figure 3.34: Test condition for measurements on the passage B2B plane. Left: testing without the TG. Right: testing with the TG.

Figure 3.35: Test condition for measurements on the COP.

3.2.5 PIV setup

Fig. 3.36 illustrates the FOV of the three PIV configurations carried out in the present study. The first configuration aims for measurements on the midspan B2B plane at the cascade upstream using a stereoscopic 2D3C PIV setup. The second configuration is again on the midspan B2B plane but in the cascade passage including the downstream region employing a planar 2D2C PIV setup. Lastly, the third configuration examines the COP near the endwall using a stereoscopic 2D3C PIV setup. The COP is located $0.5 C_{ax}$ downstream of the blade trailing edge where aerodynamic probe measurements were performed extensively in the SPLEEN project [35, 68].

3.2.5.1 Optical access

The optical access for PIV measurements is realized by combining a cascade endwall window, sidewall windows, and laser endoscopes. The orientation of the optical windows is presented in Fig. 3.37. The endwall window is mounted on the cascade endwall aligned to the central blade providing a view in the spanwise direction. The two sidewall windows are attached to the sidewall of the elbow, allowing access from the downstream of the cascade at different angles. The COP is positioned in parallel with the second row of the pressure taps located $0.5 C_{ax}$ downstream of the blade trailing edge. The center of FOV is aligned to the 16th pressure tap whose position coincides with the blade outlet metal angle line.

A new cascade endwall plate is designed and manufactured for optical measurements since the original S-1/C SPLEEN cascade endwall, which is adapted for the measurements with the probes and the sliding blades, does not allow installation of the optical instruments. The original cascade endwall and the optical one are illustrated in Fig. 3.38. The main feature of the modified design is having multiple pockets and peripheral grooves. The central pocket is used to mount the endwall window while the additional four pockets (A - D) surrounding the central pocket are mainly used for the installation of the image calibration plate. These pockets are necessary to insert, manipulate, and extract the calibration plate system without touching the other optical systems such as the endwall window and the cameras after recording the calibration images. These pockets are covered by metallic caps during the test. Some

(A) Blade-to-blade plane

(B) Cascade outlet plane

Figure 3.36: Field of view of the PIV measurements.

Figure 3.37: The orientation of optical windows of the test section.

holes are added to one of the caps to provide access to the laser endoscope. For example, PIV measurements at the cascade inlet are realized by inserting the laser endoscope via a hole in the pocket. The peripheral groove is added to the plate in order to seal the test section without the additional sealing box. This sealing-box-less architecture enables easy access to the cascade endwall.

Figure 3.38: S-1/C SPLEEN C1 endwalls: (a) Original endwall (b) Optical endwall.

The design of the endwall window is illustrated in Fig. 3.39. The window is made of clear transparent acrylic (PLEXIGLAS) and the window surfaces are polished. The endwall window has a maximum thickness of 40mm and it covers four blade passages centered on the central blade. The windowed area on the endwall extends up to 48.57 mm ($1.02 x / C_{ax}$) upstream from the blade LE and 76.82 mm ($1.61 x / C_{ax}$) downstream from the blade TE. The endwall window has 10 holes for the blade alignment and one through-hole to pass an M4 screw that holds the central blade. Fig. 3.40 shows the endwall window installed in the test section.

Fig. 3.41 shows the design of the sidewall window. The two side wall windows have a thickness of 20mm and a square shape surface area of 175 mm \times 198 mm, and each of them is attached to a metallic plate and then mounted to the wind tunnel side wall. The orientation angle of the sidewall windows 1 and 2 are respectively 40.73 degrees and 4.27 degrees with respect to the cascade outlet plane. Fig. 3.42 shows the endwall window installed in the test section.

For the measurement in the upstream B2B plane configuration, pocket A located next

Figure 3.39: The design of endwall window.

Figure 3.40: The endwall window mounted in the test section.

Figure 3.41: The design of sidewall window.

Figure 3.42: The sidewall window mounted in the test section.

to the endwall window is used for the laser endoscope insertion. Fig. 3.43 illustrates the pocket cover A with three slots for the laser endoscopes. Two slots on the top and bottom are designed for the endoscope with a diameter of 8 mm (Endoscope1: TUR1715-301), and a slot in the middle is designed to accommodate the endoscope with a diameter of 9 mm (Endoscope2: TUR2022-A02). The design of endoscopes is described in section 2.4. When the slots are not used, dummy probes are inserted to close it.

Figure 3.43: Endoscope access through Pocket cover A. (a) The design of pocket cover A. (b) Endoscope 1 installed in the cover. (c) Endoscope 2 installed in the cover.

In the following paragraphs, the setup of the laser system and cameras as well as the procedure of the image calibration are described for each PIV configuration.

B2B Upstream setup

Fig 3.44 and 3.45 show schematics and photos of the PIV setup for the B2B upstream PIV configuration. The laser head is placed in front of the endwall of the test section. The laser beam emitted from the laser head is guided through a right-angle prism and mirror to the laser endoscope installed in pocket cover A. The laser endoscope enabled the delivery of the laser beam inside the enclosed test section. The light sheet optics embedded in the tip of the endoscope create a 1.5 – 2.0 mm thick laser sheet from the beam. The precise alignment is carried out when the image calibration plate is placed in the measurement location. The yaw angle of the endoscope is adjusted so that the central part of the laser sheet illuminates the area covering 0 - 60% blade axial chord upstream of the central blade. To minimize the light reflection, a matte-black paint is applied to the central 8 blades and endwall surface. The painted blade is shown in Fig. 3.46.

Two cameras are placed in front of the endwall window in a manner of stereoscopic vision. Both cameras are equipped with an *Nikon AF Micro NIKKOR 60 mm f/2.8D* lens. The camera body is tilted with respect to the lens to satisfy Scheimpflug condition using an adapter from *LaVision*. The camera orientation parameters estimated by the pihole model in *Davis* are reported in Table. 3.8. The large RMS fit error is due to the pinhole model that can not take into account the image distortions through the optical windows. The pihole model parameters are used to solely provide the physical orientation of cameras, such as the camera angles and camera translations with respect to the measurement plane. The actual calibration parameters used for pixel to real world conversion are obtained by a 3rd order polynomial model and subsequent self-calibrations. These parameters are reported later in the subsection 3.2.5.2. While the optimum angle between two cameras for stereoscopic vision is around 90 degrees [70], the limited space due to packed hardware such as laser endoscope and calibration traverse system imposes the maximum angle between the two cameras to be around 45 degrees. Note that, the traverse system seen in the picture in Fig. 3.45 is removed and the pocket hole is closed with a cover before starting the facility.

B2B Passage setup

Fig. 3.47 and 3.48 show schematics and photos of the PIV setup for the B2B upstream PIV configuration. The laser head is placed behind the sidewall of the test section. The laser beam emitted from the laser head is guided to the light sheet optics by two mirrors. The light sheet optics consists of telescope lenses from *LaVision* Divergent sheet optics and a plano-concave cylindrical lens from *Thorlabs*. Fig. 3.49 illustrates a conceptual sketch of the light sheet optics. The first two lenses (Lens 1 and 2) work as telescope lenses, controlling the position of the beam waist of the light sheet by adjusting the distance between Lens 1 and Lens 2. The third lens (Lens 3) converts the laser beam into the laser sheet. The specifications of the lenses are listed in Table 3.9.

The light sheet is inserted into the test section from the sidewall window 2, allowing the illumination of the rear part of the central blade passage (suction side). The position of the laser sheet is preliminarily aligned before setting camera positions, and fine-tuning is done when the image calibration plate is placed on the measurement plane. Similar to the B2B upstream setup, a matte-black paint is applied to the endwall wall in order to minimize reflections. The area where the pressure taps are instrumented is not painted to avoid clogging. The central blade is coated with orange-fluorescent paint aiming at effective reduction of the light

Figure 3.44: Schematics of the laser and camera setup for B2B upstream configuration.

Figure 3.45: PIV setup for B2B upstream configuration.

Figure 3.46: Matte-black painted blade.

Table 3.8: Estimated camera orientation parameters for upstream B2B plane PIV setup using the Pinhole camera calibration model.

Parameter	With TG	
	Camera 1	Camera 2
RMS of fit [pixel]		0.67
Focal length [mm]	75.61	76.78
Origin [pixel]	(1187.62, 915.19)	
Translation [mm]	(25.00, 2.38, 313.19)	(-31.25, 1.65, 322.56)
Rotation [deg]	(-4.86, 17.89, -0.58)	(-6.91, -17.34, -0.53)
Scale factor [pixel/mm]	44.17	

Parameter	Without TG	
	Camera 1	Camera 2
RMS of fit [pixel]		0.79
Focal length [mm]	71.18	83.38
Origin [pixel]	(1041.71, 989.10)	
Translation [mm]	(18.63, 2.97, 286.62)	(-43.22, 1.66, 343.72)
Rotation [deg]	(-1.11, 16.58, -0.98)	(-2.63, -18.81, -0.96)
Scale factor [pixel/mm]	45.33	

Table 3.9: The specification of lenses in the light sheet optics. T : Transmission. R_{avg} : Average reflection.

	Vendor	Product num.	Substance	Lens type	Focal length	Coating
Lens 1	LaVision	1108405	BK7	Spherical plano-concave	NA	AR for 527/532 nm $T > 95\%$ (532 nm)
Lens 2	LaVision	1108405	BK7	Spherical plano-convex	NA	AR for 527/532 nm $T > 95\%$ (532 nm)
Lens 3	Thorlabs	LK1743RM-A	N-BK7	Cylindrical plano-concave	-100 mm	AR for 350 - 700 nm $R_{avg} < 0.5\%$

reflection. Fluorescent paint absorbs the laser light and emits a fluorescence that has a longer wavelength. Employing an appropriate optical filter such as a band-pass filter, the fluorescent light can be cut off. The painted blade and endwall are shown in Fig. 3.50. The thickness of the paint on the blade is measured to be 0.1 mm using feeler gauges. After testing, a burned pattern caused by the laser sheet is observed on the fluorescent paint of the central blade. Neither a significant change in the surface roughness nor an increase in the light reflection in the recorded image are found.

Two cameras are placed side by side facing the measurement plane through the endwall window to acquire two FOVs simultaneously as illustrated in Fig. 3.36. While camera 1 mainly focuses on the blade passage, camera 2 observes downstream of the cascade. The FOVs of the two cameras are set to overlap by approximately 20%. Due to the relatively small FOV against the size of the cameras and lenses, camera 2 has to be slightly tilted to maintain the FOV overlap. Both cameras are equipped with a *Nikon AF Micro NIKKOR 60 mm f/2.8D* lens. While a Scheimpflug adaptor is mounted on each camera, no significant Scheimpflug angle is set since the image planes are nearly parallel to the measurement plane. The optical setup results in a scaling factor of about 48 pixel/mm. Furthermore, camera 1 is equipped with a 532 ± 10 nm band-pass filter. The filter is attached to the Scheimpflug adaptor using a 3D-printed filter holder as shown in Fig. 3.51.

COP setup

Fig. 3.52 and 3.53 show schematics and photos of the PIV setup for the COP measurement. The laser head is placed in front of the endwall of the test section. The laser beam emitted from the laser head goes through the light sheet optics forming the laser sheet, then guided to the test section by two mirrors. The light sheet is inserted into the test section from the endwall window. The precise alignment of the laser sheet is carried out once the image calibration plate is placed on the measurement plane.

Fig. 3.54 shows close-up views of the measurement location of COP PIV. A matte-black paint is applied to the central 8 blades and the endwall surface except for the area where pressure taps are instrumented. Originally, the laser sheet is planned to be aligned to $0.5 C_{ax}$ downstream of the cascade trailing edge (Plane 06), where the endwall pressure taps and aerodynamics probe measurements were performed in the SPLEEN test campaign. However, the PIV measurement on the exact location of Plane 06 is prevented due to a significant light reflection on the unpainted area over the pressure taps. Instead, the COP for PIV is axially shifted by 2 mm ($0.04 C_{ax}$) upstream from Plane 06. After performing tests for the five flow conditions, i.e. 10000 PIV recordings, a burned pattern on the black paint was found. The burned paint absorbs less light, resulting in a higher reflection intensity in the PIV images and the effect is more evident in the images recorded later in the testing campaign.

Camera 1 and camera 2 are placed in front of sidewall window 1 and 2, respectively. Camera 1 is equipped with a *Tamron SP AF180 mm f/3.5 Di LD(iF) Macro* lens and camera 2 is equipped with a *AF Micro NIKKOR 200mm f/4 AF-D* lens. Lenses with different focal lengths are used between two cameras to obtain similar FOVs for different working distances. Each camera is mounted on a Scheimpflug adapter to set the appropriate tilt angle between the camera body and lens. The cameras are held by a tripod (camera 1) or a traverse system (camera 2) as well as a structure attached to the wind tunnel. The stereoscopic camera orientation parameters estimated by the pihole model in *Davis* are reported in Table. 3.10.

Figure 3.47: Schematics of the laser and camera setup for B2B passage configuration.

Figure 3.48: PIV setup for B2B Passage configuration.

Figure 3.49: Schematics of the light sheet optics.

Figure 3.50: The central blade coated with the fluorescent paint and the cascade endwall painted matte-black.

Figure 3.51: The band-pass filter attached to the Scheimpflug adaptor of camera 1.

Table 3.10: Estimated camera orientation parameters for COP PIV setup using the Pinhole camera calibration model.

Parameter	Camera 1	Camera 2
RMS of fit [pixel]		0.97
Focal length [mm]	203	181
Origin [pixel]		(1523.96, 1776.71)
Translation [mm]	(-59.43, -10.79, 644.11)	(-29.95, -18.17, 595.52)
Rotation [deg]	(-4.79, -44.15, -1.17)	(-3.54, 12.37, -0.59)
Scale factor [pixel/mm]		58.37

The large RMS fit error is due to the pinhole model not being able to consider the image distortions through the optical windows. The pinhole model parameters are used to solely provide the physical orientation of cameras, such as the camera angles and camera translations with respect to the measurement plane. The actual calibration parameters used for pixel to real world conversion are obtained by a 3rd order polynomial model and subsequent image self-calibrations. These parameters are reported later in the subsection 3.2.5.2.

3.2.5.2 Image calibration

Design of calibration plate

The image calibration is performed using the calibration target images recorded in prior to measurements. A single-level calibration target consisting of a regular dot pattern with 1 mm

Figure 3.52: Schematics of the laser and camera setup for COP configuration.

Figure 3.53: PIV setup for B2B Passage configuration.

Figure 3.54: Zoomed view of COP measurement location.

diameter circles and 2 mm space interval is used for the recording of calibration images. The target pattern is laser printed on a paper sheet, then it is attached to a 3D-printed base block that fits the cascade shape. The design of the calibration plate is illustrated in Fig. 3.55.

Figure 3.55: Design of calibration plate.

Calibration image acquisition

The calibration plate is placed in position and translated using a traverse system as illustrated in Fig. 3.56. The traverse system consists of four single-axis stages to realize multi-axis traverse capability. The calibration target plates are held via optical posts and post clamps which allows flexible tuning of the target position by sliding and rotating the post. The system is designed to support all calibration target plates. The following procedure is taken to record calibration images.

1. Place the calibration target in the correct position. (at the blade mid-span for B2B Upstream and B2B Passage, and at the cascade endwall $0.46x/Cax$ downstream from the blade TE.)
2. Close the test section except for pockets used for calibration plate insertion.
3. Set the camera in place.
4. Record calibration images.
5. For COP measurements, traverse the plane in plane-normal direction and repeat calibration image recording.

Figure 3.56: Calibration plate traversing system.

6. Remove the calibration target from the test section through the pocket.
7. Close the pockets used for the calibration plate insertion.
8. Start wind tunnel.

Fig. 3.58, 3.59, and 3.57 show the setups of the image calibration for the three PIV configurations. For B2B upstream and COP configuration, multiple calibration images at different normal-to-plane positions are acquired for stereoscopic reconstruction. The target plate is translated in the plane-normal direction, three or five equidistant positions spaced 0.5 or 1.0 mm apart, using one of the traverse stages of the system.

Processing of image calibration

The image calibration is performed using *Davis* PIV processing software. The 3rd-order polynomial function is selected for the fitting function in order to take into account arbitrary distortions caused by the optical windows. For stereoscopic PIV test cases (B2B upstream and COP), the self-calibration using particle images described by Wieneke [71] is applied after the standard stereoscopic calibration to minimize potential misalignment of the calibration plate and light sheet positions.

Table 3.11 lists the image calibration parameters obtained from the 3rd-order polynomial fitting on the calibration images for three PIV setups. The lower RMS of fit is found in the stereoscopic PIV setups (B2B upstream and COP) thanks to the self-calibration.

After image calibration in *Davis*, a conversion of the calibration target coordinate system to the measurement coordinate system is performed using *MATLAB*.

Figure 3.57: Camera calibration setup for B2B upstream configuration.

Figure 3.58: Camera calibration setup for B2B passage configuration.

Figure 3.59: Camera calibration setup for cascade outlet plane configuration.

Table 3.11: The image calibration parameter obtained with 3rd-order polynomial and image self-calibration.

PIV setup		Parameter	Camera 1	Camera 2
B2B upstream	with TG	RMS of fit [pixel]	< 0.00	< 0.00
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	43.95	
	w.o. TG	RMS of fit [pixel]	< 0.00	< 0.00
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	45.05	
B2B passage	with TG	RMS of fit [pixel]	1.26	0.78
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	44.25	48.02
	w.o. TG	RMS of fit [pixel]	0.95	0.43
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	48.24	47.61
COP	with TG	RMS of fit [pixel]	< 0.14	< 0.04
		Scale factor [pixel/mm]	58.30	

Fig. 3.60 shows the schematics of the B2B upstream coordinate system. The upright capital symbol indicates the measurement coordinate system whereas the italic symbol the image calibration system coordinate. The leading edge of the central blade is the origin of the measurement coordinate system O_{meas} . The origin of calibration coordinate system O_{calib} is aligned to O_{meas} in pitchwise direction while 1.00 mm offset is present in axial direction.

Figure 3.60: Calibration and measurement coordinate systems for B2B upstream configuration.

Fig. 3.61 illustrates the schematics of the B2B passage coordinate system. Similar to the case of B2B upstream, the leading edge of the central blade is the origin of the measurement coordinate system. The origin of the calibration coordinate system O_{calib} is the first dot downstream of the trailing edge of the central blade. The location of O_{calib} is aligned to the outlet blade metal angle $\beta_{metal, out}$ with 1.50 mm axial offset.

Figure 3.61: Calibration and measurement coordinate systems for B2B passage configuration.

Fig. 3.62 shows the schematics of the COP coordinate system. The origin of the local measurement coordinate system for COP (O_{p06}) is the intersection of the outlet metal angle

line and Plane 06 ($x/C_{ax} = 1.5$) located on the endwall ($z = 0$). However, the PIV plane is traversed 2 mm in the upwind axial direction to avoid the light reflection, thus the origin of calibration coordinate system O_{calib} is offset from both Plane 06 and the outlet metal angle line. The origin of the local coordinate system for PIV plane, $O_{P06, PIV}$, is therefore considered to be the intersection of the outlet metal angle line and the PIV plane ($1.46C_{ax}$).

Figure 3.62: Calibration and measurement coordinate systems for COP configuration.

Despite a careful positioning of the calibration plate, there is a possibility of a small misalignment which can affect the results. A correction of in-plane misalignment is applied to the coordinate system during a conversion of the calibration target coordinate system to the measurement coordinate system. Fig. 3.63 illustrates the correction procedure. The in-plane misalignment is due to translation and rotation. The first step is a realignment by translating the calibration plate so that the reference position such as the blade trailing edge or leading edge coincides with the designated point of the calibration plate. The second step corrects misalignment due to rotation, by matching the curvature of the blade and calibration plate.

Figure 3.63: Procedures for correction of calibration plate misalignment.

3.2.5.3 Seeding

Laskin-nozzle seeding generators *PIVpart14* and *PIVpart45* are used to produce DEHS droplets of approximately $1\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter. The particles are seeded downstream of the compressor stage of the wind tunnel as well as upstream of the diffuser (in the test section for aeronautical applications) as indicated in Fig. 3.64, ensuring enough distance (over 5 m) to achieve uniform seeding distribution at the test section. The air inlet of the seeding generator is fully opened to the atmosphere during the measurement. As the pressure inside the wind tunnel is reduced to around 10000 Pa during the test, the air is naturally aspirated into the seeding generator, producing the tracer particles.

Figure 3.64: Seeding setup for PIV in S-1/C.

3.2.5.4 Image recording

Table 3.12, 3.13, and 3.14 show image recording parameters for the upstream B2B, passage and downstream B2B, and COP PIV measurements. For every flow condition, 2000 images are recorded by repeating a recording of 500 pairs of images four times, in order to limit the variation of the flow condition with the seeding, as aforementioned in subsection 3.2.4. For the upstream B2B measurement at the design flow condition, four different separation times are tested in order to evaluate its impact on the mean and turbulence quantities. The results are addressed in subsection 4.2.1.4. The laser pulse intensity for the upstream B2B measurement is reduced due to the laser-induced damage threshold of the endoscope. For the COP measurement, the plane normal particle displacement is estimated to be about 10-15% of the light sheet thickness (1.5-2.0 mm), which complies with the quarter rule [72] (the plane normal displacement should be kept below 1/4 of the light sheet thickness). Note that the thickness of the light sheet should be maintained small enough to minimize the ambiguity in determining the location of the measured vectors in plane normal direction.

Table 3.12: Image recording parameter for the upstream B2B PIV measurements. f_{rec} : PIV recording frequency, N_{rec} : the number of pairs of images, I_0 : Laser pulse intensity, t_s : pulse separation time, X_d : estimated nominal particle displacement, F_s : Scaling factor.

$M_{out,is}$	$Re_{out,is}$	f_{rec}	N_{rec}	I_0	t_s	X_d	F_s
0.70	70k	15 Hz	2000	110 mJ	1.8 μ s	11.6 px/ t_s	0.02 mm/px
	120k						
0.90	70k				0.75 μ s	5.4 px/ t_s	
					1.50 μ s	10.9 px/ t_s	
					3.00 μ s	21.7 px/ t_s	
					7.50 μ s	50.7 px/ t_s	
	120k				1.50 μ s	10.9 px/ t_s	

Table 3.13: Image recording parameter for the passage and downstream B2B PIV measurements.

$M_{out,is}$	$Re_{out,is}$	f_{rec}	N_{rec}	I_0	t_s	X_d	F_s
0.70	70k	15 Hz	2000	200 mJ	1.5 μ s	16 px/ t_s	0.02 mm/px
	120k						
0.90	70k				1.15 μ s	17 px/ t_s	
	120k						
0.95	70k				18 px/ t_s		

Table 3.14: Image recording parameter for the COP PIV measurements.

$M_{out,is}$	$Re_{out,is}$	f_{rec}	N_{rec}	I_0	t_s	X_d	F_s
0.70	70k	15 Hz	2000	200 mJ	1.5 μ s	17 px/ t_s	0.02 mm/px
0.90					1.15 μ s	17 px/ t_s	
0.95					1.10 μ s	17 px/ t_s	

3.2.5.5 Image preprocessing

Before the vector field computation, image pre-processing is performed in order to minimize image background noise and strong reflections appearing on the surface hit by the laser sheet. For the B2B Upstream case, a dedicated parametric study is performed to evaluate the effect of image pre-processing on the results (see subsection 4.2.1.2). For the B2B Passage and COP cases, subtraction of the time-mean image and particle intensity normalization are applied. A case-dependent filter length varying between 11 and 51 images is used for the time-mean subtraction due to the image-to-image variation of the noise pattern.

3.2.5.6 Vector computation

The vector fields are computed using *Davis 11* multi-pass cross-correlation algorithm. For the B2B Upstream case, a dedicated parametric study is performed to evaluate the effect of vector computation setting on the results (see subsection 4.2.1.5). The nominal processing scheme for the B2B Upstream measurement is summarized in Table 3.15.

For B2B Passage and COP cases, the starting and final interrogation window size of 128×128 pixels and 32×32 pixels with 50% overlaps are chosen. This setting results in vector spatial resolutions of 0.35 mm for the B2B Passage measurement and 0.25 mm for the COP measurements. The nominal processing schemes for the B2B passage and COP measurements are summarized in Table 3.16 and 3.17.

A spatial median filter and allowable vector ranges based on the velocity magnitude, the flow direction, and the standard deviation are employed to evaluate the validity of the computed vector. Furthermore, the local uncertainty of particle displacement deduced from correlation statistics [73] is used to remove unreliable vectors. While it is mentioned that the correlation statistics-based uncertainty cannot detect the spurious vector, the excessive level of uncertainty is considered to be due to poor image quality thus resultant vectors are unreliable. The vectors that have the correlation-statistics-based uncertainty larger than 10% of the reference velocity speed (the isentropic outlet flow speed) have been discarded.

3.2.6 Numerical setup

3.2.6.1 CFD domain and mesh

2D steady RANS simulations conducted by Miglio [74] are used for comparison against the results of the B2B plane PIV measurements. The flow domain adopted for the numerical characterization is presented in Fig. 3.134. The inlet patch of CFD domain is located $0.75 C_{ax}$ upstream of the blade leading edge while the outlet patch is positioned $1.0 C_{ax}$ downstream of the blade trailing edge. The pitchwise domain size is set to equal to the cascade pitch.

A structured mesh adopting O4H topology is generated using *Cadence Autogrid5*. The first cell height at the wall is imposed to satisfy $y^+ < 1$ to resolve the viscous sub-layer. The total number of cells in the computational domain is about 100K.

3.2.6.2 Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions are set by imposing total pressure at the inlet, static pressure at the outlet, total temperature, inlet flow angle, and an inlet turbulence decay profile to match

Table 3.15: PIV processing setting for B2B Upstream configuration.

	Camera 1 and Camera 2
Image preprocessing	Time-mean image subtraction :Filter length = All images Spatial sliding average image subtraction :Filter length = 11 pixel
Vector computation	Stereo-PIV (2D3C) multi-pass cross-correlation Initial pass: 1 Initial IW: 128×128 px with 50% overlapping and square weighting Final pass: 3 Final IW: 64×64 px with 50% overlapping and round weighting Intermediate and final validation: Universal outlier detection : Remove if residual > 2.0 : Reinsert if residual < 3.0 : Filter region = 5×5 : Minimum number of vectors: 3 Stereo-PIV vector validation :Accepted stereo reconstruction error < 1.0 pixel Final vector field treatment : Remove groups with 5 vectors : Interpolation

Table 3.16: PIV processing setting for B2B passage configuration.

	Camera 1 and Camera 2
Image preprocessing	Temporal-mean image subtraction filter :Filter length = 21 - 51 images Spatial sliding average image subtraction filter :Filter length = 6 pixel
Vector computation	Planar sequential-PIV (side-by-side 2D2C) multi-pass cross-correlation Initial pass: 1 Initial IW: 128×128 px with 50% overlapping and square weighting Final pass: 3 Final IW: 32×32 px with 50% overlapping and square weighting Intermediate validation: $3 \times$ Median filter : Remove iteratively replace : Remove/replace if difference to average $> 2.0\sigma$: Reinsert if difference to average $< 3.0\sigma$ Final validation: $3 \times$ Median filter : Strongly remove iteratively replace : Remove/replace if difference to average 2.0σ : Reinsert if difference to average 3.0σ Final vector field treatment : Interpolation : Smoothing

Table 3.17: PIV processing setting for COP configuration.

	Camera 1 and Camera 2
Image preprocessing	Temporal-mean image subtraction filter :Filter length = 11 images Spatial sliding average image subtraction filter :Filter length = 12 pixel Min/Max intensity normalization filter :Filter length = 50 pixel
Vector computation	Stereo-PIV (2D3C) multi-pass cross-correlation Initial pass: 1 Initial IW: 128×128 px with 50% overlapping and square weighting Final pass: 3 Final IW: 32×32 px with 50% overlapping and round weighting Intermediate and final validation: $3 \times$ Median filter : Strongly remove iteratively replace : Remove/replace if difference to average $> 2.0\sigma$: Reinsert if difference to average $< 3.0\sigma$: Filter region = 5×5 : Minimum number of vectors: 3 Stereo-PIV vector validation :Accepted stereo reconstruction error < 5.0 pixel Final vector field treatment : Remove groups with 5 vectors : Interpolation

Figure 3.65: CFD domain for S-1/C test case.

the experimental conditions in terms of Mach and Reynolds number, turbulence intensity, and length scale. *Non-matching periodic boundary* conditions are set at the pitchwise boundaries. The spanwise boundaries are treated with mirror surfaces.

3.2.6.3 Numerical model

Steady-state RANS computations are performed using *Cadence FINE/Turbo 16.2* solver. The perfect gas hypothesis is used for the working fluid. The viscosity is calculated using *Sutherland's law*. The $k - \omega SST$ turbulence model coupled with the $\gamma - Re_{\theta t}$ transition model is adopted for turbulence closure. Viscous flux terms were discretized by means of central-difference schemes. A bounded second-order accurate *Roe* upwind spatial discretization scheme has been adopted for convective fluxes. A second-order symmetric total variation diminishing (STVD) scheme with a Min Mod limiter is used to get second-order accuracy.

3.3 Rotating annular cascade tests in a short-duration high-speed test rig (CT-3)

This section is dedicated to the PIV test case conducted in the CT-3 high-speed rotating annular cascade test rig. The test article is the NEXT high-pressure turbine (HPT) stage [75, 76]. The section introduces the research background, literature review, objectives, and experimental setup. The results of the test case are provided in subsection 4.3.

3.3.1 Background and literature review

Modern axial turbine stages for aircraft engines and power generations can achieve isentropic efficiencies in the range of 80% to 90% or even higher in some cases [77]. Further advancement of the turbine performance requires a better understanding and control of complex fluid phenomena such as wake mixing, endwall flows, tip leakage flows, unsteady vane-rotor and shock wave-boundary layer interactions, and blade cooling flows. CFD is a cost-efficient approach to predict the behavior of fluid, but in the case of turbomachinery flows with complex geometry, the prediction accuracy still needs improvement to be used with confidence.

At low technology readiness levels (TRLs), experimental investigations of turbine flows are commonly conducted using linear cascade rigs as aforementioned 3.2.1. While measurements in linear cascades can provide detailed flow information thanks to a relatively easily accessible measurement section, some key flow phenomena of turbomachinery such as the effect of annular flow path and unsteady vane-rotor interactions can not be addressed. As TRLs advance, there is a growing need for testing in annular cascade rigs that can replicate full three-dimensional turbine flows similar to those found in actual engines. Acquiring realistic aerothermal flow field data is essential for ensuring the component system design and validating CFD simulations.

3.3.1.1 Experimental investigation of annular turbine stage

Turbine test facilities are broadly classified into two types based on their operation schemes, i.e. continuously running and transient facilities. Typical continuously running annular turbine test rigs include the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) [78], ONERA [79], the Purdue University [80], the Technical University of Darmstadt (TU Darmstadt) [81, 82], and the University of Bath [83] for low-speed (relative outlet Mach number $M_{\text{out, rel}} \leq 0.6$) testing, and at DLR [84], GE [85], ITP [86], the University of Notre-Dame [87], the Graz University of Technology (TU Graz) [88], JAXA [89] for high-speed ($M_{\text{out, rel}} > 0.6$) testing.

Transient facilities for turbine stage testing include the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) [90], the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) [91], the Ohio State University (OST) [92], the Oxford University [93], and the Purdue University [94]. At the VKI, a large-scale high-speed transient turbine test rig, named CT-3, was built in the late 80s in order to reproduce the actual three-dimensional flow in turbine passages [95]. Fig. 3.66 [89] summarises the operating point of the typical annular turbine test rigs.

While continuously running test rigs are capable of adjusting their flow conditions for aerodynamic performance much more accurately than transient test rigs, the operating cost can be significantly higher. An alternative solution that requires less operating power con-

Figure 3.66: Similarity parameters of typical turbine testing facilities. Left: Operating condition in terms of Mach number and Reynolds number at vane exit. Right: Secondary air stream parameter in terms of mass flow ratio and density ratio [89].

sumption is testing in transient rigs. The transient operation is also favorable to the assessment of turbine heat transfer as the gas-to-wall temperature ratio can be matched to the one of real aircraft engines. In general, matching of correct gas-to-wall temperature is not achieved in continuous rigs due to the heating of the cascade during the long-lasting testing time.

The drawback of transient rigs is obviously the limited testing time, which necessitates special attention to instrumentation and data processing. Physical probes are widely used to generate experimental databases [76], but their instantaneous measurements are spatially sparse therefore a typical experimental campaign requires a number of repetitive tests. Furthermore, the finite geometry of probes can cause intrusive effects as reported by Boerner et al. [52] and Torre et al. [49].

Under such circumstances, the use of PIV is an attractive approach. The instantaneous and spatial velocity field acquired by PIV provides contexts of complex three-dimensional flow structures. The simultaneous multi-point data sampling allows covering a large testing matrix with fewer tests, ultimately resulting in a reduction of testing cost. The lack of physical probes within the studied flow guarantees that there are no obstructions to the flow. Moreover, the flow field in the area where an insertion of a physical probe is prohibited, such as the vicinity of the rotating blades, can be measured thanks to the contactless approach.

On the other hand, the high level of complexity in the geometries of annular cascade rigs raises various challenges for PIV implementation. For planar PIV, an ideal orientation of the optical system is to maintain the light sheet perpendicular to the optical axis of a camera [96], and thus a conventional measurement setup requires two optical accesses (one for a camera view and one for a laser sheet insertion), unless stereoscopic or tomographic system with highly skewed view angles is used [97]. This requirement is difficult to satisfy in the packed hardware geometries of annular cascade rigs. The images are likely to suffer from extreme light reflection issues as the intense laser sheet impacts the metallic surfaces of test sections. If the facility is capable of testing rotating stages, the synchronization between the rotor phase and image acquisition must be guaranteed to perform phase-resolved analysis. Furthermore, the large velocity gradients that characterize high-speed turbine flows require carefully designed seeding methods and the use of adapted processing algorithms.

Despite having numerous difficulties, several authors have reported successful implementations of PIV in both static and rotating annular cascades. Hereafter a review of some remarkable works is introduced to identify the state-of-the-art studies.

PIV in low-speed annular cascades

Gallier et al.(2004) [80] visualized the interaction between rim seal egress flow and main flow including the effects of vane-rotor interaction by means of PIV installation in the Purdue Low-speed Research Turbine at the Purdue University as shown in Fig. 3.67.

Figure 3.67: Purdue 2-stage research turbine [80].

The ambient air was drawn into the two-stage axial-flow turbine by a centrifugal blower downstream of the test section powered by a 100 hp (75 kW) electric motor. Rotational speed was held at 2500 rpm, resulting in a mean inlet velocity to the turbine stages of 28.7 m/s. Fig. 3.68-left illustrates the turbine test section. Dimensionless seal flow rate (or seal flow Reynolds number) defined as $C_w = \dot{\omega} / \mu r_0$ (the actual mass flow scaled with the fluid viscosity and outer radius of the seal) was set at 1.2×10^4 for high flow rate and 4.6×10^3 for low flow rate. The PIV acquisition frequency was 15 Hz and pulse separation time was set to $1 \mu\text{s}$. In order to illuminate measurement area, 1 mm thickness meridional plane laser sheet was introduced through the bellmouth inlet section. A single vane was removed to avoid blockage of laser light sheet insertion. As these experiments aimed at illustrating the flow physics associated with a wake crossing the rim seal rather than any specific performance evaluation, this compromise was considered accepted. The PIV measurement took place at four different circumferential positions with respect to the vane trailing edge as shown in Fig 3.68-middle. The PIV images were captured by a camera with an oblique angle through a window located over the first rotor row. An astigmatic corrective lens was employed in order to compensate the image distortion and aberration due to the imaging angle. A *Rosco 1600 Fog Machine* was used to generate the tracer particles, which are mono-disperse particles made of glycol-based mixture. The seeding particles were introduced upstream of the bellmouth inlet and were also dispersed into the ambient air. Mixing between the main flow and rim seal purge flow was sufficient to provide an adequate seed density, therefore a direct seeding in the purge gas was not necessary. The ROI size was $21.3 \times 21.5 \text{ mm}^2$ with interrogation area of $0.676 \times 0.676 \text{ mm}^2$.

The instantaneous flow field was captured at 10 rotor positions as shown in Fig. 3.68-right. A phase-locked ensemble average was made of a minimum of 100 instantaneous samples for

Figure 3.68: Left: Turbine test section diagram. Middle: Location of vane relative measurement planes and mean wake convection path. right: Rotor relative measurement planes [80].

each rotor position. The accuracy of the rotor position was quantified as better than ± 0.25 ms (± 0.00375 degrees) for a maximum speed variation of ± 15 rpm. Fig. 3.69 shows the example of PIV results. The characteristics of purge flow and its interaction with the main flow, vane wake, and rotor potential effect were investigated in detail along with the purge flow rate.

Figure 3.69: Interstage vorticity field and streamlines with a seal flow for different vane-rotor clocking angles. [80].

Porreca et al.(2006) [98] and Yun et al.(2006) [99] carried out stereoscopic PIV and Fast Response Aerodynamic Probe (FRAP) measurements in two-stage shrouded axial turbine to investigate the interaction between main and tip leakage flow of a partially shrouded turbine. The experiments were performed on the continuously running research turbine facility (LISA) at ETH Zurich as shown in Fig. 3.70 (A). The two partially shrouded rotors (Fig. 3.70 (B)) were decoupled mechanically by a twin-spool shaft design. The rotor rotational speed was 2625 rpm. The absolute Mach number at the stator exit and rotor exit were 0.35 and 0.1 respectively. Reynolds number based on the rotor was 2×10^5 . Two optical windows

made of acrylic PMMA installed in the test facility were used for image capturing as shown in Fig. 3.70-(C) and Fig. 3.71.

Figure 3.70: (A) The research turbine “LISA” at the Turbomachinery Laboratory of ETH. (B) Schematic of the partially shrouded turbine blades. (C) Optical windows and probe holes in the test turbine. [78, 98]

Figure 3.71: Left: Measurement regions: PIV, FRAP and 5HP planes. Right: Stereoscopic camera configuration in the test turbine [98].

The inner surface of the windows was designed so as it reproduce the exact curvature of the casing inner wall. DEHS particles generated by a Laskin nozzle were seeded in the entire air mass flow. It was reported that deposits of seeding material on the windows were not significant during the operation. The nominal particle diameter was around $1 \mu\text{m}$ which was considered acceptable for a frequency response up to 10 kHz. The PIV data acquisition frequency was 15 Hz. The laser beam was delivered to the test section by an articulated mirror arm and a laser endoscope of 8 mm outer diameter from *ILA Intelligent Laser Applications*. The cameras and the laser endoscope were mounted on a common traversing system that controlled the radial positions of the measurement planes. One camera faced normal to the laser sheet while the other was tilted by different angles (22° , 25° , 30°). In the inter-stage area (Between the first rotor and the stator downstream), the region of the window with an abrupt change of curvature caused a severe optical distortion. In the inter-stage region, PIV measurements were taken in 15 blade-to-blade planes from 66 to 97 percent span. One blade passing period was divided into 20 time steps, and between 60 and 100 digital image pairs

for each were recorded. Downstream of the second rotor, PIV measurements were performed on three planes inside the shroud cavity and 17 blade-to-blade planes (from 60 to 96 percent span). One blade passing period was divided into 10 timesteps, and 100 image pairs were recorded on each plane at each time step. The separation time was set to between 2 and 4 μs depending on the average flow velocity. The paper described the method and result of stereoscopic PIV uncertainty calculation. Velocity fields measured by PIV at different span locations for the interstage region are shown in Fig. 3.72. The results of the velocity field from PIV and FRAP at the turbine exit region is presented in Fig. 3.73-left. The secondary flow structures in the interstage region were visualized by reconstructing the axial plane velocity fields from multiple blade-to-blade PIV measurements (Fig. 3.73-right). The flow kinematics and loss generation mechanism have been verified from these measurement results.

Figure 3.72: PIV measured absolute yaw angle at different span location. Vectors show the in-plane velocity component – Interstage region [98].

Figure 3.73: Left: Absolute tangential velocity measured by (a) PIV and (b) FRAP at turbine exit region. Right: PIV measured absolute yaw angle at axial plane of interstage region. Vectors show the in-plane velocity component. [98]

Kegalj et al. (2009) [100] performed endoscopic PIV measurements in an open-loop, continuously running 1.5-stage axial low-pressure turbine rig at the Technical University of Darmstadt. The aim of this study was a feasibility investigation of PIV measurements using a camera borescope and a laser endoscope in a rotating annular turbine test rig. Fig. 3.74 illustrates the overview of the test facility.

Figure 3.74: Sections of the test facility. (a) Test facility, (b) measurement area [100].

Two PIV configurations, circumferential (pitch-axial) plane configuration designated as setup C and radial (span-axial) plane configuration designated as setup R were investigated as shown in Fig. 3.75. The region of interest was the inter-blade area between the rotor and the second stator. The rotational speed was set to 712 rpm. The casing in the test section was designed to be rotatable in order to enable a traverse of probes independently from the blading, and this feature resulted in the complexity of the casing geometry and made it impossible to install an optical window in it. PIV data acquisition frequency was 15 Hz. For each phase averaged vector field, one rotor passage was divided into 20 time steps. 125 data had been recorded and processed for each position. The calibration was performed using a dot pattern attached to an acrylic plate and positioned with a magnetic holder or measurement position-specific mounts. Laser endoscopes with 90-degree looking angle and straight looking angle were used for radial and circumferential plane PIV planes, respectively. The camera borescopes having a straight looking angle and 90-degree looking angle were used for radial and circumferential plane PIV measurements, respectively. The borescopes were attached to a macro lens. The diameter of both endoscopes and borescopes was 8 mm. DEHS droplets created by a Laskin-type seeding generator were injected into the settling chamber upstream of the flow. For the circumferential PIV, the distance from the light sheet to the borescope was set to 45 mm and DEHS droplets of 1 μm diameter were used for seeding. For radial PIV measurement, the distance between the laser sheet and borescope was set to 100 mm and seeding droplets with a diameter ranging 2-3 μm were used to compensate for the larger working distance. Valuable flow fields could be measured only from 10mm away with respect to the wall due to light reflection on the wall despite the black coating. A simplified numerical study estimated that the flow disturbance effect due to borescopes or endoscopes is below 1.5% in a freestream with 22 m/s flow speed.

PIV results were compared with 5HP for time-averaged results (Fig. 3.76 and 3.77) and

Figure 3.75: CAD model of Setup C and Setup R [100].

with Hot Wire Anemometry (HWA) for phase-lock averaged results. The authors concluded that the use of an endoscope enables one to obtain a planar view from several directions in complex design facilities such as turbine test rigs. While a particular challenge was found in radial plane PIV which did not provide very precise results due to the strong out-of-plane velocity component, it is still useful for special applications such as the investigation of rim seal leakage flows. The drawback of endoscopic PIV is the low light sensitivity that deteriorates the quality of captured particle images. Reducing the distance from the borescope to the light sheet can improve the resolution and quality of the results, however, a stronger flow disturbance has to be taken into account.

Figure 3.76: Comparison of time-averaged velocity field downstream of the rotor: Setup C vs. 5HP [100].

Zhang et al.(2019) [101] employed PIV to investigate the flow field in a turbine interstage with the consideration of the influence of rotor blade and purge flow. A continuously operating low-speed turbine facility of the Beihang University (Fig. 3.78) with a maximum rotating speed of 1250 rpm was used for the investigation. At Reynolds number of rotor of 2.1×10^5 , two different purge flow cases (zero purge flow and 9.4% of main annulus flow

Figure 3.77: Comparison of time-averaged velocity field downstream of the rotor: Setup R vs. 5HP [100].

rate) were conducted. The PIV measurement was performed on meridional planes located above the rim seal gap at seven different circumferential positions with a data acquisition rate of 15 Hz as shown in Fig. 3.79.

Figure 3.78: Schematics of the experimental system at the Beihang University [101].

DEHS droplets of approximately $1 \mu\text{m}$ diameter were produced by a Laskin nozzle particle generator. A uniform seeding was achieved by the use of a net-type particle spreading device located upstream of the turbine inlet. The feature of this test facility is that the turbine casing in the test section was made of transparent material, which provides a large optical window at a flexible angle. Each measurement plane covers from IGV outlet to the rotor inlet in the axial direction and the full span height of the main annulus. Five trigger positions were defined to capture the phase-locked flow field. Each phase-locked time-averaged velocity vector field was calculated from 1000 instantaneous PIV frames. The velocity fields at different measurement planes were combined together to provide a quasi-three-dimensional perspective of flow structures as shown in Fig. 3.80, providing detailed axial and radial flow structures at different circumferential position and their deviations associated with purge flow. The POD method was employed to extract the principal coherent structure from the composed quantities affected by the secondary flow, purge flow, and rotor blade potential field.

Figure 3.79: (a) Layout of the measurement and (b) measurement planes (MPs) and positions. [101].

Figure 3.80: Time-averaged flow structure of the interstage flow without purge. (a) Axial velocity contours. (b) Radial velocity contours.

Figueiredo et al. [83, 102, 103] implemented volumetric velocimetry in a continuously running single-stage low-speed turbine rig named Large Annulus Rig (LAR) at the University of Bath (Fig. 3.81). The three-dimensional measurement was conducted aiming at extending the understanding of the complex interaction between the mainstream and rim seal egress flow with the presence of endwall contouring. A design tool of laser endoscopes for volumetric illumination was presented in [103]. The designed laser endoscope was implemented within a windowed vane to ensure there was no flow disturbance. The overview of the measurement setup is shown in Fig. 3.82.

Figure 3.81: Section view of the Large Annulus Rig (LAR) at the University of Bath [83].

Figure 3.82: Volumetric velocimetry setup in the LAR [103].

The *TSI-V3V* volumetric velocimetry camera system was used for the imaging. The optical access for camera view was realized by a sapphire window mounted on the rotor casing. The inner surface of the window was machined to match the curvature of the shroud and the outer surface was made flat. The in-situ camera calibration was carried out by opening the test rig and mounting the calibration plate behind the window. The volumetric reconstruction was realized by taking multiple images of the calibration plate traversed in the plane-normal direction. DEHS droplets sizing between 0.5 to $1.0 \mu\text{m}$ were produced by two *TSI 9307-6* droplet generators. One of the droplet generators seeded the main flow via nine seeding points located in the inlet section casing of the facility and the other seeded the purge flow. The particle image was captured for a single clock angle. Due to the large size of the full volume of interest, the volumetric illumination was split into multiples while maintaining the same clock angle. Fig. 3.84 presents a measurement result for two flow conditions with and without purge flow (two non-dimensional sealing flow parameter ϕ_0) showing that the presence of purge flow contributes to the strengthening of the pressure side horseshoe vortex.

Figure 3.83: Simulated illumination pattern within the test section of LAR using volumetric light endoscope [103].

Figure 3.84: Dimensionless circulation γ_2 measured by the volumetric velocimetry [103].

Ade et al.(2023) [104] employed stereoscopic PIV in a 1.5-stage low-speed turbine test rig (LSTG) at the Technical University of Darmstadt (Fig. 3.85). The main purpose of the research was to understand the interaction of tip leakage flow with the main annulus flow for a newly designed notch tip in comparison to a common cavity squealer tip.

Figure 3.85: (Left) Overview and (Right) sectional view of the Large Scale Turbine Rig (LSTR) at the TU-Darmstadt [82].

The test article consists of a shroud-less HPT stage sandwiched between upstream and downstream nozzle guide vanes. The rotational speed was set to 1300 rpm and the outlet Mach number of the first NGV was 0.25. The PIV measurement was performed on the meridional plane in the blade tip region as shown in Fig. 3.86, covering the relative axial chord lengths from 0.3 to 1.2 and the relative channel heights from 0.7 to 1.0.

Figure 3.86: Experimental setup in LSTR [104].

The image acquisition was triggered based on the signal of the rotor shaft, realizing recordings at multiple rotor pitches ranging from -0.2 to 1.2. An optical window was mounted on the rotor casing from which the laser sheet was inserted radially to illuminate the measurement plane. For the light source, a Nd:YAG laser *NANO-L-200-15 PIV* was employed. Two CCD cameras (*ImagerPro X2M*) were placed with circumferential offsets and tilt angles for

stereoscopic view. The stereo-calibration was performed from the images of a single plane calibration target translated through the light sheet with several intermediate steps. DEHS droplets produced by *PIVpart40* aerosol generator were locally seeded in the investigated flow. The velocity field in the rotor relative frame of reference was obtained by phase-averaging 500 image pairs for each rotor pitch. Fig. 3.87 presents the measured velocity fields within the rotor passage at different axial locations. The stereoscopic PIV successfully captured the blade tip flow features, revealing that the notch tip features a tip leakage flow system with smaller-sized vortices compared to the cavity squealer tip.

Figure 3.87: Measured axial velocity component and projected relative velocity vectors, projected onto the circumferential cross section, within the blade tip flow field for different rotor pitch positions along the blade tip [104].

PIV in high-speed static annular cascade

There is scarce literature presenting PIV measurements for high-speed testing (vane exit Mach > 0.6) of annular cascade components. First, transonic test cases with stationary annular cascades are introduced.

Bryanston-Cross et al. [105] demonstrated the application of PIV measurement to the short-duration isentropic light piston cascade (ILPC) at the Royal Aerospace Establishment (RAE). Fig. 3.88 shows the schematics of the test rig. The facility operates transonic flow with a run time of around 1.0 second.

The PIV setup is illustrated in Fig. 3.89-left. The vanes at the location of PIV measurement were manufactured with a transparent material (PERSPEX) in order to allow light sheet access as shown in Fig. 3.89-right. The inlet freestream turbulence level was around 6% as measured with hot-wire anemometer. In advance to run the test facility, the pump tube was filled with seeding particles using a commercial seeding generator. 500 nm diameter styrene seeding particles were used as tracer particles. The laser beam was guided through a hollow 8 mm turbulence bar positioned 4.5 axial chord upstream of the blade row. The camera

Figure 3.88: The Isentropic Light Piston Cascade (ILPC) at the RAE [105].

Figure 3.89: (Left) Sketch of the PIV optical light sheet system. (Right) The PERSPEX nozzle guide vanes [105].

viewing window was made from two joined sections of PERSPEX and it carried both the radius of the annular cascade and an amount of cascade passage contouring. The separation time between two laser pulses was set to 0.5 and 1.0 μs to resolve high and low-speed flow respectively.

The velocity vector plots of PIV results were compared with predictions from fully three-dimensional viscous flow CFD as shown in Fig. 3.90. The study demonstrated that PIV is applicable to high-speed short-duration turbine test rigs and capable of producing instantaneous pictures of a large area of the flow.

Figure 3.90: The vector plot within the near the vane trailing edge from (left) PIV measurement (right) CFD.

Inman et al. [106] used 2D2C PIV to measure velocity fields in a central region of a vane passage of an annular cascade, conducted at the PETAL facility at Purdue University as shown in Fig. 3.91. Two flow conditions in which the Reynolds number was varied while the vane outlet Mach number was maintained to 0.73 were simulated by changing the total inlet temperature. The test facility is in transient operation, but the actual testing time was not stated by the authors.

Figure 3.91: (Left) Petal facility schematic. (Right) Flow path inside the test section and location of the test article [106].

Fig. 3.92 illustrates the PIV setup within the test section. The laser sheet was inserted by an in-house laser delivery probe and the images were captured through a circular optical

window mounted on the cascade casing. A semi-global seeding covering around 25% of the annular cascade was realized by injecting particles in several ports in the upstream part of the settling chamber. The pulse separation time was set to $3 \mu\text{s}$ targeting the average particle displacement of around 7 pixels. The imaging system was composed of a Photoron FASTCAM camera and a burst-mode Nd:YAG laser acquired double frame particle images at 10 kHz. A relatively good agreement was found in the comparison between PIV and RANS model prediction in terms of the velocity magnitude and flow angle as shown in Fig. 3.93.

Figure 3.92: Sketch of the method used to deliver the laser sheet into the annular cascade targeting a field of view located at midspan in the passage. The location of the probe avoided perturbations to the flow at the measurement location. [106].

Figure 3.93: Comparison of (left) time-averaged velocity contour with streamlines and (right) time-averaged flow angle contour between experimental measurements and CFD model predictions [106].

PIV in high-speed rotating annular cascade rigs

PIV measurements conducted in transonic rotating turbine or compressor rigs have been reported as follows.

Bryanston et al. [107] performed PIV measurement on a transonic short-duration (0.3 sec test time) rotating turbine facility at MIT (Fig. 3.94).

Figure 3.94: The MIT transient transonic blow-down turbine rig [107].

They made a helpful review of PIV installation in a high-speed rotating turbine rig and proved that PIV can be a practical and effective technique for this type of facility. The styrene particles were seeded in the supply tank prior to it reaching the final pressure. A *TSI 9306 model* six-jet atomizer was used as a seeding generator and it was assumed that it produced $5 \mu\text{m}$ water droplets containing a single styrene particle each and water evaporated before the running test facility. However, the formation of big ice flakes was found around the styrene particles due to the temperature drop as a result of rapid transonic expansion. To prevent this issue, the supply tank was heated up to 50°C before the test. Two laser endoscopes were installed into the upstream and downstream of the test facility respectively to provide uniform illumination over the inter-blade area as shown in Fig. 3.95. The optical window was made of polished glass and its inner surface profile matched the radius of the annulus. The external surface had an optimized curvature in order to minimize the optical distortion. One cassette of nozzle guide vane was replaced with transparent PERSPEX to supply unobstructed laser sheet path. The separation time between two pulses was set to $0.6 \mu\text{s}$ and the double-frame image acquisition frequency is 15Hz which results in 4 successive image pairs at each blow-down test (300 ms).

The Velocity field in the rotating frame of reference was calculated by subtracting the blade tangential velocity at the mean radius of the light sheet calculated based on the frequency of the rotation from the original velocity field obtained from PIV. Fig. 3.96 presents the (left) instantaneous and (right) quasi steady-state velocity fields in the rotor blade passage. Time-averaged, quasi steady-state solution of the flow in the complete rotor passage

was generated by superimposing a set of six images.

Figure 3.95: (Left) PIV setup for the measurements. (Right) The optical access to the rotor-stator arrangement and the position of the light probes [107].

Figure 3.96: (Left) Instantaneous flow field in the rotor passage - rotor relative velocity vectors. (Right) Steady state velocity map of the instantaneous flow field in the rotor passage [107].

Lang et al. [108] implemented stereoscopic PIV into continuously operating transonic single stage axial turbine test facility at the Graz University of Technology (Fig. 3.97). The aim of this study was to capture predominant in-plane flow as well as secondary flows and vortex shedding those have relatively low velocity but strong three-dimensional features. The rotating speed of the turbine disk was 9621 rpm and isentropic outlet Mach number was 1.23.

A plano-concave quartz glass (HERASIL) window with anti-reflection coating was installed on the cascade casing for camera view as shown in Fig. 3.98. Two cameras were mounted on the test rig with a vibration-insulated basement. One camera was placed in front of the window with its optical axis perpendicular to the laser sheet, and the other was tilted about 27 degrees towards the circumferential direction. The laser sheet probe attached to the end of the articulated arm introduced a tangential plane laser sheet in the region between the stator and rotor at a height of 37.5 mm from the hub. PIV data acquisition frequency was 15 Hz and pulse separation time was set to 0.7 μ s. One TTL pulse per rotation was used to define the rotor-stator position. The various rotor-stator clocking positions were specified by a certain trigger delay.

About 80 recordings for four rotor-stator positions were stored for the phase-lock-average. DEHS oil particles of nominal diameter 0.7 μ m were supplied by a PALLAS-AGF 5D particle generator. Particles were seeded locally through seeding pipes installed upstream of the test

Figure 3.97: The transonic test turbine facility of TU Graz [88].

Figure 3.98: (Left) Installation of cameras and light-sheet probe for PIV recording. (Right) Arrangement of the two cameras (A and B) in front of the turbine window section and areas imaged by the two cameras [108].

section. The inner diameter of the seeding pipe was 7 mm and equipped with seven rows of drilling holes (diameter 1.8 mm). The pipe end was bent perpendicular to the insertion axis so that the particles were injected parallel to the light sheet. Due to the existence of blades, image calibration was not performed in the test section. Instead, a separate calibration setup outside the turbine rig was used. It consisted of the window glass, calibration targets with support mount, the platform with the cameras and the laser sheet probe. The stator hub was painted black in order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. The example of the outcome from this study is presented in Fig. 3.99. This study revealed the influence of the rotor-stator clocking position on the wakes, shock waves, and interactions of these two. Also, the link of the vortex shedding phase and rotor position was found and the consistency with CFD simulation results was confirmed.

Figure 3.99: In-plane velocity components for four stator-rotor positions. The plane is in a midsection at 65% of channel height [108].

Göttlich et al. [109] performed succeeding stereoscopic 2D3C measurement in the same facility at the Graz University of Technology. The investigation region was the intermediate space between the stator and rotor and the downstream of the rotor. In order to minimize light reflections, the endwall, and both the vanes and blades were covered with high-temperature matt black paint. The same tracer particle as the previous test case [108] was used and its response at transonic flow was estimated such that the smearing effect is 0.5 mm in the region of trailing edge shocks. A reference signal provided by the monitoring system of blade position (uncertainty: blade pitch/300) was used to trigger data sampling. The design of optical access was similar to the one used by Lang et al. [108]. According to the laser model, the acquisition frequency was less than 50Hz. Pulse separation time was 1 μ s for the intermediate passage and 1.5 μ s for the downstream of the rotor. Two circumferential PIV planes placed near the midspan were recorded for the intermediate and rotor downstream region as shown in Fig. 3.100.

These measurement planes were set by rotating the stator and/or adjusting a trigger delay

Figure 3.100: Left: Meridional flow path and measurement planes. Right: PIV measurement locations. [109]

in the acquisition software of the PIV system, while the positions of the cameras and the light sheet optics were fixed in the facility frame. For each measurement plane, sets of 180 PIV recordings at 6 different stator-rotor positions were recorded and used to obtain an averaged vector field. The pressure waves from the rotor blade propagating upstream and hitting the stator vane were observed. Fig. 3.101 visualizes the vortices shedding from the stator vanes and rotor blades obtained by the phase-lock-average processing. The modulation of shed vortices during its travel was confirmed by both the PIV measurement result and RANS simulation.

Figure 3.101: Time-resolved stereoscopic PIV results showing vorticity distributions at midspan for different rotor-phase [109].

3.3.1.2 Objectives

Table 3.18 shows the summary of precedent PIV measurements performed in annular cascade test rigs. In the literature survey, disclosure of PIV measurements in high-speed and short-duration rotating facilities could only be found in [107] to the best of the author's knowledge. The use of photographic films for recording in [107] limited the number of images acquired during the short testing time, resulting in the computation of a quasi-steady state flow field from six pairs of images. In past decades a remarkable development of digital image recording and laser systems made high-speed PIV become popular. An experimental study of modern PIV system in short-duration test facilities will reveal the great potential of its technique and lead development of an efficient whole-field measurement method for turbomachinery flows.

This study therefore focuses on the implementation of PIV into a high-speed short-duration rotating turbine rig (CT-3) of von Karman Institute. The optical measurements are performed on a single-stage high-pressure turbine (HPT) with a purged stator-rotor hub cavity. The following subsections introduce specific designs, operation procedures, and data processing methods for PIV measurements tailored for short-duration testing of fully-featured high-speed turbines. The quality of the measured velocity fields is demonstrated through back-to-back comparison with predictions from steady-state Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) calculations of the experimental turbine case together with fast response four-hole probe (4HP) measurement results reported in [76].

3.3.2 Test rig

3.3.2.1 Rotating high-speed short-duration test rig: CT-3

The rotational annular cascade test rig, CT-3, is a short-duration blow-down type annular turbine test rig that offers an economical approach to study the aero-thermal operation of turbomachinery by reproducing temperature ratio, Reynolds and Mach numbers of the actual engine conditions. The principle of this test rig is the isentropic compression tube [95, 110]. The overview of the test rig is shown in Fig. 3.102.

An upstream cylindrical reservoir (compression tube) has 1.6 m diameter and is 8 m long, containing a free light piston. A fast-opening shutter valve separates the compression tube and the downstream until the start of blow-down tests. The downstream of the shutter valve is followed by a radial diffuser discharging the compressed air into an annular settling chamber of 500 mm inner diameter and 900 mm outer diameter. The settling chamber dumps the oscillations caused by the movement of the piston. The test section is designed to install up to 1.5 turbine stages with a maximum diameter of about 800 mm. During the present work, one full turbine stage is installed. The mass flow through the test section is regulated and stabilized by a choking condition at the sonic throat located downstream of the stage. The exiting gas is then charged into a 35 m³ dump tank which is vacuumed before the blow-down test to adjust the Reynolds number independently from the pressure ratio through the turbine. Some other geometrical details are reported in Fig. 3.103.

Table 3.18: Precedent PIV measurements in annular turbine cascade test rigs.

Facility type	Lab	Rotor speed	Testing time	$Re_{out}/10^6$	$M_{out,vane}$	Type of PIV	ROI	Rec. freq	Nb. rec.	Seeding
Short-duration fixed cascade	RAE [105]		1.0 s	3.0	0.93	2D2C	B2B Vane psg.	NA	200 - 500	Styrene particles 0.5 nm
	Purdue U [106]		NA	22 - 30/C	0.73	2D2C	B2B Vane psg.	10 kHz	101	NA
Short-duration high-speed rotating cascade	MIT [107]	6000 - 7800 RPM	0.3 s	2.7	0.9 - 1.3	2D2C	Rotor psg.	15 Hz	6	Styrene particles 0.4 μm
	VKI (Current study)	5800 RPM	0.25 s	0.28	0.78 (Rotor rel.)	2D2C	B2B Rotor outlet	1 kHz	250 - 500	DEHS droplets 1 μm
Continuous high-speed rotating cascade	TU Graz [108]	9621 RPM		NA	1.23	2D2C	B2B Vane-rotor psg.	15 Hz (Phase-locked)	80	DEHS droplets 0.7 μm
	[109]	10600 RPM		2.6 (Vane exit) 1.7 (Rotor exit)	0.46 (Rotor)	2D3C	B2B Vane-rotor psg. Rotor outlet	50 Hz	180	DEHS droplets 0.7 μm
Continuous low-speed rotating cascade	Purdue U [80]	2500 RPM	Continuous	NA	~0.1 (Turbine inlet)	2D2C	Meridional plane Vane-rotor psg. Near rim seal gap	15 Hz (Phase-locked)	100	Glycol-based fog size: NA
	ETH [98]	2625 RPM		0.2	0.35 (Vane) 0.1 (Rotor)	2D3C	B2B Vane-rotor psg. Rotor outlet Near blade tip	15 Hz (Phase-locked)	100	DEHS droplets 1 μm
Continuous low-speed rotating cascade	TU Darmstadt [100]	712 RPM		NA	NA	2D2C	B2B/Axial plane Rotor-vane psg.	15 Hz (Phase-locked)	125	DEHS droplets 1 μm
	[104]	1300 RPM		0.25	0.53	2D3C	Meridional plane Rotor psg.	15 Hz (Phase-locked)	500	DEHS droplets 1 μm
Continuous low-speed rotating cascade	Beihang U [101]	1250 RPM		0.21 (Rotational)	NA	2D2C	Axial plane Vane-rotor psg.	15 Hz (Phase-locked)	1000	DEHS droplets 1 μm
	U Bath [83, 103]	900 - 1100 RPM		0.22 - 0.28 (Axial) 0.59 - 0.72 (Rot.)	0.12 - 0.14	3D3C	3D volume Rotor psg. Near hub	15 Hz (Phase-locked)	200	DEHS droplets 0.5-1 μm

Figure 3.102: The overview of VKI CT-3 test rig. Figure adopted from [111].

Figure 3.103: Some geometrical details of CT-3 [112].

3.3.2.2 NEXT rainbow HPT stage

In this study, the NEXT rainbow HPT stage, a scaled-up version of the first stage of an aero-engine HPT, consisting of 34 nozzle guide vanes (NGV) and 48 rotor blades is studied. A rainbow rotor [76] is employed to test simultaneously six different sectors combining four different hub (H1-H4) and two different tip (T1,T2) geometries as shown in Fig. 3.104. Among them, the H1T2 sector shown in Fig. 3.105 is the reference blade geometry that adopts the axisymmetric hub and the squealer tip shape. The optimization process of hub and tip geometries are described in [75, 113]. The rainbow rotor setup allows a reduction of the number of experiments for such a number of investigated sectors. On the contrary, a dedicated data reduction technique is required to achieve sector-resolved information.

Figure 3.104: Rainbow rotor configuration.

Figure 3.105: Rainbow rotor sectors.

3.3.3 PIV setup

3.3.3.1 Optical access

Fig. 3.106 illustrates the 3D model of the test section employed for the present test campaign in CT-3. The annular test section is fully covered with metallic casings and various assembly features are implemented. For such a test section, implementing ideal optical accesses for light sheet insertions and image acquisition is challenging.

Figure 3.106: 3D model of the test section in CT-3.

Fig. 3.107 and 3.108 illustrate a meridional view and an axial view (Looking upstream from behind the rotor) of the test section. The main flow path is covered by internal and external metallic casings. A set of optical windows is mounted on the rotor shroud in the internal casing and on the external casing. The design of the optical window is not optimized for the PIV measurement since these windows are installed by reusing a pocket initially designed for casing measurements with pneumatic taps, flush-mounted fast response probes, and thin film gauges [76]. As a result, the optical window only covers -20 to 120% of the rotor axial chord distance from the rotor leading edge and about 2.5 rotor pitch. The inner surface curvature of the internal window is matched to the casing shroud surface. After preliminary tests, it was revealed that the wet surface of the internal window gets oil accumulation originating from the bearing lubrication and seeding during tests. Cleaning the windows is therefore required for every other test in order to capture images with acceptable quality. A laser endoscope, TUR1715-30 (see section 2.4.3), is used to introduce a light sheet inside the test section as the enclosed annular flow path and complex hardware geometry prohibit the direct light sheet

Figure 3.107: Meridional view of test section.

insertion from the outside.

A high-speed *Phantom v2012* camera and a high-speed *Quantronix DarwinDuo* dual cavity laser system are employed for the PIV measurement. Fig. 3.109 shows the test section instrumented with the PIV equipment. The camera sensor resolution is 1280×800 pixels with $28 \mu\text{m}$ pixel pitch. The large pixel size provides higher sensitivity to light. On the other hand, a greater magnification or larger separation time is required to ensure enough particle displacement between two successive frames. The latter option is not pursued to avoid the loss of particle pairs due to the out-of-plane component and also due to a short axial length of the FOV. The camera is equipped with a *Nikon AF Micro-Nikkor 60mm f/2.8D* lens, resulting in an approximately 0.56 optical magnification. An articulated laser guide arm is used to steer the laser beam to the laser endoscope. A beam expander consisting of a $f = -50$ mm plano-concave lens and a $f = 100$ mm plano-convex lens is attached to the exit of the guide arm. The enlargement of the beam diameter is required to control the thickness of the laser sheet to be optimal (1-1.5 mm).

The laser endoscope with an external diameter of 8 mm is inserted into the internal casing downstream of the rotor stage, using a slot originally designed for probe measurements. The endoscope yaw angle and radial position are adjusted by rotating the scope and changing the insertion depth. The PIV measurement is performed on tangential planes at 38%, 50%, and 58% of the rotor span height h_r . The appropriate illumination of the blade-to-blade planes in the rotor passage or at higher rotor span positions is not possible due to the unoptimized access for the endoscope, highly turned rotor blade, and annular flow path geometry halting

Figure 3.108: Axial view of test section. Looking upstream from behind the rotor.

Figure 3.109: Instrumented test section for PIV measurements.

the laser sheet. Furthermore, the curved surface of the window caused image distortion and its effect is further pronounced for the measurement planes closer to the hub.

The light sheet illuminates not only particles but also other components on its traveling path, such as the casing and rotor blades, yielding significant background noise compared to scattering light from particles. To reduce the light reflection, the rotor blade and the casing surface are coated with matte-black paint as shown in Fig. 3.110.

Figure 3.110: (A) Light sheet inserted in the test section. Rotor not painted. (B) Original rotor. (C) Rotor painted with black coating.

Despite applying the black paint, The direct collision of the laser sheet with the blade causes excessively intense reflections which can potentially damage the camera sensors. In order to block the reflection light entering the camera sensor, a part of the internal optical window is covered with black tape by attaching it to the outer surface of the window as illustrated in the schematics in Fig 3.111. Consequently, the region of interest is limited to a tangential plane at the rotor blade exit, located between 105% and 120% of the rotor axial chord covering a full rotor pitch (0.78 vane pitch).

3.3.3.2 Image calibration

The image calibration is performed using the calibration target images recorded before blow-down tests. Single-level calibration targets are used for the recording of calibration images. Fig. 3.112 illustrates 3D CAD model of the calibration target design. The calibration origin is set to coincide with the machine axis and the axial plane 4 mm downstream of the blade trailing edge at 50% rotor span. The regular dot pattern with 1 mm diameter circles and 2 mm space interval is distributed on the tangential plane circumscribes 50% rotor span radius at the calibration origin. For the PIV measurements other than the midspan plane, the target dots are projected onto the tangential planes at the corresponding rotor span radius by translating the pattern in tangential plane-normal direction while maintaining the calibration origin.

The target dot patterns are laser-printed on paper sheets then they are attached to 3D-printed base blocks tailored for each rotor span measurement. The base blocks are designed

Figure 3.111: (A) Reflection on the rotor. (B) Black tape covering a part of the window.

so that they fit the shape of the rotor blade and hub platform. Fig. 3.113 shows the fabricated calibration target and an example of a calibration image.

Figure 3.112: Design of calibration target on 3D CAD model.

Due to the limited space and access, placing and removing the calibration target in/from the measurement locations requires special attention. The following procedure is taken to record calibration images beforehand the test rig operation.

1. Attach the calibration target to the reference blade through the window pocket and set the angle of the blade disk to a reference position.
2. Close the test section by mounting the windows.
3. Set the camera in place using a traverse system and register the camera position.
4. Record calibration images.
5. Push back the camera using the traverse system and dismount the windows.
6. Remove the calibration target from the test section through the window pocket.

Figure 3.113: The calibration target for PIV measurement in CT-3 facility. (A) Front view. (B) Back view. (C) Installed calibration target. (D) An example of calibration image.

7. Close the test section by mounting the windows and replace the camera at the registered position.
8. Start test rig operation (Vacuuming the facility).

The image calibration is performed in *Davis* PIV processing software using the 3rd-order polynomial fitting function to take into account arbitrary distortions caused by the optical windows. Table 3.19 lists the image calibration parameters obtained for three PIV measurement planes ($h/h_r = 38\%$, 50% , and 58%).

Table 3.19: The image calibration parameter obtained with 3rd-order polynomial.

Rotor span of PIV planes	Parameter	
$h/h_r = 38\%$	RMS of fit [pixel]	0.19
	Scale factor [pixel/mm]	16.79
$h/h_r = 50\%$	RMS of fit [pixel]	0.37
	Scale factor [pixel/mm]	16.70
$h/h_r = 58\%$	RMS of fit [pixel]	0.16
	Scale factor [pixel/mm]	16.56

After image calibration in *Davis*, a conversion of the calibration target coordinate system to the measurement coordinate system is performed using *MATLAB*. Fig. 3.114 shows the schematics of the measurement coordinate system. The circumferential location of the machine axis is located in the middle of two NGVs for the experimental coordinate and is aligned to the NGV leading edge for the CFD coordinate. The origin of the post-processing coordinate system is aligned to the experimental machine axis and the axial plane where the leading edge of the rotor at the midspan circumscribes. The origin of the CFD coordinate

system is aligned to the CFD machine axis and the axial plane where the leading edge of NGV at the midspan circumscribes.

Figure 3.114: PIV calibration, postprocessing, and CFD coordinate systems for CT3 test case.

3.3.3.3 Seeding

In the present test case, DEHS droplets with $0.9 \mu\text{m}$ nominal diameter are used for seeding. Two Laskin nozzle seeding generators, *PIVpart14* and *PIVpart45*, are employed for the atomization of DEHS oil. The input pressure is set to 3 bar for *PIVpart14* and 4 bar for *PIVpart45* to ensure there is no reverse flow in the seeding generators. For the test case demonstrated by the fluorescent PIV technique, the fluorescent dye made of a mixture of DEHS and Pyrromethene 567 at a concentration of 1.25 g/L is used for the seeding oil.

In view of the limited accesses upstream of the test section, two options are considered for the seeding approach. The first option is to seed particles in the compression tube prior to the blow-down test. The primary advantage of this method is that no seeding probe needs to be inserted into the flow path, eliminating the flow disturbance. Besides, uniform particle distribution is expected because seeding can be done before blow-down i.e. there is enough time for particles to diffuse in the compression tube. The disadvantage is the possibility of damaging the piston and tube with seeding substance, and the alternation of compression tube characteristics due to seeding injections.

The second option is to inject particles via seeding probes installed upstream of the NGVs. There are available slots originally designed for aero-thermal probes at the stage inlet Plane 01 (see Fig. 3.107). These slots can be used for the seeding probes. The distance between the slots and the leading edge of NGV is approximately 50% chord length of the NGV. This approach is less harmful to the test rig while the drawback is the disturbance in the inlet flow.

Ensuring the absence of harm to the test rig and considering that the main focus of this study is the feasibility test of the measurement technique, the second option is chosen. The seeding setup is shown in Fig. 3.115. The main flow is seeded through three custom-made

Figure 3.115: Seeding locations in CT-3. (A) Side view of the test section with seeding setup. (B) Axial view of the test section looking downstream from NGV inlet.

seeding probes installed in three different circumferential positions at Plane 01.

Fig. 3.116 presents the design of three seeding probes A, B, and C designed and manufactured at the VKI. Probe A and B were originally designed by Luberti [114]. Probe A has a single row of 13 discharging holes with a diameter of 2 mm. Probe B has two rows of holes consisting of 25 holes. Probe C is newly designed for the current test campaign, it has a continuous slot with progressively enlarged opening towards the end of the cylinder. The probes are installed in slots 1-3, circumferentially distributed at every NGV passage as shown in Fig. 3.115.

In addition, the rim seal purge flow is seeded by injecting tracer particles into the purge flow supply line. The total seeding mass flow rate injected through the seeding probes is estimated to be less than 0.2% of the main flow. The effectiveness of the seeding probes and seeding slots are addressed in the result chapter 4.3.1.

3.3.3.4 Image recording

Table 3.20 lists the image recording parameters for the PIV measurements. The recording is made at acquisition frequency of 1000 Hz. Each blow-down test produces the useful testing time of approximately 250 ms, yielding 250 pairs of images. For the measurements at $h/h_r = 38\%$ and 58% , a total of 500 pairs of images is acquired from two blow-down tests, whereas only a single blow-down is performed for the measurement at $h/h_r = 50\%$. The large pixel size ($28 \mu\text{m}$) and low pixel resolution (1280×800) of the camera sensors results in the scaling factor of $F_s = 0.06 \text{ mm/px}$. The separation time between the successive frames is $1.14 \mu\text{s}$. Consequently, the nominal particle displacement is estimated to be about 2.3 px between successive frames. The short separation time is chosen considering the high blade

Figure 3.116: Seeding probe designs.

passing frequency (BPP) of 4740 Hz and high rotor tip speed reaching 250 m/s. During the pulse separation time of $1.14 \mu\text{s}$, the rotor phase varies about 5% and the rotor tip moves 0.29 mm (≈ 5 pixels). Furthermore, too long separation time is expected to cause losses of particle pairs due the short length of the FOV containing only 6 mm (≈ 100 pixels) in the axial direction. The laser pulse intensity is set to its maximum value: about 22 mJ/pulse.

Table 3.20: Image recording parameter for the COP PIV measurements. f_{rec} : PIV recording frequency, N_{rec} : the number of pairs of images, I_0 : Laser pulse intensity, t_s : pulse separation time, X_d : estimated nominal particle displacement, F_s : Scaling factor.

	$M_{03,rel}$	f_{rec}	N_{rec}	I_0	t_s	X_d	F_s
38%			500				
50%	0.78	1000 Hz	250	22 mJ	$1.14 \mu\text{s}$	$2.3 \text{ px}/t_s$	0.06 mm/px
58%			500				

3.3.3.5 Image preprocessing

A selection of image pre-processing algorithms is tested in order to obtain the highest signal-to-noise ratio in the cross-correlation operation, leading to the maximum number of valid vectors presenting a high degree of confidence. Background noise subtraction, commonly operated by subtracting non-seeded images from the test dataset, is not viable in the present case

due to the non-repetitive background originated by the motion of the rotor airfoils with diversified tip and hub geometries. Similarly, other temporal-based image processing techniques, such as time-averaged image subtraction, are not applicable to this case. As a result of the preliminary study, the best performing pre-processing strategy is found to be a combination of contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) [115], Sobel filter, and bilateral filter. The evaluation of optimal image preprocessing is discussed in subsection 4.3.3.

3.3.3.6 Vector computation

Davis 8.4 commercial software was employed for PIV vector calculation. The multi-pass cross-correlation method is used starting from 128-pixel initial square windows to 32-pixel final square windows. The window overlap is set to 75% for the last pass, resulting in a vector computation every approximately 0.5 mm. The outlier detection is performed by median filter with 5×5 neighbors and allowed vector range filter. The summary of the processing parameters is presented in Table 3.21.

Table 3.21: PIV processing setting for tests in CT-3.

	Setting
Image preprocessing	CLAHE (Open CV) Sobel filter (Davis) Bilateral filter (Open CV)
Vector computation	Planar-PIV (2D2C) multi-pass cross-correlation Initial pass: 1 Initial IW: 128×128 px with 0% overlapping and square weighting Final pass: 3 Final IW: 32×32 px with 75% overlapping and round weighting Intermediate and final validation: Universal outlier detection : Remove if residual > 2.0 : Reinsert if residual < 3.0 : Filter region = 5×5 : Minimum number of vectors: 3 Final vector field treatment : Allowed vector range ($0 < V_{axi} < 10, -5 < V_{tan} < 5$ [pixel]) : Remove groups with 5 vectors : Interpolation

3.3.4 Test conditions

A single flow condition as shown in Table 3.22, representing a HPT stage at engine cruise conditions, is considered for the present study. The pressure and temperature at the stage inlet and outlet (Plane 01 and Plane 03) are measured at midspan by circumferentially distributed probes as well as hub endwall and shroud wall pressure taps to monitor operating conditions. Fig. 3.117(A) shows a typical test condition during a blow-down sequence, and Fig. 3.117(B) presents a view zooming in the testing time. The testing time is defined based on the time window in which the inlet total pressure is stabilized. The typical length of testing time is about 250 ms.

Figure 3.117: A typical test condition of the high-pressure turbine test campaign in CT-3. (A) Overview of the test sequence. (B) Zoomed view for the testing time

To achieve a mean rotational speed of 5925 RPM (rotor tip speed = 251 m/s), the rotor is spun up to around 5820 RPM before each blow-down test. The blow-down air accelerates the rotor, resulting in an average increase of 60 - 70 RPM during the testing period (250 ms = 23-25 rotor revolutions). The increase of circumferential velocity of the rotor tip due to rotor acceleration during the test is therefore 0.4 – 0.8%. The sonic throat located downstream of the turbine stage is finely regulated for an average total-to-static stage pressure ratio (P_{01}/P_{s3}) of 2.2, establishing high subsonic flow conditions relative to the rotating blades at the stage outlet $M_{03,rel} = 0.78$, $Re_{03,C_{ax}} = 2.76 \times 10^5$. The purge mass flow rate is regulated to a mean value of 1.74% of total mass flow, by a sonic throat placed between the purge air supply tank and the test section [76].

Table 3.22: Nominal test Condition of the test campaign in CT-3 test rig.

Parameter	Value	Units
P_{01}	1037.9	mbar
T_{01}	439.4	K
$P_{01}/P_{s3,hub}$	2.195	-
$P_{01}/P_{s3,tip}$	2.214	-
Re_{03,C_x}	$2.76 \cdot 10^5$	-
$M_{03,rel}$	0.78	-
N_{rot}	5920	RPM
\dot{m}_{purge}	1.74% of \dot{m}_{total}	-

Table. 3.23 summarizes the statistics of the test condition in CT-3. A total of 157 blow-down tests were previously conducted for probe traversing measurement to map flow quantities at the inlet and outlet measurement planes. For the PIV test campaign, 27 tests are performed, involving changes in measurement locations and tuning seeding settings. In comparison between the measurements with the probe and PIV, the mean values determining the flow condition vary by less than 1% for the inlet total pressure and total-to-static pressure ratio, and about 2% for the total temperature and purge mass flow rate. The test-to-test repeatability (standard deviation covering the 95% CI) is slightly higher than the probe measurements due to the reduced number of tests for PIV measurements.

Instantaneous images acquired at four different time-instant during the testing sequence are presented in Fig. 3.118. The image instant is denoted in Fig. 3.117. Timing (i) is aligned with the shutter opening where the seeding particles accumulated in the upstream settling chamber are convected into the test section. During transient flow (ii), the particle distribution appears less homogeneous with a higher seeding concentration denoting the rotor wake and a comparatively lower concentration at the blade suction side, possibly due to the particle drifted by centrifugal force along the blade curvature. Eventually, steady flow conditions are achieved and maintained throughout the testing time (iii - iv), as the downstream sonic throat is choked until the end of the test. A more uniform seeding distribution is observed at instants (iii) and (iv), while the image sharpness progressively decreases as a result of the accumulation of seeding particles on the wetted surface of the optical window. As the refraction index of the optical path varies, the images become blurred.

Table 3.23: Statistical variation of test to test flow conditions.

		P_{01} [mbar]	$P_{01}/P_{s3,hub}$ [-]	$P_{01}/P_{s3,tip}$ [-]	T_{01} [K]	\dot{m}_{purge} [kg/s]
Probe meas.	Mean	1037.8	2.195	2.213	424.2	1.76%
	Standard dev. (95% CI)	7.4	0.012	0.018	10.2	0.001%
	Standard dev. (95% CI) / Mean	0.7%	0.6%	0.8%	2.4%	1.9%
	Number of tests	157				
PIV meas.	Mean	1042.5	2.174	2.191	432.3	1.79%
	Standard dev. (95% CI)	7.6	0.065	0.065	7.0	0.001%
	Standard dev. (95% CI) / Mean	0.7%	3.0%	3.0%	1.6%	2.0%
	Number of tests	27				
PIV/Probe meas.		100.5%	99.0%	99.0%	101.9%	102.4%

Figure 3.118: Instantaneous particle images recorded at (i) shutter opening time, (ii) flow transient, (iii) steady flow condition, and (iv) end of the testing time. Refer Fig. 3.117 for timing identification.

3.3.5 System synchronization

Synchronization of PIV system with the operation of the test rig and rotor angle is a crucial part of experiments, especially for blow-down type test facilities. The high-speed camera and the high-speed laser system are synchronized at 1 kHz acquisition frequency (laser output power: 20 - 25 W) by *Stanford DG535* digital delay/pulse generators. Operating the laser at a higher frequency causes damage to the small sealing window on the laser endoscope due to its higher beam power output (2 kHz, 40 W) concentrating into a small area. The sequence of the blow-down test with PIV measurement is described as follows:

1. The pressure in the test section and dump tank is decreased down to 25 mbar by a vacuum pump and the pressure in the compression tube is regulated by a pneumatic ejector to a certain level that will satisfy the test condition.
2. The turbine rotor is spun by an auxiliary turbine supplied by a 40 bar pressurized air line. The rotational speed is stabilized at 90% of the nominal speed.
3. The camera is set to 'Capture' status with 'Sync to External' mode in which the camera keeps capturing images at the frame rate supplied by the synchronizer. Once the internal memory of the camera becomes full, the older images are discarded. When the camera receives an acquisition trigger, it records a certain number of pre and aft-trigger images (preset in the camera control software).
4. The laser is set to 'External' mode in which the pulse repetition rate and timing are controlled by the synchronizer. The shutter of the laser head is opened, and the laser system needs a few seconds to reach the stabilized power level.
5. Turn on the seeding generators.
6. Start the tube compression sequence.
7. When the specified tube pressure level is reached, the acquisition systems and the camera are triggered to start recordings of the signals and images. This timing is marked as $t = 0$ in the time stamp of the systems.
8. The shutter is opened to start the blow-down test.

3.3.5.1 Laser pulse jitter

While the synchronizer output is set to generate triggering signals for double laser pulses with 1 μs separation time, the actual separation time of 1.14 μs is measured by a fast response photo-diode (*Thorlabs DET10A2*, 1 ns rise time). The measured value (1.14 μs) is considered as the true separation time instead of the preset value. The displacement of the rotor blades during the frame separation time is 0.5% of rotor pitch at nominal rotational speed (5920 rotation-per-minutes (RPM)).

3.3.5.2 Image - rotor angle synchronization

The Rotor speed and angle are monitored by an encoder (fast-response diode) and its signal is recorded by an acquisition system (*LDS Nicolet - Genesis*) which also records the signals of reference aero-thermal probes at 1 MHz. Fig. 3.119 illustrates a diagram of the synchronization procedure in which several steps are required to ensure the synchronization of the image and rotor angle. After preliminary tests, a significant delay was found between the encoder signal and the camera image. The quantification of delay was necessary in order to identify the individual blade and its position in each PIV image as they are required for phase-locked-averaging. The delay was found to consist of bias and random delays.

Figure 3.119: Image-rotor angle synchronization procedure.

- Bias delay

Dedicated rotor run-up tests are performed to determine the bias delay. Prior to the run-up tests, the reference rotor tip is painted with a fluorescent marker to enhance image contrast Fig. 3.120. A static calibration that associates the rotor position in the image and the rotor angle retrieved from the diode encoder is performed as shown in Fig. 3.121. The rotor is aligned to the reference positions using a 3D printed piece that fixes the angle of the rotor with respect to the stationary part. The resultant calibration curve is presented in Fig. 3.122.

During the run-up tests, instantaneous images of the reference rotor tip illuminated by laser are recorded while all the synchronization and acquisition settings are kept the same as those for PIV tests. Note that only the start of the acquisition is triggered manually for the run-up test. The rotor position in the image is retrieved by applying a series of image processing techniques. The image-based rotor position is then converted to the image-based rotor angle (θ_{IMG}) employing the static calibration data.

Comparing the time stamp (t_{Img}) for the image-based rotor angle against the time stamp

Figure 3.120: The reference rotor whose tip was painted with fluorescent marker.

Figure 3.121: A static calibration image of the reference rotor tip painted with a fluorescent marker. Three images are superimposed.

Figure 3.122: Calibration curve for conversion from pixel coordinate to rotor angle.

from the diode rotary encoder (t_{Diode}) for the corresponding rotor angle as shown in Fig. 3.123, a $527.4 \mu\text{s}$ bias delay is measured with a standard deviation of $10 \mu\text{s}$. The bias delay and the standard deviation respectively corresponded to approximately 250% and 4% of the BPP. This means that the delay measurement is compulsory for the identification of the blade captured at each image instant. Still, a delay ambiguity (random delay) of 4% of BPP results in unreliable identification of rotor position in images.

Figure 3.123: Diode-base rotor angle (solid black line) and Image-base rotor angle (red marker). (A) Plot over multiple revolutions. (B) Zoomed view.

- Random delay

The random delay of the time stamp is corrected posteriori, by determining the precise rotor angle from the reflection of the rotor trailing edge (TE) appearing in the raw PIV images as shown in Fig. 3.124. In each instantaneous raw image, one can observe the illuminated rotor TE and its reflection respectively at the left and right side of the illuminated area (pink circles). This reflection is considered as a true rotor TE position. The yellow circle indicates the position of rotor TE estimated by the encoder signal taking into account the bias delay ($527.4 \mu\text{s}$). A non-negligible mismatch between the estimated and the true TE location is observed, necessitating retrieval of the correct TE location based on the information (TE reflection) in the image.

In order to enable an algorithm to detect the reflection, image enhancement is performed by cropping the right side area (blue rectangle) which includes horizontally elongated TE reflection, and applying 2D convolution with a tailored kernel. Intensity profiles in the y direction are extracted to identify the signal peak that returns the TE circumferential position, at each horizontal (x) coordinate. Fig. 3.125 shows intensity profiles (A) without and (B) with 2D convolution, respectively. Each line shows an intensity profile at a different horizontal location (x). By applying 2D convolution, the TE reflection signal is intensified and erroneous peaks are smoothed out. As a result, one can determine the peak location which indicates the TE reflection location. The median of the peak y pixel coordinate from all profiles is taken as the true TE reflection location. The detection algorithm works reliably with less than 2% failure over 500 images for the raw images taken at 50% and 58% rotor span. For the images

at 38% span, the accuracy of TE detection significantly drops due to blurrier image quality, necessitating manual selection of the TE location for every image.

Figure 3.124: Procedure of rotor trailing edge detection to take into account the random delay.

Figure 3.125: Normalized pixel intensity profile of cropped area. (A) Without and (B) with 2D convolution.

3.3.6 Phase-lock-averaging

Fig. 3.126-left illustrates the definition of rotor angle and -right shows the distribution of rotor angle during testing time for two blow-down operations. The number of images obtained in each test is limited to 250 images due to the short testing time (250 ms). The rotor angle shows significant image-to-image variations due to the frequency mismatch between the fixed

laser pulse repetition (1 kHz) and the accelerating rotor (90 RPM increase over 250 ms), prohibiting the phase-locked image acquisition.

Figure 3.126: Left: Definition of reference blade and rotor angle. Right: Distribution of rotor angle during testing time of two blow-down operations (NXT330 and NXT331).

The classification of the rotor phase for phase-lock averaging is done considering the position of the rotor image within the FOV. The PIV FOV covers approximately 1.1 rotor pitch which corresponds to 0.78 NGV pitch. Fig. 3.127 illustrates the method of rotor phase classification. The rotor phase is based on the location of the blade trailing edge retrieved from Image-rotor angle synchronization discussed in the previous subsection 3.3.5.2. The phase is centered on the machine axis, and it increases in the moving direction of the rotor blades. Fig. 3.128 shows the distribution of the rotor phase within PIV FOV during the testing time of two blow-down operations. The rotor angle distribution (0 - 360 degree) observed in Fig. 3.126 is re-mapped in rotor phase distribution (0 - 7.5). Two types of phase-lock-average (PLA) techniques are carried out based on this rotor phase information.

3.3.6.1 Stationary-domain phase-lock-averaging

The first method sorts the instantaneous velocity fields by discretizing the rotor position in the stationary frame of reference, phased with respect to the NGV-relative position. Fig. 3.129 illustrates the conceptual sketch for the 5 phase-class discretization. The color band indicates the phase class. For example, the instantaneous snapshots whose rotor phase ϕ falls in the range of $\phi \leq 0.75$ and $6.75 < \phi$ are binned in class 1, $0.75 < \phi \leq 2.25$ are in class 2, $2.25 < \phi \leq 3.75$ are in class 3, and so on. For each phase class, the ensemble averaging is performed as shown in Fig. 3.130.

Fig. 3.131 shows the tangential velocity component ensemble-averaged over five discrete rotor phase classes in the stationary frame of reference. The black circles, which appear as thick black lines to the left of each plot, indicate the rotor TE position in the instantaneous velocity fields employed for the ensemble-averaging at each discrete phase. This coarse

Figure 3.127: Rotor phase classification within PIV FOV.

Figure 3.128: Distribution of rotor phase within PIV FOV during the testing time of two blow-down operations (NXT330 and NXT331).

Figure 3.129: 5 phase-class discretization in stationary-domain.

Figure 3.130: 5 phase-class stationary-domain phase-lock-average.

rotor phase discretization introduces an averaging effect that substantially reduces the time resolution of the measurement. Increasing the number of classes of the ensemble-averaging algorithm can reduce the uncertainty of the rotor position at the expense of a lower number of images available for each rotor phase.

3.3.6.2 Rotating-domain phase-lock-averaging

Another approach in the ensemble-averaging procedure is to compute the PLA in the rotating domain (rotor-locked), considering the rotor pitch as the ensemble-averaging domain. For every computed velocity field, the circumferential coordinate y is rephased in order to align the rotor TE to the field center ($y = 0$), assuming periodic boundaries at the peripheral extremities of the averaging domain as shown in Fig. 3.132. An example of this process is presented in Fig. 3.133. With the deterministic flow unsteadiness averaged in the rotor domain, the flow gradients associated with stationary components, such as the upstream NGV, are averaged out. The main advantage of this PLA method is the increased number of velocity fields by combining all rotor phase snapshots into a single ensemble averaging dataset and the rotor phase is ensured to be aligned to the center of the averaging window. The resulting phase-resolved information in the rotor domain is directly comparable to the results of RANS flow predictions performed using the mixing plane approach at the vane-rotor interface.

In order to account for the rainbow rotor configuration adopted in the current test article, a sector-resolved PLA can be also performed in the rotor domain, isolating the contributions of the different tip geometries. Before applying the rotating-domain PLA, the computed vector fields are classified into six sector groups using the information on the rotor angular position provided by the corrected rotary encoder signal. In order to exclude sector-to-sector flow interactions and to ensure an optimal periodicity of the sector flow field, only the six central passages of each sector are considered in the ensemble-averaging operation [76].

Figure 3.131: Stationary PLA tangential velocity fields with 5 phase-class discretization..

Figure 3.132: Conceptual sketch of rotating-domain phase-lock average method.

Figure 3.133: Example of rotating-domain phase-lock average method.

3.3.7 Numerical setup

3.3.7.1 CFD domain

Each blade design (H1T1, H1T2, H2T1, H2T2, H3T1, and H4T1) is investigated separately by individual single passage steady-state RANS simulations carried out by Burigana et al. [75]. The flow domain adopted for the numerical characterization is presented in Fig. 3.134. The domain consists of one vane passage and one rotor blade passage including the rim seal cavity. The inlet patch of CFD domain is located $1.3 C_{ax,NGV}$ upstream of the NGV leading edge while the outlet patch is positioned $3.6 C_{ax,NGV}$ downstream of the rotor blade trailing edge. The experimental measurement locations are included in the CFD domain as denoted by CT-3 inlet (plane 01) and CT-3 outlet (plane 03).

Figure 3.134: CFD domain for CT-3 test case.

The patch between the stationary and rotating frames (rotor-stator interface) is treated by the mixing plane approach that averages the flow field in pitchwise direction. Considering the cavity flow dependent on non-asymmetry pressure distribution in pitchwise direction, the mixing plane is located upstream of the cavity static lip, i.e. the rim seal cavity is included in the rotating frame. A similar approach for stator-rotor interface is found in [116].

3.3.7.2 Boundary conditions

Test-calibrated boundary conditions are imposed in the CFD studies to ensure the relevance of the flow predictions and direct comparability with the experimental dataset. Averaged total temperature and total pressure are matched at Plane 01, while the experimental outlet static pressure is matched at the endwalls in Plane 03. At the inlet of the purge channel, a constant mass-flow boundary condition is imposed, corresponding to 1.74% of the total stage mass-flow for the design flow condition. The periodic flow condition is employed at the circumferential boundaries with adjoining passages. A constant wall temperature of 300 K is imposed on all wet surfaces, respecting the experimental gas-to-wall temperature ratio of about 1.5, relevant to engine operating conditions.

3.3.7.3 Mesh

An unstructured fully hexahedral mesh is adopted for this study due to the significant complexity of the rotor blade tip and hub shapes as well as the rim seal cavity geometry under investigation. Table 3.24 summarizes the number of cells of the CFD domain.

Table 3.24: The number of cells of the CFD domain.

Domain	Number of cells
Stator	1×10^6
Rotor	$8 \sim 9 \times 10^6$

The CFD domain is meshed by *Cadence Hexpress v8.1*. The NGV domain mesh is fixed for all simulation cases, with around 1 million cells. A mesh sensitivity study has been performed varying the NGV mesh from one to eight million cells, and no significant performance difference was found [75]. On the other hand, the rotor domain is meshed with 8 - 9 million cells depending on the blade geometry in order to capture the impact of diversified tip and hub platform shapes.

3.3.7.4 Numerical model

Steady-state RANS computations are performed in *Cadence FINE/Open 9.2*. A perfect gas hypothesis is used for the working fluid. Based on previous study, the Spalart Allmaras model is adopted as turbulence model. For spatial discretization, the 2nd order central scheme is used. The numerical setup is built based on previous work performed in [117, 118].

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4

Results

Chapter 4 presents the results of the three test cases introduced in Chapter 3.

4.1 Active turbulence grid tests in a low-speed wind tunnel (L-12)

In this section, the outcomes of PIV measurements conducted on the active turbulence grid in the L-12 wind tunnel are presented. The evaluation of the recorded image quality is first discussed, then the methodology for extracting the synthetic jet flow field is verified. The following subsection presents the measurement uncertainty and validation of the fluorescent PIV technique. The near field behind the grid is analyzed in terms of mean flow quantities and frequency constituents. The results are by the proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) technique. Lastly, the turbulence quantities are examined.

4.1.0.5 Recorded images

Fig. 4.1 illustrates a schematic of the laser sheet and camera FOV for PIV measurements on the turbulence grid, followed by exemplary particle image snapshots recorded in passive mode (case A). The images recorded with camera 1 are displayed in the left column, while those captured with camera 2 are presented in the right column. Camera 2 was equipped with an optical bandstop filter with a cut-off wavelength of 532 ± 10 nm to remove the illumination laser light. The top row shows raw images in the full FOV and the bottom row presents a zoomed view specified with the red rectangles. In a similar manner, raw particle images for the active cases with the downstream jet injection are presented in Fig. 4.2 and 4.3. For the former, the main flow was seeded with the normal oil (*Ondina X420*) particles, and the synthetic jet was seeded with the fluorescent particles (case B). For the latter, the seeding materials were switched between the main and the synthetic jet (case C).

Figure 4.1: Exemplary particle images from camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right) for test case A (passive mode). 1st row: Full FOV. 2nd row: Zoomed view.

Figure 4.2: Exemplary particle images from camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right) for test case B (active mode with downstream injection). The injection jets were seeded with fluorescent particle whereas the main flow was seeded with normal oil particles. 1st row: Full FOV. 2nd row: Zoomed view.

Figure 4.3: Exemplary particle images from camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right) for test case C (active mode with downstream injection). The injection jets were seeded with normal oil particles whereas the main flow was seeded with the fluorescent particles. 1st row: Full FOV. 2nd row: Zoomed view.

Globally, camera 2 images present a lower pixel intensity as the optical band-stop filter cut off the Mie scattering signals and the limited value of the fluorescence quantum yield. Despite the use of an optical band-stop filter, significant light reflections appear on the surface of the bar in the images captured by camera 2. This is presumably caused by the accumulation of fluorescent oil on the surface. Applying an oleophobic coating is suggested for future works to minimize these reflections. Fig. 4.4 illustrates exemplary correlation maps from camera 1 and camera 2 of test case A (Fig. 4.1) evaluated at $x/D = 2.0$, $y/D = 0.0$ with a 32×32 pixel window. While multiple fallacious peaks appear in the camera 2 correlation map, the signal of fluorescent light appeared to be satisfactory in yielding a prominent peak. The image obtained from camera 2 in test case B presents the synthetic jet well isolated from the main flow. The particle image size appeared to be 1-4 pixels for both of the cameras.

Figure 4.4: Exemplary correlation map from camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right) for test case A. The map was evaluated at $x/D = 2.0$, $y/D = 0.0$ with 32×32 pixel window.

Fig. 4.5 presents the probability density function (PDF) of particle displacement in x (longitudinal) and y (transverse) directions for test cases A, B, and C. The plots in the left and right columns represent the results of camera 1 and camera 2, respectively. Despite the visually observed particle image size being around 1-4 pixels, the PDF exhibits distinctive peaks at integer values, indicating the presence of the peak-locking effect. This suggests that, one may not assume the particle image size based on the perception with human's eye. Instead, the actual particle image size should be evaluated with the PDF of particle displacements estimated by the processing algorithm. The effect is more pronounced in the PDF of camera 2, possibly due to the reduced diameter of particle image resulting from the lower intensity of fluorescent light signal compared to that of Mie scattering. The peak-locking effect is also present in the PDF of camera 2 for test cases B and C. With the presence of the peak-locking effect, the measured velocity V_{meas} involves the corresponding uncertainty ΔV_{PL} .

$$V_{meas} = F_s \frac{X_d + \Delta X_{d,PL}}{t_s} = V + \Delta V_{PL} \quad (4.1)$$

where F_s is the scaling factor, X_d is the particle displacement in pixel, and t_s is the separation time. For the present test cases, $F_s \approx 5 \times 10^{-5}$ m/pixel and $t_s = 50 \mu s$. $\Delta X_{d,PL}$ is the error in particle displacement due to the peak locking effect whose maximum value is = 0.5 pixel.

Assuming $\Delta X_{d,PL}$ has a rectangular distribution, the corresponding uncertainty in velocity is:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta V_{PL} &= \alpha \frac{\Delta X_{d,PL}/\sqrt{3}}{t_s} \\ &= 0.29 \text{ m/s}\end{aligned}\quad (4.2)$$

which amounts 6% of the upstream freestream velocity. Nonetheless, comparisons of PDF between test cases A, B, and C provide us insights into the diversified velocity constitution resulting from the synthetic jet injection. Since camera 1 is unfiltered, it always captures both Mie scattering and fluorescent emission signals, in other words, it records the movements of both the normal oil particles and fluorescent particles. On the other hand, camera 2 is equipped with the optical band-stop filter thus it only captures the movements of the fluorescent particles.

For passive mode (test case A), the particle displacement in the longitudinal direction ($X_{d,x}$) exhibits a wide range of spectrum with a distinctive peak around 8 pixel/ t_s . For active mode with downstream jet injection (case B and C), the longitudinal particle displacement of camera 1 shows a reduction in the peak height at 8 pixel/ t_s , and the entities are redistributed to around 6 pixel/ t_s . Note that the PDFs of camera 1 for test cases B and C show very similar spectra because their PDFs contain essentially the same information, i.e., the motion of both particles seeded in the jet and main flows.

Figure 4.5: Probability density function (PDF) of particle displacement for Passive mode. Left: Camera 1, Right: Camera 2, Top: x component, Bottom: y component.

4.1.1 Extraction of jet-only velocity fields

For test case B, seeding the synthetic jet with the fluorescent particle and employing the optical band-stop filter enabled recordings of jet-only particle images. To extract the flow field information from these images, several processing steps are required.

Fig. 4.6 shows the processing diagram. On the left-hand side, the processing operation sequence for the camera 1 images is presented. The particle images from camera 1 register the scatter lights from both the main-flow seeded particles and the synthetic-jet seeded particles. These images are used to compute the global vector fields (jet + main flow). First, the temporal-average intensity field is subtracted from the raw images to remove the background noise (1b). Then, the multi-pass cross-correlation scheme described in section 3.1.5.7 is applied to obtain instantaneous global vector fields (1c). This procedure is common with test cases A and C, for both camera 1 and camera 2.

Figure 4.6: Image processing and vector computation scheme.

On the right-hand side of Fig. 4.6, the processing steps tailored for the jet-only images obtained from camera 2 in test case B are illustrated. These images capture the fluorescent signal emitted by the fluorescent particles seeded in the synthetic jet. Same as in the camera 1 images, a subtraction of temporal-average intensity is initially applied to the raw images (2b). Forwarding these images directly to the cross-correlation step would result in numerous spurious vectors in the region devoid of particle signals such as the outer area of the jet. Therefore, it is essential to create a masking filter beforehand the cross-correlation step, so that the vectors are computed only within the jet. To distinguish the jet from the background, a typical segmentation approach is taken for the present study. The regions where seeding particles exist are smoothed and highlighted by applying a subtraction of the sliding spatial average, threshold criterion, and sliding spatial average (2c). Subsequently, a masking filter is created based on another threshold criterion. The created mask is then applied to the post-temporal-average subtraction images (2e), and the vector fields of the jet are computed using

Table 4.1: Operation list for creation of mask to extract the synthetic jet.

Operation	Setting
Subtract spatial sliding average filter	Filter length: 16 pixel
Threshold criterion	Discard pixel intensity below 79
Spatial sliding average filter	Filter length: 16 pixel
Threshold masking	Enable intensity above 1

the cross-correlation scheme (2f). Fig. 4.7 displays exemplary images at operation steps (2b), (2c), (2e) and the resultant instantaneous velocity field (2f). The exact parameters for the mask creation are presented in Table. 4.1.

Figure 4.7: Image processing and vector computation scheme.

4.1.2 Convergence history and Uncertainty quantification

Fig. 4.8 illustrates the points of interest (P1-P4) for evaluation of convergence history. P1($x/D = 2.0$, $y/D = 0.0$) and P2(5.0, 0.0) are located in the wake whereas P3(2.0, 1.5) and P4(5.0, 1.5) are placed behind the bar gird throat (the area in-between two bars). The color map represents the mean velocity magnitude of test case A. In Fig. 4.9, the convergence histories of the mean, 95% confidence intervals (CI), and RMS of the velocity magnitude are shown from left to right columns. Each row is the results of test cases A, B, and C, from top to bottom, respectively. The solid lines represent data from camera 1 while the dashed lines show the data from camera 2. The shaded areas shown in the figure in the left column represent the

95% CI of the velocity magnitude.

The 95% CI levels at P3 and P4 located downstream of the bar throat converge to below 1% of the mean after 1000 image pair samplings. On the other hand, the data sampled within the wake (P1, P2) present slower convergence due to the flow unsteadiness attributed to the vortex shedding from the bar.

In terms of RMS, the convergence is achieved after sampling 1000 recordings, when the variation of RMS stays below 0.1 m/s. A higher level of RMS observed at locations P1 and P2 indicates the flow unsteadiness in the bar wake. The total number of valid samples is reduced at P1 for test case B due to the excessively high seeding density at the outlet of the jet. In this region, the concentrated particles yielded a smoke-like image pattern instead of registering individual particles, hence finding a distinctive peak in the correlation map was difficult.

Figure 4.8: Sampling locations for convergence history. P1: $x/D = 2.0$, $y/D = 0.0$. P2: $x/D = 5.0$, $y/D = 0$. P3: $x/D = 1.5$, $y/D = 5.0$.

Fig. 4.10 and 4.11 present the type A and type B standard uncertainties (1σ), and the combined uncertainty with 95% confidence interval (1.96σ) for the longitudinal and transverse velocity components (V_x , V_y) of the PIV measurement for test case A. The uncertainties of results from camera 1 and camera 2 are displayed in the left and right columns, respectively.

An excessively high level of uncertainty registered in the top left corner was caused by insufficient light intensity as the region was on the edge of the laser sheet. The type A uncertainty distribution shows peaks in the area where the roll-up of the detached shear layer occurred, statistically demonstrating the flow unsteadiness. The high level of Type B uncertainties in the shear layer of the bar sides and behind the wake region is attributed to the high-velocity gradient diversifying the particle displacement within the interrogation windows.

Figure 4.9: Convergence history of mean (1st column), 95% confidence intervals (2nd column), and RMS (3rd column) of the velocity magnitude. Top row (a-c): Test case A. Middle row: Test case B. Bottom row: Test case C.

The summary of uncertainties of the PIV measurement on the active turbulence grid is shown in Table 4.9.

Figure 4.10: Uncertainty map of longitudinal velocity (V_x) measured by PIV for the test case A. Left column: Camera 1. Right Column: Camera 2. Top row: Type A uncertainty. Middle row: Type B uncertainty. Bottom row: Combined and expanded uncertainty (95% CI).

4.1.3 Validation of fluorescence imaging

The velocity fields obtained from both camera 1 and camera 2 for test case A are essentially identical since both cameras record the same particles. The only difference lies in the type of signals registered by each camera sensor. Camera 1 captures both Mie scattering and fluorescent lights, whereas camera 2 captures only the latter, as the attached optical band-stop filter blocks the former. By comparing these two velocity fields, one can assess whether the use of fluorescent particle images introduces artifacts in the measured velocity fields.

Fig. 4.12 presents the mean streamlines overlapped on the contour map of mean velocity magnitude obtained from camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right) recordings. A high

Figure 4.11: Uncertainty map of transverse velocity (V_y) measured by PIV for the test case A. Left column: Camera 1. Right Column: Camera 2. Top row: Type A uncertainty. Middle row: Type B uncertainty. Bottom row: Combined and expanded uncertainty (95% CI).

Table 4.2: Uncertainties of PIV measurements on the active turbulence grid. Type A and Type B uncertainties are expressed as the standard uncertainty (1σ), whereas the combined uncertainty is expanded to cover 95% confidence interval (1.96σ). The uncertainties are presented in both physical units and normalized units (percentage of upstream freestream velocity $V_\infty = 5$ m/s).

Camera	Quantity	Symbol	Unit	Uncertainty behind throat region			Uncertainty in wake		
				Type A	Type B	Combined (95% CI)	Type A	Type B	Combined (95% CI)
Test case A (Passive mode)									
Cam1	Longitudinal velocity	V_x	m/s	0.023 (0.45%)	0.106 (2.11%)	0.210 (4.21%)	0.028 (0.56%)	0.106 (2.11%)	0.212 (4.24%)
	Transverse velocity	V_y	m/s	0.024 (0.48%)	0.069 (1.37%)	0.142 (2.85%)	0.051 (1.02%)	0.099 (1.99%)	0.219 (4.38%)
	Velocity magnitude	$ V $	m/s	0.023 (0.45%)	0.106 (2.11%)	0.212 (4.24%)	0.028 (0.56%)	0.104 (2.07%)	0.210 (4.21%)
	Turbulence intensity	TI	%	-	-	0.330	-	-	1.470
Cam2	Longitudinal velocity	V_x	m/s	0.022 (0.45%)	0.111 (2.21%)	0.221 (4.42%)	0.023 (0.45%)	0.113 (2.26%)	0.228 (4.56%)
	Transverse velocity	V_y	m/s	0.024 (0.47%)	0.082 (1.63%)	0.166 (3.32%)	0.051 (1.01%)	0.106 (2.12%)	0.230 (4.61%)
	Velocity magnitude	$ V $	m/s	0.022 (0.45%)	0.111 (2.21%)	0.221 (4.42%)	0.028 (0.55%)	0.113 (2.26%)	0.228 (4.56%)
	Turbulence intensity	TI	%	-	-	0.340	-	-	1.600
Test case B (Active mode)									
Cam1	Longitudinal velocity	V_x	m/s	0.021 (0.41%)	0.097 (1.94%)	0.194 (3.89%)	0.029 (0.58%)	0.154 (3.09%)	0.307 (6.15%)
	Transverse velocity	V_y	m/s	0.017 (0.34%)	0.059 (1.18%)	0.121 (2.42%)	0.032 (0.65%)	0.132 (2.65%)	0.267 (5.34%)
	Velocity magnitude	$ V $	m/s	0.021 (0.41%)	0.097 (1.94%)	0.194 (3.89%)	0.029 (0.58%)	0.154 (3.09%)	0.307 (6.15%)
	Turbulence intensity	TI	%	-	-	0.290	-	-	0.890
Cam2	Longitudinal velocity	V_x	m/s	0.042 (0.84%)	0.188 (3.75%)	0.377 (7.53%)	0.030 (0.61%)	0.1923 (3.85%)	0.3816 (7.63%)
	Transverse velocity	V_y	m/s	0.036 (0.72%)	0.179 (3.58%)	0.358 (7.16%)	0.032 (0.64%)	0.172 (3.43%)	0.342 (6.84%)
	Velocity magnitude	$ V $	m/s	0.042 (0.84%)	0.188 (3.75%)	0.377 (7.53%)	0.030 (0.61%)	0.192 (3.85%)	0.382 (7.63%)
	Turbulence intensity	TI	%	-	-	0.870	-	-	0.890
Test case C (Active mode)									
Cam1	Longitudinal velocity	V_x	m/s	0.020 (0.40%)	0.100 (2.00%)	0.200 (4.01%)	0.025 (0.50%)	0.148 (2.95%)	0.294 (5.87%)
	Transverse velocity	V_y	m/s	0.017 (0.35%)	0.064 (1.28%)	0.130 (2.60%)	0.031 (0.62%)	0.131 (2.61%)	0.263 (5.26%)
	Velocity magnitude	$ V $	m/s	0.020 (0.40%)	0.100 (2.00%)	0.200 (4.01%)	0.025 (0.50%)	0.148 (2.95%)	0.294 (5.87%)
	Turbulence intensity	TI	%	-	-	0.300	-	-	0.660
Cam2	Longitudinal velocity	V_x	m/s	0.021 (0.42%)	0.120 (2.41%)	0.240 (4.79%)	0.025 (0.50%)	0.181 (3.63%)	0.359 (7.18%)
	Transverse velocity	V_y	m/s	0.018 (0.35%)	0.092 (1.85%)	0.184 (3.69%)	0.031 (0.62%)	0.167 (3.33%)	0.332 (6.64%)
	Velocity magnitude	$ V $	m/s	0.021 (0.42%)	0.120 (2.41%)	0.240 (4.79%)	0.025 (0.50%)	0.181 (3.63%)	0.359 (7.18%)
	Turbulence intensity	TI	%	-	-	0.370	-	-	0.810

similarity is observed between the results from different cameras, including some prominent flow features such as a pair of counter-rotating recirculation zones behind the bar.

A quantitative evaluation is made through a comparison of the transverse-wise distribution of velocity components and turbulence intensity as presented in Fig. 4.13. The profiles on the left column are obtained at $x/D = 2.0$ and those on the right column are extracted at $x/D = 5.0$. The black circle markers represent the data from camera 1 whereas the data from camera 2 were displayed with red triangles. The green diagonal cross markers show the linear interpolation of camera 2 data on the camera 1 grid for calculation of the difference between the two profiles which is presented in blue cross markers. While the differences in velocity components are mostly below 0.1 m/s (2% of upstream freestream speed), a relatively large difference, amounting to around 0.3 m/s, is found in the high-velocity gradient region where the limited number of sampling points may cause an error in the linear interpolation. Additionally, the difference of 0.3 m/s is consistent with the measurement uncertainty due to the peak-locking effect anticipated in fluorescent PIV results (subsection 4.1.0.5). In terms of turbulence intensity, the difference reaches 2% in the edge of the bar wake. Overall, the fluorescent PIV technique captures most of the flow features obtained from the standard Mie scattering PIV approach.

Figure 4.12: Comparisons of streamlines and contour map of velocity magnitude obtained from camera 1 and camera 2.

4.1.4 Time-averaged flow field

Fig. 4.14 compares mean flow fields of passive (left) and active modes (right). The subfigures in the first to the fourth rows show; the streamlines with the colored maps of velocity magnitude, contour maps of the longitudinal velocity component, contour maps of the transverse velocity component, and contour maps of the plane normal vorticity. For a quantitative comparison, the transverse-wise distributions of velocity components are presented in Fig. 4.15. The longitudinal and transverse velocity components are plotted in the top and bottom rows, respectively. The passive case is shown in the left column and the active test case, including both the jet and main flows, is shown in the right column. Each sub-figure contains three profiles extracted at different longitudinal locations ($x/D = 2.0, 3.0,$ and 5.0). The flow field for the active test case is obtained from the camera 1 recording acquired in test case C.

With the introduction of downstream jet injection, the recirculation bubbles behind the

Figure 4.13: Comparisons of velocity and TI profiles obtained from camera 1 (Black, circle markers) and camera 2 (Red, triangle markers). Green diagonal cross markers represent data of camera 2 linear interpolated onto camera 1 coordinate. The difference between camera 1 and 2 is presented with blue cross markers using the vertical axis on the right-hand side. Left column: $x/C_{a,x} = 2.0$. Right column: $x/C_{a,x} = 5.0$.

Figure 4.14: Contour maps of velocity magnitude overlapped with streamlines (top row), longitudinal velocity (second row), transverse velocity (third row), and plane-normal vorticity (bottom row) for passive (left) and active cases (right).

Figure 4.15: Velocity component profiles for the passive (left) and active (right) cases extracted at $x/D = 2, 3$ and 5.

bar vanish as the jet fills the bar wake. The jet core accelerates the low-momentum flow in the wake resulting in an evident reduction of the wake deficit. It also facilitates entrainment of the main flow in the wake area, as seen in the streamline contraction and the amplified magnitude of the transverse velocity component directed towards the center line from either side of the wake.

The jet injection also has an impact on the freestream near the throat between the adjacent bars. The profiles at $x/D = 2.0$ show a reduction of the longitudinal velocity by about 1 m/s. As the bar wake length is shortened, the effective area downstream of the bars is increased thus the flow diffused more quickly.

The vorticity contour map of the passive case illustrates an antisymmetric distribution about the centerline which represents the shear layer vortices detached from either side of the bar. For the active test case, another pair of antisymmetric vorticity is distributed in the wake center suggesting the existence of an additional shear layer between the jet and bar wake.

4.1.5 Frequency analysis

To grasp the impact of the synthetic jet in the unsteady flow behind the bars, one may look at the frequency content of the flow fields. Fig. 4.16 shows the power spectral density (PSD) of each velocity component sampled at the location P2 (in the bar wake centerline) and P4 (1.5 D away from the centerline in the transverse direction) indicated in Fig. 4.8. Figures on the left and right columns represent the passive and active cases, respectively. The PSD is obtained from 2000 time-resolved PIV recordings acquired at 1 kHz. The most significant feature is the peak appears at around 110 Hz, which matches with the vortex shedding frequency f_{shed} estimated from the Strouhal-Reynolds number relation.

$$\begin{aligned} f_{shed} &= \frac{St \cdot V_{FS}}{D} \\ &= \frac{0.22 \cdot 5.0}{0.01} \\ &= 110 \text{ Hz} \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

Where St is the dimensionless Strouhal number, V_{FS} is the upstream freestream velocity, and D is the diameter of the bar. In the present test cases, a Strouhal number of 0.22 is employed with the Reynolds number based on the bar diameter and upstream freestream velocity being 3225. For the active case, the peak associated with the vortex shedding frequency is less pronounced and its frequency seems to be slightly reduced. The inertial subrange is found after 100 Hz, displaying the decaying slope following Kolmogorov's $f^{-5/3}$ law (indicated with dashed lines).

The individual frequency contents of the jet and main flows for the active case, obtained from fluorescent PIV recordings, are displayed in the left and right columns in Fig. 4.17, respectively. In the PSD of the jet, f_{shed} peak is only apparent in the transverse velocity component sampled at the wake center. The PSD spectra of the main flow are very similar to those of jet+main. At this point, one can presume that the downstream jet radically changes the vortex-shedding structure whereas there is still a trace of unsteadiness associated with the vortex shedding in the frequency content.

Figure 4.16: PSD of velocity fluctuations sampled at P2 and P4. Left column: Passive mode. Right column: Active mode.

Figure 4.17: PSD of velocity fluctuations sampled at P2 and P4. Left column: Active mode, jet only. Right column: Active mode, main flow only.

4.1.6 POD analysis

In order to gain more insights into the unsteady flow behavior and the impact of the synthetic jet, proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) is applied to the PIV results. POD mode analysis offers an effective method to investigate the wake vortex shedding state and its constitution as demonstrated in literature [1–3]. The energy distributions over the spatial eigenmodes for the passive and active test cases are presented in Fig. 4.18. The left plot displays the percentage of the cumulative POD mode energies to the total one and the right plot represents the percentage of each POD mode energy. In the passive test case, approximately 25% of the total energy is contained in each of the first two modes. In contrast, the active case demonstrates a redistribution of energy to lower-rank modes, with the first and second modes individually representing only 10% of the total energy.

Figure 4.18: Energy content of spatial eigenmodes obtained from POD.

Fig. 4.19 shows the first five dominant spatial eigenmodes of velocity fields obtained from POD analysis. The background contour map represents the plane-normal vorticity, ω_z . The left and right columns present the results of the passive and active cases, respectively.

The eigenmodes for the passive test case are in agreement with the results reported by Feng et al. [1] and Gao et al. [3]. They addressed that the first two modes exhibit vorticity concentrations symmetric about the centerline and alternating longitudinally, whereas the third and fourth modes are antisymmetric about the centerline. Konstantinidis et al. [4] addressed that the symmetric vorticity fields (the first and second modes) stand for the Karman vortex with antisymmetric shedding mode, while modes 3 and 4 represent the symmetric spatial small-scale structures.

The eigenmodes for the active case also display the symmetric vorticity fields about the centerline but stretched in the streamwise direction, forming a bow-shaped distribution. The stretched vortex structure means an increase in the temporal space between the vortex-associated velocity fluctuations, presumably causing the slight reduction of peak frequency in the PSD spectra in Fig. 4.16.

For lower-rank eigenmodes, both passive and active cases exhibit the antisymmetric vorticity distribution about the centerline, but their patterns are significantly diversified. The 3rd spatial eigenmode of the passive case shows a pair of round-shape vorticity concentrations shedding from either side of the bar, indicating the simultaneous roll-up of the symmetric shear layer vortex. In the active case, the area behind the bar is filled with longitudinally

Figure 4.19: Spatial eigenmodes obtained from POD. From top to bottom: 1st to 5th modes. Left column: Passive mode. Right: Active mode.

monotonic vorticity concentrations which presumably represent the shear flow between the jet and main flows.

The contributions of the jet and main flows on the global flow field can be individually investigated using the fluorescent PIV results. Fig. 4.20 shows the first five dominant POD spatial eigenmodes of the jet-only (left) and main flow-only (right) flow fields.

The first two modes present a fairly similar structure between the jet and main flow while being diversified from the passive case, suggesting the significant impact of the jet on the main flow behavior.

The 3rd mode of the jet flow exhibits the vorticity concentration antisymmetric about the centerline and longitudinally monotonic. The series of instantaneous reconstructed flow fields using the first 6 POD modes (provided later) revealed that this pattern represents the shear flow at the border of the jet's potential core. The 3rd mode of the main flow shows the typical pattern of the free shear layer originating from the separation zone on the bar, but unlike the passive case, there is no signature of a round-shape recirculation zone behind the bar. In the 4th and 5th modes, the vorticity distribution of the jet exhibits a longitudinally alternating sign, indicating that there are some sort of periodic oscillations within the jet.

Fig. 4.21 shows the instantaneous reconstructed flow fields for the passive (left) and active (right) test cases, using the first 6 spatial POD eigenmodes. Velocity fields at different time instants are displayed from top to bottom in chronological order. T_{shed} represents the expected shedding period ($= 1/f_{shed} = 0.009$ s) for the passive test case. Similarly, Fig. 4.22 shows the instantaneous flow fields reconstructed using either the jet-only (left column) or the main flow-only (right column) recordings for the active test case. Note that the time instant of the main flow-only reconstructed flow fields (Fig. 4.22-right column) aligns with that of main + jet reconstructed flow fields (Fig. 4.21 - right column) as these two datasets are simultaneously recorded. On the other hand, the jet-only reconstructed flow fields are obtained from a separate measurement; hence, the time instant is not synchronized with the others. Nonetheless, the flow fields exhibiting similar phases are displayed for the sake of ease of side-by-side comparison.

Ma et al. [5] addressed that only the first two modes are required for the reconstruction of the regular vortex shedding process, while Konstantinidis et al. [4] reported that the first six modes are needed to distinguish two-pair vortex shedding modes. In the study of Feng et al. [1] who investigated the wake of a circular cylinder with synthetic jet injection used the first four modes to include the characteristics of the synthetic jet. In this study, the first six modes are utilized to ensure the reconstructed flow fields involve both the vortex shedding and synthetic jet flow characteristics.

The time series of the passive test case presented in the left column in Fig. 4.21 demonstrates the antisymmetric shedding process of the Karman vortex. The period for one cycle of the shedding process is found to be slightly shorter than the expected one ($T_{shed} = 110$ Hz).

The flow fields of the active test case presented in the right column verify the radical change in the flow structure. The interaction of the jet with the free shear layer behind both sides of the bar diminishes the formation of the large-scale Karman vortex seen in the passive case. Instead of the large-scale vortex, the jet forms a thin, thread-like shear flow in the bar wake represented by the antisymmetric vorticity concentration about the centerline. The temporal evolution of the vorticity displays the periodic oscillation of the jet. The frequency of the jet oscillation is close to that of the Karman vortex for the passive case, suggesting

Figure 4.20: Spatial eigenmodes obtained from POD for the active test case. From top to bottom: 1st to 5th modes. Left column: jet only field. Right: main flow only field.

Figure 4.21: Instantaneous reconstructed flow fields for the passive (left) and active (right) cases, using the first 6 eigenmodes. T_{shed} is the expected shedding period for the passive case.

Figure 4.22: The jet-only (left) and main flow-only (right) instantaneous reconstructed flow fields for the active test case using the first 6 eigenmodes. T_{shed} is the expected shedding period for the passive case.

that the jet flow undergoes the oscillation of the wake shear layers separating from the bar. Despite the absence of the large-scale Karman vortex due to the disruption by the jet, the instability remains in the form of the oscillating jet.

4.1.7 Turbulence field

Lastly, the turbulence characteristics behind the bar gird are examined in terms of the turbulence intensity, turbulence kinetic energy, and integral length scales.

4.1.7.1 Turbulence intensity and turbulence kinetic energy

Fig. 4.23 displays the turbulence intensity and turbulence kinetic energy fields in the top and bottom rows, respectively. The left and right columns represent the passive and active mode cases. For a quantitative comparison, the transverse-wise distributions of the turbulence intensity and turbulence kinetic energy are presented in Fig. 4.24. Each sub-figure contains three profiles extracted at different locations in the longitudinal direction, $x/D = 2.0, 3.0,$ and 5.0 . The turbulence field for the active case is obtained from the dataset of camera 1 recorded in test case C.

Figure 4.23: Contour maps of velocity magnitude (overlaped with streamlines), longitudinal velocity, transverse velocity for passive (left) and active modes (right). velocity fields of both modes are obtained from camera 1 recordings.

Introducing the synthetic jet, the turbulence intensity in the bar wake is reduced significantly by about 20%. This is mainly due to the higher velocity in the wake resulting from the jet filling the velocity deficit, as seen in Fig. 4.14. In fact, the peak of TKE at $x/D = 2.0$ shows a similar value ($\approx 7 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}^2$) between the passive and active cases whereas the velocity magnitude is much larger for the active case as presented in Fig. 4.15.

Figure 4.24: Profiles of turbulence intensity and turbulence kinetic energy for passive (left) and active (right) cases extracted at $x/D = 2, 3$ and 5 .

The synthetic jet also has a large impact on the diffusion of turbulence kinetic energies both in streamwise and transverse directions. The active case exhibits a near plateau profile at $x/D = 5.0$. Presumably, the thread-like shear flows in the active case, which is addressed in the POD analysis, diffuse much quicker than the large-scale Karman vortices present in the passive case.

4.1.7.2 Integral length scale

Another important parameter describing turbulence characteristics is the integral length scale (ILS), which represents the largest eddy size in the turbulent flow. ILS is obtained from the integral of the normalized velocity auto-correlation function $R(r)$ [6]:

$$R(r) = \frac{\overline{V'_i(x)V'_i(x+r)}}{\left(\overline{V'_i(x)^2}\right)^{1/2} \left(\overline{V'_i(x+r)^2}\right)^{1/2}} \quad (4.4)$$

$$ILS = \int_0^{\infty} R(r) dr \quad (4.5)$$

where x is the point of interest, r is the distance from x , and V'_i is the fluctuating component of the instantaneous velocity. The definition of the denominator in Eq.4.4 is defined based on the method described by Banerjee et al. [7]. If Taylor's hypothesis is valid for the investigated turbulence field, i.e., the turbulent fluctuations at a point are caused by the advection of a frozen turbulence field passing the point, the ILS is obtained by the auto-correlation function in time domain [8].

$$R(\tau) = \frac{\overline{V'_i(t)V'_i(t-\tau)}}{\overline{V'_i^2}} \quad (4.6)$$

$$ILS = |V| \int_0^{\infty} R(\tau) d\tau \quad (4.7)$$

Where τ is the time delay for the auto-correlation function and $|V|$ is the longitudinal mean velocity.

Fig. 4.25 presents the spatial auto-correlation function of the longitudinal (top) and transverse (bottom) velocity components for the passive (left) and active (right) cases. The Spatial auto-correlation is calculated at each transverse point (y/D), which is represented by the color. The auto-correlation is applied in the longitudinal range of $1.5 \leq x/D \leq 6.0$.

Fig. 4.26 shows the temporal auto-correlation function of the longitudinal (top) and transverse (bottom) velocity components for the passive (left) and active (right) cases. The temporal auto-correlation is calculated at every local point. Fig. 4.26 displays those computed at $x/D = 5.0$ for different transverse locations represented by the color. Auto-correlation is computed over 2000 PIV recordings with a fixed time interval of 1.0 ms. For the sake of visibility, the abscissa is truncated at $\tau = 0.01$ s.

In literature, the bounds of integration of the correlation function are chosen differently depending on authors [7, 9, 10]. Following the description by Tritton [10] and O'Neill et al. [9], the bounds of integration of the correlation function are determined from $r = 0$ or $\tau = 0$ to the point where $R(r)$ or $R(\tau)$ crosses zero for the first time.

Fig. 4.27 compares the transverse-wise distribution of the ILS obtained from PIV results using the spatial and temporal auto-correlation methods. The black and red markers represent the passive and active cases, respectively. The ILS computed from the longitudinal and transverse velocity components are displayed separately in the left and right figures. The spatial method is applied to the longitudinal range of $1.5 \leq x/D \leq 6.0$. The temporal method utilizes the time history of velocity fluctuations sampled at $x/D = 5.0$.

Figure 4.25: Spatial auto-correlation of V_x (top) and V_y (bottom) for the passive (left) and active (right) cases.

The auto-correlation function exhibits continuous modulation along the transverse direction. In terms of the longitudinal velocity component, an exponential decay becomes increasingly evident, and cosine-shaped periodic fluctuation is less pronounced as the transverse position approaches the centerline (transitioning from blue to green or from red to green). Such a modulation indicates a more random and less periodic nature of the fluctuation in longitudinal velocity. For the passive test case, the auto-correlation function displays the shortest periodicity pitch around $y/D = \pm 0.7$, resulting in double negative peaks in the transverse-wise ILS distribution in Fig. 4.27.

Concerning the transverse velocity component, towards the centerline, the frequency of the auto-correlation function increases and its amplitude becomes larger. This implies that the transverse velocity fluctuation behind the bar contains deterministic periodicity. The results are in line with the frequency analysis (4.1.5) demonstrating the absence and presence of a peak at vortex shedding frequency in the longitudinal and transverse velocity components. Unlike the longitudinal velocity, the transverse velocity ILS distribution shows a wide deficit region around the centerline Fig. 4.27.

The introduction of the synthetic jet drastically alters the auto-correlation function by ex-

Figure 4.26: Temporal auto-correlation of V_x (top) and V_y (bottom) for the passive (left) and active (right) cases.

Figure 4.27: ILS estimated from the PIV results using the spatial and temporal auto-correlation methods. Left: longitudinal velocity component (V_x). Right: Transverse velocity component (V_y).

tending the periodicity. The ILS distribution suggests that the synthetic jet globally increases the ILS for the longitudinal velocity component, whereas it reduces the ILS for the transverse component.

The back-to-back comparison between spatial and temporal auto-correlation functions reveals a similar trend, supporting a partial applicability of Taylor's hypothesis. The computed ILS shows general agreement outside the wake ($y/D < -1$, $1 < y/D$), with the deviation between the two methods approximately less than 1 mm. The significant discrepancy found in the bar wake ($-1 < y/D < 1$) is attributed to the applicability of the hypothesis not being guaranteed in non-homogeneous turbulent flows where the variation of mean velocity and fluctuating velocity are large compared with the average velocity over the whole flow [11]. Additionally, the relatively coarse temporal resolution (1 KHz) for the turbulence scale and convection velocity can introduce errors in the auto-correlation function thus the values of ILS.

Despite these limitations, applying the temporal auto-correlation method to the PIV data comprising the time-resolved instantaneous velocity fields can provide the local ILS distribution, which might bring an intuitive understanding of ILS evolution. Fig. 4.28 shows the spatial ILS distributions of the longitudinal (top) and transverse (bottom) velocity components from the passive (left) and active (right) test cases. Sampled local time histories of the velocity fluctuation and the auto-correlation function are presented in Fig. 4.29 and 4.30, respectively. The sampling points are (a: $x/D=0.5$, $y/D=1.0$), (b: 2.0, 0.0), (c: 2.0, 1.5), (d: 3.0, 0.0), (e: 5.0, 0.0) and (f: 5.0, 1.5), as indicated in Fig. 4.28.

Figure 4.28: Spatial distribution of ILS for the passive (left) and active (right) cases. Top row: longitudinal component. Bottom row: transverse component.

The ILS from longitudinal velocity shows a large variation within the FOV. Near the throat of the bar grid (location: a), the ILS goes over 200 mm. Presumably, the large scale

of incoming turbulence is associated with the dimension of the wind tunnel duct comprising 200 mm height or width. $2D$ downstream the throat (location: c), this large-scale turbulence structure is broken down into smaller scale sizing around 9 to 10 mm, which corresponds to the diameter of the bar. Further downstream (location: f), the ILS is found to be even smaller, around 5 mm for the passive case and 7 mm for the active case. On the centerline, the ILS from the longitudinal velocity seems to increase downstream, from 5 to 8 mm for the passive case and from 8 to 11 mm for the active case. For the passive case, a peak in ILS (up to 35 mm) exists on the centerline between $2.0 < x/D < 4.0$ (location: d). Although this may be attributed to the Karman vortexes being formed just before this ILS peak spot, the first zero-crossing point in the temporal auto-correlation function ($\tau_{1st\ cross} \approx 0.06$ s) is larger than the shedding period of Karman vortexes ($1/f_{shed} \approx 0.009$ s). In the active case, the ILS in the wake increases monotonically towards downstream.

For the ILS from the transverse velocity, the spatial variation is similar to that of the longitudinal component in the region behind the bar grid throat. A remarkable difference is found around the centerline, where there is no apparent peak spot of a large ILS is observed. Globally the ILS is smaller than that computed from the longitudinal component, which is in agreement with the description of Roach ($ILS_x \approx 1.9 ILS_y$) [8].

4.1.8 Summary

The PIV measurement conducted on the active turbulence grid in the low-speed wind tunnel demonstrated the fundamental capability of the fluorescent particle and examined the unsteady flow structure behind the grid. The multi-constituent flow, composed of the main flow and synthetic jet, was discerned by using standard oil particles and fluorescent particles. The lower intensity of the fluorescent signal caused the peak-locking effect, introducing additional uncertainty amounting to about 3% of the freestream velocity to the result obtained by the fluorescent PIV technique. Nevertheless, the acquired velocity fields retained most of the flow features. The visualization of the mean flow field and application of the POD technique to the time-resolved PIV datasets revealed the synthetic jet occupying the bar wake and forming a shear layer between the jet and the main flow. This promoted the mixing process behind the bar, resulting in quicker diffusion of turbulence kinetic energy. Lastly, the ILS was computed employing the auto-correlation methods in time and space domains. Despite the examined flow being a non-homogenous turbulent flow, a similarity in the auto-correlation functions was observed, suggesting a partial applicability of the time-domain auto-correlation method.

Figure 4.29: Time history of streamwise velocity fluctuation for the passive (left) and active (right) cases sampled at the locations (a) $x/D = 0.5$, $y/D = 1.0$, (b) $x/D = 2.0$, $y/D = 0.0$, (c) $x/D = 2.0$, $y/D = 1.5$, (d) $x/D = 5.0$, $y/D = 0.0$, and (e) $x/D = 5.0$, $y/D = 1.5$.

Figure 4.30: Auto-correlation function $R(\tau)$ of longitudinal velocity fluctuation for the passive (left) and active (right) cases sampled at the locations (a) $x/D = 0.5, y/D = 1.0$, (b) $x/D = 2.0, y/D = 0.0$, (c) $x/D = 2.0, y/D = 1.5$, (d) $x/D = 5.0, y/D = 0.0$, and (e) $x/D = 5.0, y/D = 1.5$.

4.2 Linear cascade tests in a high-speed wind tunnel (S-1/C)

This section presents the results of PIV measurements on the high-speed linear cascades tested in the S-1/C facility.

The first subsection focuses on the measurements conducted on the blade-to-blade (B2B) plane upstream of the cascade. The effect of image preprocessing, the number of samples, the separation time of double pulses, and the size of the interrogation window on the mean and turbulence quantities are assessed and the results are compared against CFD simulation, five-hole-probe (5HP), and hot-wire (HW) probe measurements.

The second subsection discusses the measurement results on the B2B plane within the cascade passage and downstream. The lack of seeding in the proximity to the blade suction surface is addressed and the possible cause is analyzed by Lagrangian particle tracking simulation. The mean quantities are compared against steady RANS and 5HP measurements. Extensive attention is given to the velocity, vorticity, and turbulence profiles in the blade wake.

Finally, the third subsection addresses the outcomes of the measurements on the cascade outlet plane (COP). The secondary flow structure near the cascade endwall is quantitatively characterized in terms of the mean Mach number, yaw angle, and pitch angle fields. The componentality analysis on the turbulence fields provides insights into the turbulence anisotropy of the flow.

4.2.1 B2B Upstream

This subsection presents the results of PIV measurements conducted on the midspan B2B plane upstream of the cascade.

4.2.1.1 Recorded images

This subsection focuses on reviewing the quality of the raw particle images, with specific attention given to two key parameters: particle image sizes and seeding densities, as these significantly impact the attainment of accurate measurements. (2.6.2.2). In contrast to artificially generated images or experimentally captured images in a simplified measurement setup, the images obtained in the current test cases lack "perfect" quality due to various factors including equipment availability, specific geometries of the test article, operational constraints of the facility, and challenging flow conditions.

Fig. 4.31 shows a schematic of camera orientation for B2B upstream PIV and exemplary particle images recorded during a test at the nominal flow condition. The top row displays raw images, the middle row shows pre-processed images, and the bottom row presents zoomed views of the areas indicated by red rectangles in the middle row images.

A direct incident of laser sheet generates a strong flare on the blade surface near the leading edge as shown in the white saturated areas of the camera 1 image. For camera 2, the reflection near the leading edge is less evident thanks to the camera angle inversely inclined. The round-shape bright area that appears in the top right in the camera 2 image is a reflection of the camera 1 lens. The lens is illuminated by the flare on the blade surface, then the lens image is reflected on the surface of the endwall window. The thick bright line horizontally distributed in the middle of the images is a reflection of the endwall cavity slot which probably

Figure 4.31: Exemplary particle images from camera 1 and camera 2. Top row: raw images. Middle row: pre-processed images. Bottom row: Zoomed views of the area indicated with the red rectangles in the middle row images.

is not uniformly coated with matte-black paint. While most of these undesired background signals are removed by image preprocessing, some residual background noise remains.

Within the zoomed view, particle images sizing between 3-10 pixels are observed. The variation in particle size is due to the opened lens aperture resulting in a defocusing effect within the laser sheet thickness. The particle size can be tuned by changing the optical magnification, lens aperture, image-focusing, camera sensor size, tracer particle size and its refraction index, and illumination intensity. For the present study, the tracer particle size and its refraction index are constrained by the flow traceability and availability of the seeding material and equipment. The optical magnification is maximized by using a macro lens and placing the camera as close as possible to the investigation area. The pulse intensity of the laser is limited to 55% of its maximum output due to the damage threshold of the laser endoscope. The lens aperture is fully opened otherwise the scattering light from particles is too weak to be captured.

Fig. 4.32 shows the probability density function of the particle displacement for each velocity component. No distinctive peak at integer value is observed, indicating there is no serious peak-locking effect present in this measurement.

Figure 4.32: Probability density function (PDF) of particle displacement. Left to right: Axial, tangential, and radial velocity components.

The image seeding density is controlled by adjusting the injected seeding mass flow. For the present test case, the seeding mass flow is limited by the capacity of the seeding generator. The reusability of particles circulating the closed-loop wind tunnel is marginal since the air inside the test rig has to be continuously extracted by a vacuum pump to maintain a low-density (therefore low-Reynolds) environment.

Fig. 4.33 presents the time-averaged seeding density estimated using a built-in function of *Davis11* PIV software, expressed in particle-per-pixel (ppp). The estimation algorithm exhibits a high sensitivity to the image background noise, resulting in an overestimation of seeding density near the blade leading edge in the camera 1 frame and a part of the freestream region in the camera 2 frame where the image is strongly affected by reflections. Excluding these areas, the seeding density is estimated to be approximately 0.004-0.005 ppp in the upstream freestream region. Based on Fig. 2.53, the expected measurement uncertainty in particle displacement for this seeding density is around 0.002 pixel for a 64 pixel interrogation window and 0.005 pixel for 32 pixel interrogation window, which is sufficiently small and can be neglected.

Figure 4.33: Time-averaged seeding density (ppp) for the nominal flow condition.

4.2.1.2 Effect of Image preprocessing

Table 4.3 lists the image preprocessing setups investigated for the present test case. Each preprocessing scheme is applied to the 500 PIV images recorded at the nominal test condition ($M_{out,is} = 0.9$, $Re_{out,is} = 70k$) equipped with the upstream TG. Fig. 4.34 and 4.35 show exemplary raw and pre-processed images captured with cameras 1 and 2. The majority of reflections are removed except for the areas where the aforementioned intensive reflections appear.

The histograms of Fig. 4.34 and 4.35 show pixel intensity distributions normalized by the maximum intensity of each image. Note that the vertical axis is a logarithmic scale. Pre03 - Pre07 show very similar intensity distributions. The effect of intensity normalization applied in the Pre08 setting significantly increases the particle signal level as well as the residual background noises.

Table 4.3: Tested image preprocessing schemes

Scheme	Pre00	Pre01	Pre02	Pre03	Pre04	Pre05	Pre06	Pre07	Pre08
Temporal sliding average	-	-	All	All	21	-	21	All	All
Spatial smoothing	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3x3 gauss. LP filter	3x3 gauss. LP filter
Intensity normalization	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11 px
Spatial sliding average	11 px	5 px	-	11 px	11 px	-	-	11 px	11 px
BG removal with anisotropic diffusion	-	-	-	-	-	-	200 iter.	-	-
BG removal with POD	-	-	-	-	-	5 modes	-	-	-

Figure 4.34: Images and intensity histograms with different preprocessing setups, raw, Pre00, Pre01, Pre02, and Pre03.

Figure 4.35: Images and intensity histograms with different preprocessing setups, Pre04, Pre05, Pre06, Pre07, and Pre08.

The effect of image preprocessing is evaluated based on the characteristics of the resultant mean and statistical velocity information. For the vector computation, a multi-pass cross-correlation method, initiating the evaluation with 128 pixel square windows and concluding with 64 pixel square windows, is employed. For the last pass, the window overlap is set to 50%. The validity of the computed vector is evaluated with a spatial median filter, velocity magnitude threshold, and standard deviation threshold. The fraction of valid vectors out of 500 instantaneous velocity fields obtained with different image preprocessing is summarized in Fig. 4.36. The Pre02 - Pre07 image preprocessing settings improved the fraction of valid vectors to over 78%, recovering approximately 10% of vectors compared to the raw images.

Figure 4.36: Fraction of valid vectors over 500 instantaneous velocity fields with different image preprocessing.

Fig. 4.37 and 4.38 illustrates contour maps of the in-plane Mach number and yaw angle (β) computed from the corresponding pre-processed images. The blank areas are masked by the vector validation. The extended masked region observed in the result from the raw image indicates the negative impact of the background noise on the computation of valid vectors. The image preprocessing effectively corrects spurious distributions of Mach number and yaw angle, represented by the smoother contour lines around at $x/C_{ax} = -0.2$.

Fig. 4.39 presents the pitchwise distributions of the in-plane Mach number and yaw angle extracted at $x/C_{ax} = -0.5$ from Fig. 4.37 and 4.38. The results of the 5HP measurement and RANS simulation are also included for comparison. The Mach number and yaw angle profiles obtained from the pre-processed images exhibit a small shift from the raw image results around $y/g_{local} = 0.5$. The removal of the camera lens reflection from the camera 2 image is attributed to the shift. Among the preprocessing settings, Pre08 shows noisier results compared to the others. Overall, the effect of image preprocessing on the mean flow field is relatively small, the difference from the raw image result is below 0.03 for Mach number and 0.05 degree for yaw angle.

Fig. 4.40 illustrates contour maps of the two-component TI computed using different image preprocessing setups. The excessively high TI distributions ($TI > 3$) near the blade trailing edge ($C_{ax} > -0.2$) aren't reliable as the estimated local uncertainty is too high for quantitative turbulence intensity evaluations. The Pre08 result exhibits a suspiciously high

Figure 4.37: Contour maps of in-plane Mach number using different preprocessing setups.

Figure 4.38: Contour maps of in-plane yaw angle using different preprocessing setups.

Figure 4.39: Pitchwise distributions of in-plane Mach number and yaw angle computed using different preprocessing settings. The distribution profiles are extracted at $x/C_{ax} = -0.5$.

TI spot at around $-0.5 < x/C_{ax}, 0.2 < y/g < 0.6$, indicating its negative impact on the measurement reliability. This is due to the intensity normalization amplifying the noise signal originating from the camera lens reflection.

Fig. 4.41 presents the pitchwise distribution of the TI for different image preprocessing settings. The blue triangle markers represent the HW traverse measurement. The plot on the right displays an enlarged view of the left plot. Except for Pre08, a common trend of TI distribution is observed regardless of different preprocessing settings. The discrepancy of TI attributed to the preprocessing setting is below 0.2%.

To determine the optimal image preprocessing setup, it is essential to consider both the lead time and computation time required by each preprocessing setup.

The POD background removal is the most time-consuming approach due to the operation of singular value decomposition over a large dataset and the additional file transfer processes to handle the dataset between different software. For example, in a scenario where 2000 pairs of 4M pixel images with 12-bit depth are recorded in *Davis* format, and the POD background removal is applied in *MATLAB*, followed by vector computation is performed in *Davis*, the entire process takes about one day using an *Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-3740QM* CPU.

The background removal with anisotropic diffusion ranks as the second most time-consuming scheme, as it involves multiple iterative image processing to compute each instantaneous background image. Setting the number of iterations to 200 as recommended in the software manual [12] resulted in the computation time of about 20 hours using the aforementioned CPU.

The sliding time average (moving time window average) needs to compute the windowed time average field for every time instant, resulting in a higher computational cost than the average over the entire dataset.

Considering the processing time penalty and the relatively minor discrepancy compared to other settings, the Pre03 setting, which involves the time-averaged image subtraction and spatial sliding average subtraction, is adopted as the standard image preprocessing setting for the following analysis.

Figure 4.40: Contour maps of in-plane two-component turbulence intensity using different preprocessing setup.

Figure 4.41: Pitchwise distributions of turbulence intensity computed using different preprocessing settings.

4.2.1.3 Effect of the number of recordings

The dependency of mean and turbulence quantities on the number of PIV recordings is evaluated in this subsection. The velocity field is computed using the Pre03 image preprocessing and multi-pass cross-correlation scheme aforementioned in the previous subsection. Fig. 4.42 and Fig. 4.43 present the mean in-plane Mach number and yaw angle fields computed using 100, 500, and 2000 PIV recordings. The convergence histories of the velocity magnitude extracted at nine locations (P1[-0.5, -0.5], P2[-0.3, -0.5], P3[-0.1, -0.5], P4[-0.5, 0], P5[-0.3, 0], P6[-0.1, 0], P7[-0.5, 0.5], P8[-0.3, 0.5], P9[-0.1, 0.5]) are plotted in Fig. 4.44 (See Fig. 4.42 for the locations of the extract points). Subfigure (A) shows the convergence of mean velocity magnitude with the shaded area representing the 95% confidence interval. Subfigure (B) presents the convergence of 95% confidence interval normalized by the local mean velocity magnitude in solid lines, and RMS of the velocity magnitude in dashed lines). The mean velocity magnitude exhibits a convergence to a deterministic value followed by a confidence interval below 0.25% after averaging over 500 recordings.

Figure 4.42: Contour maps of in-plane Mach number for different numbers of PIV recordings.

The pitchwise distributions of mean in-plane Mach number and yaw angle computed from different numbers of PIV recordings are shown in Fig. 4.45. The distribution profiles are

Figure 4.43: Contour maps of yaw angle for different numbers of PIV recordings.

Figure 4.44: (A) Convergence history of mean in-plane velocity magnitude. The shaded area indicates 95% confidence interval. (B) Convergence history of 95% confidence interval and RMS of in-plane velocity magnitude.

extracted at constant axial location $C_{ax} = -0.5$ as indicated by the dashed line in Fig. 4.42. The results of the 5HP measurement and 2D steady RANS simulation are also included for comparison. The profiles exhibit convergence of the mean quantities with an increase in the number of PIV recordings. The yaw angle requires more samples to achieve a converged result compared to the Mach number. Using 1000 PIV recordings seems to be a reasonable approach to have a reasonably converged result.

Figure 4.45: Pitchwise distributions of mean in-plane Mach number and yaw angle computed from different numbers of PIV recordings.

Fig. 4.46 presents the turbulence intensity fields computed over different numbers of PIV recordings. The pitchwise distributions at $C_{ax} = -0.5$ are shown in Fig. 4.47. With only 100 samples, several peaks are found in the freestream region, indicating the computed TI field is not converged. Similar to the mean quantities, the TI field exhibits reasonable convergence for numbers of recordings exceeding 1000.

Figure 4.46: 2D contours of Turbulence intensity for different number of PIV recordings.

4.2.1.4 Effect of pulse separation time

In order to evaluate the effect of the pulse separation time on the measurement result, four sets of 500 PIV images are recorded with different pulse separation time, $0.75 \mu s$, $1.5 \mu s$, $3.0 \mu s$, and $7.5 \mu s$ for the design flow condition ($M_{out,is} = 0.9$, $Re_{out,is} = 70k$, and with the

Figure 4.47: Pitchwise distribution of turbulence intensity computed from different numbers of PIV recordings.

Table 4.4: Separation time setting and estimated particle displacement at cascade inlet.

Pulse separation time [μs]	Particle displacement [pixel] (Upstream freestream)
0.75	5.4
1.5	10.9
3.0	21.7
7.5	50.7

TG). The estimated particle displacements corresponding to each pulse separation time t_s are addressed in Table 4.4. The velocity fields are computed using the Pre03 image preprocessing and multi-pass cross-correlation scheme as aforementioned in the previous subsection.

Fig. 4.48 and 4.49 show the in-plane Mach number and yaw angle fields obtained using PIV images recorded with different separation times. For the largest t_s , the blank region near the blades is significantly extended. This is due to the loss of particle pairs between successive frames as the particles exit the camera frame after a long separation time.

Fig. 4.50 presents the pitchwise distributions of the in-plane Mach number and yaw angle extracted at $C_{ax} = -0.5$ compared with the 5HP measurement and 2D steady RANS prediction. The shortest separation time yields the distributions of both quantities deviating from those with longer separation time. This can be explained by the dependency of the systematic uncertainty of measured velocity Δ_V on the separation time. Recalling the Eq. 2.125 leads to:

$$\Delta_V = \sqrt{\frac{X_d^2}{t_s^2} \Delta_{F_s}^2 + \frac{F_s^2}{t_s^2} \Delta_{X_d}^2 + \frac{F_s^2 X_d^2}{t_s^4} \Delta_{t_s}^2} \quad (4.8)$$

Figure 4.48: Contour maps of mean in-plane Mach number with different pulse separation times.

Figure 4.49: Contour maps of mean yaw angle with different pulse separation times.

Figure 4.50: Pitchwise distribution of 2D Mach number and yaw angle with different pulse separation time.

When t_s is the only parameter to be changed in the experimental setup, the scaling factor F_s and its uncertainty Δ_{F_s} are constant. The ratio of particle displacement to the separation time X_d/t_s is the true flow velocity V which is also a constant value for a given flow condition. The remaining unknown is the uncertainty of particle displacement Δ_{X_d} . Fig. 4.51 (adopted from [13]) shows the measurement uncertainty for different interrogation window sizes and particle image displacement using single-pass and multi-pass evaluation schemes. For single-pass evaluation, the measurement uncertainty increases due to the loss of particle pairs between successive frames as the particle displacement is increased. This is why a general rule of thumb suggests particle displacement to be equal to or less than one-quarter of the interrogation window for single-pass evaluation [14]. For multi-pass evaluation algorithms, this rule applies only for the first pass therefore the IW size for the following path can be reduced iteratively. As a result, a multi-pass evaluation scheme offers the uncertainty of particle displacement Δ_{X_d} being nearly independent of a variation of X_d .

Figure 4.51: Measurement uncertainty as a function of particle image displacement [13].

Considering X_d is solely a function of t_s for the given flow condition, one can treat Δ_{X_d} as a constant value as well. Furthermore, it is reasonable to assume the uncertainty of Δ_{t_s} to be a constant over the range of the examined t_s . 2.6.2.3. Replacing these terms with C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 for sake of simplicity, Eq. 4.8 becomes:

$$\Delta_V = \sqrt{C_1 + \frac{C_2}{t_s^2} + \frac{C_3}{t_s^2}} \quad (4.9)$$

Eq. 4.9 tells that for the situation where the separation time is the only parameter to be changed, the longer separation time yields smaller measurement uncertainty. However, increasing separation time, i.e. particle displacement, introduces a higher risk of having bias errors due to out-of-plane loss of particle pairs and curved streamlines. Furthermore, the estimation of turbulence intensity is also affected since flow fluctuation in a small time scale is not captured if the separation time is longer than half of the fluctuation period.

Fig. 4.52 presents the contour maps of the in-plane two-component turbulence intensity for different separation times and Fig. 4.53 shows their pitchwise distributions extracted at

$C_{ax} = -0.5$. The HW probe measurement result and estimations using Roach's correlation [8] are also plotted in the figure. The correlation formula is introduced as:

$$TI = C \left(\frac{x}{d} \right)^{(-5/7)} \quad (4.10)$$

where x is the distance downstream of the grid (note that the cascade is inclined with respect to the grid orientation) and d is the representative grid dimension. In this test case, the rod diameter of the turbulence grid (2 mm) is used for this value as suggested in the literature [8]. The constant C is a function of the grid geometry and Reynolds number. For parallel array grids comprising round rods, the value of 0.80 is proposed by Roach.

Figure 4.52: 2D contours of turbulence intensity with different pulse separation time.

Figure 4.53: Pitchwise distribution of 2D turbulence intensity with different pulse separation time.

The shortest separation time exhibits a substantially differentiated TI field compared to the longer separation times, presumably due to a higher systematic uncertainty as discussed above. For the separation times exceeding $1.5 \mu\text{s}$, the TI fields show similar trends, with a maximum variation of about 0.2% at $C_{ax} = -0.5$. While the TI measured by PIV ranges from

1.5 to 1.8%, the HW and Roach's correlation with $C = 0.8$ reaches 2.5 to 2.8%. The positive slope along with the increase in the pitchwise coordinate y/g represents a TI decay in the streamwise distance downstream of the turbulence grid. Modifying the constant C to 0.55, a good matching is observed between the correlation and PIV for $t_s = 3.0$ or 7.5. The similar decay trend of the TI due to the inclination of the cascade relative to the turbulence grid is also reported from similar experimental studies [15]. The determination of optimal separation time for turbulence field measurements is addressed in the later subsection (4.2.1.6) as it has to be coupling with the interrogation window size.

4.2.1.5 Effect of interrogation window size

The effect of the interrogation window (IW) size for the vector computation on the vector field is investigated by varying the final window size between 32×32 and 96×96 pixel. The number of passes is set to three. The initial window size is set to 128×128 pixel and the final window overlap is fixed to 50% through the cases. The other parameters in the recording and processing setups are maintained the same as in the aforementioned subsections.

Fig. 4.54 and 4.55 present the contour maps of the mean in-plane Mach number and yaw angle. The pitchwise distributions extracted at $C_{ax} = -0.5$ are shown in Fig. 4.56. While the noise is amplified for the smallest IW size, the deterministic values of both the Mach number and yaw angle are well-matched between different IW sizes.

Figure 4.54: Contour maps of mean Mach number computed using different IW sizes.

Fig. 4.57 and Fig. 4.58 respectively present the contour maps and pitchwise distributions of the in-plane two-component TI obtained with different IW sizes. The latter is extracted at $C_{ax} = -0.5$. Contrary to the mean flow quantities, the turbulence field changes radically by increasing the IW from 32 to 64 pixel. The pitchwise distribution of turbulence intensity for IW = 32 pixel shows the opposite trend against the expected turbulence decay: TI is supposed to decrease towards negative y/g as the distance from the upstream TG increases. The doubtful result obtained by 32 pixel IW size is due to the lack of particles in the small IW. As discussed in 4.2.1.1, the current setup can not support a higher seeding density due to the limited number of seeding generators and the low-Reynolds testing environment requiring a continuous air extraction from the wind tunnel.

While the smallest IW size is limited by the particle image density, the upper limit is also imposed by the spatial low-pass filtering effect on the velocity field. As the velocity

Figure 4.55: Contour maps of mean yaw angle computed using different IW sizes.

Figure 4.56: Pitchwise distributions of in-plane Mach number and yaw angle computed using different IW sizes.

computed with PIV algorithms is based on the average displacement of the particle group in the IW, turbulent structures with length scales smaller than the IW size are filtered out. According to the study of Spencer et al. [16], the effect of spatial low-pass filtering exceeds 5% on the RMS velocity. The systematically lower turbulence intensity for the result of 96 pixel IW compared to that of 64 pixel IW is presumably due to this spatial filtering effect.

Figure 4.57: Contour maps of turbulence intensity computed using different IW sizes.

Figure 4.58: Pitchwise distributions of turbulence intensity computed using different IW sizes.

4.2.1.6 Convergence of turbulence level

The previous subsections suggest a careful consideration of the separation time and IW size, as they have a considerable effect on the measured TI.

The TIs measured with different separation times t_s and different IW sizes for the design flow condition are shown in Fig. 4.59. The horizontal axis is expressed in the mean particle displacement ($\overline{X_d}$) corresponding to the different separation times (see Table 4.4 for conversion). The markers represent the spatial mean of the TI over a rectangle area covering $-0.6 < x/C_{ax} < -0.2$, $-0.4 < y/g < 0.6$ and the error bar indicates the standard deviation of spatial variations within the averaging window.

Figure 4.59: Estimated turbulence intensity as a function of the nominal particle image displacement $X_{d,nom}$ for different interrogation window sizes D_{IW} .

The experimental data points are fitted with a curve defined by Scharonowski et al. [17] as:

$$TI_{meas} = \sqrt{TI_{turb}^2 + \frac{\Delta_{X_d}^2}{X_d^2}} \quad (4.11)$$

where TI_{meas} is the measured turbulence intensity directly given by PIV, TI_{turb} is the true turbulence intensity of the flow, and Δ_{X_d} is the random uncertainty of particle displacement. When there are multiple datasets of TI_{meas} for different \bar{X}_d , the two unknowns, TI_{turb} and Δ_{X_d} , can be estimated from a curve fitting of Eq. 4.11 to the scatter plot of measurement data.

The data points and fitted curve depict the trend of turbulence intensity with increases in particle displacement. For $X_d > 20$, data points from all three IW sizes overlap, indicating that the measured TI becomes less sensitive to the interrogation window size. The curve fitting parameters, summarized in Table 4.5, show that TI_{turb} computed with different IW sizes also converges to 1.75%. The excessive values of Δ_{X_d} are due to the limited points available for fitting. The convergence trend and the curve fitting parameters suggest setting the mean particle displacement to 20 pixels, corresponding to a separation time of $3.0 \mu s$ for the current PIV setup. 64 pixel IW size is a good compromise between the spatial resolution and uncertainty level.

4.2.1.7 Nominal PIV setting for on- and off-design flow conditions

Table 4.6 summarizes the nominal PIV settings used for the image recordings and processing to obtain results for both on- and off-design flow conditions. While these settings generally

Table 4.5: Turbulence intensity and random error in pixel displacement estimated from curve fitting.

IW size	TI_{turb}	Δ_{X_d}
32pixel	1.748 %	13.00 pixel
64pixel	1.774 %	6.09 pixel
96pixel	1.741 %	4.01 pixel

align with suggestions derived from the aforementioned parametric studies, certain parameters of the image recording settings, such as the pulse separation time, were predetermined and may not necessarily represent the optimum values.

Table 4.6: Nominal PIV setting for B2B upstream measurements

Parameter	Setting
Particle image size	3 - 10 pixels (Constrained)
Seeding density	0.004 - 0.005 ppp
Image preprocessing	Temporal sliding average subtraction (All images) Spatial sliding average subtraction (11 pixels)
Number of samples	2000
Pulse separation time	1.5 μ s (for $M_{out,is} = 0.90$) 1.8 μ s (for $M_{out,is} = 0.70$)
Interrogation window size	64×64 pixel

4.2.1.8 Uncertainty analysis

This subsection provides the uncertainty of PIV results computed using the nominal setting addressed in the previous subsection 4.2.1.7. Fig. 4.60, 4.61, and 4.62 present the type A and type B standard uncertainties (1σ), and the combined uncertainty with 95% confidence interval (1.96σ) for the velocity magnitude, yaw angle, and pitch angle measured by PIV at the design flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k$, $M_{out,is} = 0.90$ with the upstream TG). The uncertainty of velocity magnitude is normalized by the local mean velocity magnitude. The summary of uncertainty for the B2B upstream measurement is shown in Table 4.7.

The excessively high uncertainty observed in the region near the blade leading edge is due to the intense light reflection or the no illumination as the light sheet is halted by the blade. The vertical stripe pattern observed in type B and combined uncertainty fields is attributed to the fringe pattern present in the light sheet. Arguably, the fringe is attributed to a laser beam interference occurring through the optics in the endoscope cylinder.

The combined uncertainties of the velocity magnitude and yaw angle are below 2.5% and 1.5 degrees, reasonable values for PIV measurements. On the other hand, the pitch angle uncertainty exhibits a much higher level amounting up to 5.5 degrees. The main reason for the difference in the uncertainty level between yaw and pitch flow angle is the stereoscopic camera arrangement used for this study.

Figure 4.60: Uncertainties of velocity magnitude $|V|$ measured by PIV for the design flow condition. From left to right: Type A, Type B, and Combined uncertainty. The values are normalized with the local mean velocity magnitude.

Figure 4.61: Uncertainties of yaw angle β measured by PIV for the design flow condition. From left to right: Type A, Type B, and Combined uncertainty.

Figure 4.62: Uncertainties of pitch angle γ measured by PIV for the design flow condition. From left to right: Type A, Type B, and Combined uncertainty.

Fig. 4.63 shows a relative error e_{SR} between out-of-plane component and in-plane component depending on the angle between two cameras for symmetric rotational setup [18]. The error ratio is expressed as a function of the camera angle $\alpha = \alpha_1 = \alpha_2$ and the ratio of in-plane coordinate to the object-to-lens distance y/d .

$$e_{SR} = \sqrt{\frac{\cos^2(\alpha) [1 + (y/d_0)^2 \sin^2(\alpha)]}{\sin^2(\alpha) + (y/d_0)^2 \cos^4(\alpha)}} \quad (4.12)$$

To obtain three velocity components with equal velocity reconstruction error, one should choose the angle between two cameras to be around 90 degrees ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 45$ degree) which yields the error ratio of 1. For the present test case, however, the camera angles has to be reduced to $\alpha_1 = 20.89$ degree and $\alpha_2 = 19.02$ degree to avoid interference of cameras with the laser endoscope and calibration plate traverse system. As a result, the estimated error ratio amounts to 3.15, indicating that the uncertainty in the out-of-plane velocity component (V_{rad}) is amplified more than three times higher than that in the in-plane velocity components (V_{axi} and V_{tan}). Due to the excessive uncertainty level, presentations of the quantities involving the out-of-plane velocity component (V_{rad}) are excluded from this thesis. Nevertheless, the employment of the stereoscopic PIV system is beneficial to eliminate the perspective error present in 2D2C planar PIV techniques.

Figure 4.63: The stereoscopic PIV system and the ratio between the x -component (out-of-plane) and the y -component (in-plane) particle displacement errors e_{SR} . The figures are adopted from Lee et al. [18]

4.2.1.9 Results of on- and off- design flow conditions

Fig. 4.64, 4.65, 4.66 show the mean in-plane Mach number, mean yaw angle, and TI fields for on- and off-design conditions. Their pitchwise distributions extracted at two axial locations

Table 4.7: Overview of uncertainties for B2B upstream PIV measurements. Type A and Type B uncertainties are expressed as the standard uncertainty (1σ), whereas the combined uncertainty is expanded to cover 95% confidence interval (1.96σ). For the velocity components, the uncertainties are presented in both physical unit and normalized unit (percentage of local mean velocity magnitude).

Quantity	Symbol	Unit	Uncertainty in freestream		
			Type A	Type B	Combined (95% CI)
Axial velocity	V_{axi}	m/s	0.07 (0.04%)	1.84 (1.11%)	3.61 (2.18%)
Tangential velocity	V_{tan}	m/s	0.07 (0.04%)	1.84 (1.11%)	3.62 (2.18%)
Radial velocity	V_{rad}	m/s	0.14 (0.08%)	5.88 (3.55%)	11.53 (6.96%)
Velocity magnitude (2D, in-plane)	$ V_{2D} $	m/s	0.07 (0.04%)	1.84 (1.12%)	3.61 (2.19%)
Velocity magnitude (3D)	$ V_{3D} $	m/s	0.07 (0.04%)	1.89 (1.14%)	3.70 (2.24%)
Yaw angle	β	deg	0.01	0.79	1.54
Pitch angle	γ	deg	0.06	2.53	4.95
Turbulence intensity (2D)	TI_{2D}	%	-	-	0.04
Turbulence intensity (3D)	TI_{3D}	%	-	-	0.06

$x/C_{ax} = -0.2$ and $C_{ax} = -0.5$ are presented in Fig. 4.67, 4.68, 4.69. For the design flow condition, PIV results are compared with traverse measurements of 5HP and HW carried out at $x/C_{ax} = -0.5$. The global trend in the flow field as a function of the flow condition is summarized by area-averaged values presented in Fig. 4.70 and 4.70. The error bars represent the variations of the quantities within the averaging window.

For the same outlet Mach number, a slightly higher Mach number is measured for high Reynolds number cases ($Re_{out, is} = 120k$, dashed lines) compared to the low Re cases ($Re_{out, is} = 70k$, solid lines). The slope in the pitchwise distribution of Mach number and yaw angle is attributed to the orientation of the linear cascade mounted with an angle with respect to the incoming flow. The variation within one blade pitch is approximately 0.05 for Mach number and 1 degree for yaw angle. Approaching the cascade, the blade potential effect is pronounced in a distinctive sine-wave pattern in both Mach number and yaw angle fields.

In the yaw angle fields, a systematic offset of approximately 1 degree is observed between the cases with and without the TG. This discrepancy can be attributed to the different lengths of the top and bottom walls of the inlet duct caused by the inclined orientation of the cascade. In the absence of the TG, a laminar boundary layer develops over the walls until it reaches the cascade. The boundary layer is thicker on the top wall which has a longer length from the duct inlet to the cascade row. Consequently, the boundary layer blockage effect at the cascade inlet becomes asymmetric between the top and bottom wall regions, leading to a skewed inlet flow angle distribution. Installing the TG, the laminar boundary layer should be disrupted and a thinner turbulent boundary layer is expected to restart after the grid [19]. As a result, the blockage effect is mitigated and the mean inlet flow angle aligns to the duct. Another cause of the offset in the flow angle can be due to a rotational misalignment of the calibration target. To install or remove the TG, the PIV cameras had to be dismantled, necessitating a new image calibration.

The TI fields present a nonuniform distribution with some spurious peaks in the 2D colormap. Nonetheless, the variations are within a reasonable range (0.25%) and PIV measurements globally align with the anticipated increase in turbulence levels resulting from the installation of the TG. The measured value without the TG is close to the natural inlet turbulence intensity of the facility (0.9%) reported in [20]. The systematic offset between PIV and HW results is attributed to the filtering effect of PIV, which disregards the contribution of turbulence whose scale is too small to be resolved with the given IW size. The area-averaged data suggests that there is no serious Mach number or Reynolds number effect on the incoming TI.

Lastly, the ILS is estimated using the spatial auto-correlation method previously described in section 4.1.7.2. Fig. 4.72-left depicts the streamlines overlaid on the contour map of mean velocity magnitude for the design flow condition. Instantaneous spatial distributions of the streamwise velocity fluctuation are extracted along each streamline whose color is associated with the starting pitchwise coordinate ($-0.1 \leq y/g \leq 0.8$). The axial range of streamlines is limited between $x/C_{ax} = -0.65$ and $x/C_{ax} = -0.15$. The spatial auto-correlation function is computed for each instantaneous velocity fluctuation distribution and then averaged over 2000 recordings before the spatial integration.

Fig. 4.72-right presents the estimated ILS for on- and off-design flow conditions. At a glance, a large variation of ILS is observed between different flow conditions when the TG is

Figure 4.64: 2D Mach number fields for on- and off- design flow conditions.

Figure 4.65: Yaw angle fields for on- and off- design flow conditions.

Figure 4.66: Two-component turbulence intensity fields for on- and off- design flow conditions.

Figure 4.67: Pitchwise distributions of in-plane Mach number extracted at $x/C_{ax} = -0.20$ and -0.50 for on- and off- design flow conditions.

Figure 4.68: Pitchwise distributions of Yaw angle extracted at $x/C_{ax} = -0.20$ and -0.50 for on- and off- design flow conditions.

Figure 4.69: Pitchwise distributions of turbulence intensity (in-plane) extracted at $x/C_{ax} = -0.20$ and -0.50 for on- and off-design flow conditions.

Figure 4.70: Area-average of in-plane Mach number and yaw angle for on- and off-design flow conditions. Averaging area covers $-0.6 < x/C_{ax} < -0.2$, $-0.4 < y/g < 0.6$.

Figure 4.71: Area-average of in-plane turbulence intensity for on- and off-design flow conditions. Averaging area covers $-0.6 < x/C_{ax} < -0.2$, $-0.4 < y/g < 0.6$.

not installed. Increasing the Mach number from 0.70 to 0.90, the ILS decreases from about 6-7 mm to 2-3 mm. With the TG installed, the variation in the ILS depending on the flow condition is reduced to about 1 mm.

Fig. 4.73 illustrates the auto-correlation functions for the investigated flow conditions. The curve color corresponds to the streamline at different pitchwise positions presented in Fig. 4.72. The auto-correlation function for the cases with the TG depicts a smooth exponential decay, suggesting that the turbulence fluctuation constitutes a relatively large-scale pattern. In contrast, without the TG, the auto-correlation function exhibits a sudden reduction near the zero spatial-lag region. Furthermore, there appears to be a Reynolds number effect on the ILS, as indicated by a larger area under the curve for the cases of $Re_{out, is} = 70k$. Perhaps, there might be large-scale fluctuations persisting in the flow when the Reynolds number is sufficiently low.

Figure 4.72: Left: Streamlines used to extract instantaneous velocity fluctuations for computation of ILS. Right: Pitchwise distribution of ILS.

Figure 4.73: Auto-correlation function computed along streamlines.

Table 4.8 summarizes the ILS reported from literature considered the same wind tunnel and TG. Michálek et al. [20] estimated the ILS by means of cross-HW probe adopting Taylor's frozen turbulence approximation [21]. They claimed that the ILS with the TG corresponds to the grid mesh size (12 mm) or the order of magnitude of the endwall boundary layer thickness. Without the TG, the ILS went up to 0.5 m, presumably associated with a large-scale pattern developed through the inlet duct whose channel height is approximately 0.5 m. Discarding this significantly large-scale content, they found the ILS to be about 30 mm which is comparable size of the inlet boundary layer thickness. Similar ILS values were obtained by Pastorino et al. [22] from HW measurements applying the zero-frequency extrapolation in the PSD. They showed that the ILS without the TG can diversify from 14 mm to 40 mm depending on the averaging spectra range for zero-extrapolation. In the study of Miglio [23], the ILS was deduced from the decay of TI, using the following relations.

$$TKE = \frac{3}{2} (|V|TI)^2 \quad (4.13)$$

$$\epsilon = C_\mu^{\frac{4}{3}} \frac{TKE^{\frac{3}{2}}}{ILS} \quad (4.14)$$

Where $|V|$ is the inlet velocity magnitude, ϵ is the dissipation rate of turbulence kinetic energy, and C_μ is a model constant whose value is 0.09. Fig. 4.74 shows the TI decay obtained from experimental data fitting (purple line) and CFD simulations. Tuning the ILS, the value of 2.5 mm was found to provide a good agreement between the simulated and experimental TI decay.

The ILS calculated from PIV data falls in between the values obtained from the HW measurements and CFD TI decay fitting. The ILS from PIV can be underestimated due to the relatively small spatial auto-correlation window. The usable signal length, i.e. the path length of the instantaneous fluctuations along the streamline, is about 30 mm. Therefore the eddies of a similar or larger scale are not correctly accounted for in the ILS estimation with PIV. On the other hand, the zero-frequency extrapolation applied to the HW signals may depend primarily on artistic taste in the extrapolation method [24], as varying the averaging frequency range has a significant effect on the resultant value.

Table 4.8: ILS in the S-1/C wind tunnel obtained from different approaches.

	$Re_{out, is}$	$M_{out, is}$	ILS w/o. TG	ILS w. TG	Method
Michálek [20]	120k	0.65	30 mm/ 0.5 m	12 mm	HW Frozen turbulence approx.
Pastorino [22]	70k	0.90	30-40 mm	11-15 mm	HW PSD zero-freq. extrapolation Averaging over 0-100 Hz
			14-19 mm	8-13 mm	PSD zero-freq. extrapolation Averaging over 100-400 Hz
Miglio [23]	70k	0.90	NA	2.5 mm	TI decay fitting
Okada	70k	0.70	6.6-7.5 mm	NA	PIV
		0.90	2.5-3.3 mm	4.2-4.5 mm	Spatial auto-correlation,
	120k	0.70	5.4-6.8 mm	4.6-5.1 mm	sampling over 30 mm streamline
		0.90	2.9-3.6 mm	3.6-4.3 mm	path length

Figure 4.74: Turbulence intensity decay after the turbulence grid estimated by experimental data fitting (purple) [23].

4.2.2 B2B Passage

This subsection presents the results of PIV measurements conducted on the midspan B2B plane located in the passage and downstream of the cascade.

4.2.2.1 Recorded images

Similarly to the B2B upstream case, we first evaluate the quality of raw particle images acquired from the experiments. Figure 4.75 illustrates a schematic of the laser sheet and camera FOV for the B2B passage PIV, followed by exemplary particle image snapshots recorded during a test under the design flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k$, $M_{out,is} = 0.90$, and with the TG). The top row displays raw images, the middle row shows pre-processed images, and the bottom row provides zoomed views of the areas indicated by red rectangles.

In both camera frames, strong reflections appear near the blade suction side and trailing edge due to a direct collision of the laser sheet with the blade surface. Additionally, the end-wall surface, where the pressure taps are instrumented, generates a significant background image since the matte-black paint is not applied to this area to avoid clogging. The effectiveness of temporal mean subtraction for removing this background image is marginal.

The particles appear to be 3-10 pixels for the camera 1 images and 2-4 pixels for the camera 2 images. The image signals registered in camera 2 are lower compared to camera 1. The difference in particle size and signal intensity between the two cameras is due to the increased working distance of camera 2. Offsetting camera 2 slightly farther from the optical window is necessary to maintain the FOV overlapping while avoiding interference between the two camera bodies (see section 3.2.5).

Figure 4.75: Schematic of FOV and exemplary particle images from camera 1 and camera 2. Top row: Full FOV. Middle row: Full FOV after image preprocessing. Bottom row: Zoomed view of the area indicated with the red rectangles.

4.2.2.2 Seeding distribution

The recorded particle images in the blade passage exhibit very few or no tracer particles near the blade suction surface. While it is reasonable to assume that a particle slip during a short time interval between a pair of laser pulses is small within a flow lacking abrupt acceleration/deceleration, the cumulative effect of this minor drift can be significant, leading to undesirable seeding distributions.

Fig. 4.76 shows the frequency of particle occurrence obtained from the count of a sum of pre-processed 500 PIV images of camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right) for the design flow condition. Before the summation, a series of image preprocessing consisting of the time-series background subtraction, spatial Gaussian sliding average subtraction, max-min filter, and particle intensity normalization is used. The dark area indicates a high probability of particle presence in the PIV recording. Note that the black areas near the blade surface, trailing edge, and pressure taps are artifacts from the light reflection on the objects. The red and blue lines departing from the same locations, upstream of the blade leading edge, represent the streamlines of the fluid (air) and the trajectory of the seeding particle (DEHS droplets, $d_p = 1\mu\text{m}$, $\rho = 916\text{kg/m}^3$), respectively. The streamlines and particle trajectories are predicted by a one-way coupling Lagrangian particle tracking simulation based on the 2D RANS simulations using *Cadence FINE/Turbo 16.2*.

Figure 4.76: Frequency of particle occurrence estimated from 500 PIV images. Red line: Fluid streamline (2D RANS). Blue line: Particle trajectory (2D RANS + Lagrangian track)

Losses of particles near the blade suction side and in the airfoil wake are evident in the recordings of camera 1, and the particle tracking simulation closely predicts the experimental seeding distribution. Further downstream, as shown in the camera 2 frame, the experimental seeding density exhibits a recovery in the wake thanks to mixing with the freestream. The lower particle occurrence found in the bottom part of the camera 2 frame is attributed to the weak intensity of the laser sheet edge as illustrated in the schematic in Fig. 4.75.

Fig. 4.77 displays contours of the particle concentration predicted by the Lagrangian particle tracking simulation for different particle sizes ranging from 0.1 to 5.0 μm . The flow condition is fixed to the design condition. The concentration is normalized by the inlet particle concentration. Areas without particles drastically expand with an increase in the particle size.

Fig. 4.78 presents the 99% boundary layer thickness, δ_{99} , and the limit lines until which

Figure 4.77: Concentration of the number of particles estimated by Lagrangian particle tracking simulation.

no particles exist in the surface normal direction predicted by the simulation. The horizontal axis s/S_L represents the blade surface length. The diameter of particle (d_p) is varied from 0.1 to 1.0 μm . The excessive peak values of δ_{99} near the leading and trailing edges ($s/S_L < 0.03$, $0.99 < s/S_L$) are due to an artifact from the interpolation process. For $d_p = 1.0\mu\text{m}$, the zero particle limit line grows rapidly along the blade surface, and the particle is drifted outside the boundary layer after 0.18 s/S_L . Decreasing the particle size to 0.5 μm allows the particle to stay inside the boundary layer, yet not in the region below 50% of δ_{99} . A particle sizing 0.1 μm shows that the drifting effect is negligible over the entire blade surface. In view of this evaluation, the PIV technique in the present test case is not able to measure the flow field within the boundary layer over the blade suction surface.

Figure 4.78: Estimated boundary layer thickness over the blade suction surface and the zero particle limit lines for different particle diameters.

4.2.2.3 Convergence history and Uncertainty quantification

Fig. 4.79 shows the convergence histories of the mean, 95% CI, and RMS of the velocity magnitude for the design flow condition. The data is sampled at four different locations denoted by P1-4 in Fig. 4.80. P1 and P2 are positioned in the freestream region whereas P3 and P4 sample the blade wake. The shaded areas shown in the left figure indicate the 95% CI.

The 95% CI levels for all sampling locations converge to below 1% of the mean after 500 image pair samples, and to 0.5% over 2000 samples. In terms of RMS, the convergence is achieved after sampling 1000 recordings, when the variation of RMS stays below 2 m/s. A higher level of RMS observed at locations P3 and P4 indicates the flow unsteadiness in the blade wake. Moreover, the total number of valid vectors is reduced in P3 and P4 because a large fraction of vectors at these locations are eliminated by the validation process. Inspection of instantaneous velocity fields suggests that most of the invalid vectors are attributed to the vortex cores in the wake where seeding density tended to be low. This implies that the mean velocity in the wake can be biased to the values measured outside the vortex cores. Nonetheless, the reduced number of samples is still satisfactory to achieve converged RMS.

Figure 4.79: Convergence history of mean, 95% confidence intervals, and RMS of the velocity magnitude at midspan B2B for the design flow condition ($Re_{out, is} = 70k, M_{out, is} = 0.9$).

Figure 4.80: Contour map of velocity magnitude for the design flow condition. The rectangle markers P1-P4 indicate the sampling locations for convergence history evaluation.

Fig. 4.81 and 4.82 present the type A and type B standard uncertainties (1σ), and the combined uncertainty with 95% CI (1.96σ) for the velocity magnitude and yaw angle measured by PIV at the design flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k$, $M_{out,is} = 0.90$). The yaw angle is defined using the in-plane velocity component, $\beta = \tan(V_{axi}/V_{tan})$. The uncertainty of the velocity magnitude is normalized by the local mean velocity magnitude. The combined uncertainties in the freestream regions are estimated to be below 3% and 2 degrees for the velocity magnitude and the yaw angle, respectively. An excessively high level of uncertainty registered in the region near the blade suction surface and blade trailing edge is due to the intense light reflection and the low seeding concentration. These regions correspond to the low seeding concentration areas indicated in Fig. 4.76 and 4.77.

Figure 4.81: Uncertainty map of in-plane velocity magnitude measured by PIV for the design flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k$, $M_{out,is} = 0.9$). From left to right: Type A, Type B, and Combined.

The high level of uncertainty seen in the bottom of the camera 2 frame ($y/g > 1.2$) is attributed to the low illumination intensity in the edge of the laser sheet as sketched in Fig. 4.75. The vertically distributed peaks observed in type B and combined uncertainties indicate the location where pressure taps are instrumented on the cascade endwall. In this area, the endwall is not painted black, resulting in a noisier background image. Consequently, a slightly higher uncertainty level is observed compared to the surrounding areas. Additionally, the presence of a highly turbulent swirling flow adversely affects the uncertainty, as seen in the blade wake regions. In these regions, the uncertainty is estimated to be 1.5-2.0 times higher than in the mainstream, owing to the deteriorated image correlation statistics.

Fig. 4.83 shows the probability density function of particle displacement for each velocity

Figure 4.82: Uncertainty map of yaw angle measured by PIV for the design flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k, M_{out,is} = 0.9$). From left to right: Type A, Type B, and Combined.

component. No distinctive peak at integer value is observed, indicating there is no serious peak-locking effect present in this measurement.

Finally, Table 4.9 shows representative uncertainties in the freestream and wake for the PIV measurements on the B2B passage plane. The uncertainties of the velocity component are expressed both in the absolute unit and percentage of the local velocity magnitude.

4.2.2.4 Results of on- and off- design conditions

Mean flow fields

Fig. 4.84, 4.85, 4.86, 4.87 show the in-plane Mach number and yaw angle fields on the midspan B2B passage plane for $Re_{out,is} = 70k, 120k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.70, 0.90, \text{ and } 0.95$ with the TG, measured by PIV and predicted by the 2D RANS simulation. The PIV flow fields from the two cameras are stitched together to provide a single whole-field view.

The comparison globally shows a good agreement between PIV and RANS. The targeted outlet Mach number is reached in the downstream inviscid region (outside of the airfoil wakes). The flow topology at different flow conditions is well resolved in the center of the passage. The suction side boundary layer and the near-trailing edge wake are not properly resolved due to the low seeding concentrations and light reflections in these regions.

In the Mach number field for $M_{out,is} = 0.90$, the presence of a triangle-shaped supersonic region near the throat is visible in both PIV and RANS. By increasing the outlet isentropic Mach number to 0.95, the cascade becomes choked as the supersonic region grows and

Figure 4.83: Probability density function (PDF) of particle displacement. Left: Camera 1, Right: Camera 2, Top: Axial component, Bottom: Tangential component.

Table 4.9: Overview of uncertainties for B2B passage PIV measurements. Type A and Type B uncertainties are expressed as the standard uncertainty (1σ), whereas the combined uncertainty is expanded to cover 95% confidence interval (1.96σ). The uncertainties are presented in both physical unit and normalized unit (percentage of local mean velocity magnitude).

Quantity	Symbol	Unit	Uncertainty in freestream			Uncertainty in wake		
			Type A	Type B	Combined (95% CI)	Type A	Type B	Combined (95% CI)
Axial velocity	V_{axi}	m/s	0.07 (0.04%)	3.73 (1.09%)	7.34 (2.14%)	0.69 (0.24%)	4.20 (1.37%)	8.35 (2.72%)
Tangential velocity	V_{tan}	m/s	0.07 (0.03%)	4.74 (1.34%)	9.30 (2.62%)	0.45 (0.16%)	4.57 (1.52%)	9.00 (2.99%)
Velocity magnitude	$ V $	m/s	0.07 (0.03%)	4.41 (1.23%)	8.64 (2.46%)	0.56 (0.20%)	4.42 (1.46%)	8.74 (2.88%)
Yaw angle	β	deg	0.01	0.79	1.54	0.13	0.93	1.84
Turbulence intensity	TI_{2C}	%	-	-	0.04	-	-	0.47

Figure 4.84: Mach number fields for different flow conditions with TG measured by PIV.

Figure 4.85: Mach number fields for different flow conditions predicted by RANS.

Figure 4.86: Yaw angle fields for different flow conditions with TG measured by PIV.

Figure 4.87: Yaw angle fields for different flow conditions predicted by RANS.

interacts with the adjacent blade. In the wake region, PIV measures a higher Mach number compared to RANS. While this is attributed to a typical shortfall of RANS prediction accuracy [25], PIV results might also involve a bias error originating from the particle loss in the vortex cores, where absolute velocity is lower. The yaw angle fields reveal a larger turning of the outlet flow with an increase of Mach number, while the turning is reduced when the Reynolds number is increased. The variations of outlet flow angle depending on the flow conditions are often associated with the boundary layer state on the blade suction surface. For example, several studies have shown that a thicker boundary layer or a separated flow on the blade suction surface leads to a deviation of flow and so decreases the turning [26].

Fig. 4.88 compares the pitchwise distributions of the absolute Mach number at PL06: $0.50C_{ax}$ downstream of the blade trailing edge obtained from the PIV measurements (circle marker), 5HP measurements (triangle marker), and steady 2D RANS simulations (solid line). Distributions for three different Mach numbers (0.70, 0.90, and 0.95) at a fixed Reynolds number of $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ are displayed. The extraction location is indicated by the dotted line in Fig. 4.84. The 5HP measurements are a part of the work performed by Lopes et al. [27] on the characterization of the steady aerodynamics of the SPLEEN cascade C1 at on- and off-design conditions. The total expanded uncertainty of the Mach number and yaw angle for the 5HP measurements are estimated to be ± 0.005 and ± 0.42 degree, respectively.

Figure 4.88: Pitchwise distribution of absolute Mach number at cascade outlet ($x/C_{ax} = 1.50$) from PIV, 5HP, and RANS.

The freestream Mach number measured with PIV and computed with the RANS display a good agreement for the lowest Mach number investigated. Increasing the Mach number widens the offset between the PIV and RANS, with the PIV displaying a higher value than the latter. On the other hand, the Mach number measured by the 5HP is substantially lower than those obtained with PIV and RANS. The offset between PIV and 5HP increases from 0.025 to 0.100 as the Mach number is increased from 0.70 to 0.95. Even though the probe is calibrated at atmospheric pressure and is used at a lower pressure environment, the Reynolds number based on the probe diameter is still sufficiently high ($Re_{probe} = 3000$) to rule out the effect of the Reynolds number [28]. The discrepancy is attributed to a probe blockage effect that forces the redistribution of mass flow to passages not being blocked by the probe. This causes a local reduction of the static pressure in the passage being measured by the 5HP. This effect was also observed by Boerner et al. [29] and Sanders et al. [30]. Lopes et al. [31] characterized this effect at different locations of the cascade: upstream, downstream, and on the blade SS.

Fig. 4.89 compares the pitchwise distributions of Mach number normalized by their freestream values to compensate for the offsets found between the 5HP and PIV or RANS results presented in Fig 4.88. The wake depth measured by the 5HP and PIV are in good agreement despite the issues in retrieving static pressure with the 5HP. The difference in the wake velocity deficit is within 1% of the mean value. The wake width is also in accordance between both techniques.

Figure 4.89: Pitchwise distribution of normalized Mach number at cascade outlet ($x/C_{ax} = 1.50$) from PIV, 5HP, and RANS. For the outlet Mach numbers of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95 and Reynolds numbers of 70k and 120k.

The PIV results display wake misalignment compared to the 5HP measurements and RANS predictions. The shift is systematic and amounts to 0.05 y/g between all the investigated cases. The error of the measurement position between the PIV and 5HP is estimated to be around 0.015 y/g (0.5 mm).

On the other hand, a large discrepancy between the RANS and experiments takes place. RANS predicts larger Mach number deficits by as much as 6% in the wake compared to the measurements. The thinner and deeper wake is attributed to turbulence models used in RANS struggling to accurately predict wake mixing when compared with higher-order methods [25, 32].

At $M_{out, is} = 0.70$, both measurements and RANS present symmetric profiles, while increasing the Mach, the distribution is modulated, and an asymmetry appears. At $M_{out, is} = 0.95$, The overshoot of probe-measured Mach number near the border of the wake is a typical pattern as reported in literature [29, 30, 33] and is caused by the probe not retrieving the static pressure distribution in the high-velocity gradient field.

Fig. 4.90 displays the pitchwise distributions of the deviation in yaw angle with respect to the mean value. The PIV result displays angle oscillations that are contained within ± 1 degree. On the other hand, the 5HP displays sinewave oscillations around the wake center that are caused by the probe head blockage and interaction with the blade wake. Torre et al. [33] have recently quantified this effect in a numerical setup. The distributions obtained with PIV present a reduction of the flow direction in the wake. However, no positive bump as seen for the 5HP results is observed. As the Mach number is increased, the amplitudes of the wake patterns grow, from 1.2 to 2.8 degrees in the 5HP, from 0.2 to 1.0 degrees in the PIV, and 0.1 to 0.4 degrees in the RANS results, respectively.

Even though the tap spatial displacement of the 5HP head is accounted for according to the first correction proposed by Ligrani [34], the velocity gradient correction is not applied.

Figure 4.90: Pitchwise distribution of yaw angle (β) deviation from the mean (β_{mean}) at cascade outlet ($x/C_{ax} = 1.50$) from PIV, 5HP, and RANS. For the outlet Mach numbers of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95 and Reynolds numbers of 70k and 120k.

Chernoray [35] highlighted that the first correction provides the largest difference to the uncorrected results. On the other hand, Torre et al. [33] found that even with the application of the complete correction, an underprediction of the transversal velocity components can lead to a discrepancy of 1 degree between the corrected and uncorrected results.

From above, the accurate measurement of Mach number and flow angles in transonic cascade flows is found to be challenging with physical probes due to the blockage effects. For such a flow environment, the advantage of optical measurement techniques like PIV is emphasized.

Vorticity fields

Fig. 4.93 presents the time-averaged vorticity fields for $Re_{out,is} = 70k, 120k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.70, 0.90, 0.95$ with the TG, measured by PIV. A distinctive vorticity intensity distribution in the blade wake indicates the presence of a trailing edge vortex shedding, which plays an important role in the wake mixing process and trailing edge pressure distribution [36]. While the unsteady characteristics of the vortex shedding are of interest, limitations in the laser pulse repetition and camera frame rate of the PIV system prohibit the image recordings of the high-frequency vortex shedding phenomena in a time-resolved manner.

For instance, the wake vortex shedding frequency f_{shed} is estimated from [36]:

$$f_{shed} = St \frac{V_{out,is}}{t_{te}} \quad (4.15)$$

where t_{te} is the trailing edge thickness, which is reported to be 0.87 mm for the present test article. Investigations carried out by Heinemann and Bütetfish [37] suggested that the Strouhal number covers a wide range: $0.2 \leq St \leq 0.4$ with different blade geometries for outlet isentropic Mach numbers varying from subsonic to transonic values. For the design flow condition ($M_{out,is} = 0.90, Re_{out,is} = 70k$), the isentropic outlet flow speed is calculated to be $V_{out,is} = 309$ m/s. The corresponding shedding frequency range is estimated to be $71 \text{ kHz} \leq f_{freq} \leq 142 \text{ kHz}$.

Although the acquisition frequency of PIV measurement (15 Hz) is not high enough to resolve vortex shedding frequency in the time-domain, the spatial information on the vortex shedding is registered in each instantaneous velocity field. Here a pseudo-phase-lock-average

Figure 4.91: Time-averaged spanwise vorticity for different flow conditions with TG measured by PIV.

(P-PLA) method, similar to that employed by Woisetschlager et al. [38], is developed to retrieve the frequency content from a set of instantaneous velocity fields.

Fig. 4.92 illustrates the procedure of the P-PLA. First, instantaneous vorticity fields are calculated from the corresponding instantaneous velocity fields. The obtained vorticity fields are noisy due to invalid vectors and blank spots. In the second step, a convolution with a 6×6 Gaussian kernel is applied to the vorticity fields to suppress the noise and enhance the flow feature associated with the vortex shedding. Subsequently, the enhanced vorticity distributions are extracted along the blade outlet metal angle line. These 1D vorticity signals, obtained as a function of the distance from the reference point (e.g. the blade trailing edge), essentially contain the fluctuation information associated with the vortex shedding frequency. The extracted instantaneous space-domain signals are then converted to the time-domain signal by dividing the distance by the mean velocity magnitude sampled in the wake region. Now, a Fourier transform is applied to each time-domain 1D signal to calculate its frequency composition. Averaging the frequency spectra (amplitude distributions) over the number of extracted signals, the vortex shedding frequency can be found at the peak. The vortex shedding phase of each recording is obtained from the phase corresponding to the shedding frequency available in the output of the Fourier transform. Based on this phase information, each recording is classified into 18 phases (discretization interval of 20 degrees), and an ensemble average is performed to obtain P-PLA results.

Fig. 4.93 shows the P-PLA spanwise vorticity contours for different flow conditions with the TG. Unlike the time-averaged vorticity contour, the individual cores of clockwise (positive) and anti-clockwise (negative) vortices are visualized, verifying the applicability of the proposed P-PLA method. The near trailing edge vorticity field is not valid as the result has high uncertainty in the region due to the lack of particles and strong light reflections.

Figure 4.92: P-PLA procedure.

Figure 4.93: P-PLA spanwise vorticity for different flow conditions with TG measured by PIV.

Fig. 4.94 summarizes the vortex shedding frequencies and Strouhal numbers for different flow conditions measured with PIV. The shedding frequencies are obtained from the peak in the ensemble-averaged frequency spectra. The corresponding Strouhal numbers are calculated using Eq. 4.15. The dot-dash grey line represents the shedding frequency estimated using the correlation with the typical Strouhal number of 0.22 [39]. The error bars indicate the uncertainty attributed to the frequency resolution of this analysis. The length of the 1D signals is limited by the image FOV whereas the sampling resolution is constrained by the IW size and pixel resolution of the image sensor. One must make a compromise between these two parameters as the extension of the signal length must be done by decreasing the magnification, thus in exchange for the spatial resolution.

The vortex shedding frequency rises with the increase of the outlet Mach number and the slope is steeper for the lower Reynolds number. The higher shedding frequency is also represented by the shorter intervals of the vortex cores appearing in the vorticity contour map. The shedding frequency for $Re_{out, is} = 120k$ matches with the values obtained from the correlation, resulting in the Strouhal numbers varying from 0.2 to 0.25 with the Mach number increase. For the $Re_{out, is} = 70k$ cases, the shedding frequency is found to be lower and the corresponding Strouhal number remains at 0.15 for all Mach number cases. Such a low value is not found in literature [36], thus validation of the presented result is expected with fast-response measurements and high-fidelity numerical simulations in future work.

Turbulence fields

Fig. 4.95 and 4.96 present contour maps of the in-plane two-component TI and TKE measured by PIV. The upstream turbulence grid is installed for the presented cases. The TI and TKE are calculated using Eq. 2.60 and 2.62. The particle displacement between double

Figure 4.94: Vortex shedding frequencies and Strouhal numbers for different flow conditions measured by PIV.

frames is on average 10-20 pixels. As aforementioned in subsection 4.2.1.6, it is found that the turbulence quantities tend to be overestimated for smaller interrogation window sizes. To minimize this artifact, image cross-correlation is performed with 64×64 pixels interrogation window instead of 32×32 pixels for the computation of turbulence fields. Near the blade surfaces and in the region of the wake near the trailing edge, the value of TI is not reliable as there are not enough valid vectors due to the loss of particle information and strong light reflections.

For quantitative evaluation, Fig. 4.97 presents the distributions of TI (top), TKE (middle), and velocity magnitude (bottom) along the streamline in the freestream region as indicated with a yellow line in Fig. 4.95. The horizontal axis (s) is the path length of the streamline. The step that appears in the distribution profiles at $s = 40$ mm is associated with the junction of datasets obtained from camera 1 and camera 2 recordings. The amplified velocity fluctuation in the camera 2 region is attributed to the lower signal intensity in camera 2 images as discussed in section 4.2.2.1. While it is not appropriate to compare the absolute values between camera 1 and camera 2 regions, the major trends of the turbulence field depending on the different flow conditions are shared between the two cameras.

Introducing the TG, the TI is augmented by 0.2 - 0.5% throughout the blade passage. The TI is the highest at the upstream of the throat ($S > 20$ mm), amounting to 1.3 - 2.1% depending on the flow conditions, and it decreases towards the downstream. Until the cascade throat, the level of TI is higher for the higher outlet Mach number cases. Such a trend is also reported in hot-wire measurements performed in a stage vane passage [40] and Large eddy simulation (LES) [41].

A similar trend is also displayed in the distribution of the TKE. On the other hand, the distribution of velocity magnitude shows a steep acceleration in the blade passage until it reaches a peak near the throat. This implies that the reduction of TI in the blade passage is due to a combination of the decay of the velocity fluctuations and the increment of the local velocity.

At $M_{out,is} = 0.95$, a prominent peak appears near the throat ($s = 20$ mm) in the TI and

Figure 4.95: In-plane two-component turbulence intensity fields measured by PIV for different flow conditions with TG.

Figure 4.96: In-plane two-component turbulent kinetic energy fields measured by PIV for different flow conditions with TG.

Figure 4.97: Distributions of TI (top), TKE (middle) and Velocity magnitude (bottom) extracted along with the streamline in the blade passage as indicated in Fig. 4.95.

TKE distributions. This peak is assumed to be associated with the unsteady relocation of the shock wave that increases the RMS of flow fluctuations. The peak sits in the location of the shockwave visible in Fig. 4.84. Lopes et al. [27] argued that a shock-boundary layer interaction occurs on the suction side of the cascade operating at $M_{out, is} = 0.95$. He reported the onset of a laminar separation bubble located at about 74% of the SS surface length based on surface pressure measurements. This location is consistent with the impingement point of the shock wave on the blade suction side shown by the PIV results (about 72% of the SS surface length). Downstream the throat, the TI for the lowest outlet Mach number case becomes the highest as a result of the slow decay of TKE and moderate acceleration of the flow through the passage.

Fig. 4.98 displays the pitchwise TI distribution extracted $0.50C_{ax}$ downstream of the blade trailing edge. In the freestream region, a variation is observed in the TI, showing reduced turbulence levels for higher outlet Mach number cases. On the other hand, the turbulence kinetic energy remains the same for all flow conditions. This implies that the variations in turbulence intensity in this region are due to the mean freestream stretching the velocity fluctuations.

Figure 4.98: Pitchwise distribution of in-plane two-component turbulence intensity and turbulence kinetic energy at cascade outlet ($x/C_{ax} = 1.50$) from PIV. For the outlet Mach numbers of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95 and Reynolds numbers of 70k and 120k. TG equipped.

In the wake, reductions in TI and TKE are registered for the cases of $Re_{out, is} = 120k$ compared to the cases of $Re_{out, is} = 70k$ for the same outlet Mach number. The primary reason for this trend is attributed to the boundary layer state on the blade suction surface. Fig. 4.99 presents the isentropic Mach number distributions on the blade midspan obtained from the blade static pressure and the freestream total pressure by Lopes et al. [27]. The left figure shows both pressure and suction side distributions over the whole blade chord length, whereas the right figure displays a zoomed view of the rear part of the suction side. Distinctive closed separation bubbles are observed in the case of $Re_{out, is} = 100K$ and $120k$ for $M_{out, is} = 0.70$. On the other hand, the separated boundary layer does not seem fully reattached by the blade trailing edge in the case of $Re_{out, is} = 65K$ and $70k$. This accounts for the broader and higher peaks observed in the TI and the TKE profiles at the cascade outlet. The flow separation on the suction side also explains the wake width widens toward

the suction side in the case of $Re_{out,is} = 70k$. Bitter et al. [42] reported the same trend in their PIV measurements performed at $Re_{out,is} = 60K$ and $120k$ for $M_{out,is} = 0.7$.

Increasing the outlet Mach number to 0.90, a growth of wake profiles of turbulence intensity and turbulence kinetic energy is observed. While the distinctive difference in the wake profile between the low and high Re flow cases is still observed, the blade isentropic Mach number distribution suggests much less Reynolds number dependency on the boundary layer state for the high Mach number cases. The boundary layer for the cases of $M_{out,is} > 0.90$ undergoes separation and no reattachment is predicted from the blade loading. Thus, the difference in turbulence wake profiles between the low and high Re for the high Mach number cases might be due to the diversified mixing process downstream of the cascade rather than the boundary layer state on the blade suction surface. A faster decay of turbulence intensity is in fact observed in the 2D contour map in Fig. 4.95.

For the highest Mach number case ($M_{out,is} = 0.95$), the peak height of the TI and TKE in the wake is reduced compared to the case of $M_{out,is} = 0.90$. This could be attributed to a weak normal shock near the throat region as observed in Fig. 4.84. The shock wave-boundary layer interaction can force a transition of the boundary layer to turbulent, decreasing the size of the separation.

Figure 4.99: Comparison of PS and SS profile isentropic Mach number distribution (left) and detail of rear part of SS (right) for different flow conditions at the blade midspan [27].

Fig. 4.100 compares the pitchwise TI distribution with and without the TG. The last few peripheral points on the pressure side of profiles are not reliable due to a high uncertainty near the border of FOV. The freestream TI exhibits 0.5-1.0% lower level for the cases without the TG, which aligns with the TI measured upstream of the cascade. Installing the TG, i.e. increasing the freestream TI, the width and peak of the wake profiles decrease. Zhang et al. [43] found the similar wake profile tendency in the pressure loss coefficient obtained from

LES prediction performed on the T106D-EIZ profile at $Re_{out,is} = 60k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.4$ (Fig. 4.101 left). They confirmed that the separation regions over the blade suction surface are compressed as the inlet freestream TI increased. This is due to the background turbulence promoting a rapid break-down of the spanwise vortex rolling-up in the separation region. Consequently, for higher freestream TI, the separated shear layer is characterized with smaller vortices which are presumably attributed to boundary layer reattachment. An investigation with DNS conducted by Durović et al. [44] also revealed the similar trend in the loss coefficient profile (Fig. 4.101 right), arguing that boundary layer transition is proceeded rapidly in a high freestream turbulence as streamwise vortices retards or suppress the flow separation.

The effect of inlet freestream TI on the wake profile is less pronounced for the highest Mach number case.

Figure 4.100: Pitchwise distribution of in-plane two-component turbulence intensity at cascade outlet ($x/C_{a,x} = 1.50$) with and without TG measured with PIV. For the outlet Mach numbers of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95 and Reynolds numbers of 70k and 120k.

Figure 4.101: Left: Total pressure loss coefficient ω at cascade outlet obtained from LES and experiment [43]. Right: Total pressure loss coefficient c_{pt} obtained from DNS and experiment [44].

Fig. 4.102 displays the Reynolds normal stress in streamwise ($V'_{str} V'_{str}$) and crosswise ($V'_{crs} V'_{crs}$) direction, and Reynolds shear stress as a product of streamwise and crosswise velocity fluctuations ($V'_{str} V'_{crs}$) measured by PIV. Fig. 4.103 illustrates a schematic for the definition of local streamwise and crosswise velocity components. The instantaneous velocity is evaluated based on the local mean yaw angle $\bar{\beta}$ for the decomposition. The streamwise veloc-

ity fluctuation V'_{str} and the crosswise velocity fluctuation V'_{crs} are calculated by subtracting mean streamwise and crosswise velocity (\overline{V}_{str} , \overline{V}_{crs}) from the instantaneous streamwise and crosswise velocities (V_{str} , V_{crs}).

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\beta} &= \tan^{-1}(\overline{V}_{axi}/\overline{V}_{tan}) \\ \overline{V}_{str} &= \overline{V}_{axi} \cos \bar{\beta} + \overline{V}_{tan} \sin \bar{\beta} = |\overline{V}| \\ \overline{V}_{crs} &= \overline{V}_{tan} \cos \bar{\beta} - \overline{V}_{axi} \sin \bar{\beta} = 0\end{aligned}\quad (4.16)$$

$$\begin{aligned}V_{str} &= V_{axi} \cos \bar{\beta} + V_{tan} \sin \bar{\beta} \\ V_{crs} &= V_{tan} \cos \bar{\beta} - V_{axi} \sin \bar{\beta}\end{aligned}\quad (4.17)$$

$$\begin{aligned}V'_{str} &= V_{str} - \overline{V}_{str} \\ V'_{crs} &= V_{crs}\end{aligned}\quad (4.18)$$

In terms of Reynolds normal stress, the crosswise direction exhibits higher values compared to the streamwise direction, with the ratio between these two components reaching a maximum value of 1.6 for the case of $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.90$. For $M_{out,is} = 0.70$, the streamwise Reynolds stress displays two peaks in the wake, suggesting that the mixing of the wake with the freestream does not reach the core of the wake. Ames and Plesniak [40] found a similar double-peak wake pattern from the testing in a first-stage nozzle vane at the low Mach number ($M_{out,is} = 0.27$). They explained this is due to the occurrence of maximum velocity gradients on either side of the wake resulting in a high turbulence production rate.

The Reynolds shear stress shows a distinctive sine-wave-like pattern which is also reported in [40] and [25]. The positive and negative signs of Reynolds shear stress identify the coherent correlation between streamwise and crosswise velocity fluctuations. The positive peak on the suction side and the negative peak on the pressure side indicate the entrainment of the freestream into the shear layer of the wake.

Figure 4.102: Pitchwise distribution of Reynolds normal stress ($V'_{str}V'_{str}$ and $V'_{crs}V'_{crs}$) and Reynolds shear stress ($V'_{str}V'_{crs}$) at cascade outlet ($x/C_{ax} = 1.50$) from PIV. For the outlet Mach numbers of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95 and Reynolds numbers of 70k and 120k. TG equipped.

Figure 4.103: Schematics of streamwise and crosswise velocity decomposition.

Fig. 4.104 shows the in-plane two-component symmetric degree of anisotropy (DA) calculated using Eq. 2.67. Unlike the DA proposed in [45], the symmetric DA is zero-centered, thus the sign of the quantity directly indicates whether the turbulence field is streamwise component dominant or crosswise and radial components dominant. The credibility of distinctive high positive values near the blade suction surface and trailing edge is not verified as the regions exhibit a high level of uncertainty due to the deteriorated image quality.

Apart from that, several flow features are observed from the DA map. The majority of the freestream region is characterized by negative DA where the fluctuation aligned to the streamline is stretched by the accelerating flow. The distribution of neutral to positive DA registered around the airfoil wake suggests the wake mixing process is isotropic. Such a constitution of DA is also found at the exit of a stator blades row with a fast response aerodynamic probe by Porreca et.al [45].

DA analysis also revealed the presence of a double peak around the wake. Yanovych et al. [46] who carried out turbulence measurements behind an airfoil argued that the double peak corresponds to the region of the outer-wake shear layer where the streamwise fluctuation predominates. In addition, it corresponds to the position of the inflection point for the Reynolds shear stresses component. Whereas, for the inner part of the wake, the crosswise fluctuation becomes larger than the streamwise one. The dominance of streamwise fluctuation in the wake shear layer is pronounced with the increase of Reynolds number, suggesting a change in the wake mixing process in this region.

Another aspect observed from the DA field is the Mach number effect. Increasing the outlet Mach number decreases DA as the stretching effect on the streamwise fluctuation becomes more pronounced in high acceleration flows. In the cascade throat area, a positive DA is developed in the surface-normal direction for $M_{out, is} = 0.9, 0.95$. The location corresponds to the weak shock wave observed in Fig. 4.84. A steep increase in the DA over a shock and its

decay in the post-shock wave is also reported from LDV measurements performed by Jacquin et al. [47] and DNS calculation performed by Lee et al. [48] and Mahesh et al. [49].

Figure 4.104: In-plane two-component degree of anisotropy ($DA_{sym,2C}$) measured by PIV. For the outlet Mach numbers of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95 and Reynolds numbers of 70k and 120k. TG equipped.

4.2.3 Cascade outlet plane

This subsection presents the results of PIV measurements conducted on the near endwall COP located 50% downstream of the blade trailing edge.

4.2.3.1 Recorded images

Fig. 4.105 displays exemplary particle image snapshots recorded at the design flow condition. The top row displays raw images, the middle row shows images after image preprocessing, and the bottom row provides zoomed views of the areas indicated by red rectangles. The images in the left column are obtained from camera 1 whereas those in the right columns are recorded with camera 2.

In both camera frames, strong reflections appear near the endwall due to a direct incident of the laser sheet with the blade surface. The diffusion reflection on the endwall illuminated blades seen behind the measurement plane, and a significant light signal from the trailing edge is captured in the camera 2 images. The temporal mean image subtraction removed most of the background image noises, but the signal of trailing edge reflection persisted as the vertical line.

The particle images appear to be strongly deformed in both cameras. In the images obtained with camera 1, the recorded particle image shows a star-like shape as the signals are stretched diagonally. A similar optical deformation pattern is known to be a result of comatic aberration and tangential and/or sagittal astigmatism. The images of camera 2 on the other hand exhibit the particle shape elongated vertically. Although these optical aberrations and distortions are unfavorable for PIV measurements, they have to be accepted due to the limited availability of the test rig.

Combined with the optical aberrations and distortions, the sizes of particles are found to be 3-10 pixels in the camera 1 images and 2-30 pixels in the camera 2 images. Fig. 4.106 shows the probability density function of particle displacement for each velocity component. No distinctive peak at integer value was observed, indicating the absence of a significant peak-locking effect in this measurement.

4.2.3.2 Convergence history and Uncertainty quantification

Fig. 4.107 shows the convergence histories of the mean value, 95% confidence intervals (CI), and RMS of the velocity magnitude for the design flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k$, $M_{out,is} = 0.9$). The convergence histories are sampled at four different locations denoted by P1-4 in Fig. 4.108. The horizontal (pitchwise) axis of the figure is aligned such that $y/g = 0$ corresponds to the intersection of the blade exit metal angle with the outlet measurement plane. The values of CI are normalized by the local mean velocity magnitude. P1 and P2 are positioned in the freestream region whereas P3 and P4 sample the blade wake. The shaded areas shown in the left figure indicate the 95% CI. Note that the velocity information near the endwall ($z/H < 0.005$) is not reliable due to the significant light reflection on the wall surface.

The 95% CI level at each sampling location converges to below 1% of the mean after 500 recordings, and to 0.5% over 2000 recordings. In terms of RMS, the convergence is achieved after sampling 1000 recordings, with the variation of RMS staying below 1 m/s.

Figure 4.105: Exemplary particle images from camera 1 (left) and camera 2 (right). Top row: Full FOV. Middle row: Full FOV after image preprocessing. Bottom row: Zoomed view of area indicated with the red rectangles.

Figure 4.106: Probability density function (PDF) of particle displacement. From left to right: pitchwise, spanwise, and axial component.

Higher levels of the RMS observed at the locations P3 and P4 indicate the flow unsteadiness in the blade wake and secondary flow regions. The total number of valid samples is mostly retained at every sampling location thanks to the vector interpolation employed during the vector processing step in the *Davis* PIV software.

Figure 4.107: Convergence history of mean, 95% confidence intervals, and RMS of the velocity magnitude at COP for the nominal test condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k, M_{out,is} = 0.9$).

Fig. 4.109, 4.110 and 4.111 illustrate the distributions of type A, type B, and combined uncertainties of the velocity magnitude, yaw angle and pitch angle measured by PIV at the design flow condition. The type A and type B uncertainties are expressed as the standard uncertainty (1σ) whereas the combined uncertainty is expanded to cover 95% confidence intervals (1.96σ).

The type A uncertainty has an impact of approximately one order of magnitude lower than that of the type B uncertainty. The combined uncertainties including 95% CI are below 3% for the velocity magnitude and below 2 degrees for the yaw and pitch angles in most of the inviscid flow regions. The higher uncertainties are observed in the wake and secondary flow regions due to the flow unsteadiness which contributes to the increase in both the type A and type B uncertainties. Also, a high-velocity gradient in the secondary flow regions reduced the seeding density, leading to a lower signal-to-noise ratio in the cross-correlation map, consequently yielding a higher uncertainty as estimated by the correlation statistics method. A local peak of uncertainty appears at around $y/g = 0.3$ and $z/H = 0 - 0.04$ and is caused by the intense light reflection on the blade trailing edge remaining even after applying the image preprocessing.

The summary of uncertainties for the COP measurement is shown in Table 4.10. The

Figure 4.108: Data sampling location P1 - P4 for convergence evaluation. The contour map displays the velocity magnitude for the design condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k, M_{out,is} = 0.9$).

Figure 4.109: Uncertainty map of velocity magnitude measured by PIV for the nominal flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k, M_{out,is} = 0.9$). From left to right: Type A, Type B, and combined uncertainties. The combined uncertainty is multiplied by a factor of 1.96 to cover 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 4.110: Uncertainty map of yaw angle measured by PIV for the nominal flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k, M_{out,is} = 0.9$). From left to right: Type A, Type B, and combined uncertainties. The combined uncertainty is multiplied by a factor of 1.96 to cover 95% confidence intervals.

Figure 4.111: Uncertainty map of pitch angle measured by PIV for the nominal flow condition ($Re_{out,is} = 70k, M_{out,is} = 0.9$). From left to right: Type A, Type B, and combined uncertainties. The combined uncertainty is multiplied by a factor of 1.96 to cover 95% confidence intervals.

Table 4.10: Overview of uncertainties for COP PIV measurements. Type A and Type B uncertainties are expressed as the standard uncertainty (1σ), whereas the combined uncertainty is expanded to cover 95% confidence interval (1.96σ). The uncertainties are presented in both physical unit and normalized unit (percentage of local mean velocity magnitude).

Quantity	Symbol	Unit	Uncertainty in freestream			Uncertainty in wake		
			Type A	Type B	Combined (95% CI)	Type A	Type B	Combined (95% CI)
Axial velocity	V_{axi}	m/s	0.18 (0.06%)	4.92 (1.65%)	9.65 (3.24%)	0.70 (0.28%)	8.40 (3.37%)	16.52 (6.63%)
Tangential velocity	V_{tan}	m/s	0.12 (0.04%)	2.95 (0.99%)	5.77 (1.94%)	0.45 (0.18%)	4.00 (1.59%)	7.88 (3.13%)
Radial velocity	V_{rad}	m/s	0.17 (0.06%)	2.94 (0.99%)	5.78 (1.94%)	0.45 (0.18%)	4.00 (1.59%)	7.88 (3.13%)
Velocity magnitude	$ V _{3D}$	m/s	0.15 (0.05%)	3.88 (1.30%)	7.61 (2.55%)	0.55 (0.22%)	5.91 (2.35%)	11.64 (4.62%)
Yaw angle	β	deg	0.03	0.81	1.59	0.15	1.66	3.26
Pitch angle	γ	deg	0.05	0.88	1.73	0.18	1.62	3.19
Turbulence intensity	TI_{3C}	%	-	-	0.06	-	-	0.47

listed uncertainty values are the representatives sampled in freestream and wake regions. The velocity components are expressed in both physical units (m/s) and as percentages normalized by the local velocity magnitude.

4.2.3.3 Results of on- and off-design conditions

Mean flow field

Fig. 4.112, 4.113, and 4.114 display the contour maps of the absolute Mach number, yaw angle, and pitch angle for different flow conditions ($Re_{out,is} = 70k$, and $M_{out,is} = 0.70, 0.90$, and 0.95), as measured using PIV and 5HP. All measurements on the COP are performed with the TG installed upstream of the cascade. The data of 5HP measurements are adopted

from the work of Lopes et al. [27].

Blank areas near the endwall are masked-out regions due to the excessive uncertainty level. The masked region expands as the outlet Mach number is increased. This occurred because the endwall black paint degraded or ablated with repeated exposure to the high-intensity laser sheet, especially in the later testing of high Mach number cases. Homogeneous seeding near the endwall is also more challenging in high-speed flows.

Figure 4.112: COP Mach number contours measured by PIV (top) and 5HP (bottom) for $Re_{out, is} = 70k$ and $M_{out, is} = 0.70, 0.90, \text{ and } 0.95$ with TG.

Similar to the B2B measurement results, the PIV measurements confirm that the target Mach number is reached in the freestream region of the passage. On the other hand, the Mach number fields provided by the 5HP show lower values with the offset ranging from 0.05 to 0.10 as the $M_{out, is}$ is increased from 0.70 to 0.95. The underestimation of the Mach number is attributed to the probe blockage and static pressure misleading as observed in the B2B measurements. The tendency of probes to underestimate the flow speed is also reported by Chemnitz et al. [50] even for a lower Mach number case ($M_{out, is} = 0.6$).

The secondary flow pattern exhibits a good agreement between the PIV and 5HP measurements, and it is aligned with the models in literature [51–54] (Fig. 4.115). A region of low Mach number is visible near the endwall because of a corner vortex (CV). The presence of CV is also identified by the under-turned region near the endwall in the yaw angle field. The cross-markers indicate the local minima of Mach number in the second velocity deficit region. This region results from the combined effect of the passage vortex (PV) and trailing shed vortex (TSV). The horizontal dotted lines specify the span position of the local minima of Mach number for the case of $M_{out, is} = 0.70$. The velocity deficit region occurs at $z/H \approx$

Figure 4.113: COP yaw angle (β) contours measured by PIV (top) and 5HP (bottom) for $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.70, 0.90,$ and 0.95 with TG.

0.10-0.12 in the PIV results, while the 5HP displays the core to be offset by 0.01-0.02 z/H towards the midspan compared to the PIV. Increasing the outlet Mach number, a typical Mach number effect [55], the secondary flow structure migrating closer to the endwall, is observed.

Fig. 4.116 shows the spanwise distribution of pitchwise-area-averages of the Mach number, yaw angle, and pitch angle obtained from PIV and 5HP. Pitchwise-area-average of a generic quantity q is calculated by:

$$\bar{q}_{area} = \int_0^1 q d(y/g) \quad (4.19)$$

The Mach number distribution highlights the underestimation by 5HP becoming prominent for higher Mach numbers. The relatively flat trend of the Mach number along the spanwise direction confirms that the static pressure behind the cascade is nearly constant. Near the endwall ($z/H < 0.02$), the 5HP result shows a steep reduction of Mach number and increase of pitch angle while PIV does not present such a tendency. This is likely due to the wall proximity effect of the 5HP, the probe head near the endwall blocks the flow thus the static pressure measured by the central and down holes increases. As the measurement location approaches the cascade midspan, the discrepancy in the pitch and yaw angles between 5HP and PIV decreases. This is due to the reduced effect (stem length) of probe immersion thus the blockage and deviation of flow become less prominent [33]. The PIV results near the endwall are not available for $M_{out,is} = 0.90$ and 0.95 since a large portion of vector information is invalid at the corresponding span location.

Figure 4.114: COP pitch angle (γ) contours measured by PIV (top) and 5HP (bottom) for $Re_{out, is} = 70k$ and $M_{out, is} = 0.70, 0.90,$ and 0.95 with TG.

Figure 4.115: Secondary flow models from Takeishi et al. [51] (left) and Kang [52] (right). PV: Passage vortex, HV: Horseshoe vortex, TLV: Tip leakage vortex, TSV: Tip secondary vortex, SV: Secondary vortex, CSV: Concentrated shed vortex, CV: Corner vortex.

Figure 4.116: Pitchwise area-averaged spanwise distribution of Mach number, yaw angle, and pitch angle obtained from PIV and 5HP measurements.

Vorticity fields

Fig. 4.117 presents the secondary flow streamlines and contour maps of the streamwise vorticity coefficient $K_{\omega,s}$ for the cases of $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.7, 0.9,$ and 0.95 measured with the PIV and the 5HP. The secondary flow components are calculated using Eq. 2.46 and 2.47. The streamwise vorticity coefficient is computed according to the method of Gregory-Smith et al. [56] and employing the normalization reported by Taremi [57] (see Eq. 2.51).

In Eq. 2.51, C is the blade chord length, $V_{out,is}$ is the isentropic outlet flow speed, and β_{MS} is the flow yaw angle at the midspan. For the PIV vorticity fields, β_{MS} is computed from the yaw angle measured with the B2B passage PIV measurements. The axial vorticity ω_{axi} is directly computed from the COP PIV velocity fields using Eq. 2.48, whereas the tangential vorticity ω_{tan} is estimated using the Crocco relation (Eq. 2.48) as suggested in [57]. The total pressure gradient at the outlet measurement plane, $\partial(\ln P_{0,out})/\partial z$, is taken from the 5HP measurements.

The streamwise vorticity field highlights the previously mentioned secondary flow structures: CV, PV, and TSV (Fig. 4.115). The rotating pattern of PV is clearly visualized with the secondary flow streamlines from both measurement techniques.

Overall, the PIV results present a lower level of streamwise vorticity than that of the 5HP which can be due to the overestimation of the flow angles measured by the 5HP. The shape of PV and its core location measured by PIV are squeezed towards the endwall compared to the 5HP results. On the other hand, the migration trend of the vortical structure with the increase of Mach number is highly similar. The inverted triangles plotted in Fig. 4.117 show the local minima of $K_{\omega,s}$ in the TSV region, and the horizontal dashed lines are aligned to the local minima for the case of $M_{out,is} = 0.70$. As the Mach number is increased, the TSV shifts towards the endwall by about 1.5% of the blade span, for both the PIV and 5HP measurement results. The observed Mach number effect is in line with precedent studies [55], confirming the validity of measurement results.

Turbulence field

Fig. 4.118 shows the TI field for $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.70, 0.90,$ and 0.95 , with the TG measured by PIV. The TI of each velocity component and the three-component TI are computed using Eqs. 2.59 and 2.61, respectively.

Figure 4.117: COP secondary flow streamline and streamwise vorticity coefficient $K_{\omega,s}$ contour measured by PIV (top) and 5HP (bottom) for $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.70, 0.90,$ and 0.95 with TG. The inverted triangles indicate the local minima in the TSV region.

Figure 4.118: Turbulence intensity fields on the COP with TG. Top row: $Re = 70k, M_{out, is} = 0.70$. Middle row: $Re = 70k, M_{out, is} = 0.90$. Bottom row: $Re = 70k, M_{out, is} = 0.95$. From left to right column: TI_{str} , TI_{crs} , TI_{rad} , and TI_{3C} .

High levels of turbulence are observed in the secondary flow region with the highest value of 12% for the three-component TI. Regions of high streamwise and crosswise turbulence intensities are found in correspondence with the blade wake along the cascade span where significant shear stress exists. A core of high turbulence intensity in the radial component is associated with the interaction of the PV with the TSV. The shear between the vortices and freestream is therefore suspected to be responsible for the production of turbulence as previously reported by MacIsaac et al. [15]. The lowest level is registered in the clean 2D freestream region where the TI of all components is lower than 6%.

The turbulence components measured by Chemnitz and Neihuis [50] using a HW probe and PIV in a high-subsonic ($M_{out, is} = 0.6$) linear cascade flow also showed that all three components have high turbulent fluctuation spots in the wake. The reported maximum TI of 13–15% in the secondary flow region matches the values measured in this study. However, unlike the present case, they reported the highest value occurred in the streamwise component instead of the crosswise component. On the other hand, Moore et al. [58] found the crosswise Reynolds normal stress component having the largest peak using a two-wire HW probe in a low-speed linear cascade wind tunnel.

Fig. 4.119 illustrates the symmetric DA defined by Eq. 2.66 for the test cases of $Re_{out, is} = 70k$ and $M_{out, is} = 0.70, 0.90,$ and 0.95 measured with PIV. The TG is installed for all test cases. Positive values of the DA_{sym} are distributed on the suction side region up to 50% of the cascade pitch and above 6% of the blade span. The vortical structures observed in Fig. 4.117 generate anisotropic turbulence in this region, especially at the interface of the TSV with the freestream or the upper part of the PV. A precedent study of turbulence anisotropy in the flow downstream of an airfoil showed a distribution of high DA on the suction side near the boundary between the wake and freestream regions [46], suggesting that the high DA occurs in the area where shear layers are present. The anisotropy of the turbulence field downstream of the LPT cascade was also observed in [50].

On the other hand, the pressure side region up to 20-40% of the cascade pitch is characterized by the negative DA_{sym} where the contribution of $\overline{V'_{crs}}$ and $\overline{V'_{rad}}$ are more pronounced than the streamwise component. A similar distribution of the DA was measured by Porreca et al. [45] using a two-sensor fast response probe downstream of the annular stator vanes. He ascribed the crosswise dominant turbulence anisotropy to the stretching of the streamwise vorticity component in the uniform flow region. Similarly, Chasoglou et al. [59] reported a DA downstream of a rotor row using a four-sensor fast response probe. The measured turbulence field exhibited a similar DA distribution where streamwise turbulence fluctuation becomes more pronounced in the rotor wake and secondary flow structures.

Interestingly, the area with $DA_{sym} \approx 0$, i.e. isotropic region, is found around the wake center and on the suction side between 0-50% pitch below 5% blade span. This may imply that the turbulence fluctuations are redistributed in all directions within the secondary flow structures that enhance the isotropic flow mixing.

By increasing the outlet Mach number, the TI of all components consistently decreases, and the area of the negative DA_{sum} expands. On the other hand, the Mach number fields show that the size of the secondary flow region is maintained or even reduced. This indicates that, at higher Mach numbers, the stretching effect on the flow fluctuations by the freestream becomes stronger, and the effect is especially more pronounced for the streamwise component than the transverse components.

Figure 4.119: Symmetric degree of anisotropy on the COP for $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.70$, 0.90 , and 0.95 with TG.

Another approach to characterize turbulence anisotropy is the use of the invariants of anisotropy tensor introduced by Lumley and Newman [60]. The method is described in section 2.5.4. Fig. 4.120 illustrates the anisotropy invariant map (AIM) [60], also called Lumley triangle, for different outlet Mach numbers. Each marker represents the local state of turbulence by its location within the triangle whose bounds are defined by the realizability of turbulence decomposition. In some regions, the measured turbulence anisotropy is found in the unrealizable range. The anisotropy tensor in these regions is rescaled to retain information about the turbulence componentality. The rescaling method is addressed in Appendix B.

While the AIM provides a convenient method to depict graphically the state of turbulence, its presentation can be misleading due to the non-linearity hidden in the definition of variants I_2 and I_3 . Re-projection of the state of turbulence from the non-linear to the linear domain is realized in Fig. 4.121, using the barycentric map introduced by Banerjee et al. [61]. Similar to AIM, the vertices of the barycentric map represent the three limiting states of turbulence. For the investigation of a large number of data points provided by PIV, it is convenient to use the componentality contour as proposed by Emory and Iaccarino [62]. Using their method, a colormap that represents anisotropy componentality information is reconstructed in the physical domain from the coordinates in the barycentric map. The colormap scheme (a), (b), and (c) refereed in this study is presented in Fig. 4.122.

The componentality contours obtained from the PIV measurements, using the color scheme (a) and (b), are presented in Fig. 4.123. The black contour lines represent the Mach number distribution for the corresponding flow condition. The PIV results are compared with the large eddy simulations (LES) conducted on the same SPLEEN C1 cascade performed by Perkins [63]. Fig. 4.124 and 4.125 present the predicted componentality contours on the B2B plane at 30% blade span and on the COP at $0.1-0.5 x/C_{ax}$ downstream the blade trailing edge, respectively. His results are presented using the color scheme (c). An analysis of turbulence anisotropy using the componentality contour approach is also reported by Afshar et al. [64] and Morsbach et al. [41] for the MTU T161 LPT cascade as shown in Fig. 4.126 and 4.127.

In the freestream, the PIV results show the two-component turbulence fluctuations. A similar behavior is reproduced by the LES predictions. This is due to the acceleration of the

flow stretching the inlet isotropic turbulence in the streamwise direction. The stretching process of the turbulence fluctuation is observed as a change of color through the blade passage in the results of LES (from cyan to magenta in Fig. 4.126 and from blue to green in Fig. 4.124). In the secondary flow region near the endwall, the turbulence is closer to the isotropic state. This observation is also aligned with the LES predictions. Morsbach et al. [41] argued that the turbulence becomes close to isotropy in the area where the passage vortex influences. The thin vertical distribution of the one-component turbulence state near the blade suction side (red in RGB colormap and yellow in YCM colormap) is presumably attributed to the turbulence characteristic in the blade surface boundary layer. Afshar et al. [64] reported that the flow near the blade surface is governed by a one-component anisotropy state. Increasing the outlet Mach number, the two-component turbulence distribution in the freestream expanded towards the endwall whereas, near the core of the Mach number deficit, the turbulence state seems to become closer to isotropic.

In summary, the turbulence fields in the transonic turbine cascade exhibited a complex constitution, a significant diversity of the states of turbulence were found in different regions. PIV measurements generally agreed with the predictions made by LES, suggesting the potential of the technique for turbulence anisotropy analysis.

Figure 4.120: Anisotropy invariant map for $Re_{out, is} = 70k$ and $M_{out, is} = 0.70, 0.90,$ and 0.95 with TG.

Figure 4.121: Anisotropy barycentric map for $Re_{out, is} = 70k$ and $M_{out, is} = 0.70, 0.90,$ and 0.95 with TG.

Figure 4.122: Color schemes for anisotropy componentality contours.

Figure 4.123: Anisotropy componentality contours obtained from PIV for $Re_{out,is} = 70k$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.70, 0.90, \text{ and } 0.95$ with TG.

Figure 4.124: Anisotropy componentality contours on B2B plane obtained from LES on the SPLEEN C1 cascade for $Re_{out,is} = 70k$, $M_{out,is} = 0.90$, and inlet TI of 2.4% [63]

Figure 4.125: Anisotropy componentality contours on cascade outlet planes obtained from LES on the SPLEEN C1 cascade for $Re_{out,is} = 70k$, $M_{out,is} = 0.90$, and inlet TI of 2.4% [63]

Figure 4.126: Anisotropy componentality contours on B2B plane obtained from LES on the MTU T161 cascade for $Re_{out,is} = 90K$ and $M_{out,is} = 0.60$, and inlet TI of about 5% [64].

Figure 4.127: Anisotropy componentality contours in blade passages obtained from LES on the MTU T161 cascade for $Re_{out, is} = 90K$ and $M_{out, is} = 0.60$, and inlet TI of about 5% [41].

4.3 Rotating annular cascade tests in a short-duration high-speed test rig (CT-3)

In this section, the results of PIV implementation in the CT-3 short-duration rotating turbine stage test rig are presented. First, the effectiveness of seeding approaches and image preprocessing schemes are evaluated to establish a robust measurement setup for obtaining valid velocity fields. Subsequently, the convergence of rainbow-averaged PLA velocity fields for the available number of samples is verified and the measurement uncertainty is quantified. The rainbow-averaged and sector-resolved PLA flow fields are compared against RANS predictions and 4HP measurements, offering insights into the validity and limitations of the measurement. Finally, a result obtained using the fluorescent tracer particle is introduced and the feasibility of the technique is discussed.

4.3.1 Seeding effectiveness

The effectiveness of the seeding probe designs and seeding locations is evaluated based on the intensity of particle images recorded with different seeding setups. The seven colormaps (i - vii) in Fig. 4.128 represent the image intensities averaged over the testing time for the different seeding setups. The images are recorded at 38% rotor span height maintaining the same recording setup except for the seeding probe and location. The seeding locations and the design of the seeding probes are illustrated on the left with indicators 1-3 and A-C, respectively. Above each colormap, the corresponding seeding setup is specified. The letter 'P' indicates seeding via the rim seal purge supply line.

Fig. 4.129 presents the area-average of each image intensity colormap. Surprisingly, probe design A results in a higher image intensity compared to the other two designs, despite having the smallest opening area. Comparing setups ii, iv, and v, the seeding slot 1 exhibits the highest image intensity, although the distribution appears concentrated in the upper part of the FOV. Considering the significant flow turning through the NGV and the circumferential transport through the rotor passage, particles seeded from slot 3 do not appear to effectively enter the FOV. The injection of particles in the rim seal purge flow contributes to the seeding in the FOV to some extent. Overall, using all available seeding slots yields the highest seeding density, making this setup the choice for productive tests in this study. Although the insertion of the seeding probe in front of the NGV certainly causes disturbances in the flow, the current approach is accepted due to the unavailability of alternative seeding access. While the impact of the seeding on the rig operating condition is shown to be marginal (see section 3.23), the local flow disturbances caused by the probe blockage effect and the added seeding mass flow are not quantified in this study.

4.3.2 Recorded images

Acquiring particle images with adequate image characteristics: particle diameter, shape, seeding density, and signal-to-noise ratio, is particularly challenging in this test case due to the geometrical complexity and transient operation of the test rig. Fig. 4.130 displays the exemplary raw particle images recorded at three different rotor span heights, $h/h_r = 38\%$, 50%, and 58%. The particles appear blurred, making it challenging to distinguish individual

Figure 4.128: Normalized time-averaged intensity of particle images with different seeding setups.

Figure 4.129: Time- and Area-averaged normalized intensity of particle image.

particles. This is attributed to the combined effect of optical distortion caused by the curved window and the accumulation of seeding particles and machine lubrication oil on the wet surface of the window. Furthermore, the images exhibit an uneven seeding density and light intensity distribution including a pronounced reflection on the blade trailing edge.

The lack of particles in the blade suction side downstream the trailing edge is attributed to the lower seeding density caused by the particle drift on the blade surface as addressed in section 4.2.2.2. The stator-rotor interaction may also prevent seeded flow from reaching certain areas as a function of relative stator-rotor positions, resulting in poorly seeded images at certain phases in certain regions. Besides, transient operation of the test rig in which the flow condition drastically changes while being established can also cause a deviation of seeding density from the optimum condition. Such an imperfect image quality necessitates image preprocessing to enhance particle image signals for extracting meaningful flow field information.

Figure 4.130: Exemplary raw images recorded at $h/h_r = 38\%$, 50% , and 58% .

4.3.3 Effect of image preprocessing

Selected combinations of image preprocessing algorithms are listed in Table 4.11. Typical temporal average filters are not usable due to the strong image-to-image variation in background and reflection patterns originating from the rotating components. Fig. 4.131 and 4.132 show examples of raw and pre-processed images with different setups, and their image intensity histograms. The image intensities are normalized by the maximum pixel intensity found in the FOV.

The effectiveness of the image preprocessing is evaluated by the estimated uncertainties.

Table 4.11: Tested image preprocessing schemes.

	Preprocessing schemes
Pre01	CLAHE
Pre02	Sobel filter
Pre03	Bilateral filter
Pre04	POD-BG removal (98%)
Pre05	CLAHE + Bilateral filter
Pre06	CLAHE + Sobel filter + Bilateral filter
Pre07	CLAHE + POD_BG removal (98%) + Bilateral filter

Figure 4.131: Examples of raw and pre-processed images.

Figure 4.132: Histograms of raw and pre-processed images shown in Fig. 4.131.

Here, two uncertainty sources, the correlation statistics (CS)-based [65] and the statistical type A (see the subsection 2.6) uncertainties are considered. Fig 4.133 and 4.134 respectively present the CS-based and type A-based uncertainties distributions. The presented values are obtained from a single blow-down test and phase-lock-averaged in the rotating domain. The CS-based approach calculates the uncertainty of each instantaneous velocity field, indicating confidence in the estimated velocity by statistically evaluating cross-correlation map quality. The type A approach indicates the level of velocity fluctuations over the averaged samples. An excessive level of uncertainty suggests the presence of spurious vectors.

Figure 4.133: Uncertainty of velocity magnitude based on correlation statistics (CS) method.

The Sobel filter [66] and POD background removal [67] are found to be the most effective in reducing the CS-based uncertainty. As both algorithms filter out the low-frequency

Figure 4.134: Uncertainty of velocity magnitude based on statistical evaluation (type A) method.

background noise, a higher peak ratio is assumed in the correlation map. The drawback of this algorithm is a high local type-A uncertainty peak appearing around $\phi/\Delta\phi = 0.3$. This might be due to the local noise signal originating from the reflection on the blade enhanced by the filter. This artifact is found to be suppressed by combining with the contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) [68] and bilateral filter [69].

The area-averaged uncertainties for different preprocessing setups are summarized in Fig. 4.135. Considering the reduced uncertainty and suppressed artifact result, the Pre06 setting consisting of CLAHE, Sobel filter, and bilateral filter is adopted as the nominal image preprocessing scheme. The Pre06 image preprocessing results in a reduction in CS-based uncertainties by 60% and in type A uncertainty by 18%, compared with those obtained from the raw images.

Finally, the absence of the peak-locking effect is verified with the PDF of particle displacement for each velocity component shown in Fig. 4.136. No prominent periodic peaks are found at integer values.

4.3.4 Rainbow-averaged rotating-domain PLA

This subsection presents the results obtained from the rainbow-averaged rotating-domain PLA (see section 3.3.6.2). All velocity fields were used for the PLA process regardless of the rainbow sector group classification. The flow fields are presented in the rotating frame of reference.

Figure 4.135: Area-averaged uncertainties of velocity magnitude based on correlation statistics (CS) and statistical evaluation (type A) methods for different image preprocessing setups.

Figure 4.136: Probability density function (PDF) of particle displacement for the axial (left) and tangential (right) components.

4.3.4.1 Convergence of PLA velocity field

Fig. 4.137 shows the convergence histories of the mean value, 95% CI, and RMS of the velocity magnitude obtained from the rainbow-averaged rotating-domain PLA flow field. The convergence histories are extracted at four different locations denoted by P1 - 4 in Fig. 4.138. The sampling locations are tangentially distributed while maintaining the axial position at $x/C_{ax} = 1.1$. The shaded areas shown in the left figure indicate the 95% CI. In the middle figure, the value of CI is normalized by the local mean velocity magnitude.

The PLA velocity magnitude reasonably converges after averaging 200 samples, although the 95% CI remains over 1% of the mean value even after 500 samples. The RMS values are fairly converged after 200 samples revealing the deterministic RMS levels depending on the rotor-relative locations. Interestingly, the velocity fluctuations at P1 and P4, sampled outside the wake, are higher than those near or in the rotor wake. This could be attributed to the rotating-domain rephasing process. While the sampling location is fixed with respect to the rotor blade, the relative location to the upstream vane can vary. Averaging this upstream vane effect may cause an increase in the statistical velocity fluctuation.

In conclusion, for a given image acquisition frequency of 1 kHz, a single blow-down test producing 250 image pairs is anticipated to be sufficient for computing reasonably converged rainbow-averaged mean velocity fields.

Figure 4.137: Convergence history of mean, 95% CI, and RMS of the velocity magnitude sampled at P1 - P4. The data is sampled at $h/h_r = 58\%$.

4.3.4.2 Uncertainty analysis

Fig. 4.139 shows the type A uncertainties of the axial and tangential velocity components, $\Delta \overline{V_{axi,typeA}}$ $\Delta \overline{V_{tan,typeA}}$, calculated using Eq. 2.147 at different rotor spans ($h/h_r = 38\%$, 50% , and 58%). The number of samples is 500 for the measurements at $h/h_r = 38\%$ and 58% whereas only 250 samples are available for the measurement at $h/h_r = 50\%$. The uncertainties are displayed in the rotating frame of reference and normalized by the local mean velocity magnitude. The high uncertainty area diagonally distributing over the FOV indicates a strong velocity fluctuation in the rotor wake. The increase in global uncertainty level as the measurement plane approaches the hub is primarily attributed to the flow unsteadiness of secondary flows, such as the passage vortex. Additionally, the deteriorated image quality, involving the noisier background and amplified optical distortion for the measurement plane closer to the hub, may negatively affect the uncertainty level.

Figure 4.138: Data sampling location P1 - P4 for convergence evaluation. Colormap displays the tangential velocity at $h/h_r = 58\%$.

Figure 4.139: Type A uncertainty of axial (top) and tangential (bottom) velocity components at $h/h_r = 38\%$, 50% , and 58% (from left to right).

In addition to the type A uncertainties, the type B uncertainties are estimated considering the parameters presented in Table 4.12. The uncertainty of calibration plate positioning with respect to the laser sheet plane is estimated to be ± 1 mm for misalignment in optical axis direction (parallel to laser sheet) and ± 2 deg for angular misalignment. The calibration dot pattern is printed by a laser printer at 1200 dots-per-inch (dpi) corresponding to 0.021 mm/dot resolution. The dot pattern physical coordinate uncertainty is estimated to be 0.02 mm assuming 120% of printing resolution. The calibration function fitting error is estimated from the RMS of fitting error computed using the commercial PIV software *Davis*. The uncertainty of laser pulse separation time (4 ns) is determined as 2% of the measured variation in the separation time. The uncertainty of particle displacement is initially assessed using the built-in CS-based method of *Davis*. Fig. 4.140 illustrates the type B uncertainty including the uncertainty of particle displacement estimated with the CS-based method. Despite the improvement made through the tailored image preprocessing, the images still exhibit a low signal-to-noise ratio compared to typical PIV images, yielding an unrealistically high uncertainty level exceeding 20% of the mean velocity magnitude. Alternatively, the type B uncertainty is calculated with a typical particle displacement error of 0.05 pixels attributed to the displacement estimation process using a cross-correlation algorithm with a sub-pixel interpolation [70]. Fig. 4.141 shows the type B uncertainty estimated using this typical error value. While the real uncertainty of particle displacement is not rigorously treated in this assumption, this approach at least provides a reasonable uncertainty level taking into account the minimal contribution of the particle displacement error.

Table 4.12: Sources of type-B uncertainty.

	$h/h_r = 38\%$	$h/h_r = 50\%$	$h/h_r = 58\%$
Calibration plate translation misalignment	± 1 mm (Rectangle distribution)		
Calibration plate angle misalignment	± 2 deg (Rectangle distribution)		
Calibration fitting RMS error	0.163 pixel	0.371 pixel	0.187 pixel
Cross-correlation with sub-pixel interpolation	0.05 pixel		
Pulse separation	4×10^{-9} (Gaussian distribution)		

Finally, the combined and expanded (covering 95% CI) uncertainties of the axial and tangential velocities are presented in Fig. 4.142 for the PIV measurements at different rotor span locations. The maximum uncertainty level excluding the perimeter of the FOV is estimated to be 10% and 7% for axial and tangential velocities, respectively.

4.3.4.3 Comparison between PIV, 4HP, and RANS

Fig. 4.143 presents the contour maps of axial and tangential velocity at $h/h_r = 58\%$, obtained from RANS simulation. The rectangles indicate the FOV of the PIV results and the dashed lines show the location of the 4HP measurements.

Figure 4.140: Type B uncertainty for axial and tangential velocity components including the CS-based uncertainty.

Figure 4.141: Type B uncertainty for axial and tangential velocity components assuming fixed particle displacement uncertainty of 0.05 pixel.

Figure 4.142: Combined uncertainty for axial and tangential velocity components assuming fixed particle displacement uncertainty of 0.05 pixel.

Figure 4.143: Large scale view of axial (left) and tangential (right) velocity components around the rotor predicted by RANS simulation. A slice is made at $h/h_r = 58\%$.

The rainbow-averaged rotating-domain PLA contour maps of the axial and tangential components at 58%, 50%, and 38% span are presented in Fig. 4.144 and 4.145. For comparison, the flow fields predicted by the steady RANS simulation are shown next to the PIV results. The axial component obtained with the PIV generally shows a strong attenuation of the wake deficit as it goes downstream which is not observed from the RANS simulation. The tangential velocity distribution confirms the trend of the flow field characterized by the wake and its size expanding towards the blade hub. The larger size of the wake is considered to be accounted for by the secondary flows merging with the blade profile wake. A particularly good agreement between PIV and RANS is found in the result of the tangential component at 58% blade span.

Figure 4.144: Rainbow-averaged rotating-domain PLA axial velocity measured by PIV compared against RANS simulation.

Fig. 4.146 and 4.147 present the pitchwise distributions of the axial and tangential velocities extracted at different axial locations from Fig. 4.144 and 4.145. The red circle marker, blue triangle marker, and solid black line represent the results of PIV, 4HP, and RANS, respectively. From the left to right columns, the profiles are extracted at $x/C_{ax} = 1.05, 1.10, 1.15,$ and 1.48 . The profiles for the first three axial locations are provided by the PIV measurements whereas the 4HP measurements are performed only at the furthest downstream. As the 4HP measurements are not conducted at the specified span heights of 38%, 50%, and 58%, the plotted data represents the measurements from the two nearest span locations to illustrate variations within the span gap.

Regarding the axial component, at 58% span, PIV persistently measures higher axial velocity than RANS predictions at every axial location. Such a trend is consistent with the measurement result from 4HP. At lower span positions, the magnitude of axial components match broadly, while the shape of the profiles shows discrepancies. The noisier profiles at 50% span are due to a reduced number of available samples. On the other hand, the noisy profiles at 38% span are due to the effect of deteriorated image and diversified secondary flow

Figure 4.145: Rainbow-averaged rotating-domain PLA tangential velocity (rotor relative) measured by PIV compared against RANS simulation.

effect associated with different hub platform geometries. Through all three span positions, the depth of the wake deficit is reduced in the PIV results compared to the RANS predictions. At further downstream locations where 4HP measurements are conducted, the velocity profile is leveled as the wake is diffused, therefore it is difficult to identify the wake velocity deficit.

Looking at the tangential component, the comparison between PIV and RANS shows a good agreement at 58% span. At the midspan, both the PIV and RANS results show consistent wake patterns, however, there are up to 20-40 m/s offset between the measured and predicted profiles. Surprisingly the discrepancy is less pronounced in the comparison at 38% span, the tangential velocity in the wake center matches well between PIV and RANS results. Another interesting feature in comparison at 38% span is the significant mismatch between 4HP and RANS results, despite the comparisons of the results at other span and axial components show generally a good agreement. This might be due to the large variation in the flow angle associated with secondary flow structures being out of the probe calibration range.

One of the causes of discrepancy between PIV and RANS results is considered to be the error in the measurement plane alignment. For example, the misalignment in spanwise direction is estimated to be ± 1 mm, or $\pm 1.5\%$ of the rotor span due to the confined test section making alignment of the laser sheet and calibration plate very challenging.

Another cause can be a deviation of PIV tangential plane from the constant radius slice on which the RANS data is extracted. Fig. 4.148 presents a schematic illustration of the measurement plane system. The magnitude of the deviation increases as the interrogation location on the PIV plane departs from the point of tangency. Table 4.13 summarizes the estimated deviation of measurement location from the constant radius. The maximum mismatch in the radial position is estimated to be 2.8% of the rotor span.

In addition, there is a geometric deviation in the tangential velocity component between PIV and RANS as the in-plane two-component PIV data can not be transformed into cylin-

Figure 4.146: Rainbow-averaged experimental and numerical pitchwise axial velocity profiles at $x/C_{ax} = 1.10, 1.15, 1.20,$ and 1.48 . The results are expressed in the rotating frame of reference.

Table 4.13: Deviation of measurement location from constant radius.

Pitch 1	Pitch 2	Span	Radius	Tangential distance 1	Tangential distance 2	Radial deviation		Plane-normal deviation	
ϕ_1	ϕ_2	h/h_r	R_{span}	d_1	d_2	δ_{R_1}	δ_{R_1}/h_r	δ_{z_1}	δ_{z_1}/h_r
		38%	364.1 mm	35.9 mm	11.9 mm	1.76 mm	2.67%	1.75 mm	2.66%
5.625 [deg]	1.875 deg	50%	372.2 mm	36.6 mm	12.2 mm	1.80 mm	2.73%	1.79 mm	2.72%
		58%	377.3 mm	37.2 mm	12.4 mm	1.83 mm	2.77%	1.82 mm	2.76%

Figure 4.147: Rainbow-averaged experimental and numerical pitchwise tangential velocity profiles at $x/C_{ax} = 1.10, 1.15, 1.20,$ and 1.48 . The results are expressed in the rotating frame of reference.

Figure 4.148: Deviation of PIV measurement plane from the ideal constant radius plane.

drical coordinates. The use of three-component PIV systems such as stereoscopic or tomographic PIV systems is necessary to eliminate this error. Comparing the tangential and circumferential components of the RANS flow field estimates the error to be less than 5%. Nevertheless, the discrepancies associated with the geometric deviation are averaged out through the rephasing of tangential coordinates in the rotor-domain PLA processing. Therefore the actual errors are expected to be smaller than the estimation.

The seeding probe and injected seeding flow cause local disturbance in the flow, potentially modifying the flow field measured downstream. Finally, as the PIV window covers only 0.78% vane pitch, the averaged PIV data can be biased by the variation of the flow field associated with the upstream vane location.

On the other hand, RANS prediction has also limited accuracy. The employment of the turbulence model is known to inaccurately predict airfoil wakes and their mixing behaviors [25].

4.3.5 Sector-resolved PLA

This subsection presents the sector-resolved rotating-domain PLA results. Each instantaneous velocity fields are classified into six blade sectors (H1T1, H1T2, H2T1, H2T2, H3T1, and H4T1. See subsection 3.3.2.2) before applying the PLA processing.

4.3.5.1 Distribution of sector groups

For the sector-resolved PLA, only the six central passages of each sector are considered in the averaging operation to exclude sector-to-sector flow interactions and ensure optimal sector flow periodicity. Justification of the number of central passages for averaging is reported

in [71]. Fig. 4.149 shows the distribution of PIV samples over different sectors of the rainbow rotor. In the current setup, the PIV acquisition frequency is limited to 1 kHz and the testing time is about 250 ms. While two blow-down test datasets, producing a total of 500 instantaneous velocity fields, are available for $h/h_r = 58\%$ and 38% , only one single blow-down test dataset, comprising 250 PIV recordings, is produced for $h/h_r = 50\%$. In total, about 25% of the PIV datasets are classified as sector-to-sector interface data and discarded for the sector-resolved PLA processing. No significant bias in the sector distribution is observed.

Figure 4.149: Distributions of blade sector groups.

4.3.5.2 Convergence history

Fig. 4.150 presents the convergence histories of the sector-resolved area- and phase-lock-averaged velocity magnitude (top) and its 95% CI (bottom). While a converging trend is seen, the level of the 95% CI achieved for the available samples (about 60 samples) is approximately 5% of the mean value which can be too large for differentiating the sector-related flow features. Repeating more blow-down tests are required to record enough number of recordings for the sector-resolved PLA. For example, the convergence history of rainbow-averaged PLA results suggests the use of a minimum of 200 images for proper evaluation of PLA fields. To obtain 200 images for each sector in the current rainbow rotor configuration (6 sectors), one of the following approaches or compromise between those two is required: repeating four blow-down tests with the same sampling frequency (1 kHz) and/or performing a single measurement at an acquisition frequency higher than 4 kHz.

4.3.5.3 Sector-to-sector comparison

Fig. 4.151 and 4.152 show the sector-resolved rotating-domain PLA velocity magnitude ($|V|$) and yaw angle β at $h/h_r = 38\%$ compared against steady RANS simulations. For the blade geometry H1T2, the velocity and yaw angle are presented in the absolute values. For the rest of the blade sectors, the colormaps represent the difference from H1T2. Even though the convergence history (Fig. 4.150) implies the number of samples would not be sufficient to achieve convergence for the sector-resolved results, some deterministic variations are depicted between the different blade geometries. For example, a slightly higher velocity magnitude is observed for the reference axisymmetric hub (H1T1 and H1T2) in both PIV and RANS results. Also, a higher yaw angle distribution for the blade geometry H3T1 is consistent in PIV and RANS. Given the measurement span position being close to the hub ($h/h_r = 38\%$), the effect of the hub-contouring is expected to be responsible for these variations.

Figure 4.150: Convergence histories of the sector-resolved area-averaged PLA velocity magnitude for $h/h_r = 38\%$ and 58% . Top: mean value. Bottom: 95% confidence interval normalized by the mean value.

Figure 4.151: Sector-resolved velocity magnitude $|V|$ at $h/h_r = 38\%$ Top: measured with PIV. Bottom: RANS prediction.

Figure 4.152: Sector-resolved vyan angle β at $h/h_r = 38\%$ Top: measured with PIV. Bottom: RANS prediction.

Further simplified results are shown in Fig. 4.153 by comparing the pitchwise averaged in-plane velocity magnitude and yaw angle. The displayed quantities are the difference from the H1T2 sector normalized by the H1T2 value. The data of two rotor span locations, $h/h_r = 38\%$ and 58% , are plotted in the left and right columns, respectively. Every subfigure has four clusters consisting of rainbow bar plots, presenting data of PIV (at $x/C_{ax} = 1.1$), RANS (at $x/C_{ax} = 1.1$), 4HP ($x/C_{ax} = 1.48$), and RANS (at $x/C_{ax} = 1.48$) from left to right. Each bar in the clusters represents the value of the rainbow-sector, H1T1 (yellow), H2T1 (blue), H2T2 (red), H3T1 (green), and H4T1 (pink), from left to right.

At $h/h_r = 38\%$, PIV and RANS at $x/C_{ax} = 1.1$ exhibit a similar ranking order whereas 4HP and RANS at $x/C_{ax} = 1.48$ disagrees with each other. One can assume that a strong effect of the contoured hub geometries present near the endwall is captured by both PIV and RANS near the blade while the complex mixing phenomena downstream resulted in a discrepancy between the 4HP and RANS results.

At $h/h_r = 58\%$, the ranking obtained from PIV seems to be closer to that of 4HP downstream, instead of the RANS prediction at the same axial location. Such a trend is pronounced in the yaw angle comparison. Possibly, the experimental results present the effect of the hub contouring reaching over the blade midspan whereas the RANS predicts its impact is minor at this rotor span height.

Overall, regardless of the limited number of samples, the relative differences between sectors seem to be partially observed by the PIV measurements, demonstrating its potential capability as an investigation tool for the rainbow rotor setup even in a short-duration test rig. The reliability and accuracy of the results can be increased by maximizing the number of test repetitions or the acquisition frequency.

4.3.6 Application of fluorescent PIV in CT-3

Additionally, PIV measurements using the novel fluorescent tracer particle (see subsection 2.3) are carried out in CT-3 in order to investigate the feasibility of the technique in an engine-relevant turbomachinery testing environment. The measurement is carried out at 50% rotor span height. The fluorescent particle is made of a solution of DEHS and P567 at 1.25 g/L concentration. Due to the limited amount of the fluorescent solution, only a single seeding generator (*PIVpart14*) is employed. The particles are injected using the seeding slot 1 (see Fig. 3.115). An OD6 optical band-stop filter with a blocking wavelength of 532 ± 10 nm FWHM is attached to the camera lens. While the standard PIV technique requires a part of the optical window to be covered as shown in Fig. 3.111 to avoid excessive light incidence to the camera sensor, the fluorescent PIV technique does not require such a treatment as the filter cuts off the undesired light reflections. Consequently, the region of interest is enlarged to the rear part of the blade passage as shown in Fig. 4.154. The rest of the setup is maintained the same as that of the standard PIV measurements.

Fig. 4.155 (a) shows a cropped snapshot of a raw particle image taken without the optical filter. Reflections on the rotor surface and background are evident. Most notably, the reflection near the rotor trailing edge is excessively strong, resulting in a residual image effect in the successive frame (pixels completely blacked out) which prevents the estimation of vectors in the region. Besides, the employment of pricey high-speed cameras should be avoided under such circumstances due to possible damage to the image sensor.

Figure 4.153: Sector-resolved pitchwise averaged velocity magnitude (top) and yaw angle (bottom) obtained by PIV and 4HP measurements, and RANS simulations at $h/h_r = 38\%$ (left) and 58% (right).

Figure 4.154: Field of view of the fluorescent PIV measurements in CT-3.

The removal of the undesired reflection is achieved in the fluorescent particle images as shown in Fig. 4.155 (b) and (c). Image (b) is taken at a time when the flow is being established whereas image (c) is captured during the testing time. The timing of image acquisition for images (b) and (c) aligns with the timing (ii) and (iii) indicated in Fig 3.22. A visible reflection on the rotor blade surface is attributed to the deposit of fluorescent oil on the blade surface. The critical issue with the fluorescent particle images lies in the much weaker particle signals limiting the number of particles appearing in raw images. This limitation stems from the necessity of higher illumination intensity for fluorescence imaging, which restricts the observable particles to those within an area where both the illumination intensity and seeding density are sufficiently high. With the use of only one seeding generator, the seeding density is globally lower than that in the standard PIV test case. The absence of particles on the suction side downstream of the trailing edge is attributed to the uneven seeding distribution, given that the seeding is injected only through slot 1. Additionally, fewer particles are observed in the images taken during the testing time. One potential cause is the accumulation of oil droplets on the wet surface of the optical window, absorbing fluorescence signals emitted from the particles. For the current setup, improvement in the image quality is limited by the capacity of the laser system and the available amount of fluorescent oil. The laser power output is set to the system's maximum level, corresponding to a laser pulse intensity of about 20 mJ.

Figure 4.155: Snapshots of particle images in the rotor passage taken (a) without filter during testing time, (b) with filter before testing time, (c) with filter during testing time.

Fig. 4.156 displays contour maps of the instantaneous axial velocity at different time instants. The left and right columns represent before and during the testing time, respectively. The figures in the top row are acquired with the fluorescent PIV, whereas the bottom figures are obtained with the standard PIV technique. Fig. 4.157 presents the PLA axial velocity fields in the rotating frame of reference. Subfigure (a) is obtained with fluorescent PIV

by combining snapshots captured before-the-testing-time and during-the-testing-time. The reduced number of useful particle images captured during the testing time necessitates the inclusion of before-the-testing-time snapshots. Subfigure (b) is obtained with the standard PIV taking only the during-the-testing-time snapshots. In total 229 and 124 instantaneous velocity fields are applicable for the PLA of the fluorescent and standard PIV, respectively. Subfigure (c) shows the prediction obtained from the steady-RANS simulation. Fig. 4.158 and 4.159 show the same figures for the tangential velocity components.

Fig. 4.160 shows profiles of velocity components extracted from Fig. 4.157 and 4.159 along with the lines L_1 and L_2 as indicated with solid lines. While L_1 goes through the rotor passage with an angle approximately aligned to the outlet flow angle, L_2 is defined at a constant axial location downstream of the rotor $x/C_{ax} = 1.1$.

Figure 4.156: Instantaneous axial velocity fields obtained from Fluorescent PIV (top) and standard PIV (bottom). Left column: Results captured before testing time. Right column: Results captured during testing time.

The colormaps illustrate the extended measured area by the fluorescent PIV compared to the standard PIV. Vectors in the rotor passage and proximity to the blade surface are partially retrieved, especially before the testing time when more particles appear in the raw images as seen in Fig. 4.155. However, since the flow is still being established at this time, the flow field deviates from the nominal steady condition. On the contrary, during testing time, the

Figure 4.157: Comparison of mean axial velocity fields. (a) PLA result using fluorescent PIV images captured before and during testing time. (b) PLA result using standard PIV images captured during testing time. (c) Steady RANS simulation result.

Figure 4.158: Instantaneous tangential velocity fields obtained from Fluorescent PIV (top) and standard PIV (bottom). Left column: Results captured before the testing time. Right column: Results captured during the testing time.

Figure 4.159: Comparison of mean tangential velocity fields. (a) PLA result using fluorescent PIV images captured before and during testing time. (b) PLA result using standard PIV images captured during testing time. (c) Steady RANS simulation result.

Figure 4.160: Profiles of axial (left) and tangential (right) velocity components extracted along lines L_1 (top) and L_2 (bottom).

flow field obtained with the fluorescent PIV are fairly similar to the standard PIV and RANS, although it has a notable amount of blank spots due to the lack of particles in the image. The comparison of the velocity profile along L_1 shows relatively good agreement, capturing the global trend of the flow through the rotor passage. On the other hand, the comparison along L_2 shows significantly diversified profiles.

The inclusion of the pre-testing-time data is obviously one of the causes of the discrepancy. Acquiring more images by repeating blow-down tests or increasing acquisition frequency is a solution to obtain a larger number of snapshots during testing time. However, the fundamental issue is the poor seeding and illumination conditions of the current setup that yielded low signal-to-noise ratio in the fluorescent particle images.

Fig. 4.161 displays the valid number of vectors. The left figure considers only during-the-testing-time recordings whereas the right figure includes both before- and during-the-testing-time recordings. Very few, below 40% of total samples, are valid for the data acquired during the testing time. Extending the averaging window to the before-testing time, the region with a large number of valid vectors appears near the pressure side of the rotor. This region corresponds to the area where the particles are illuminated relatively well with the central part of the laser sheet and its reflection on the rotor surface. Assessment of raw particle images also shows that this region tends to have a higher seeding density.

Figure 4.161: Fraction of the number of valid vectors to the total number of available velocity fields from before-testing and during-testing time (229 velocity fields).

Overall, the attempt to apply the fluorescent PIV technique to the short-duration rotating turbine test facility clarified the challenges involved in the technique and its application. The major drawback is the reduction of particle image signals since the intensity of fluorescence is much weaker than that of Mie scattering, resulting in very few valid vectors retained in the FOV. Since the current fluorescent PIV setup only utilizes a single seeding generator, there is still room for improvement in seeding density by adding seeding generators and injecting more tracer particles using the vacant seeding slots and via the rim seal purge line. Another approach is increasing the dye concentration, which would enhance the quantum yield of the fluorescent particle. Based on the measurement result presented in Fig. 2.32, the fluorescence intensity is expected to increase by 30% by raising the dye concentration from 1.25 g/L to

2.00 g/L. Employing a more powerful laser system would improve the image signal-to-noise ratio, as the fluorescent PIV technique typically requires the pulse intensity to be 2-3 times higher compared to the standard PIV. However, the use of higher pulse intensity raises the risk of laser-induced damage to the optical window of the laser endoscope.

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5

Conclusions

This thesis has presented the design and implementation of PIV measurement systems in turbomachinery-related applications and evaluated the feasibility and capability of the technique. The experimental test campaigns were conducted in three test facilities of the von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics, namely: the L-12 low-speed wind tunnel equipped with an active turbulence grid, the S-1 high-speed wind tunnel hosting a linear low-pressure turbine cascade, and the CT-3 short-duration high-speed rotating test rig fitted with a single high-pressure turbine stage.

Several techniques necessary for PIV measurements in the presented applications were introduced in this thesis.

Two laser endoscopes were designed and manufactured to deliver a laser sheet into confined test sections in the S-1/C and CT-3 wind tunnels. Both scopes incorporate a plano-concave cylindrical lens and a mirror prism to create a laser sheet with a right angle relative to the probe axis. The first endoscope, which adopted an 8mm external diameter, was designed to fit the existing slot in the CT-3 test section, and its emitting port was sealed with an acrylic window. The window was found to be vulnerable to high-intensity short pulses (over 80 mJ with a pulse width of 10 ns), which is commonly used for low-speed PIV system. Nevertheless, the window withstood the use with a high-speed laser system with a relatively lower pulse intensity (up to 40 mJ with a pulse width of 120 ns), enabling the PIV measurements in the enclosed annular cascade test rig. The second laser endoscope, which adopted a 9 mm external diameter, used a cylindrical quartz glass window. The quartz glass showed a higher damage threshold compared to acrylic, withstanding the pulsed laser with an approximate pulse intensity of 120 mJ. The higher laser induced damage threshold allowed us to conduct PIV measurements in the S-1/C transonic cascade wind tunnel where a high-intensity laser pulse was needed for recordings of particle images with limited seeding capacity.

A sub-micron scale fluorescent particle, based on DEHS with P567 dye, was developed to eliminate undesired reflections and to distinguish a specific flow from surrounding flows.

Fluorescence spectra of bulk solutions of P567 in DEHS, excited by Nd:YLF laser (wavelength: 527 nm wavelength) showed intensity peaks between 540 and 585 nm, providing useful information for the selection of optical filters. The fluorescence intensity in the form of sub-micron scale droplets was investigated by pixel intensity of particle images. The intensity level was found to be primarily proportional to the dye concentration. The fluorescent particle was employed for PIV measurements in the L-12 wind tunnel to distinguish the synthetic jet from the main flow. The performance of the fluorescent particle as a measure of undesired reflection removal was assessed in the CT-3 wind tunnel, revealing remaining challenges to be used in high-speed flows and non-homogeneous seeding conditions.

5.1 Summary of test cases

5.1.1 Active turbulence grid tests in a low-speed wind tunnel (L-12)

The PIV measurement on the active turbulence grid presented the core capability of the fluorescent particle as a simultaneous multi-constituent flow field acquisition technique. The main flow and the synthetic jet injection were distinguished by employing the standard mineral oil particle and the fluorescent particle for each flow. A set of image pre-processing was found to be effective in extracting the jet-only flow field. The flow unsteadiness behind the bar was investigated using the proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) technique. The synthetic jet was found to diminish the large-scale Karman vortex formation. The synthetic jet filled the bar wake and a strong shear layer was formed between the jet and the main flow. This enhanced the mixing process behind the bar, making the turbulence intensity (TI) and integral scale more uniform downstream of the bar.

5.1.2 Linear cascade tests in a high-speed wind tunnel (S-1/C)

The PIV measurements in the high-speed linear cascade flow were carried out in three configurations: on the midspan blade-to-blade (B2B) plane upstream of the cascade, on the midspan B2B in the cascade passage and downstream, and on the cascade outlet plane (COP) 50% downstream of the blade trailing edge.

The measurements on the upstream B2B plane were conducted to verify the capability of PIV as an investigation tool for the inlet flow condition of the high-speed cascade testing. The laser endoscope developed in this study was employed in order to deliver the laser sheet in the cascade inlet where no direct optical access for the light sheet insertion was available. A parametric study on the data acquisition and processing settings confirmed that the measured TI is more sensitive to the setting parameters than the mean flow quantity such as the velocity magnitude and flow angles. An especially high sensitivity to the particle displacement suggested acquiring images with multiple pulse separation times for accurate measurement results. The flow fields for the on- and off-design flow conditions showed a reasonably good agreement with the results obtained from 5HP measurements and RANS predictions. The discrepancy between PIV and 5HP compared at 50% upstream of the blade trailing edge amounted to 0.02 for the Mach number and 0.5 degrees for the yaw angle. The measured TI

was about 1.7-2.0% with the upstream TG and 0.6-1.0% without the TG. The TI measured with PIV at the design flow condition was 0.5% lower than the TI measured with a HW at the same flow condition.

The PIV measurements on the B2B plane in the blade passage and downstream were conducted to exploit the performance of the PIV technique in a transonic and high-velocity gradient flow, and to cross-validate the RANS predictions and 5HP measurement results. The measurements were carried out for the outlet Reynolds number of 70k and 120k, outlet Mach number of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95, with and without the TG. The high-speed flow condition and aggressive curvature of the blade caused a deviation of particle path from the fluid streamline, resulting in the absence of particles near the blade suction surface. A Lagrangian particle tracking simulation suggested the use of particle sizing below $0.5 \mu\text{m}$ to enable the tracer particle to follow the flow near the blade surface. The flow fields for the on- and off-design conditions revealed a good agreement in the global flow topology between PIV and RANS. The comparison of the PIV and 5HP results highlighted the probe interference effect: the 5HP struggles to retrieve the correct absolute Mach number and the flow angles in high-speed cascade flows.

The measurements on the COP were performed using a stereoscopic setup to capture three-dimensional secondary flow structures present near the cascade endwall. The measurements were carried out for a outlet Reynolds number of 70k and varying outlet Mach number of 0.70, 0.90, and 0.95 with the TG. The measured three velocity components represented the typical secondary flow topology found in linear cascade flows, aligning with the results obtained with the 5HP measurements. As it was observed in the measurement on the B2B plane, the 5HP results exhibited the underestimation in the Mach number due to the probe blockage effect, emphasizing the importance of a non-intrusive approach for the measurements in transonic cascade testing. The turbulence field at the COP was analyzed in terms of TI, degree of anisotropy, and anisotropy invariant map. The results were globally aligned with the literature, suggesting potential uses of the PIV for investigations of secondary flow and turbulence fields in high-speed turbomachinery flows.

5.1.3 Rotating annular cascade tests in a short-duration high-speed test rig (CT-3)

PIV measurements in the CT-3 short-duration rotating turbine rig demonstrated the feasibility of the measurement technique in a complex test facility that can simulate engine-relevant flow conditions. The testing environment was even more challenging with the adoption of the rainbow rotor configuration where multiple blade geometries were tested in a single rotor. The region of interest was on a tangential plane at 38%, 50%, and 58% of the rotor blade span, covering a full rotor pitch downstream of the rotor between 105% and 120% of the rotor axial chord.

An evaluation of convergence history concluded a minimum of 200 recordings were required to achieve a converged phase-lock-average (PLA) flow field. With the current setup, each test generated 250 pairs of snapshots providing a sufficient number of samples for the rainbow-averaged PLA. The sector-resolved PLA results suggested 7-10 repetitive tests for convergence due to the reduced number of sector-bounded snapshots available.

The rainbow-average PLA results qualitatively confirmed the flow features predicted by the RANS simulation, characterized by the rotor wake. Particularly, the tangential component at $h/h_r = 58\%$ showed a good agreement with the RANS result. On the other hand, distinct discrepancies were observed in the axial velocity component for every span position and in the tangential component at $h/h_r = 50\%$.

The sector-resolved PLA presented distinctive velocity distributions dependent on different blade geometries despite the reduced number of samples which could not grant complete convergence.

5.1.4 Reviews of PIV measurements in turbomachinery flows

Through these three test cases, the current study concludes that PIV is a promising investigation tool for turbomachinery flows. Particularly, the verification of the applicability of PIV to transonic, high velocity gradient turbine flow is the main novel outcome of the thesis. With PIV, it is possible to obtain various flow characteristics, namely, velocities and vorticities either in mean or phase-lock-averaged manner, as well as turbulence intensity and anisotropy, even in challenging engine-relevant flow conditions. On the other hand, the study also addresses how the technique is sensitive to the way the measurement systems are installed and the results are processed. Furthermore, measuring the boundary layer over a turbine blade with a strong curvature is still prohibited due to the nature of motion dynamics and light scattering of the tracer particles. Overall, expertise in the technique is necessary to setup the measurement system properly and yield trustworthy results. To facilitate this, the succeeding section provides guidelines for the successful implementation of the technique. Future work could combine PIV, CFD, and other measurement results using data assimilation techniques to mutually complement the shortcomings of each technique and provide whole-field flow information with high accuracy.

5.2 Guidelines for implementation of PIV in turbomachinery flows

Finally, this thesis concludes with guidelines for implementing PIV in turbomachinery flows. The guidelines are divided into three parts based on the experimental phases.

5.2.1 Design phase

A design of experiments is key for successful measurement. The first design aspect to consider is the feasibility of seeding in the test facility. It is highly recommended to explore various options, as estimating the exact seeding distribution and density prior to experiments is not trivial work. This consideration becomes crucial in turbomachinery applications, where one must account for the aggressive flow turning through blade passages and circumferential transport by rotating components. Typically, tracer particles are introduced in an upstream settling chamber using distributors, such as probes and rakes, to achieve a homogeneous seeding distribution and minimize disturbances in the flow in the test section. Some legacy test facilities, like CT-3, may have specific geometries that constrain accessibility for seeding. This thesis demonstrated the possibility of injecting tracer particles through the slot for

inlet flow monitoring probes. While the influence of seeding injection on the overall operating point of the turbine stage was marginal, the impact on the local flow field has not been quantified.

In terms of particle material, the first constraint is the compatibility with the test facility. For turbomachinery applications, oil-based droplets are usually more suitable than solid particles, considering agglomerations and potential damage to the facility components such as the lubrication system. The other characteristics to be considered for the particle material are its density, viscosity, refractive index, and flash point. Density is one of the key parameters that determine the flow traceability, whereas the viscosity (and also density) matters for compatibility with seeding devices.

A common seeding device that can produce particles at a high particle production rate is the Laskin-nozzle type, which relies on the shear stress between the induced jet and oil in the device. Typical Laskin-nozzle seeding generators produce particles with a diameter of 0.5-1.0 μm when used with DEHS or vegetable oils. It is recommended to analyze particle size when materials with different characteristics are used. The relaxation time of particle, accelerating/decelerating in a flow, is proportional to the particle density and the square of particle diameter, making using small particles crucial for ensuring flow traceability. Seeding in the boundary layer over a turbine blade surface with a strong curvature is challenging due to the centrifugal force acting on the particle. Currently, studying this region with PIV is limited to low-speed testing conditions. For transonic cascades, the particle size has to be below 0.1 μm to obtain seeding particles within the boundary layer. One must note, however, that a particle size smaller than the wavelength of illumination light results in a much weaker scattering intensity. The refractive index is a parameter that affects the light scattering characteristics. For applications that reproduce engine-relevant flow conditions, where the flow temperature can be significantly high, the flash point of the particle should be considered to ensure that the particle survives during the test.

The use of fluorescent particles is an option for eliminating undesired reflections on surfaces of obstacles and casings or for differentiating a specific flow within multi-constituent flows. The current study showed that imaging fluorescence requires a much higher illumination intensity compared to typical Mie-scattering recordings.

The second consideration is optical systems. It is essential to define the measurement objective and verify if the available equipment is satisfactory for it. The acquisition frequency is one of the main parameters to consider. Common low-speed PIV systems consist of a high pulse intensity laser (~ 200 mJ) and cameras with high pixel resolutions (~ 4 MP) for acquisition frequencies of 10 \sim 15 Hz. Typical high-speed PIV systems can acquire pairs of images at 100 \sim 10000 Hz, utilizing a high-repetition-rate laser with a typical pulse intensity of 20 \sim 60 mJ and high-speed cameras with a relatively low camera resolution 1 \sim 2 MP. If the measurement purpose is to fully resolve flow unsteadiness over a periodic event, such as the wake-boundary layer interaction and evolution of transitional boundary layer over the blade or bar passing period, a high-speed PIV system is necessary. Alternatively, it is a common practice to employ a low-speed PIV system and perform phase-locked image acquisitions to obtain quasi-time-resolved phase-lock-averaged flow fields. The synchronization of the PIV system with the phase of the rotating component is essential for phase-resolved measurement. Another situation where the use of a high-speed PIV system becomes necessary is testing in short-duration facilities. As presented in this thesis, the limited testing time necessitates the

use of a high-speed PIV system to maximize the number of recordings. One must note that high-speed cameras usually have a larger pixel size $20 \sim 28 \mu\text{m}$ to increase the sensitivity to light. Therefore, a higher optical magnification and a smaller FOV are required to ensure a sufficient particle size on the image so that the peak-locking effect is avoided.

Additionally, when conducting stereoscopic measurements, one must ensure the optimal viewing angle (around 90 degrees) between two cameras. This can be achieved by either having a sufficiently large window shared by two cameras or by having multiple windows, each providing individual viewing access to one camera.

The easiest method for introducing a light sheet into the test section is through an optical window. This approach is typically possible for rectangular wind tunnels and linear cascade test rigs. For investigations on the boundary layer of a blade, it is advisable to design the optical access so that it allows alignment of the laser sheet parallel to the blade surface. This setup minimizes reflections on the blade surface. In annular cascade test rigs, introducing a light sheet through an optical window is feasible for measurements on axial or meridional planes, while measurements on a tangential plane generally require a light sheet probe. Although the geometry of the light sheet probe is specific to the test rig, the constitution of optical elements is generally common, as found in various test cases in the literature. This study demonstrated that a laser sheet probe with an external diameter of 8 mm can effectively serve the purpose. From an optical design point of view, however, it is recommended to adopt a large probe diameter for easier laser alignment and probe assembly. Additionally, larger dimensions offer more off-the-shelf optical components. The sealing window is susceptible to laser-induced damage, thus it is advisable to use a material resistant to high-intensity laser pulses.

PIV systems commonly employ green lasers whose wavelength is around 527 - 532 nm for particle illumination. Using a laser with a shorter wavelength is beneficial for the use of smaller particles as it extends the Mie scattering regime. However, one must be careful with the transmittance of the optical window and camera lens, and the quantum efficiency of the camera sensor. Typically, the transmittance of acrylic windows and quantum efficiency of PIV camera sensors drop sharply for wavelengths below 400 nm. Applying an anti-reflection coating to the optical window surface is a good practice to maximize the light transmittance and minimize the undesired reflections.

The design of an image calibration system is another critical element for obtaining accurate results from PIV measurements. The test section and calibration system should be designed in such a way that the calibration target can be precisely placed and retrieved without interfering with the other measurement system. Turbomachinery applications often impose a challenging environment for satisfying this requirement due to the packed and complex geometries. In such cases, one must prepare a robust system that can precisely align the whole measurement system to replicate the same setup before and after extracting the calibration target.

Finally, applying light-absorbing paint to the reflective surface is highly recommended unless other countermeasures such as using fluorescent particles are implemented. This is particularly crucial for measurements on rotating components, as the reflection pattern varies from image to image, making the removal of the reflections more problematic.

5.2.2 Experiment phase

During the experiment, several parameters need to be adjusted. The following introduces a practically convenient procedure for tuning these parameters.

The first parameter to be fixed is the particle image size and intensity to achieve an adequate particle image intensity distribution to avoid the peak-locking effect and to obtain accurate sub-pixel interpolation results. As presented in Fig. 2.54, the particle size should be around 1.5-2.0 pixels for a single-pass evaluation or larger than 3 pixels for a multi-pass evaluation. Assuming that the camera sensor size, optical magnification, and physical particle characteristics are fixed in the design phase, the particle image size can be adjusted by changing the lens aperture, image focusing, and illumination intensity. Typically, the particle images acquired in high-speed turbomachinery flows exhibit small and weak signals due to the use of small physical size of tracer particles for traceability. It is advisable to increase the laser pulse intensity first, up to the laser-induced damage threshold of optical elements while maintaining the lens aperture moderately closed. Opening the lens aperture significantly increases the amount of light passed to the image sensor, thereby increasing the image intensity. However, a too-thin in-focus zone causes a serious out-of-focus effect, resulting in a variation in particle image size and blurring obstacle images (such as the blade profile for measurements on a blade-to-blade plane).

The second parameter is the seeding density. Given that the light sheet intensity and lens aperture are fixed in the previous step, the seeding density is tuned by adjusting the amount and location of tracer particle injection. This is the reason why it is recommended to explore various seeding methods in the design phase. For measurements in high-speed flows, a high seeding flow rate is often required. Furthermore, the seeding density can be constrained by a specific testing condition, such as for a low-density environment where the air inside the test rig must be constantly extracted.

The third parameter to be concerned with is the pulse separation time, which showed a great impact on the measurement results, especially on the turbulence quantities (see section 4.2.1.4). While the well-known rule of thumb suggests setting the separation time so that the particle displacement between successive frames becomes about a quarter of interrogation window size [1], such a setting may not be optimum for accurate turbulence measurements. According to literature [2] and the test case presented in this thesis, the estimated turbulence level with different separation times and interrogation window sizes converges to a similar value for a particle displacement larger than 20 pixels. On the other hand, a too-large separation time will cause both in-plane and out-of-plane losses of particles and bias errors due to flow acceleration or curved streamlines. It is highly recommended to carry out image recordings with multiple separation times to find a compromised value to achieve converged turbulence level and to minimize loss-of-particle and bias error effects.

The fourth parameter is the number of images to obtain statistically converged results. Presented test cases on the linear cascade with steady incoming flow showed that 500 recordings are sufficient for convergence of mean quantities, whereas it is recommended to acquire more than 1000 recordings for convergence of turbulence quantities. For measuring phase-lock-average flow fields in rotating cascades, more recordings are required due to the rephasing process averaging the pitchwise variation of the incoming flow. For measurements in short-duration test rigs where acquiring a large number of datasets is challenging, recording

at least 250 image pairs is suggested to resolve the deterministic phase-lock-averaged flow feature.

Additionally, for rotating applications, it is necessary to evaluate the accuracy of the image-rotor phase synchronization during the experiment phase. A high rotational speed and a large number of blade counts result in a high blade passing frequency. If a significant delay is found between the acquisition systems, a calibration of the system must be conducted. For the presented case, a bias and random delays between the recording times of the camera and diode signal accounted for 250% and 10% of the blade passing period, respectively (see section 3.3.5).

5.2.3 Data processing phase

The first step in the data processing procedure is image pre-processing. For images recorded in a linear cascade test section, subtractions of temporal average and spatial average are sufficient to remove major background image noises and light reflections. Improvements by applying more time-consuming processing schemes are anticipated to be marginal as presented in section 4.2.1.2. On the other hand, images recorded in rotating annular cascade test rigs can exhibit severely deteriorated image quality due to light refraction caused by the curved optical window. Moreover, the collision of laser sheets with rotating blades yields unsteady reflections that can not be removed by subtracting the temporal average. For such cases, a combination of other schemes, for example, contrast-limited-adaptive-histogram-equalization, Sobel filter, and Bilateral filter can be effective in removing the noise and enhancing particle image signals (see section 4.3.3).

Once particle images are prepared, the interrogation window size can be tuned based on the seeding density and required vector resolution. The optimum image preprocessing and interrogation window settings can be explored by checking their effect on the uncertainty level, turbulence level, and the number of valid vectors.

The uncertainty of measured velocity components, as well as quantities derived from them, can be evaluated with a method presented in section 2.6. The major error source contributing to the measurement uncertainty is attributed to the quality of the cross-correlation map which is evaluated using the correlation statistics method [3].

Finally, the velocity fields obtained with PIV can be utilized to derive various quantities, namely: Mach number, vorticity, secondary flow components, turbulence intensity, Reynolds stress, degree of anisotropy, and anisotropy invariants.

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Publications

A.1 Publications in international journals

- Okada, M., Pinho, J., Cernat, B., Lavagnoli, S. (2023). Particle Image Velocimetry in a High-Speed Short-Duration Turbine Rig. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 145(2), 021006.
- Cernat, B. C., Pinho, J., Okada, M., Lavagnoli, S. (2023). Experimental Investigation of a High-Speed Turbine With Rainbow Rotor and Rim Seal Purge Flow. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 145(7), 071014.
- Okada, M., Simonassi, L., Lopes, G., Lavagnoli, S. (2024). Particle Image Velocimetry Measurements in a High-Speed Low-Reynolds Low-Pressure Turbine Cascade. *Journal of Turbomachinery*, 146(3).

A.2 Publications in international conferences

- Okada, M., Pinho, J., Lavagnoli, S. (2022). Fluorescent Tracer Particles for PIV Measurement in Gas Flows. 20th International Symposium on Applications of Laser and Imaging Techniques to Fluid Mechanics, July 11-14, 2022, Lisbon, Portugal
- Okada, M., Pinho, J., Cernat, B., Lavagnoli, S. (2022). A fluorescent PIV technique for turbomachinery flows. XXVI Biennial Symposium on Measuring Techniques in Turbomachinery (MTT2622), September 28-30, 2022, Pisa, Italy
- Okada, M., Pinho, J., Cernat, B., Lavagnoli, S. (2023). PIV feasibility for aerodynamics measurements of a rainbow rotor in a short-duration turbine rig. The 10th EVI-GTI International Gas Turbine Instrumentation Conference, April 25-27, 2023, Budapest, Hungary

B

Turbulence anisotropy invariant analysis

Anisotropy invariant map

The normalized anisotropy Reynolds stress tensor, \mathbf{a} or a_{ij} , is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{a} = a_{ij} &= \frac{\overline{u_i' u_j'}}{2k} - \frac{\delta_{ij}}{3} \\ &= \frac{1}{6k} \begin{bmatrix} 2\overline{u'u'} - \overline{v'v'} - \overline{w'w'} & 3\overline{u'v'} & 3\overline{u'w'} \\ 3\overline{u'v'} & 2\overline{v'v'} - \overline{u'u'} - \overline{w'w'} & 3\overline{v'w'} \\ 3\overline{u'w'} & 3\overline{v'w'} & 2\overline{w'w'} - \overline{u'u'} - \overline{v'v'} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where k is the turbulent kinetic energy $k = (\overline{u'u'} + \overline{v'v'} + \overline{w'w'})/2$ and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker's delta. The anisotropy tensor is symmetric, thus diagonalization will find the eigenvalues λ_i of the tensor for its eigenvector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3)^T$.

$$a_{ij} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{x} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is the diagonal eigenvalue matrix composed of the eigenvalues sorted in decreasing order ($\lambda_1 > \lambda_2 > \lambda_3$). The eigenvalues are determined by solving the characteristic equation:

$$\det(\mathbf{a} - \lambda \mathbf{I}) = 0 \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \lambda^3 - (a_{11} + a_{22} + a_{33}) \lambda^2 \\
& + (a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}a_{33} + a_{22}a_{33} - a_{12}a_{21} - a_{13}a_{31} - a_{23}a_{32}) \lambda \\
& - (a_{11}a_{22}a_{33} + a_{12}a_{23}a_{31} + a_{13}a_{21}a_{32} - a_{11}a_{23}a_{32} - a_{12}a_{21}a_{33} - a_{13}a_{22}a_{31}) \\
& = \lambda^3 - I_1 \lambda^2 + I_2 \lambda - I_3 \\
& = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{B.4}$$

where I is the identity matrix of order of three. The scalar coefficients I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 are the first, second, and third invariant of the anisotropy tensor. The relation between roots and coefficients of cubic equation derives:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &= \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 \\
I_2 &= \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3 + \lambda_1 \lambda_3 \\
I_3 &= \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3
\end{aligned} \tag{B.5}$$

From Eq. B.1, the first invariant I_1 is equal to zero.

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &= a_{11} + a_{22} + a_{33} \\
&= a_{ii} \\
&= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{B.6}$$

$$\lambda_3 = -\lambda_1 - \lambda_2 \tag{B.7}$$

From the square of $I_1 = 0$,

$$a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}a_{33} + a_{22}a_{33} = -\frac{1}{2} (a_{11}^2 + a_{22}^2 + a_{33}^2) \tag{B.8}$$

This leads the second invariant to be:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_2 &= a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}a_{33} + a_{22}a_{33} - a_{12}a_{21} - a_{13}a_{31} - a_{23}a_{32} \\
&= -\frac{1}{2} (a_{11}^2 + a_{22}^2 + a_{33}^2) - a_{12}a_{21} - a_{13}a_{31} - a_{23}a_{32} \\
&= -\frac{1}{2} (a_{11}^2 + a_{22}^2 + a_{33}^2 + a_{12}a_{21} + a_{21}a_{12} + a_{13}a_{31} + a_{31}a_{13} + a_{23}a_{32} + a_{32}a_{23}) \\
&= -\frac{1}{2} a_{ij}a_{ji} \\
&= -(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{B.9}$$

From the cubic of $I_1 = 0$,

$$a_{11}a_{22}a_{33} = \frac{1}{3} (a_{11}^3 + a_{22}^3 + a_{33}^3) \tag{B.10}$$

This leads the third invariant to be:

$$\begin{aligned}
I_3 &= \det(\mathbf{a}) \\
&= a_{11}a_{22}a_{33} + a_{12}a_{23}a_{31} + a_{13}a_{21}a_{32} - a_{11}a_{23}a_{32} - a_{12}a_{21}a_{33} - a_{13}a_{22}a_{31} \\
&= \frac{1}{3}(a_{11}^3 + a_{22}^3 + a_{33}^3) + 2a_{12}a_{13}a_{23} - a_{11}a_{23}^2 - a_{22}a_{13}^2 - a_{33}a_{12}^2 \\
&\quad + a_{11}a_{12}^2 - a_{11}a_{13}^2 + a_{11}a_{13}^2 - a_{11}a_{13} \\
&\quad + a_{22}a_{12}^2 - a_{22}a_{13}^2 + a_{22}a_{23}^2 - a_{11}a_{23} \\
&\quad + a_{33}a_{13}^2 - a_{33}a_{12}^2 + a_{33}a_{23}^2 - a_{33}a_{23} \\
&= \frac{1}{3}(a_{11}^3 + a_{22}^3 + a_{33}^3) + 2a_{12}a_{13}a_{23} \\
&\quad - (a_{11} + a_{22} + a_{33})(a_{12}^2 + a_{13}^2 + a_{23}^2) \\
&\quad + a_{11}a_{12}^2 + a_{11}a_{13}^2 + a_{22}a_{12}^2 + a_{22}a_{23}^2 + a_{33}a_{13}^2 + a_{33}a_{23}^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{3}(a_{11}^3 + a_{22}^3 + a_{33}^3) \\
&\quad + a_{11}a_{12}^2 + a_{11}a_{13}^2 + a_{22}a_{12}^2 + a_{22}a_{23}^2 + a_{33}a_{13}^2 + a_{33}a_{23}^2 + 2a_{12}a_{13}a_{23} \\
&= \frac{1}{3}a_{ij}a_{jk}a_{ki} \\
&= -\lambda_1\lambda_2(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)
\end{aligned} \tag{B.11}$$

From Eq. B.1, the diagonal element of the anisotropy tensor a_{ii} must be larger than $-1/3$ otherwise the turbulent kinetic energy in that component becomes negative. Moreover, none of the diagonal tensor elements can be greater than $2/3$, corresponding to the vanishing of the other two components [1]. The bounds of the off-diagonal elements are $-1/2 < a_{ij} < 1/2$, the minimal value is reached when $u'_i u'_j = -k$, the maximal value occurs when $u'_i u'_j = k$. The limiting conditions are summarized in Eq. B.12.

$$\begin{aligned}
-1/3 &\leq a_{ii} \leq 2/3 \\
-1/2 &\leq a_{ij} \leq 1/2, \quad (i \neq j)
\end{aligned} \tag{B.12}$$

These limits impose the realizable range of invariants of the anisotropy tensor (I_2 and I_3).

$$\begin{aligned}
-1/36 &\leq 3I_3 \leq 2/9 \\
-2I_2 &= \frac{2}{9} + 2 \cdot 3I_3 \\
-2I_2 &= \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{4}{3} |3I_3|^{2/3} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{B.13}$$

The resultant is a triangle plotted in $I_2 I_3$ -plane, called the anisotropy invariant map (AIM) of Lumley and Newman [1] [2] or simply, the Lumley triangle. As it is yielded based on the limit values of the anisotropy tensor, all the possible states of turbulence must be contained in this triangle. Furthermore, the AIM provides the characteristic states of turbulence based on the location of the plotted turbulence state in the triangle, as depicted in Fig. 2.48.

Barycentric map

Another method to visualize the state of turbulence anisotropy is using a barycentric map (BM) introduced by Banerjee et al. [3]. The BM is presented by a triangle whose vertices is defined by three points x_{1c} , x_{2c} and x_{3c} in the Euclidean space as shown in Fig. 2.49. x_{1c} corresponds to the one-component (1c) state of turbulence where there is only one component of turbulent kinetic energy. x_{2c} corresponds to the two-component (2c) isotropic state of turbulence where there are two equal turbulent components while the rest vanishes. x_{3c} corresponds to the three-component (3c) isotropic state of turbulence where three equal turbulent components exist.

A coordinate of point (x_n, y_n) that represents the anisotropy state in the BM is calculated by the combination of the vertex:

$$\begin{aligned} x_n &= C_{1c}x_{1c} + C_{2c}x_{2c} + C_{3c}x_{3c} \\ y_n &= C_{1c}y_{1c} + C_{2c}y_{2c} + C_{3c}y_{3c} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.14})$$

where C_{1c} , C_{2c} and C_{3c} are normalized coefficients whose values range from 0 to 1 and are satisfying:

$$C_{1c} + C_{2c} + C_{3c} = 1 \quad (\text{B.15})$$

Now, we recall the diagonalized anisotropy tensor $a_{ij} = \mathbf{\Lambda}\mathbf{x}$ from Eq. B.2. The eigenvalues corresponding to the one-component state of turbulence are:

$$\lambda_{1,1c} = \frac{2}{3}, \quad \lambda_{2,1c} = \lambda_{3,1c} = -\frac{1}{3} \quad (\text{B.16})$$

The eigenvalues corresponding to the two-component isotropic state of turbulence are:

$$\lambda_{1,2c} = \lambda_{2,2c} = \frac{1}{6}, \quad \lambda_{3,2c} = -\frac{1}{3} \quad (\text{B.17})$$

The eigenvalues corresponding to the three-component isotropic state of turbulence are:

$$\lambda_{1,2c} = \lambda_{2,2c} = \lambda_{3,2c} = 0 \quad (\text{B.18})$$

Substituting these eigenvalues in λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 , the tensors represent one, two, and three-component (isotropic for latter two) states of turbulence $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{1c}$, $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{2c}$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3c}$ are written by:

$$\mathbf{\Lambda}_{1c} = \begin{bmatrix} 2/3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1/3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1/3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.19})$$

$$\mathbf{\Lambda}_{2c} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/6 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1/3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.20})$$

$$\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3c} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.21})$$

All possible turbulence state can be expressed by a combination of $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{1c}$, $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{2c}$ and $\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3c}$, thus:

$$\mathbf{\Lambda} = C_{1c}\mathbf{\Lambda}_{1c} + C_{2c}\mathbf{\Lambda}_{2c} + C_{3c}\mathbf{\Lambda}_{3c} \quad (\text{B.22})$$

Implementation of Eq. B.19, B.20, B.21 in Eq. B.22 and the constraint of coefficients (Eq. B.15) give the relation between the coefficients and the eigenvalues as:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{1c} &= \lambda_1 - \lambda_2 \\ C_{2c} &= 2(\lambda_2 - \lambda_3) \\ C_{3c} &= 3\lambda_3 + 1 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.23})$$

As an analogy to Eq. B.22, the coordinate of BM (Eq. B.14) is calculated. If BM is plotted such that the triangle is equilateral with its vertices at $x_{1c} = (1, 0)$, $x_{2c} = (0, 0)$ and $x_{3c} = (1/2, \sqrt{3}/2)$, the coordinate system in Cartesian coordinate is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} x_n &= C_{1c}x_{1c} + C_{2c}x_{2c} + C_{3c}x_{3c} = C_{1c} + \frac{1}{2}C_{3c} \\ y_n &= C_{1c}y_{1c} + C_{2c}y_{2c} + C_{3c}y_{3c} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}C_{3c} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.24})$$

Componentality contours

The AIM and BM are useful to grasp the state of turbulence anisotropy with respect to the limiting state. On the other hand, these techniques cut out the information on the spatial distribution of the Reynolds stress in the physical domain during the mapping process, thus the physical context is not evident. Besides, when the data size is large, such as data over a plane or a volume, the map becomes overcrowded and too complicated to comprehend. One of the visualization techniques that shows the state of turbulence anisotropy is the componentality contours introduced by Emory and Iaccarino [4]. The basis of this technique is to assign a color map constructed from the barycentric map coordinates to each physical coordinate. They proposed the modified color map for the RGB channel as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} R \\ G \\ B \end{bmatrix} = C_{1c}^* \mathbf{n}_1 + C_{2c}^* \mathbf{n}_2 + C_{3c}^* \mathbf{n}_3 \quad (\text{B.25})$$

$$C_{ic}^* = (C_{ic} + C_{off})^{C_{exp}} \quad (\text{B.26})$$

where C_{off} and C_{exp} are the offset and exponent coefficients which the user can select based on which region of BM is being focused. \mathbf{n}_i is a 3×1 vector that defines the color scheme. For example, $\mathbf{n}_1 = [1, 0, 0]^T$, $\mathbf{n}_2 = [0, 1, 0]^T$ and $\mathbf{n}_3 = [0, 0, 1]^T$ assign red, green and blue to each vertex of BM triangle. Examples of colormap for the componentality contours are illustrated in Fig. 2.50 and B.1.

Figure B.1: Variation of componentality color contours adapted to barycentric map. [4]

Rescaling of anisotropy tensor

Anisotropy invariant maps (AIM) describe turbulence componentality based on the invariants of anisotropy tensor projected on a two-dimensional domain bounded by limiting states. While all realizable turbulence state has to be projected within the bounds of the AIM and BM, in practice, experimentally obtained turbulence quantities can fall outside the realizability bounds. For example, Andersson et al. [5] reported the turbulence characteristics measured with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) exhibiting unrealizable turbulence states prevailing in a large portion of the measured region (Fig. B.2).

Figure B.2: MRI-measured Reynolds stress characteristics in an idealized constriction [5].

Unrealizable turbulence states are also found in the results obtained from the COP PIV measurement presented in this thesis. Fig. B.3 and B.4 depict the BM and componentality map. The unrealizable turbulent states are mainly distributed in the freestream region, where the streamwise turbulence fluctuation is significantly stretched. Simply discarding these unrealizable results substantially truncates the spatial context of the turbulence state; therefore, it is beneficial to consider rescaling the measured anisotropy tensor to extract meaningful turbulence componentality information.

Although it is possible to detect an element in the anisotropy tensor that does not satisfy the limiting conditions written in Eq. B.12, normalizing the whole tensor while maintaining the relative amplitude between elements is not straightforward. Therefore, it is favorable to consider the diagonalized anisotropy tensor, with which the shape of the anisotropy tensor is expressed by three eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$, and an eigenvector $(x_1, x_2, x_3)^T$. Since there is no off-diagonal element in this form of anisotropy tensor, the limiting conditions one must account for are reduced to:

Figure B.3: Barycentric map obtained from COP PIV in S-1/C wind tunnel.

Figure B.4: Componentiality contour obtained from COP PIV in S-1/C wind tunnel.

$$-1/3 \leq \lambda_i \leq 1/3 \quad (\text{B.27})$$

Since the relative size of the eigenvalues along the orthogonal axes (eigenvectors) represents the turbulence componentality, scaling the eigenvalues with an identical value will retain the relative shape of the anisotropy tensor. Such an idea suggests rescaling the anisotropy tensor by the eigenvalue that exceeds the limiting conditions:

If $\lambda_i > 2/3$ (for $i = 1, 2, 3$),

$$\begin{aligned} C_{i,scale} &= \lambda_i / (2/3) \\ \lambda'_1 &= \lambda_1 / C_{i,scale} \\ \lambda'_2 &= \lambda_2 / C_{i,scale} \\ \lambda'_3 &= \lambda_3 / C_{i,scale} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.28})$$

If $\lambda_i < -1/3$ (for $i = 1, 2, 3$),

$$\begin{aligned} C_{i,scale} &= \lambda_i / (-1/3) \\ \lambda'_1 &= \lambda_1 / C_{i,scale} \\ \lambda'_2 &= \lambda_2 / C_{i,scale} \\ \lambda'_3 &= \lambda_3 / C_{i,scale} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.29})$$

The results of this scaling process are depicted in Fig. B.5 and B.6. The unrealizable turbulence states (points that appeared outside the triangle) are now projected within the limiting bounds, primarily along the peripheral line representing the two-component limit. As presented in section 4.2.3.3, the scaled results demonstrate a reasonable agreement with LES prediction, suggesting a fair validity of this scaling method.

Figure B.5: Barycentric map obtained from COP PIV in S-1/C wind tunnel. Scaling is applied.

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Figure B.6: Componentiality contour obtained from COP PIV in S-1/C wind tunnel. Scaling is applied.

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